

**CHARLES STURT UNIVERSITY
AUSTRALIA**

**Voices from a Leprosy Colony: A Critical Ethnography of the Impacts of
Community Empowerment and Social Inclusion Program at
Sitanela Leprosy Village, Indonesia**

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Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	I
CERTIFICATE OF AUTHORSHIP	V
ABSTRACT	VI
DEDICATION	VII
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	VIII
LIST OF TABLES	X
LIST OF FIGURES	XI
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. Introduction	1
1.2. Background	1
1.3. Global leprosy situation	3
1.4. Leprosy situation in Indonesia	4
1.5. Significance of the study	9
1.6. Research aims	11
1.7. Research questions	11
1.8. Research design and methodology	12
1.9. Presentation of the thesis	14
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	15
2.1. Introduction	15
2.2. A brief overview of leprosy	15
2.3. Leprosy and social exclusion	20
2.4. Stigmatisation of leprosy	26
2.5. Community empowerment and social inclusion (CESI)	32
2.6. Conclusion	35
CHAPTER 3: INTERVENTION APPROACHES WITH PEOPLE AFFECTED BY LEPROSY AND DISABILITY	37
3.1. Introduction	37
3.2. Social model of disability	37
3.3. Critical disability theory	40
3.4. Social inclusion	43
3.5. Community empowerment.....	46
3.5.1. Theories of power	47
3.5.2. Community empowerment continuum	51
3.5.3. Capacity building and participation.....	53
3.6. Conclusion	55
CHAPTER 4: METHODOLOGY.....	56
4.1. Introduction	56
4.2. Epistemology	56
4.3. Design.....	58

4.4. Research setting and access.....	60
4.5. Data collection	62
4.5.1. Recruitment of participants	63
4.5.2. Participant observation	63
4.5.3. Focus group discussion.....	64
4.5.4. In-depth interview	65
4.5.5. Secondary data	65
4.6. Data Analysis	65
4.7. Ethical considerations	68
4.7.1. Benefits and risks of participation.....	68
4.7.2. Participant’s involvement and the consent form.....	69
4.7.3. Confidentiality and privacy.....	70
4.7.4. Dissemination of research results	70
4.8. Trustworthiness	70
4.9. Conclusion	70
CHAPTER 5: GOVERNMENT POLICIES.....	72
5.1. Introduction	72
5.2. Laws and regulations.....	72
5.2.1. Before UNCRPD	73
5.2.2. After UNCRPD.....	76
5.3. Central government policy.....	78
5.3.1. Ministry of Social Affairs.....	78
5.3.2. Ministry of Health.....	81
5.4. Local Government Policy.....	84
5.4.1. Jakarta Province	84
5.4.2. Tangerang Municipality.....	87
5.5. Conclusion	90
CHAPTER 6: COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT AND SOCIAL INCLUSION PROGRAM IN SITANALA	91
6.1. Introduction	91
6.2. Government	91
6.2.1. Ministry of Social Affairs (MoSA).....	91
6.2.2. Ministry of Health (MoH)	102
6.2.3. Ministry of Domestic Affairs (MoDA)	103
6.2.4. Ministry of Manpower and Transmigration (MoMT).....	103
6.2.5. Ministry of Sport and Youth Affairs (MoSYA).....	104
6.2.6. Local Government of Tangerang.....	105
6.3. Faith-based organisation (FBO).....	105
6.4. Community association (CA)	108
6.5. University community service (UCS).....	109
6.6. Non-government organisation (NGO).....	110
6.7. Corporate social responsibility (CSR)	112
6.8. Conclusion	112

CHAPTER 7: SOCIAL AND HISTORICAL CONTEXT OF THE SITANALA LEPROSY VILLAGE	116
7.1. Introduction	116
7.2. The history of Kampung Kusta Sitanala	116
7.2.1. Sitanala leprosy hospital	117
7.2.2. Leprosy patients	121
7.3. Kampung Kusta Sitanala today.....	132
7.3.1. The profile of Kampung Kusta Sitanala	132
7.3.2. Social and economic livelihood	138
7.4. Conclusion	148
CHAPTER 8: PERCEPTIONS AND EXPERIENCES ABOUT COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT AND SOCIAL INCLUSION PROGRAM	149
8.1. Introduction	149
8.2. Economic empowerment program	149
8.2.1. Vocational training program	150
8.2.2. Productive economic business program	156
8.2.3. Joint business group program	159
8.2.4. Microcredit program	160
8.3. Social empowerment program	162
8.3.1. Youth organisation program	162
8.3.2. Family welfare movement program.....	164
8.4. Political empowerment program.....	165
8.5. Social inclusion program	167
8.5.1. Health program	167
8.5.2. Educational program	168
8.5.3. Employment program	171
8.5.4. Recreational program.....	178
8.6. Non-CESI program	180
8.6.1. Food aid program	180
8.6.2. Medical aid program	182
8.6.3. Cash transfer program.....	182
8.7. Conclusion	183
CHAPTER 9: THEORISING AND ANALYSING THE PRACTICE OF COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT AND SOCIAL INCLUSION	189
9.1. Introduction	189
9.2. Exploring findings with existing theories	189
9.2.1. Examination of findings through social stigma and social exclusion theories.....	190
9.2.2. Examination of findings through critical disability theory.....	196
9.2.3. Examination of findings through community empowerment and social inclusion theories	200
9.3. Grounded theorising the findings based on field data: Paternalism in human service practice	204
9.4. Conclusion	212

CHAPTER 10: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	214
10.1. Introduction	214
10.2. Conclusion in relation to research question	214
10.2.1. Core findings for research question 1	215
10.2.2. Core findings for research question 2	217
10.3. Limitations and strength of the study.....	230
10.3.1. Limitations of this study	230
10.3.2. Strengths of this study.....	230
10.4. Implications of this research	231
10.4.1. Implications for theory	231
10.4.2. Implications for policy	232
10.4.3. Implications for social work practice.....	233
10.5. Directions for future research.....	234
10.6. Conclusion	235
LIST OF REFERENCES	236
APPENDICES	261
Appendix A-1: Information Sheet for Participants (Focus Group Discussion)	261
Appendix A-2: Information Sheet for Participants (Focus Group Discussion) in Bahasa Indonesia.....	264
Appendix A-3: Information Sheet for Participants (In-depth Interview)	267
Appendix A-4: Information Sheet for Participants (In-depth Interview) in Bahasa Indonesia	269
Appendix B-1: Observation Guidelines	272
Appendix B-2: Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guidelines.....	273
Appendix B-3: Interview Guidelines.....	274
Appendix B-4: Document Study Guidelines	275
Appendix C: Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) Approval.....	276
Appendix D: Conference Presentations	278

Certificate of Authorship

I hereby declare that this submission is my own work and that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, it contains no material previously published or written by another person nor material which to a substantial extent has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma at Charles Sturt University or any other educational institution, except where due acknowledgement is made in the thesis. Any contribution made to the research by colleagues with whom I have worked at Charles Sturt University or elsewhere during my candidature is fully acknowledged.

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Wagga Wagga, 3 August 2017

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Arif Rohman', is written over a horizontal line. The signature is stylized and somewhat illegible.

Arif Rohman

Abstract

This research is focused on exploring the experiences of persons affected by leprosy who live in Sitanala Leprosy Village in Indonesia; in order to analyse and develop an understanding of how they give meaning to the community empowerment and social inclusion (CESI) program in that place. Qualitative, ethnographic, and observational research methods were used to collect the field data. Ethnographic and content analysis shows various causes and types of discrimination and disadvantage experienced by the people affected by leprosy. The nature and depth of disadvantage is extreme, and many state-provided services have not helped to improve their conditions to the extent they should have. The main findings in relation to the implementation of CESI program were: (a) people affected by leprosy encounter significant systemic barriers to full inclusion and participation in their community; (b) the barriers that prevented full participation in society ranged from social to physical; (c) inflexible laws, policies and practices play an important role in making the barriers more cultural and systemic; and (d) the dominance of moral and medical models make the barriers difficult to eliminate. Further, the analysis shows that lack of information of their disability and rights contribute to perpetuating the existing barriers. Finally, this research found that paternalism and unqualified community workers contribute to lowering the impacts of CESI programs in Sitanala. The findings have implications for all stakeholders, including government, non-government organisations and private sectors to provide a wider support through empowering and anti-discriminatory approaches.

Dedication

This dissertation is dedicated in memory of the Chief Librarian of the Armidale Memorial Library 1961-1984, the late Enid Isaacs, O.A.M, BA, DipSocStud, Reg. Lib.

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List of Tables

Table 1.1	Trends in the Detection of New Cases of Leprosy, 2009-2014	4
Table 1.2	Trends of Leprosy Cases in Indonesia, 2005-2015	6
Table 1.3	High Burden of Leprosy in Indonesia, 2012	7
Table 2.1	WHO Leprosy Disability Grading	20
Table 6.1	The Raskin Program in Indonesia, 1998-2016	98
Table 6.2	The Cash Transfer Program in Indonesia, 2005-2015	99
Table 6.3	The Program Keluarga Harapan in Indonesia, 2007-2015	101
Table 6.4	The Schedule of Tutorial Program in Sitanala.....	110
Table 6.5	The CESI and Non-CESI Programs Available in Sitanala, 1953- present	114
Table 8.1	The Implementation, Benefit, and Impact of CESI and Non-CESI Programs in Sitanala.....	185

List of Figures

Figure 1.1	Trends in the Detection of New Cases of Leprosy, 2009-2014	7
Figure 3.1	The ICF Interactive Model	40
Figure 3.2	Community Empowerment Continuum	53
Figure 4.1	Five Sequences of Thematic Analysis	67
Figure 6.1	Four Directorate Generals in the Ministry of Social Affairs	92
Figure 7.1	Sitanala Leprosy Hospital Map	118
Figure 7.2	A Pedicab Driver Passing Sitanala Leprosy Hospital	119
Figure 7.3	A Woman Cooking on an Open Fire Outside Her Home in Kampung Kusta Sitanala	132
Figure 7.4	Total Population of Persons Affected by Leprosy in Sitanala, 2015	133
Figure 7.5	A woman Uses Orthotic and Prosthetic Devices	134
Figure 7.6	Poor Home Hygiene and Sanitation	135
Figure 7.7	Current Population of Disabled Persons due to Leprosy in Sitanala by Occupation, 2015	139
Figure 7.8	An Old Woman Sitting in Her House in Sitanala	143
Figure 9.1	Paternalism Views Sitanala People as the Lowest Class	205
Figure 9.2	Paternalism and Unqualified Social Worker in the CESI Program ...	211
Figure 9.3	Intervention Model to Empower Persons Affected by Leprosy in Sitanala	212

'One can live without fingers, but not self-respect.'

(Baba Amte)

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1. Introduction

The main focus of this thesis is to explore the state/conditions of Sitanala leprosy village, Indonesia, and experiences of people affected by leprosy, particularly in regard to community empowerment and social inclusion policies and programs. To introduce the thesis, this chapter discusses the background of the study, the global leprosy situation, the leprosy situation in Indonesia, the significance of the study, the research aims and questions, and the presentation of the thesis.

1.2. Background

My interest in leprosy began when I was ten, when two of my relatives in Central Java had leprosy. My first relative died due to her chronic illness. It was too late for her to have medical treatment. My second relative was more fortunate because her leprosy was detected earlier. However, I still remember how she was embarrassed and went to the village hall together with other persons affected by leprosy to receive health education about leprosy. She kept the secret of her leprosy during her treatment so that her children and the neighbours did not know that she had leprosy. What she did was understandable since people in our village believed that leprosy was a highly contagious disease and they saw this disease as a punishment from God. People in my village called leprosy *penyakit daging busuk* (rotten meat disease). Many who had a deformity because of leprosy felt ashamed and preferred to move and live in the leprosy colony in Tugu Hospital in Semarang, Central Java. These experiences made me curious about understanding the phenomenon of leprosy.

My curiosity about leprosy increased when I read the *Suara Pembaruan Daily* on 27 May 2010, which mentioned that in Tangerang (about an hour from the Jakarta airport), there was a leprosy colony called Sitanala Leprosy Village. This colony had

existed since the 1950s and today the population has reached about one thousand. Most of the residents are former patients who have received medical treatment from the Sitanala Hospital. They live in poor conditions, excluded from the general community and work as beggars to make a living. The children although free of leprosy are vulnerable due to the community's bad sanitation, lack of nutrition and lack of education. Sadly, some people have labelled persons affected by leprosy as 'zombies'. These attitudes have not changed over time.

Another news report that shocked me was that on 13 May 2013 Ustadz Maulana, a very popular Muslim scholar, preached that leprosy is caused by sexual intercourse conducted by parents during menstruation. His lessons aired on one of the biggest TV stations in Indonesia. This is despite the publication of a letter by *Komisi Fatwa Majelis Ulama Indonesia* (Fatwa Commission of Indonesian Ulema Council) on 12 April 1982 that leprosy is caused by bacteria. As a result of Ustadz Maulana's broadcast, a wave of protests together with a petition by people affected by leprosy and NGOs, were organised and an apology demanded from him. However, he refused to apologise based on the reasoning that it is mentioned in the teachings of Islam. This refers to the hadith (saying of Prophet Muhammad) that sexual intercourse during menses, brings about leprosy to the fetus. The hadith says, '*If one has sexual intercourse with his wife while she is going through her monthly menstruation period, and a child is conceived who happens to have leprosy, he should blame none other than himself*' (Shirazi, 2013).

Law no. 4 was passed in 1997 concerning Disabled Persons and gave a mandate for the Indonesian government to provide social protection for all persons with disabilities. This Act also provides an opportunity for non-government organizations, the private and the public sectors to participate in providing social services for disabled people. For this many community empowerment and social inclusion programs have come to the Sitanala leprosy village. However, the facts show that persons affected by leprosy today are still in poverty, experience high level of stigma and have been rejected by society (Indonesian National Commission on Human Rights, 2011).

As a social worker who works for the Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs at the social policy level, I feel that this phenomenon indicates the urgency of research about this colony and the impact and implementation of community empowerment and social inclusion program and future changes.

1.3. Global leprosy situation

Leprosy or Hansen's disease is a chronic infectious disease, caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*. It affects skin, peripheral nerves and mucous membranes of the nose, throat, and eyes. Damage to the peripheral nerves may result in loss of sensation and along with the decline of tissue functions, it causes deformities of the feet and hands. In some cases, leprosy can also cause disfigurement of the face and blindness (Park & Park, 2011). Although it is contagious, leprosy is difficult to spread in comparison to other infectious diseases. Recent studies show that of the 95% of people are believed to be naturally immune to leprosy, 3% could become affected by leprosy which resolves without treatment and only 2% are infected and need medical treatment (Kearns & Nash, 2013; Scollard et al., 2006). Today, leprosy can be cured by Multi-Drug Therapy (MDT), which refers to a combination of three drugs, such as dapson, rifampicin, and clofazimine. However, late detection and inappropriate medical treatment can lead to disability (Hatta, Ratnawati, Ito, Shirakawa, & Kawabata, 2010). In relation to disability caused by leprosy, the World Health Organization (WHO) classified disability due to leprosy into 3 categories: (1) Grade-0, characterized by no loss of sensation and no visible deformity or damage; (2) Grade-1, indicated by loss of sensation present, but no visible deformity or damage; and (3) Grade-2, shown by visible deformity or damage present (Brandsma & van Brakel, 2003). According to Walker, Withington, and Lockwood (2014), currently, it is estimated that about 3 million people are permanently disabled due to leprosy.

In 1985, leprosy was categorised as a public health problem in the world. Since then many efforts have been made to achieve the elimination of leprosy. The World Health Assembly (WHA) reported that elimination of leprosy as a public health problem is defined as the reduction of prevalence to a level below one case per 10,000

population (WHA, 1991). According to the United Nations Department of Economics and Social Affairs (UNDESA), more than 14 million persons with leprosy have been treated using MDT over the past 20 years. This contributes to the decrease of the leprosy prevalence rate from 21.1 per 10,000 persons to less than 1 per 10,000 persons in 2000 (UNDESA, 2015).

However, leprosy remains a public health problem in the majority of developing countries, where more than 200,000 new cases are detected every year. For example, in 2011, there were 219,075 new cases detected with South-East Asia contributing 73% of these (WHO, 2012). The report from UNDESA also mentioned that even though leprosy has been eliminated from 119 out of the 122 countries, persons affected by leprosy still face high levels of exclusion in society. As a consequence, it leads to social isolation, discrimination and under-representation in education, employment and other social domains. Furthermore, the misconception that leprosy is merely a health problem has excluded sufferers from the disability rights movement, nationally and globally (UNDESA, 2015).

Table 1.1
Trends in the Detection of New Cases of Leprosy
2009-2014

WHO Region ¹	No. of New Cases Detected					
	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
African	28,935	25,345	12,673	20,599	20,911	18,597
Americas	40,474	37,740	36,832	36,178	33,084	33,789
South-East Asia	166,115	156,254	160,132	166,445	155,385	154,834
Eastern Mediterranean	4,029	4,080	4,346	4,235	1,680	2,342
Western Pacific	5,243	5,055	5,092	5,400	4,596	4,337
Total	244,796	228,474	219,075	232,857	215,656	213,899

¹ Reports from the European Region are not included in the original report.

Source: WHO (2012, 2013, 2014, 2015a)

1.4. Leprosy situation in Indonesia

Leprosy is still a significant health problem in Indonesia. Various attempts have been made by the Indonesian government to eradicate leprosy, such as: increasing detection of new cases; administration of drugs and regular monitoring of medical

treatment; education and training for health workers about leprosy; providing free medical treatment for leprosy patients; intensifying efforts to prevent disability; as well as increasing self-care counselling for persons affected by leprosy (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2012c). As a result, Indonesia achieved the elimination of leprosy as a public health problem, in which the prevalence rate in Indonesia declined from 4.9/10,000 population in 1991 to 0.86/10,000 population in 2000 (WHO, 2010).

After achieving the stage of elimination of leprosy as a public health problem, the Indonesian government was active in supporting the *Global Strategy for Further Reducing the Leprosy Burden and Sustaining Leprosy Control Activities (2006-2010)*. This strategy aims to further reduce the leprosy burden and maintain the continuity of leprosy eradication (World Health Organization, 2006). Through the Ministry of Health, Indonesia is currently focusing in the implementation of *Global Strategy for Further Reducing the Disease Burden Due to Leprosy (2011 - 2015)*. The main target of this strategy is to reduce grade-2 disabilities among new cases of leprosy by at least 35% between the end of 2010 and the end of 2015 (World Health Organization, 2009). To make it successful, the Novartis Foundation commits to the supply of free drugs through WHO, while the Netherlands Leprosy Relief and the Sasakawa Foundation provide operational and technical assistances (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2010).

A report from WHO mentioned that in 2011, the number of new cases detected in Indonesia reached 20,023. This number put Indonesia as the country with the third highest leprosy population in the world, after India and Brazil, with 127,295 new cases and 33,955 new cases respectively. These three countries contributed about 83% of total new cases detected in 2011, with India contributing 58%, Brazil 16% and Indonesia 9% (WHO, 2012). Of the 20,023 new cases detected in Indonesia, 2,025 cases (10.11%) were classified as significant disability or Grade-2, whilst 2,452 (12.25%) occurred in children, and 16,099 cases (80.40%) were categorized as multibacillary (MB) or contagious when untreated (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2012c, 2013b).

Table 1.2
Trends of Leprosy Cases in Indonesia
2005-2015

No.	Year	New Cases	Disability Grade-2	Child Cases	MB Cases
1.	2000	14,697	1,231	1,499	11,267
2.	2001	14,722	1,300	1,466	11,314
3.	2002	16,253	1,251	1,449	12,398
4.	2003	15,913	1,275	1,676	12,223
5.	2004	16,572	1,430	1,763	12,957
6.	2005	19,695	1,722	1,790	15,639
7.	2006	18,300	1,575	1,905	14,750
8.	2007	17,723	1,527	1,824	14,107
9.	2008	17,441	1,668	1,987	14,328
10.	2009	17,260	1,812	2,073	14,227
11.	2010	17,012	1,822	1,904	13,734
12.	2011	20,023	2,025	2,452	16,099
13.	2012	16,123	1,838	1,793	13,268
14.	2013	16,856	1,694	2,002	14,062
15.	2014	17,025	1,596	1,894	14,213
16.	2015	17,202	1,687	1,930	14,545

Source: Indonesian Ministry of Health (2013a, 2014, 2015b, 2016)

The report from the Indonesia government revealed that in 2012 there were 14 provinces in Indonesia classified as carrying a high burden of leprosy, while the other 20 provinces (59%) were low. Interestingly, almost all provinces in eastern Indonesia were included as high burden of leprosy areas (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2013a).

Table 1.3
High Burden of Leprosy in Indonesia
2012

No.	Provinces	New Cases	CDR	Region
1.	Papua	1,348	4.29	Eastern Indonesia
2.	Papua Barat	594	7.27	Eastern Indonesia
3.	Maluku	649	4.01	Eastern Indonesia
4.	Maluku Utara	535	4.92	Eastern Indonesia
5.	Sulawesi Tenggara	300	1.29	Eastern Indonesia
6.	Sulawesi Selatan	1,100	1.41	Eastern Indonesia
7.	Sulawesi Barat	211	1.73	Eastern Indonesia
8.	Sulawesi Utara	444	1.91	Eastern Indonesia
9.	Sulawesi Tengah	368	1.35	Eastern Indonesia
10.	Gorontalo	220	2.03	Eastern Indonesia
11.	Jawa Timur	4,807	1.26	Western Indonesia
12.	Jawa Tengah	1,813	0.56	Western Indonesia
13.	Jawa Barat	2,316	0.56	Western Indonesia
14.	Aceh	565	1.23	Western Indonesia
	Total	16,123		

High Burden: Case detection rate (CDR) > 1/10,000 or New Case ≥ 1,000

Low Burden: Case detection rate (CDR) < 1/10,000 or New Case ≤ 1,000

Source: Indonesian Ministry of Health (2013a)

Figure 1.1
High Burden of Leprosy in Indonesia
2012

Source: Indonesian Ministry of Health (2013a)

In relation to the prevalence of leprosy, Nafsiah Mboi, the Minister of Health, said that '*Nationally it is not perceived as severe, because it is less than one in 10,000, but we should not underestimate it*'. This was stated during her visit to Sitanala leprosy hospital in observation of the 60th Anniversary of World Leprosy Day (Antara News, 2013). At that event, she also mentioned that many persons affected by leprosy are still living in poverty, besides experiencing stigma and rejection from their society. As an example, around 5,000 former patients still occupy a five-hectare plot at the *Komplek Serba Guna* (Multipurpose Complex) of the hospital due to public rejection. Because the majority of people who live in this complex are persons affected by leprosy, people called it *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* (Sitanala Leprosy Village). The Minister also acknowledged that the most difficult challenge today is how to improve people's well-being after finishing medical rehabilitation and how to eliminate the stigma of leprosy, which is already embedded within the community (The Jakarta Post, 2013).

Issues of stigma and discrimination against persons affected by leprosy has brought attention from international communities. This can be seen from a resolution issued by the United Nations Human Rights Council (UNHRC) concerning *Elimination of Discrimination against Persons Affected by Leprosy and Their Family Members* (United Nations Human Rights Council, 2008). The resolution was followed up by the publication of *Guidelines for Strengthening the Participation of Persons Affected by Leprosy in Leprosy Services* (WHO, 2011). In Indonesia, one of the active agencies that has a commitment to promote the rights of people with leprosy is the Indonesian National Commission of Human Rights. Based on the latest Commission report, persons affected by leprosy in Indonesia experienced difficulties in fulfilling their basic needs and suffered from stigma and discrimination (Indonesian National Commission on Human Rights, 2011). Another report issued by the Indonesian government also mentioned that there were 500 persons affected by leprosy who lived in Jongaya, Makassar. Most of them had facial disfigurements and severe disabilities. They were categorised as 'invisible people' due to their poverty and less attention from the government and society (Kortschak & Sitanggang, 2010). Jongaya is one of the leprosy colonies in Indonesia that still exist today. It is estimated that

there are around 65 leprosy colonies in Indonesia that need more attention (Ratnawati & Noviandari, 2012).

Based on these issues, exploratory research about persons affected by leprosy, especially those who have finished their medical treatment, has been carried out at Sitanala leprosy village in Indonesia between November 2013 and June 2014; and from March to May 2016. It captures the current situation of persons affected by leprosy and the disadvantage experienced by them due to stigma and discrimination. The research location was in Kampung Kusta Sitanala, Tangerang, which is categorized as the biggest and the oldest leprosy colony in Indonesia.

1.5. Significance of the study

The profession of social work has a close tie with persons affected by leprosy, as one of its fields of practice is disability. According to Mackelprang and Salsgiver (1996) and van Wormer (2005), social work is the profession with primary responsibility toward people who are subjected to discrimination and oppression. People usually experience this discrimination and oppression based on race, gender, disability, and class (Collins, 2003; Collins, 2010; Laird, 2008; Thompson, 2006). However, persons affected by leprosy suffer more due to not only race, gender, and class but also their poverty and health status, which elevates the level of stigma (Balcazar, Suarez-Balcazar, Taylor-Ritzler, & Keys, 2010; Cook, 2003).

The International Federation of Social Workers (IFSW) defines social work as follows:

Social work is a practice-based profession and an academic discipline that promotes social change and development, social cohesion, and the empowerment and liberation of people. Principles of social justice, human rights, collective responsibility and respect for diversities are central to social work. Underpinned by theories of social work, social sciences, humanities and indigenous knowledge, social work engages people and structures to address life challenges and enhance wellbeing (IFSW, 2014).

The IFSW's definition of social work above is basically more up-to-date and fits with the current situation. This can be seen through the definition of social work proposed

by Werner W. Boehm (in Skidmore, Thackeray and Farley, 1994, p. 5), that is quite simple:

Social work seeks to enhance the social functioning of individuals, singly and in groups, by activities focused upon their social relationships which constitute the interaction between man and his environment. These activities can be grouped into three functions: restoration of impaired capacity, provision of individual and social resources, and prevention of social dysfunction.

According to Bernstein and Gray (1996), social work focuses on the interaction between people and the institutions of society. Furthermore, they identified four purposes of social work. These are: (1) to promote the well-being of people; (2) to help people meet needs or solve problems; (3) to help people to find the resources to meet their needs; and (4) to help build a just and responsive society. Similarly, other scholars, such as Baer and Federico (1978), identified the purposes into three categories, involving: (1) the enhancement of problem-solving, coping and developmental capacities of people; (2) promoting the effective and humane operation of the systems that provide people with resources and services; and (3) linking people with systems that provide them with resources, services and opportunities. Based on its purposes, social workers work with individuals, groups of people and communities. Thus, central to the social work approach is how to empower the client/people, so that they can achieve their goals. Social workers may help clients to work towards changing themselves, changing factors at various levels of the environment, or both these approaches (Bernstein & Gray, 1996). In relation to this, Vass (1996, p. 5) states the importance of *'developing abilities which allows them to integrate knowledge, values and skills in order to produce competent practice'*.

Persons affected by leprosy as a disadvantaged group are often excluded from general society. They face many restrictions of access to opportunities and participation in social, economic, and political activities. Therefore, they become a vulnerable and marginalised group that live in poverty and find it difficult to meet their basic needs. According to Sherwin (2010), social inclusion becomes very important in working with persons with disability. Furthermore, social workers

should acknowledge the empowerment and self-determination principles in working with persons with disabilities (Hiranandani, 2005); focusing on strengths, hopes and aspirations of persons with disabilities (Raske, 2005); and using the bio-psycho-social approach and recognising their rights (Smith & Smith, 1991).

Based on the explanation above, this study will contribute to an understanding of the uniqueness of the leprosy colony in the Sitanala leprosy village based on the perspective of persons affected by leprosy. It will also provide basic information about the leprosy colony, so that it can be used by other scholars who want to explore more about this community. Moreover, the study will generate new knowledge and understanding of their lived experiences and perspectives on community empowerment and social inclusion programs in the Sitanala leprosy village. It is also expected that the findings will help create new discussions with social workers and other professionals, volunteers, government, and non-government organisations regarding the design and implementation of a future community empowerment and social inclusion program that better addresses the needs of persons affected by leprosy.

1.6. Research aims

The aims of this study are to:

1. Explore the leprosy colony in Sitanala and its culture;
2. Consider the implementation of the community empowerment and social inclusion program in the leprosy colony and its use by people affected by leprosy;
3. Analyse the experiences and perceptions of people affected by leprosy about community empowerment and social inclusion program and its impact;
4. Contribute to the knowledge base about what key elements are required for a successful community empowerment and social inclusion program;
5. Suggest policy and practice implications for relevant stakeholders.

1.7. Research questions

The main research questions to be addressed within the context of this study are:

1. What are the conditions of the leprosy colony and people living there?

2. How are the community empowerment and social inclusion program implemented and what impacts does it have on the Sitanala community and people affected by leprosy?

To explore the main research questions further, the following sub questions will be addressed:

- What is the origin and nature of the leprosy colony?
- What are the current conditions in the leprosy colony?
- How do people live there?
- What is the leprosy colony's culture?
- How do persons affected by leprosy sustain this colony?
- What are the services related to the community empowerment and social inclusion programs in the leprosy colony?
- How is the community empowerment and social inclusion program implemented?
- How do people benefit from the program and services?
- What are the experiences of persons affected by leprosy in receiving the community empowerment and social inclusion program?
- What are their perceptions of the community empowerment and social inclusion program?
- Does the community empowerment and social inclusion program empower this leprosy colony?
- Does the community empowerment and social inclusion program facilitate participation in community activities?
- What key elements are required to enhance the benefit of the community empowerment and social inclusion program to the community?
- What are the implications for policy and practice?

1.8. Research design and methodology

This study has taken an exploratory and descriptive approach; complemented through critical ethnography (Carspecken, 1996) and qualitative design for addressing the research aims and questions. Critical ethnography emphasises processes of unfairness or injustice within a particular lived domain as ethical

responsibility. This means the critical ethnographer contributes to emancipated knowledge and discourses of social justice. This model is very useful in this research because it represents and analyses social life for the political purpose of overcoming social oppression.

During the data collection, I used participant observation, focus group discussion (FGD) and in-depth interviews. I also used study documentation as a part of data collection. The documentation collected was related to policies of the government and local government and other local documents available. I observed actions or interactions, behaviour and listened to conversations while simultaneously observing the context (particularly the time and location) in which these actions are undertaken. I was involved in some social activities such as *pengajian* (communal Islamic studies), *posyandu* (centre for pre- and postnatal health care and information for women and for children), a wedding, delivering social aids (rice and daily goods), and helped in starting a community welfare bank. The process was written in memos and field notes.

In-depth interviews were conducted with 12 participants. Five focus group discussions with 36 participants had been conducted also to get general ideas about their living experiences in the leprosy colony. This information was used to cross check the consistency of in-depth interview results. I found the participants after discussing with the head of the village regarding those individuals who have the potential to become participants, making a list of potential participants, filtering them during the participant recruitment process by selecting those participants most likely to be able to give useful information and who were representative of age and gender, and by confirming their willingness to participate in the research through a consent form.

Data analysis in this research was conducted using a qualitative analysis technique. The aim of qualitative data analysis is to find meaning in the information collected. This involves thematic analysis and micro-analysis of selected segments. To do it, I combined all the data available such as secondary written sources from Ministry of

Health, Ministry of Social Affairs, village office and District Social Office with participant observations (reflective journal and direct recordings), with more formal interviews and focus group data; and checked the consistency. More details about research method is discussed in chapter 4.

1.9. Presentation of the thesis

The thesis will be presented in ten chapters. The next chapter reviews relevant literature and a theoretical approach that can be used to explore the relationship between leprosy, disability, stigma, community empowerment and social inclusion. Chapter 3 discusses key intervention approaches, which were/are influenced by specific theories or models. In chapter 4, the research methodology is presented and justified. Chapter 5 describes the government policies in relation to persons affected by leprosy and disability. Chapter 6 presents various Community Empowerment and Social Inclusion (CESI) programs in Sitanala. Chapter 7 describes the social and historical context of the Sitanala leprosy village. Chapter 8 presents the experiences of people with leprosy in receiving the community empowerment and social inclusion program. This chapter also discusses whether the community empowerment and social inclusion program really empowers and facilitates their participation in community activities or not. Chapter 9 provides theorising and analysing the practice of community empowerment and social inclusion in Sitanala. Chapter 10 provides the conclusion and recommendations of the study. It also identifies limitations and potential areas of future research.

*'The biggest disease today is not leprosy or tuberculosis,
but rather the feeling of being unwanted.'*

(Mother Teresa)

Chapter 2: Literature review

2.1. Introduction

Leprosy or Hansen's disease prompts much concern and interest from different professions as well as academia. This is because the disease, which is caused by the leprosy bacillus, *Mycobacterium leprae*, has a dreadful effect. If it is not detected early enough, it will lead to deformity and disability (Hatta et al., 2010). The topic of this research is the impact of community empowerment and social inclusion in the leprosy colony. This chapter will review concepts and previous studies that relate to the topic. The purpose of this literature review is to get more understanding of the socio-economic and cultural issues of leprosy and interventions for social problems related to leprosy and identify research gaps and questions.

2.2. A brief overview of leprosy

Based on the historical record, leprosy has haunted the lives of human beings for a long time ago. This disease was recognised in ancient civilizations in China, Egypt, and India. A written reference about leprosy was first discovered in an Egyptian papyrus document dated 1550 BC. Around 600 BC, people in India had written about a disease resembling leprosy (Browne, 1985; Luka, 2010). In Europe, leprosy appeared for the first time in the records of ancient Greece, after the troops of Alexander the Great returned from India, and in Rome in 62 BC (Manchester, 1984). The discovery in India in 2009 of skeletons of people with leprosy, shows that the disease has existed since at least 4,000 years ago. The term 'leprosy' originally came from the word 'lepra' that mentioned in the Greek New Testament, which means a scaly skin disease (Bennett, Parker, & Robson, 2008; Kearns & Nash, 2013; Worobec, 2012).

Historically, leprosy was feared and misunderstood by common people in that time. They believed that leprosy was a hereditary disease, a curse, or a punishment from God. People at that time also considered that the disease is highly contagious. Leprosy patients were treated as a deviant group of people. Consequently, many of them were stigmatized and ostracised. For example, in Europe during Middle Ages, leprosy patients had to wear special clothing, and ring bells to warn people around them of their approach. In certain places, they had to walk in a certain way, depending on which direction the wind blew. Leprosy was often treated as a 'living death'. Even their families could claim their inheritance (Moore, 1990). For leprosy patients who could not provide a specific isolation room in their houses, they had to accept that they would be ostracised and collected in leprosy colonies named *lazarets* or *leprosaria*, to control the spread of the disease and were offered little treatment (Bennett et al., 2008). Due to the fear of contracting the disease, special currency was issued in the leprosy colonies, to be used only among persons affected by leprosy. In church, they had to sit on a separate seat and using the basin for holy water separately. In some cases, the church provided a 'leper's window' or slot in the church to observe services from outside the church (Kearns & Nash, 2013).

At the end of the 19th century, the traditional view of leprosy as a scary disease started to decrease. This is because Dr Armauer Gerhard Henrik Hansen of Norway in 1873 had successfully identified the germ that causes leprosy under a microscope (Feeny, 1964; Rees, 1989). Hansen's discovery of *Mycobacterium leprae* proved that leprosy in general is like other diseases. This was different from the 'dark ages' that labelled and associated the disease with superstition and horror (Obregón, 1996).

In the early 20th century, leprosy doctors often treated their patients by injecting oil from the chaulmoogra nut. This treatment resulted in a tremendous pain. Many patients were getting benefits, but the long-term effects of this treatment were still questionable (Browne, 1985). Attention to leprosy increased when the U.S. Public Health Service established the first national Leprosarium in Carville, Louisiana, in 1921. This leprosarium became an institution for people with leprosy, a hospital for experimenting with treatments for leprosy and a laboratory to study the organism.

Thus, the centre became a place for leprosy patients who sought medical treatment and a scientific research centre to find a cure for this disease (Jacobson & Krahenbuhl, 1999).

Modern treatment of leprosy first appeared in the late 1940s through introducing dapsone. Unfortunately, leprosy bacilli later became resistant to this drug (Browne, 1985). In 1941, promin, a sulfone drug, had been found. It successfully cured leprosy, but the injection of this drug was very painful. People called promin the "Miracle of Carville" (Trautman, 1990). Until the end of the 1950s, dapsone pills pioneered by Dr R.G. Cochrane at Carville, were still an option in the treatment of leprosy (Jacobson, 1994). Finally, in 1960, rifampicin and clofazimine had been discovered to cure leprosy (Kearns & Nash, 2013). In the 1970s the use of multi-drug treatment (MDT) regimen for leprosy successfully developed on the island of Malta. In 1981, MDT, a combination of three drugs: dapsone, rifampicin, and clofazimine for treatment was first recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO). Treatment using MDT takes from six months to a year or even more, depending on the strength of leprosy infection (Curtiss et al., 2001; Ladhani, 1997; Lancet, 2009). Because the treatment process is long term, many patients discontinue the treatment. As a result, the risk of drug resistance in leprosy treatment is very high (Luka, 2010). In 1995, WHO started to provide free MDT for all leprosy patients in the world (Rodrigues & Lockwood, 2011). Now, MDT is still the best treatment in preventing nerve damage, deformity, disability, and further transmission. Researchers also are still working to develop a vaccine and methods to detect leprosy early, to start treatment earlier (Rodrigues & Lockwood, 2011).

The general assumption that leprosy was an hereditary disease that could be transmitted easily, through even unintentional touch, turned out to be a myth. This is because leprosy is a most difficult transferable disease, compared to other infectious diseases. The transmission of *M. leprae* through the skin lesions is also unlikely as the bacteria does not infect through skin contact (Cairns et al., 2004; Frist, 2003). Recent studies of leprosy indicate that 95% of people nowadays are naturally immune to the leprosy germ (Kearns & Nash, 2013; Scollard et al., 2006). How leprosy

is transmitted has invited debate among professionals (Hatta et al., 1995). However, it is believed that humans are a major host of *M. leprae* (Adriaty, Wahyuni, Iswahyudi, Agusni, & Izumi, 2010). Thus, those who are already infected with multi-bacillary leprosy and receive no treatment with a combination of two or three anti-leprosy drugs (MDT), can be a major source of infection (Franzblau et al., 1988; Wheeler, 1984). A study conducted by Bryceson and Pfalzgraff (1990), shows that leprosy is spread through droplets from the nose and mouth; and it can also through close and intense long-term contact. However, they believe that the nose is a major route for entry and exit of the bacteria. Most likely, the disease spreads through coughing and sneezing.

The incubation period of this disease is about 5-7 years longer than other bacterial disease. The shortest incubation period is 2-3 years, and the longest period is 40 years. The culmination of this disease is in young adulthood, between 20-30 years old. The disease is rarely found in children under 5 years old (Perkins & Spiegel, 1998). This long incubation period means that early signs and symptoms of leprosy are very subtle and occur slowly. Common signs of leprosy include spots on the skin; it may be slightly red, darker, or lighter than the normal skin. The spots are likely to become numb and have lost hair. These spots often appear on the arms, legs or back. This explains why diagnosis of leprosy is often made from the anaesthetic skin lesions and inflammation of peripheral nerve trunks (ILEP, 2011).

Regarding the leprosy spectrum, Ridley and Jopling (1966), classified leprosy into six groups:

- Indeterminate leprosy (I);
- Tuberculoid leprosy (TT);
- Borderline tuberculoid leprosy (BT)
- Borderline or mid-borderline leprosy (BB)
- Borderline lepromatous leprosy (BL); and
- Lepromatous leprosy (LL).

Based on the number of skin lesions, WHO divided leprosy into two groups, namely paucibacillary leprosy (PB) and multibacillary leprosy (MB). Based on this classification, I, TT and BT are classified as paucibacillary, whilst BB, BL and LL types are designated as multibacillary (WHO, 1982). Thus, nowadays, paucibacillary leprosy (PB) often is called as 'leprosy', whilst multibacillary leprosy (MB) is called as 'lepomatous leprosy'. PB is characterized by few skin lesions with no bacilli (*M. leprae*) seen in a skin smear. On the other hand, MB is characterized by skin lesions over 5 and with bacilli (Kumar, Girdhar, & Girdhar, 2012). According to Parkash (2009), PB is less severe and more superficial than MB. This is because the affected person manifests considerable biological resistance to the disease, so it is less likely to evolve, and even if it develops, it will be very slow growing. This is different from MB, in which the affected person manifests no resistance to the disease. This type involves primarily the nerve trunks and it tends to cause swollen and hardened limbs. At first, MB patients experience irritation and pain, followed by loss of sensation in spots. Thus, the nerve becomes paralysed and that causes difficulty in walking or moving the limbs.

In relation to disability due to leprosy, according to Brandsma and van Brakel (2003), in 1998, WHO has set disability grading as follows:

- Mild disability; warning of possible trouble in the future, need for education.
- Moderate disability; therapeutic action needed to prevent severe disability.
- Severe disability; may be too far advanced for effective treatment under field conditions.

Table 2.1
WHO Leprosy Disability Grading

Grade	Hands and Feet	Eyes
0	No loss of sensation, no visible deformity or damage	No eye problem due to leprosy, no evidence of visual loss
1	Loss of sensation present, but no visible deformity or damage	Eye problem due to leprosy present, but vision not severely affected as a result of this
2	Visible deformity or damage present	Severe visual impairment

Source: Brandsma and van Brakel (2003)

Leprosy can essentially be cured, and if treatment is given in the early stages, the further occurrence of disability can be prevented. In this context, early detection of leprosy and treatment by Multidrug therapy (MDT) are the most important steps in preventing deformity and disability (Grange & Lethaby, 2004). For treatment, MDT with three antibiotics (dapson, rifampicin, and clofazimine) is used for MB, while a modified MDT with two antibiotics (dapson and rifampicin) is recommended for PB and composes most current treatments today. Since 1982, WHO has advocated the use of MDT regimens to treat PB (6 months) and MB (12 months). This regimen has served as the cornerstone for elimination efforts (Dogra, Narang, & Kumar, 2013; Prasad & Kaviarasan, 2010).

2.3. Leprosy and social exclusion

It is a fact that the health sector has made the greatest contribution to leprosy research. Much of this research has focused on etiology, the spread of disease and the microbiological aspects of leprosy (Lobo & Narain, 2005; Perkins & Spiegel, 1998; Rodrigues & Lockwood, 2011). However, the over emphasis on health issues has meant that the social aspects of leprosy are overlooked. This creates a gap between the health issues and social issues related to leprosy (Kazeem & Adegun, 2011; Walter, 1999). Psychosocial problems are often overlooked during their medical treatment. This contrasts with the definition of well-being that includes all aspects such as physical, intellectual, emotional, social, and spiritual that must be viewed as

a whole (DuBois & Krogsrud Miley, 2011). This could partly explain why progress on leprosy control through medical treatment has not been followed by successful programs dealing with the social impact of leprosy. For example, most persons affected by leprosy still live in poor conditions, isolated from society.

Social exclusion as a concept originally came from France in 1960s. It refers to the risk associated to the loss of collective values between individual and society due to the destruction of the social fabric (Bhalla & Lapeyre, 1999). There are at least three paradigms to understand social exclusion (Jenks, 2003; Silver, 1994; Singer, 1997). The first paradigm is the specialisation paradigm that emphasises social exclusion as a situation or a process of marginalisation experienced by individuals. Social exclusion therefore reflects discrimination to full participation in their society. The second paradigm is the solidarity paradigm. This paradigm highlights social exclusion as the structural process in the society because of the malfunctioning of social institutions. This leads to the breakdown of the social cohesion and fragmented social relations. In other word, the social institutions failed to construct social order and to integrate individuals within the community (Room, 1995). The third paradigm is called the monopoly paradigm, which views social exclusion in terms of monopoly. In this context, society is hierarchical, and a different group controls the resources and creates barriers to other groups. This group also promotes social solidarity within the group. Therefore, the other groups faced social restriction to access occupation, cultural resources, goods, and services (Appasamy, Guham, Hema, Majumdar, & Vaidyanathan, 1996).

As a complex concept, social exclusion is a process that involves power relations among social actors (Bhalla & Lapeyre, 1999; Rodgers, Gore, & Figueiredo, 1995). According to de Haan (1998), social exclusion is the opposite of social integration; and as a multi-dimensional concept, it involves economic, social, and political spheres. Furthermore, de Haan and Maxwell (1998) suggest using three arenas and elements to identify social exclusion: (1) *rights* (human, legal/civic, democratic); (2) *resources* (human and social capital, labour markets, product markets, state

provisions, common property resources); and (3) *relationships* (family networks, wider support networks, voluntary organisations).

Available literature illustrates that leprosy stigma creates an extreme social exclusion (Coveying-Kwong, Chan, & Leung, 2001; Weiss, Ramakrishna, & Somma, 2006). Leprosy studies consistently show that many persons affected by leprosy suffered from social rejection and experience socioeconomic difficulties due to leprosy stigma (Nicholls, 2000). Regarding this, Kazeem and Adegun (2011) notes that the study of leprosy stigma should be understood through the historical, social, economic, and political context. By using this approach, it will be beneficial to design effective and sustainable interventions to deconstruct leprosy stigma to gain acceptance, care and support for persons affected by leprosy. In this section, the author believes that leprosy stigma leads persons affected by leprosy to experience social exclusion.

The impact of leprosy stigma often becomes a greater source of suffering than symptoms of the disease (Kaur & Gandhi, 2003; Kaur & van Brakel, 2002b). Individuals with leprosy tend to have emotional stress and anxiety that potentially lead to mental disorder and lower quality of life (Peters & Eshiet, 2002; Salodkar, Tiwari, & Zodpey, 2000). They become isolated and forced to live in leprosy colonies (Kaur & van Brakel, 2002b). According to Scott (2000), persons affected by leprosy need counselling and psychosocial support due to grief. Their needs are for self-acceptance, family acceptance and community acceptance. Through a social exclusion lens, it shows that leprosy has affected their rights, resources, and relationships.

At the institutional and legislative level, Krishnatray and Melkote (1998) mentioned that persons affected by leprosy in India are prohibited from obtaining a driver's licence due to the Motor Vehicles Act (1939) although they only suffer from 25% sensory loss of their limbs. In Japan, even though, the government had withdrawn policy about leprosy in 1996, many persons affected by leprosy had become disadvantaged by the policy and already lost their property. It has violated human rights due to many practices such as abortion, sterilisation, and isolation on a remote

Island long after the discovery of MDT (Watts, 2001). According to Burki (2009), leprosy stigma has not been explored in policy debate, since in some countries, leprosy is no longer seen as a public health problem. Nowadays the governments are still shy to enact this issue in legislation. Sometimes it is enacted but the implementation is hard due to low budgets (Kazeem & Adegun, 2011).

In the medical context, there were some cases where doctors in India refused to treat leprosy patients (Jenks, 2003). This has also been found to be the case also in Malaysia, where dental clinicians in the Gambak Hospital routinely refused to treat them (Bedford, 2013). According to Scott (2000) and Arole, Premkumar, Arole, Maury, and Saunderson (2002), studies have shown that many professional medical workers often display the highest-level stigma when treating leprosy patients. According to White (2008), these phenomena reflect iatrogenic stigma (stigma produced by the attitude and behaviours of professional health workers). This can be seen through a study conducted in Nigeria in which many nurses still have fear of leprosy and lack knowledge about the disease (Awofeso, 1992). Surprisingly, a study in Guyana shows misconception and prejudice about leprosy and some health workers still believe that leprosy patients need to be isolated (Briden & Maguire, 2003).

The difficulties experienced by persons affected by leprosy to access medical services have been discussed and documented by many scholars (Kaur & van Brakel, 2002b; Tsutsumi et al., 2004). Due to fear of discrimination, many persons with leprosy often conceal their disease, delay in seeking treatment and are less motivated to continue their medical treatments (van Brakel, 2003; Varkevisser et al., 2009; White, 2002; Yamaguchi, Poudel, & Jimba, 2013). As a result, their leprosy becomes more severe and the risk of complications is increased (Heijnders & van Der Meij, 2006). Another consequence affecting the transmission of the disease is being unable to monitor those who have not received any medical treatment (Barrett, 2005). Patients of leprosy often frustrated in continuing their treatment due to the length of time that lead to potential for drug resistance (Kaur & van Brakel, 2002b). In general, stigma makes public health services for leprosy patients more difficult and complicated.

In the economic context, poverty is a crucial problem that is often examined by scholars. Leprosy stigma creates social instability in a self-sufficient community and worsening conditions of those who are already poor. Most of them are refused employment or lose their jobs due to their disease and complications that lead to brutal consequences on the financial burden (Kaur & Ramesh, 1994; Rafferty, 2005; White, 2009). A study in India shows that 16-44% of persons affected by leprosy experienced a fall in their income (Palande, Rao, & Rao, 2000). In South Africa, many of them concealed their disease from their employer because of the fear of losing their job (Scott, 2000). Job loss leads them to live in extreme poverty, with few opportunities of earning income. Therefore, many persons affected by leprosy end up as beggars and begging is their main source of income (de Stigter, de Geus, & Heynders, 2000; Kumar & Anbalagan, 1983; Link & Phelan, 2001).

The beggars experience *dehabilitation*, which is a process of social estrangement and progressive loosening of social bonds with their families and communities. This phenomenon happens basically due to lack of social support and self-confidence (Kaur & van Brakel, 2002b). This means the community has failed to deal effectively with leprosy. Many people with leprosy who live as beggars epitomise stigmatisation and degradation (Kaur & van Brakel, 2002b; Navon, 1998; Nicholls & Smith, 2002). Other studies revealed that social stigma and deformities contribute to socio-economic deterioration of persons affected by leprosy. Those who have deformities experience 10 times the social and economic problems compared to persons affected by leprosy without deformity (Kopparty, 1995; Kumar & Anbalagan, 1983). From this point, it can be concluded that physical impairment, social stigma, and participation restriction contribute to failure of rehabilitation and socio-economic deterioration.

Their socioeconomic condition also influences their inconsistency of access to healthcare facilities and continuing their treatment (Pal, Ramanathan, & Ramu, 1985). According to Neira (2001), poverty can be viewed as a cause and a result of leprosy. Poverty as a cause means: the potential of ill health, slum housing and poor standards of living, lead to low immunity. Poverty thus refers to permanent disability

and leprosy stigma that contribute to their economic deterioration. Regarding this, White (2009) believes that ethnography may help to contribute effective interventions for them.

In a relationships context, leprosy stigma also affects social relationships in families and communities. According to Scott (2000), one third of leprosy patients experienced desertion by their marriage partner. Unmarried persons affected by leprosy also have difficulty finding a marriage partner even though they carry no signs of the disease (Deepak, Gopal, & Hisch, 2000; Pfaltzgraff & Bryceson, 1989). In some cases, they also experienced segregation within their families (Burathoki, Varkevisser, Lever, Vink, & Situala, 2004; de Stigter et al., 2000). In general, most persons affected by leprosy are unable to sleep or eat with their families and experience restriction of attendance at social activities such as festivals, formal and informal gatherings, markets, employment, local water supply and other public facilities. Their children also have difficulty attending education due to discrimination between those who have leprosy and those who do not have leprosy and then are forbidden to marry (Croft & Croft, 1999; Nicholls, 2000; Pfaltzgraff & Bryceson, 1989).

Gender is another issue that has been examined by many scholars in the context of leprosy-related stigma. Many studies identified that women suffer more biologically and socially due to leprosy compared to men. They had a minimal access to health education and health care. Women also experience more rejection from their spouse, their community and more loss of self-respect compared to men (Arole et al., 2002; Salodkar et al., 2000; Shale, 2000; Vlassoff, Khot, & Rao, 1996). Women with leprosy have been viewed as a threat to the family. This fear prevents their emotional bonding with their children. As reported from Nagpur, India, 49% of breast-feeding mothers with leprosy had to stop breast feeding their children due to fear of contracting the disease (Vlassoff et al., 1996). According to Jenks (2003), women were isolated from their daily tasks, such as cooking for everyone and forbidden to touch others. They also faced restriction on going out, travelling, attending festivals, worship places, marriages, and other family activities.

A study conducted in South East Nigeria between 1988 and 1997 reveals that women tended to have late detection and treatment of leprosy that led to complications and disability (Singhasivanon et al., 2004; Withington et al., 2003; World Health Organization, 2006). Similarly, in Southern Nigeria, Peters and Eshiet (2002) found that most women with leprosy who came to health facilities usually had more visible deformity. In Taiwan, women affected by leprosy usually have physical impairment and disability. If elderly, they also must survive with other chronic health diseases of the aged (Shieh, Wang, & Lin, 2006). Other studies mentioned that women with leprosy are also more vulnerable to abuse and have less access to health facilities (Le Grand, 1997; Shale, 2000; Vlassoff et al., 1996). This phenomenon happens because in many communities the position of women is more inferior than that of men (Varkevisser et al., 2009). The dominance of male general health care workers also contributes as a barrier for women to access health facilities for reasons of privacy/modesty (Alubo, Patrobas, Varkevisser, & Lever, 2003; Burathoki et al., 2004).

A study of Varkevisser et al. (2009) which was conducted in Indonesia, Nigeria, Nepal, and Brazil considered the reasons why women with leprosy were under reporting. Some factors that contribute to this are strong patriarchal traditions, the low status of women, the limited mobility, illiteracy, and poor knowledge of leprosy. However, these studies do not address the voices of women and ignore the strengths of women coping with the stigma.

2.4. Stigmatisation of leprosy

Stigma can be defined as *'an attribute that is deeply discrediting and that reduces the barrier from a whole and usual person to a tainted, discounted one'* (Goffman, 1963, p. 3). According to Heijnders and van Der Meij (2006), stigma is a social process that exists when elements of labelling, stereotyping, separation, status loss and discrimination occur in a power situation that allows them. The term 'stigma' originally came from a Greek word to describe the mark burnt on to certain people's skin to make their social status visible. Usually they were slaves, and the mark was intended to facilitate recognition and return them to owners when they escaped

(Falk, 2001; Goffman, 1963). The word stigma therefore is often used to indicate a *'mark of disgrace or physical disorder'* (Hotez, 2008, p. 1). Currently, the word 'stigma' refers to a feature of an individual that is discredited by their peers, which detracts from viewing the person as a whole (Falk, 2001). In everyday life, the stigma is institutionalised through interpersonal communication in society. It then spreads and is interpreted continuously by using languages and symbols.

From a sociological perspective, it is natural that to create a collective identity in a social group, members of the group stigmatise a difference. Determining who is different allows them to label themselves as 'insiders' and justify themselves as 'normal' (Falk, 2001). However, what is regarded as deviant in a community, in fact, it may be considered 'normal' by other communities (Jones et al., 1984). Consequently, people may have false assumptions influenced by the public views (Link, Phelan, Bresnahan, Stueve, & Pescosolido, 1999). Stigma later becomes a collective opinion, where people in the community can feel prejudice against the others. Thus, people must follow the opinion because of labelling and fear of rejection by the majority (Jones et al., 1984).

Stigma evolves through different stages. First, there is an element of social selection, in which the difference in individuals is overlooked, but then some differences become the focus of stigma and discrimination (Link & Phelan, 2001). It also occurs in health-related stigma, where there are certain medical conditions that are considered socially less acceptable than other diseases. For example, cancer has less stigma compared to mental illness and leprosy. Second, the different labels should be associated with negative stereotypes, such as the community's belief that mental illness is dangerous, or leprosy is very contagious.

When the differences and stereotypes happen, there will be a separation between 'us' and 'them'. This separation becomes a justification of 'us' to discriminate against 'them'. These differences therefore become the status of the individuals concerned (Link & Phelan, 2001). The stigma can then lead to social exclusion and affect aspects of a person's life. Those who are discriminated against usually have a low social

power, limited ability to stigmatise others, and feel isolated (Link & Phelan, 2001; Weiss et al., 2006). Their lower social power may contribute to the stigma of their condition. For example, socio-economic stigma can lead to a poor health environment, and this can affect people's health. Furthermore, health-related stigma may cause socio-economic problems (Weiss et al., 2006). It is a vicious circle.

Goffman (1963), an expert in the field of stigma, identified three aspects of the differences that contribute to creating stigma, such as abominations (disfigurement) of the body, blemishes of individual character and tribal identity. In relation to health-related stigma, Weiss et al. (2006) have analysed Goffman's work related to health policy, especially in developing countries. First, the language used by Goffman is outdated and somewhat difficult to use either as a definition or application to the policies. Second, the term stigma used by Goffman is so common that it still needs more exploration in relation to health-related stigma. Third, the concept of dominant norm would be problematic as it seems to deny the success of multicultural societies. This is because the concept of dominant culture in the reality does not fully lead to stigma and discrimination in multicultural societies. Based on the complexity of stigma, Cross (2006) believes that different interventions are required, as the education of those who are 'normal' is not enough to eliminate health-related stigma. This is because there are other dimensions, such as felt-stigma (resulted from storytelling), that may not be eliminated through education for the potential stigmatisers only.

Leprosy stigma is often interpreted in several ways. Some people strongly feel that suffering from leprosy is shameful and unacceptable in the normal society. Leprosy stigma is also called leprosy-related stigma, leprostigma and stigma of leprosy. Many studies have been conducted by scholars on the effects of stigma against persons with leprosy that affect their mobility, interpersonal relationships, marriage, work, leisure time and involvement in social and religious activities (Bainson & van den Borne, 1998). In general, stigma can be divided into two categories: public stigma and self-stigmatisation. Here, self-stigma is related to shame and lowered self-esteem, while public stigma is associated with the general public's prejudice (Arboleda-Florez,

2002; van Brakel et al., 2012). In relation to leprosy stigma, stigma can be classified into 3 categories. First, perceived stigma, refers to stigma that is viewed from the perspective of people with leprosy. This involves feelings of worthlessness, shame, introversion, and withdrawal from society, triggered by negative stereotypes. Second, self-stigma, refers to fears of being discriminated against. It is internalised in the persons affected by leprosy. Third, experienced stigma (enacted), in which people with leprosy experience discrimination. These stigmas lead to difficulties in social participation, social exclusion, and lower quality of life of leprosy patients (Bainson & van den Borne, 1998). Severe deformity and disfigurement of persons with leprosy also contribute to strengthening the stigma (Kaur & van Brakel, 2002a; Tsutsumi et al., 2007), while those without visible deformity or ulceration are easier to integrate into society (Cross & Choudhary, 2005; El Hassan, Khalil, & El-Hassan, 2002).

Understanding about how leprosy stigma developed is very important for any efforts to reduce stigma. Stigma does not develop automatically, but it develops through two stages: a cognitive dimension stage and an affective stage. In the first phase, leprosy affects the person's mind, while in the second stage, there is a tendency in decreasing value, individually or socially (van Brakel, 2006). A study conducted by Heijnders (2004), in Nepal shows a similar process, in which patients with leprosy passed two stages in coping with their condition, involving concealment and exposure stages. In the changes from the first stage to the second stage, visible signs of leprosy trigger exposure and discrimination. During that process, stigma plays an important role in creating inequality in the community. Other factors such as sex, age and social class also contribute in developing stigma (Weiss & Ramakrishna, 2006).

There are many factors contributing to the stigma of leprosy and it varies across communities and continents. The first factor that has been identified through the review of literature is cultural beliefs and misconception about leprosy stigma (Edmond, 2006; Kazeem & Adegun, 2011; Volinn, 1989; Wong, 2004). Consequently, many persons affected by leprosy are outcast by general society. In this view, persons affected by leprosy are cursed or victims of witchcraft; blameworthy and immoral; and carry disease that is well deserved (Nsagha et al., 2011). For example, people in

India believed that leprosy is basically a punishment from God due to their sins (Browne, 1975; Muthankar, 1979; Richards, 1977). Whilst in China, leprosy is seen as a consequence of immoral behaviours, such as having sex with prostitution, people in Botswana see leprosy as bad or unclean blood, evil spirits, local charms, witchcraft or breaking a taboo and they call leprosy 'ngara' or 'lepero' (Kumaresan & Maganu, 1994). The belief that leprosy is a matter of heredity is also found in Africa, India, China, and Malaysia (Chen & Sim, 1986; Gussow, 1989). A study conducted in Nepal presents that 64% of interviewed respondents believed that leprosy was highly contagious, about 9% of respondents see leprosy as a curse from God, and 18% of them believe that leprosy is both contagious and a curse from God (de Stigter et al., 2000). A study conducted by Alubo et al. (2003) in Nigeria shows that members of the community avoid handshaking with persons affected by leprosy because of their fear of contracting the disease.

In the context of Indonesia, several studies about leprosy stigma have been carried out. However, a lack of knowledge in the interventions to reduce stigma from the perspective of persons affected by leprosy has been identified. A research conducted by Peters et al. (2012) in Indonesia shows that traditional beliefs and religious views play important roles in creating stigma which must be taken into consideration. Regarding this, Elissen (1991) notes that, the impact of these views is that persons affected by leprosy tend to self-discriminate. Similar research in Uttar Pradesh, India also reveals that most people who believe that leprosy is about blood or divine curse, are illiterate and know little about leprosy (Rao, Barkataki, & Kumar, 2006). Surprisingly, research about the same topic in Karachi, Pakistan shows the opposite results. Other members of the community accept persons affected by leprosy very well and treat them in positive ways (Nisar, Khan, Qadri, & Shah, 2007). These findings suggest the fact that views and attitudes towards persons affected by leprosy should be contextual and cannot be generalised.

The second factor which contributes to the stigma of leprosy is lack of knowledge and awareness related to leprosy in the community (Rafferty, 2005; Rao et al., 2006; Rensen, Sudhakar, Gopal, & van Brakel, 2011; Tsutsumi et al., 2007; Wong, 2004).

Insufficient information about the nature of leprosy tends to make the public afraid of contracting the disease. Regarding this, Mehari (2008) criticises elite and educated people who contribute to the creation of stigma. Her study about persons affected by leprosy in Ethiopia shows that leprosy affected persons used to be highly valued and churches and rulers of Ethiopia provided them with charity. However, at the beginning of the twelfth century with the popularity of leprosarium and euro-centric explanations of leprosy, the positive attitude toward leprosy was challenged. As a result, the elite people became fearful about leprosy, which isolated the sufferers.

Insufficient knowledge about leprosy also causes delay in seeking medical treatment. Alubo et al. (2003) states that leprosy patients in Northern Nigeria often think they have ring worm, rashes, eczema, or general skin disease when presenting to health care centres for the first time. In addition, some of them also think that they have fever due to malaria, not leprosy. The failure to recognise the signs and symptoms shows that most people still lack knowledge and awareness about leprosy (Awofeso, 1995). A study conducted by Reddy, Satpathy, Krishnan, and Srinivasan (1985) in Northern Nigeria found 47% of leprosy patients have late detection of leprosy because they went to the traditional healers first before coming to health care centres. This trend also happens in Adamawa State and Bostwana (Kumaresan & Maganu, 1994; van de Weg, Post, Lucassen, de Jong, & van den Broek, 1998).

Poor knowledge and misconceptions are also found in general health care workers. A study conducted in Nigeria shows that 65% of final year nurse students believe that leprosy was highly contagious, and deformity was inevitable (Awofeso, 1992). Other study in the Philippines also reveals that 88.4% of general health care workers agree with the germ theory of disease, 70% agreed that leprosy was highly contagious and about 11.6% still believe that leprosy is caused by bad 'unclean blood' and witchcraft (Valencia, 1983). Sadly, in Guyana, 50% of general health care workers did not know that leprosy is curable and 15% of them think that leprosy can be easily contracted through touching (Wong, 2004).

The third factor that contributes to leprosy stigma is disability and deformity. This means patients with lepromatous leprosy (shown by deformity in physical appearance facial symptoms - wider nose, ridged and thick skin, loss of their fingers and legs), reinforces leprosy stigma. This involves their infected ulcers and smell (Rafferty, 2005). A study in India and Myanmar shows that persons affected by leprosy experienced unsympathetic responses, insults, hate and rejection by society (Kant, 1984; Myint, Thet, Htoon, & Win, 1992; Ulrich et al., 1993). However, only those who have severe diseases, ulcerated lesions and severe deformities will likely experience leprosy stigma. Persons affected by leprosy who are without visible deformity or ulceration can easily integrate to their society (Cross & Choudhary, 2005; El Hassan et al., 2002).

2.5. Community empowerment and social inclusion (CESI)

The previous discussion has shown that stigma of leprosy led to social exclusion in various forms. Community empowerment and social inclusion programs are believed to be effective strategies to address the issues of stigma and poverty. Community empowerment can be defined as a process to enable people and communities (especially those frequently marginalized), as having both the opportunity and the capability to participate effectively in social, economic, and political spheres (Helling, Serrano, & Warren, 2005). In addition, Bishop, Frain, and Tschopp (2009) argue that community empowerment covers four elements: self-efficacy, self-advocacy, competence, and self-perceived stigma. Furthermore, it can lead to work status, adjustment to disability, functional ability, and quality of life. The term social inclusion often refers to the opposite of social exclusion. Social exclusion has a meaning that people *'do not have the opportunity for full participation in the economic and social benefits of society'* (Guildford, 2000, p. 1).

'The word rehabilitation has been in use for many years in connection with persons handicapped from causes other than leprosy' (Gokhale, 1974, p. 32). According to Allan (1958, p. 1), rehabilitation refers to *'making a person aware of his potential and then providing him with the means of attaining that potential'*. In relation to this Gokhale (1974, p. 32) states *'There are two main aspects of rehabilitation for persons*

affected by leprosy: (1) Reestablishing the economic productivity of the patient; and (2) re-assimilation in society. Without either of these, the rehabilitation is incomplete'.

Cook (2003) suggests the use of the terminology 'social inclusion' rather than 'social rehabilitation'. This is because social inclusion underpins the process of changing mainstream attitudes to address the inequality issues, commitment to fully accessible services, valuing and celebrating differences, and promoting partnership.

An alternative response to deal with social and economic hardship is through community empowerment and social inclusion interventions. These interventions aim to make persons affected by leprosy to be agents of their own socio-economic rehabilitation and integration. This is because overcoming the infection is not enough as they have difficulties in their socio-economic aspect of their lives and cannot return to their previous lifestyle (Nicholls, 2000). In relation to this, Dr Arole in International Leprosy Association Conference in Beijing, September 1998, states:

A change of paradigm is needed, recognising people as subjects, not objects, and workers as enablers and not providers. Interventions must be supportive and responsive, empowering rather than diagnostic. They must include addressing the needs and resources of the community and extending its capacity (Nicholls & Smith, 2002).

Since the introduction of multi-drug therapy (MDT) in 1981, the global leprosy prevalence has declined dramatically. For those who are disabled, socio-economic rehabilitation becomes a priority program intervention (Shumin, Diangchang, Bing, Lin, & Xioulu, 2003). According to Jenks (2003), until recently, the concept of 'rehabilitation' in which persons affected by leprosy stay as permanent residents in leprosy rehabilitation centres and engage in a different occupation such as agriculture, animal husbandry and tailoring, is now considered outdated. This is because this approach prevents persons affected by leprosy reintegrating with their family and community. Through socio-economic rehabilitation, persons affected by leprosy are assisted to regain a place in their community. By developing opportunities and helping them to find productive employment which will allow them to contribute to the economy of their families and live with dignity (Nicholls, 2000; Plagerson, 2005). In this context, Cornielje, Nicholls, and Velema (2000) believe that vocational

training, job placement and interest-free loans become an important entry point for integration in the community with equal rights and breaking the 'disability cycle' of isolation, dependence, and chronic poverty. Thus, to avoid stigma to those who cannot be active economically (elderly, young and those who have multiple impairments), the interventions should be directed into creating a supportive environment and special programs such as financial assistance and subsidised education of children (Gershon & Srinivasan, 1992). To do this, the socio-economic rehabilitation needs adequate finances and trained staff (Withington et al., 2003).

The discussion about health education and socio-economic rehabilitation is often separate in the literature. This is because the scheme of health education is commonly operated on a large scale (regional or national level), whilst socio-economic rehabilitation is generally local (Plageron, 2005). However, discussion on health education and socio-economic rehabilitation has shown that both are basically complementary. Health education targets knowledge and behaviour of daily practice between persons who are and are not affected by leprosy. Meanwhile, successful socio-economic rehabilitation recognises psychological, social, and economic factors determined by the attitude of the community towards leprosy. Furthermore, since much socio-economic rehabilitation is related to impairment, health education will help persons affected by leprosy to minimise the length of rehabilitation. In this context, socio-economic rehabilitation will be effective because it only targets those who really need it (Jenks, 2003). According to Palande et al. (2000), both programmes will have limited impact if there is no participation, ownership, and a strong educational component. Nicholls (2000) suggests the potential benefits of integrating a socio-economic rehabilitation program into a wider national scale program, so that persons affected by leprosy have a link to the existing services, rather than creating a new stand-alone project that risk further stigma. However, it is difficult to apply (Arole et al., 2002).

In providing human services to persons affected by leprosy, Deepak et al. (2000) argue that all programs should be implemented together with people with leprosy, their families and community. The programs also need to integrate with society, so it

will prevent segregation. More specifically, community empowerment and social inclusion programs should be understood by and synchronised with health services (Brandsma, Schwarz, Anderson, & Herm, 2005). An example of a synchronised program is a community-based rehabilitation (CBR) program in Kerala State, South India. Jayadevan and Balakrishnan (2002) suggest that CBR be used as a medium of community empowerment and social inclusion program because it appears to be an effective way to help to move the focus of services from medical issues to social issues. This suggests that CBR has the potential to use a social development approach for integrating people affected by leprosy. However, one needs to be aware that destigmatisation campaigns for persons affected by leprosy need to be implemented carefully, otherwise the program will be counterproductive and increase stigmatisation risk due to the messages that use symbols of stigmatisation (Jacob & Franco-Paredes, 2008).

The latest Indonesian research related to leprosy from a social perspective has been conducted in Cirebon, West Java. The results of the study show that persons affected by leprosy who are in treatment or have been declared cured still face stigma and discrimination. It suggests leprosy services should be individualised according to people's experiences, and not offered as a 'one size fits all' response (Peters et al., 2013). Previous research conducted in rural areas in Sulawesi, Indonesia highlights the difficulties faced by persons with disabilities due to leprosy. Barriers preventing them from participating in their community include lower education, income, and marriage prospects according to this study (Schuller et al., 2010). A different study in Cirebon, West Java argues that persons affected by leprosy and its context have personal knowledge that could be used when developing strategies to reduce stigma. The personal knowledge includes knowledge about leprosy, knowledge about program and knowledge about individual and social (Miranda-Galarza, Lusli, Dedding, Budge, & Zweekhorst, 2013).

2.6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the study of leprosy in the past has been dominated by the health sector (Hatta et al., 2010; Lobo & Narain, 2005; Perkins & Spiegel, 1998; Rodrigues &

Lockwood, 2011). Even though the health sector greatly contributes in the leprosy research, the over emphasis on health concerns and overlooking of social and economic matters create a large gap between health and social issues related to leprosy. This can be seen by successful programs in health sector such as leprosy control and medical treatment, but it has not been followed by good achievement in social and economic rehabilitation programs. Consequently, many people with leprosy often live in poor condition and are still excluded from general society. However, with the burgeoning social and economic problems of persons affected by leprosy, the research about stigma and culture is becoming increasingly urgent (Joseph & Rao, 1999; Kaur & van Brakel, 2002b). In relation to this, Mitchell and Shillington (2002) argued that community empowerment and social inclusion programs are believed to be an alternative solution that answers questions about stigma and poverty. A synchronised program such as a CBR model seems to be useful. However, the body of literature shows that the studies about leprosy stigma in Indonesia are few in numbers.

The findings admit the fact that stigma and discrimination against persons affected by leprosy existed since ancient civilizations to until today. However, the views and attitudes towards people affected by leprosy are varied and it should not be generalised, as in several communities such as Karachi, Pakistan, people treat them in positive ways. The literature also shows that the research about the leprosy colony, which the community empowerment and social inclusion program emphasises will fill the gap among other research (Griffiths, 2012; Voorend, van Brakel, Cross, Augustine, & Ebenso, 2011). It is also expected that the research will not only contribute to knowledge, but also help to address the issues and aspirations of persons affected by leprosy.

'The best way to find yourself is to lose yourself in the service of others.'

(Mahatma Gandhi)

Chapter 3: Intervention approaches with people affected by leprosy and disability

3.1. Introduction

This chapter discusses key intervention approaches, which were/are influenced by specific theories or models such as the social model of disability, critical theory of disability, community empowerment and social inclusion.

3.2. Social model of disability

There are three influential models in viewing disability - Hammell (2006) entitled this as 'cultural models of disability'. He asserts that the three models grow in different times and reflects a pattern of thought about disability. First, the oldest model of disability is the 'moral/religious model'. This model views disability as a punishment from God for sins that have been made. Second, the model that comes up during the enlightenment period in Western history, namely 'medical model' that describes disability as a failure in the structure and function of the body. Third, the 'social/political model' that views disability as lost or limitation of opportunities to participate in society.

The social model grew out of a strong objection to the medical model. It emerged during the 1970s when the disability rights movement occurred. This model seeks to highlight that it can be cruel assumption to view disability as a personal problem. The medical model portrays persons with disabilities (of physical, cognitive, or sensory impairments) and presents them as limited and deficient, leading to marginalisation (Bogdan & Taylor, 1987). The Union of the Physically Impaired Against Segregation (UPIAS) clarified the definition of disability as *'Disability is the disadvantage or restriction of activity caused by contemporary organization which takes no or little*

account of people who have physical impairments and thus excludes them from the mainstream of social activities' (UPIAS, 1976, p. 14). Individuals with disabilities are seen as a minority group and subject to discrimination in the ableist society. Those who promote their non-disability are superior (Barnes, Mercer, & Shakespeare, 1999). In other words, this model transforms the handicap situation into a disadvantaged minority group (Hahn, 1988; Morris, 1992). Therefore, persons with disabilities need better services and facilities related to their disabilities, provision of education and employment as well as increasing public access to the entire facilities of the able bodied (Asch & Fine, 1988).

The social model views disability as a problem that is constructed by an oppressive and discriminatory society. Persons with disabilities are a group of people who experience discrimination, and are institutionalised in society (Oliver, 1990). In this context, disability is a product of specific economic and social structures that systematically exclude them (Hughes & Patterson, 1997; Oliver, 1996; Shakespeare, 1994). This exclusion affects economic independence and their social participation and invites oppressive practice and inequality (Barnes, 1998; Erevelles, 1996). The social model greatly influences the definition of disability issued by WHO through the ICF, which states that disability is a consequence of contextual factors (environmental and individual) that limit activities and restriction in full participation in society (WHO, 2001).

The social model gains significant political support from those who live with disabilities (Oliver, 1996). This model also successfully brings disability issues into discussions related to social change (Beckett & Wrighton, 2000). Persons with disabilities cannot be discriminated against, excluded from participation, or avoided from sources such as shelter, employment, education, and public service buildings. The model changes the focus from disabled individual to societal structures (Morris, 1991; Tregaskis, 2002) and of oppression to empowerment and inclusion in the lives of individuals with disability (Barnes, 2003). It rejects the idea that disability is a personal deficiency, they believe that persons with disabilities require equal treatment and they are not alone in experiencing disabilities.

However, this model received criticism because it proposes the separation of body and culture, impairment, and disability. As a result, the body is missing from the discourse of disability (Asch, 2001; Hughes & Patterson, 1997; Shakespeare, 2004). Above all, this social model has provided a powerful framework that brings persons with disabilities back into society equally and with their rights. In other words, the social model promotes the idea that persons with disabilities are active persons in their own lives, rather than passive recipients of care.

Currently, greater consensus about the definition of disability has now emerged. This can be seen through the definition issued by the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) in 2001 and the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) in 2006. Both ICF and UNCRPD view disability as interaction between health conditions and physical features on the individual physical, social and environmental behaviours that prevent full and effective participation in society. This can be seen through UNCRPD's definition about persons with disabilities as *'those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others'* (United Nations, 2006, p. 3); whilst the ICF defines disability as the negative aspects of the interaction between an individual (with a health condition) and that individual's contextual factors (personal and environmental factors).

The ICF was developed through a lengthy process, involving academics, clinicians and the most important group that is persons with disabilities. The ICF tried to integrate disability into bio-psychosocial model of health and functioning (WHO, 2001). Figure 3.1 shows that the ICF focuses especially on the interaction between personal factors, environmental factors, the health condition, and its impact on functioning.

Figure 3.1
The ICF Interactive Model

Source: WHO (2002b)

3.3. Critical disability theory

In the context of disability, Stevens (in Oliver, Sapey, and Thomas, 2012, p. 6) believes that it cannot be denied that social work has important roles including *‘the provision of personal social work help to individuals and families, the assessment of needs, the provision of support and rehabilitation, support and training of social care staff and co-ordination of care packages’*. Social work wishes to develop better practice in anti-discriminatory practice (Hicks, 2008). However, Oliver, Sapey, and Thomas (2012, p. 6) revealed that *‘social workers have often failed to recognise the potential of working with disabled people’*. Similarly, Priestley (2004, p. 259) also criticises *‘the core role of social work as being structured to enforce dependency’* and it is often that the practice of care assessment and management mislead to *‘a technical gate-keeping mechanism’*. Disabled people also expressed their disappointment of being treated on less than equal basis in the professional/client relationship (Finkelstein, 1991).

Critical theory of disability centres on disability and views that the conception of disability should be built on the perspective of disabled people's needs. The key concern of critical disability theory is to avoid over and under inclusion of the concept of disability. Critical disability theory supports the 'universalist' concept of disability, emphasises the assumption that everyone can be placed on the continuum from disabled to not disabled. People sometimes become disabled in their life. Critical disability theory believes that it is an insufficient basis to analyse and respond to the condition of disabled people and develop social policy against the interest of the diverse population (Hosking, 2008).

The second element of critical disability theory is multidimensionality. Critical disability theory acknowledges that disability is basically a result of the politics of identity. Society tends to structure disability into social identity. Therefore, 'disability' is often used to refer to diversity of population, like other dimensions such as country, ethnicity, group, class, and gender. Critical disability theory also sees that persons with disability face subordination not only because of their disability but also influences of other dimensions. The intersection of these dimensions is important for analysis of disability issues based on social structures in society. In other words, critical disability theory believes that disability is basically multidimensional (Hosking, 2008; McDonald, Keys, & Balcazar, 2007).

The third element of critical disability theory is valuing diversity. Critical disability theory acknowledges the differences and supports equality in the framework of diversity. Ignoring the differences will make disabled persons being rejected and marginalised. Thus, a systematic response to the differences, should protect the rights of persons with disability to fully participate in their communities. The response also needs to eliminate factors and obstacles that prevent their participation (Campbell, 2002; Hosking, 2008).

According to Hosking (2008), the fourth element of critical disability theory is rights. Critical disability theory holds the view that disabled persons have a right of equality

and full integration into all aspects in the society. This means that critical disability is concerned with an individual's rights (autonomy) and their social rights (participation). Consequently, it urges the use of a rights-based approach in disability services and at the same time also values diversity and equality (Barnes & Mercer, 2006). According to Banks and Kayess (1998), advocacy for the rights of people with disability is more talk rather than action and often focuses on the weakness of people with disabilities. Therefore, a framework that contains their rights, ethics and justice is needed to secure the position of people with disabilities in modern society. In addition, the transition to achieve a rights base for disabled people requires a strong relationship in development between community, persons with disabilities and professionals (Bellamy, 1998). Regarding this, Hanley (1998) advises that social providers such as non-governmental organisations (NGOs) should involve persons with disabilities as a partner in the process of building consensus and management. This reflects the motto of 'nothing about us without us' (Yeo & Moore, 2003).

The fifth element of critical disability theory is voice. Traditionally, the voice of disabled people has been marginalised in society. Critical disability theory applauds their stories and puts their voice on the stage. Therefore, listening to their voices and valuing their perspectives should be used to understand the suffering, dependency, and worthlessness of the disabled in the society (Hosking, 2008; Scott-Hill, 2002). Regarding this, it is important to refer to Edwin Ardener's work, which proposed a theory of 'muted groups'. He argued that the dominant groups in society generate and control the dominant modes of expression. Muted groups are silenced by the structures of dominance, and if they wish to express themselves they are forced to do so through the dominant modes of expression, the dominant ideologies (Ardener, 1975). Even though the muted group theory is associated to feminist theory, it can also be applied to other silenced or disadvantaged groups (Hechter, 2004).

The sixth element of critical disability theory is language. Language influences the concept of disability and its status. This can be seen by the words describing, labelling and portraying disability. Critical disability theory sees that language is inherently political, reflecting the ideology of the society. Labelling usually uses negative

attributes that will lead to negative connotations. For example, the words such as deficient and pitiable are often presented in high and low culture or in print and visual media. Consequently, it will contribute to the image of disabled persons as highly dependent, powerless, and valueless. Changing language and labelling therefore will help to reduce and eliminate negative stereotypes (Hosking, 2008; Longmore, 1985; Zola, 1993).

The last element of critical disability theory is transformative policy. As discussed above, critical theory implies changing economic, political, and social structures through emancipation and the disability movement. Hosking (2008) states that critical disability theory is not merely the joy of theorising or improving understanding and explanation, rather it implies empowerment to gain equality and create policies of inclusion for persons with disabilities who are excluded from general society. Social construction of disability therefore provides a theoretical base to develop more effective policies. In other words, critical disability theory supports changing policies and supports democratisation (Oliver & Zarb, 1989).

3.4. Social inclusion

The previous discussion has shown that stigma of leprosy led to social exclusion in various forms. The term social inclusion often refers to the opposite of social exclusion. Hayes, Gray, and Edwards (2008) note that historically, the idea of social inclusion can be traced through the early 19th century, when sociologist Weber emphasised the importance of social cohesion. Frenchs in 1970 use *les exclus*, for those who excluded from the insurance system. Thus, this concept spread to Europe and during the 1980s and 1990s. After that time, social inclusion was identified with social exclusion as the counterpart. According to Burchardt (2002), individuals experience social exclusion when they cannot participate in key activities in the communities in which they live. Social exclusion refers to the risk associated with the loss of collective values between the individual and society due to the destruction of the social fabric (Bhalla & Lapeyre, 1999). Social exclusion also has a meaning that people *'do not have the opportunity for full participation in the economic and social benefits of society'* (Guildford, 2000, p. 1). Specifically, Levitas et al. (2007) state that

social exclusion is a complex and multi-dimensional process, in which individuals face lack of, or to denial to access of resources, rights, goods and services, and cannot participate in the community in terms of economic, social, cultural, and political aspects that affect their quality of life, equity and social cohesion. In this context, social exclusion is related to access and participation.

Social inclusion in the field of disability refers to '*greater participation in community-based activities and a broader social network*' (Abbott & Mcconkey, 2006, p. 275). It is expected that social inclusion will be helpful to combat stigma, discrimination, and social exclusion. Thus, the disabled will have full and fair access to services and activities in their communities that is no different to non-disabled citizens. In this context, social inclusion rejected the idea that people with disabilities spend their whole lives with the segregated disability services (Bates & Davis, 2004). For example, housing can be the key for successful community inclusion. However, the reality shows that the number of people who supported people with disabilities to live independently in the community remains small (Abbott & Mcconkey, 2006). This explains that social inclusion is not just about places, but also people. At this point, relationships also can be a cornerstone to achieve social inclusion. Putnam (2000) classified relationship into bridging relationship and bonding relationship. Bonding relationship is characterised by strong sense of loyalty between the parties. Family relationships are the example of bonding relationship. In reverse, bridging relationships outnumber family relationship and have a broader range of people. In this context, those who are successful usually have many bridging relationships. Unfortunately, the problem with disabled people is that they often have few bonding relationship, whilst bridging relationships are limited and poorly developed (Annison, 2006).

Social inclusion has potential advantages. For example, social inclusion helps to broaden the definition of disadvantage from focusing only on poverty issues. It also contributes to emphasising that social problems do not fall under the traditional concept of poverty. Furthermore, social inclusion provides room for political discourse related to the extremely disadvantaged in the society and mobilising

support in the community. Social inclusion also puts more effort into diminishing multiple barriers often faced by people with disabilities. That is important for creating coherent policies that are pro-disabled persons. In addition, it also highlights the importance of joint services and coordination among social providers. Social inclusion also contributes to identifying the role of social institutions, groups, and local communities, and offers structural change in the best interest of disadvantaged groups (Hayes et al., 2008).

Cook (2003) suggests the use of the terminology 'social inclusion; rather than 'social rehabilitation'. This is because social inclusion underpins the process of changing mainstream attitudes to addressing the inequality issues, commitment to fully accessible services, valuing and celebrating differences, and promoting partnership. The origin and nature of the concept of social inclusion cannot be separated from the principle of normalisation and social role valorisation. The normalisation principle suggests that people with disabilities would be easily accepted by the general society if they have pattern of life and conditions of everyday living as close as or the same as regular circumstances that exist in the community. This principle had been developed from the first time in Scandinavia before spreading to western countries. It has successfully influenced the disability service throughout 1970s and 1980s. This can be seen by the phenomenon of deinstitutionalisation of disability services in that time, whereby disabled people returned to the community to live independently (Culham, 2003; Nirje, 1999; Thomas & Woods, 2003).

In the early 1980s, Wolfensberger (1983) refined the principle of normalisation. He believed that people with disabilities are stigmatised and devalued because they rarely play valued social roles in their communities. To explain his argument, he introduced the concept of social role valorisation (SRV), which has become a popular theory. The social role valorisation theory says that it is the task of professionals to use appropriate methods to teach valued skills, so that disabled persons can perform their valued roles in their community.

It needs to be admitted that both normalisation principle and social role valorisation have made great impacts on modern rehabilitation and disability services. However, both normalisation and social role valorisation still receive criticism from other scholars. For example, Clare and Cox (2003) state that the concept of normalisation implies judgment between normal and abnormal. Therefore, it would be dangerous if professionals impose these judgments without considering personal preferences and cultural factors. Another criticism of the normalisation principle and social role valorisation theory is that they contribute to strengthen the paradigm that disability is the matter of personal tragedy that invites domination of professionals and institutional based services. It has also been argued that the concept of normalisation views persons with disabilities as deviants, and the need to build and maintain valued social roles, are questionable. Another critic suggests that the concept of normalisation is basically not to adjust persons with disabilities to the environment, but rather to the dominant social class (Silvers, Wasserman, & Mahowald, 1998).

3.5. Community empowerment

The concept of community empowerment originally comes from the earlier literatures in community psychology, community organisation and liberation education (Laverack & Wallerstein, 2001). The World Health Organization defines community empowerment as *'the process of enabling communities to increase control over their lives'* (WHO, 2015b). This definition highlights 'communities' as the subject and the setting of the process, whilst 'control' is connected to the concept of power.

Empowerment is an individual, social, and political process targeted to ensure the full involvement of people in decision and evaluation (Angeloni, 2013). Putting empowerment in the social work and social development context, Cox and Pawar (2013) believe that power and control are not the objectives of the process, but rather achieving selected goals, such as maximising equity, justice, and well-being. Furthermore, considering that some communities may experience oppression for such a long time and accept it due to frustration, for example, people affected by leprosy in Sitanala colony and similar settlements, the approach for empowerment

and consciousness-raising undertaken by community workers should reflect sensitivity and offer constantly available and ongoing support (Cox & Pawar, 2013; Pawar, 2014). Empowerment should be a right based approach. According to Pawar (2012b), the right-based approach can be defined as follows:

For conceptual clarity, the rights-based approach may be defined as an empowering approach that stems from the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which suggests that citizens have justifiable entitlement, with human dignity and worth, to basic services – for example, food, education, health, and employment, and justifiable duties to the community – and nation-states have an obligation to meet those entitlements, and citizens have obligation to meet duties (Pawar, 2012b, p. 35).

3.5.1. Theories of power

The essence of empowerment is the idea of power. This can be seen through the aim of empowerment, which is to increase the power of the disadvantaged (Ife & Tesoriero, 2006). This means individuals, groups, or communities need to take power into their own hands and redistribute it from the 'haves' to 'have nots'. For example, Ife and Tesoriero (2006) have classified the perspectives of power into four categories. Those are pluralist, elitist, structural and post structural perspectives.

3.5.3.1. Pluralist perspective

Functional sociologists such as Parsons contributed to the developing of pluralist perspective. This perspective views power in society as a variable sum. This means the total amount of power in the society is not fixed, but variable. As a consequence, in this point of view, terms such as oppression, powerless, domination and struggle are not improper to use. Empowerment is basically a process of helping the disadvantaged (individual and group) to compete more effectively by assisting them to learn and use lobbying skills and media become involved in political action, understand how the system works, and so on. Example of the implementation of this perspective in practice can be seen through the works of Alinsky (1971, 1996). Saul Alinsky, one of influential figures in community work, in 1930s, develop a model of community empowerment in Chicago's Back of the Yards neighbourhood (Finks, 1984; Stoecker, 2002). In his model, he did not change the political system, but instead simply taught African-American communities in the United States to compete

effectively in the system with other powerful groups through social action, political pressure, and publicity.

3.5.3.2. Elitist perspective

According to Weber (1946), power can be defined as the ability to influence others to do what they want, based on their interests. This involves the relation between the powerful and powerless. Those who are powerful, thus are elite. The elites have access and control of resources through their networks. Their capacities allow them to control key institutions, such as media, education, political party, social policy, bureaucracy, parliament, profession, and so on. So, it can be said that the 'elite point of view' believes that society is a hierarchy and only certain groups hold power and control (Mayo & Craig, 1995).

Based on this stance, empowerment through enhancing players' capacity to compete for political power in the game and know the rules is not enough. Considering that power is possessed by elites, Ife and Tesoriero (2006) suggest that the disadvantaged: (1) join the elite with the aim of influencing them; (2) create allies with the elites; or (3) reduce the power of elites through fundamental changes and confrontation. Even though this view received supports from its followers, Mayo and Craig (1995) warn that this view makes empowerment becomes more problematic. This is because if the amount of power in society is fixed, increasing power for one group means of decreasing power of other groups.

3.5.3.3. Structural perspective

The structural point of view highlights the importance of structural inequality or oppression as a major form of power. From the structural perspective's point of view, elites who act as a representative of a dominant group also tend to reinforce structural inequality. Therefore, it leads to unequal distribution of power (Ife & Tesoriero, 2006).

Empowerment can only be achieved effectively if the structural disadvantage forms are eliminated and challenged. In this context, a wider program of social change can

be a solution to overcome those barriers. Therefore, political education and working with elite groups for empowerment is not enough, as it needs real changes in power relationships and addressing the structural issues such as class, gender, race, and ethnicity.

3.5.3.4. Poststructural perspective

According to Foucault (1980), power is used to control and define knowledge. As a result, knowledge exists as 'regime of truth' and operated by regime of power. Thus, they believe that the power of truth needs to be detached from the forms of hegemony, social, economic, and cultural. To do this, he suggests tracing how ideas, languages, and the definition of language has been constructed and used as vehicle of control mechanism (Rouse, 1994).

Based on the poststructural perspective, empowerment becomes a process, which is challenging and changing discourses. Ife and Tesoriero (2006) state that empowerment requires subjective understanding and how people construct their world views, before deconstructing these understandings and building a new vocabulary of empowerment. Thus, he believes that the voices that dominate discourses need to be validated and provide room for alternative voices to be heard. Put simply, education and participation on discourses of power is the central tenet of this view.

3.5.3.5. Analysing power

The concept of power and how to analyse it invites debate in social science since the 1960s. It became complicated when the idea of empowerment was introduced. Based on different views about what is power is and how it works, Nelson and Wright (2001), classified power into three models. Those are 'power to', 'power over' and 'decentred' models of power. The first model has been described as 'power to' referring to the metaphor of human development. Using this metaphor, power is like human abilities, which can grow if people work at it and this growth does not negatively affect others. However, the danger with this model is that the meaning of power as a personal attitude can be misleading. This model suggests the powerless

develop their confidence and change their behaviours and attitudes. Based on this model, empowerment can be reached through three steps: (1) developing confidence and abilities in personal level; (2) developing skills to negotiate and influence close relationships; and (3) work collectively to have greater impact. The second model is often called 'power over' is based on an understanding that control of resources has been institutionalized. Therefore, gaining access to political decision making is essential. This model advises the marginalised group to gain treatment as an equal partner in such institutions, to have long-term access to resources and decision making. The last model also known as 'decentred' model rejects the previous models. This model asserts that power is not possessed and exercised by persons or institution, but it is subjectless and it is basically related to discourse matters.

In relation to understanding how power works, Ife (2013) presents three forms of power that involves 'power over', 'power to', and 'power with'. The idea of 'power over' is a form of power that connects to hierarchy and domination. This power is used to describe power over resources and power that dominates other groups.

The example of 'power over' can be found in the bureaucracy in Indonesia that is strongly coloured by the Javanese culture. Javanese paternalism views the relationship between patron and client as father and son. The father provides all that is needed by the son to legitimate his authority, whilst the son complies with the order of his father. This mechanism becomes a principle that legitimates the existence of the patron society (Dwiyanto & Kusumasari, 2001a; Mahar, 1998). In the context of public services, paternalism has potential to lead the lack of accountability (Dwiyanto & Kusumasari, 2001b). It can also create the elite capture phenomena that refers to people who influence policies for their own benefit (Setiadi, Sulistiyo, Satiti, & Yuliono, 2016).

While 'power to' refers to action and opening the possibilities, 'power with' asserts the importance of such actions in the collective and solidarity ways rather than acting alone. Observing these forms of power, it is clear that 'power to' and 'power with' fit with the spirit of community empowerment (Ife & Tesoriero, 2006).

The studies of power and how power works indicate the complexity of the concept and provide a framework for thinking about the context of the community empowerment model. When designing the model of community empowerment, the community worker can seek some value from each perspective. For example, the pluralist and elite views contribute to the debate on power and social action. Many strategies on empowerment are also derived from these perspectives. On the other hand, the structural and poststructural perspectives that are based on a thorough conceptual foundation, are of benefit for more radical and fundamental changes. It can help an empowerment model to be incorporated into a social justice and human right strategy. For challenging dominant structures of oppression and reconstructing of dominant discourse of power, these perspectives become important (Ife, 2013).

3.5.2. Community empowerment continuum

In general, empowerment can be classified into three categories: (1) psychological; (2) organisational; and (3) community empowerment. The first classification, psychological empowerment focuses on how individuals gain control over their own lives, whilst organisational empowerment concentrates on collective capacities, and community empowerment emphasises the social context where empowerment applied (Israel, Checkoway, Schulz, & Zimmerman, 1994; Wallerstein & Bernstein, 1994). This means empowerment occurs at different levels (Robinson & Elliott, 2000; Smith, Littlejohns, & Thompson, 2001). However, each level is closely connected to others. For example, community empowerment covers organizational empowerment, and organizational empowerment depends on empowering its members (Labonté, 1994; Wallerstein & Bernstein, 1994). Even though three levels of empowerment are interdependent, each empowerment level may have different aims (Laverack & Wallerstein, 2001; Robertson & Minkler, 1994). Consequently, these differences may obstruct in practice as the distinction between levels of empowerment is not clear.

In relation to individual empowerment, Wilson (1996) states that individual change is a prerequisite for social change. As a bridge for community connectedness and

social change, individual empowerment needs to enable people to solve their problems through partnership and collaboration with others. Thus, the synthesis between individual and social change is the core of the empowerment process (Florin & Wandersman, 1990; Speer & Hughey, 1995). In a different level, organizational empowerment aims to generate psychological empowerment among the members and to enhance the effectiveness of organisations to achieve their goals (Zimmerman, 1995; Zimmerman, 1999). The goal achievement, therefore, can be seen through its resources and management (Perkins & Zimmerman, 1995). At the community level, Laverack and Wallerstein (2001) describe nine aspects that influence community empowerment: (1) participation; (2) leadership; (3) problem assessment; (4) organisational structures; (5) mobilisation of resources; (6) networking; (7) critical assessment; (8) program management; and (9) role of outside agents. Other scholars, Bush, Dover, and Mutch (2002) simplify these domains of empowerment into four components such as activation of the community, competence of the community in solving its own problems, program management skills, and ability to mobilising resources (political, social, intellectual, and financial). These elements of community empowerment need to be considered and directed to achieve the goals. The goals of empowerment may include decreasing community threats, improving quality of life and increasing citizen participation - it is important to consider these indicators (trust, reciprocity, mutuality, and cooperation) as outcomes of community empowerment.

Community empowerment is both a goal and a process for overcoming social exclusion and cultural disrespect (Powell, 2001). Community empowerment has been mostly viewed consistently as a process (Swift & Levin, 1987; Wallerstein & Bernstein, 1988). According to Tremblay and Gutberlet (2010), empowerment is *'an intervening process where the individuals involved are the agents of change, rather than merely the recipients'*. Community empowerment as a process can be defined as increasing the ability of individuals, groups, organisations or communities through: (1) analysing their environment, (2) identifying problems, needs, issues and opportunities, (3) formulating strategies to deal with these problems, issues and needs, and seizing the relevant opportunities, (4) designing a plan of action, and (5) assembling and using effectively and on a sustainable basis resources to implement, monitor and evaluate

the plan of actions, and (6) using feedback to learn lessons (UNDP, 1995). Some scholars describe empowerment as a process of maximising the progress of people from individual to collective action based on the form of a dynamic continuum, involving: (1) personal empowerment; (2) development of small mutual groups; (3) community organization; (4) partnership; and (5) social and political actions (Jackson, Mitchell, & Wright, 1989; Labonte, 1989; Rissel, 1994).

Figure 3.2
Community Empowerment Continuum

Source: Labonte (1989), Jackson et al. (1989), and Rissel (1994).

Figure 3.2 shows the community empowerment continuum based on the works of Labonte (1989), Jackson et al. (1989), and Rissel (1994). The process of community empowerment can be considered as a continuum because it reflects larger forms of social organization and collective action. It is dynamic because when one step is achieved, the empowerment can move to the next point. Each points of this continuum can be viewed also as an outcome (Laverack, 1999).

3.5.3. Capacity building and participation

Since the mid-1990s, the discussion about community empowerment has been overshadowed by community capacity building. The concept of community capacity building is not new, but it is the modification of the ideas of community empowerment. Both concepts refer to the capability of problem solving individuals, organisations, and communities (Hawe, 1994; Laverack & Wallerstein, 2001; Yadama & Dauti, 2010). However, Laverack (2005) argues that the difference of these terms lies in the agenda and purpose of the process:

The difference between capacity building and empowerment approaches lies in the agenda and purpose of the process. Empowerment approaches have an explicit purpose to bring about social and political changes and this is embodied in their sense of action and emancipation, whereas capacity building has the purpose of the development of skills and abilities that enable others to take decisions and actions for themselves, but does not explicitly include political activism (Laverack, 2005, pp. 267-268).

There are many interpretations and thoughts about capacity building. For example, capacity building can be defined as a process to meet certain purposes and objectives through increasing the ability of individuals, organisation, or system (Brown, LaFonf, & Mavintyre, 2001; Labonté & Laverack, 2001). It can also be viewed as a process of seeking to strengthening capabilities to respond a changing environment (Morrisson, 2001). Capacity building is not about training and development of individuals, but it has a wider meaning and a wider policy agenda, such as supporting civic participation, local service delivery and modernising local government structures (Jupp, 2000). Above all, capacity building is important part of empowerment as organising and mobilising individuals, groups and communities will help to achieve social and political changes related to their powerlessness (Laverack & Wallerstein, 2001).

It is obvious that community empowerment requires participation of community members. According to Minkler and Wallerstein (2004), participation can be both an outcome of empowerment and a strategy for effective empowerment. Participation and empowerment are basically reciprocal. Through participation, people will learn new skills, gain confidence, and develop their own voices and ability to control their lives. In reverse, when they feel empowered, they are more likely to participate (Bureau of International Information Programs, 2012). World Health Organization (WHO) defines participation as:

A process by which people are enabled to become actively and genuinely involved in defining the issues of concern to them, in making decisions about factors that affect their lives, in formulating and implementing policies, in planning, developing and delivering services and in taking action to achieve change (WHO, 2002a).

To explain the relationship between empowerment and participation, Ledwith (1997, p. 1) states *'Empowerment involves a form of critical education that encourages people to question their reality: this is the basis of collective action and is built on principles of participatory democracy'*.

Along with the social model of disability, other interventional approaches such as social inclusion, community empowerment, capacity building and participation are relevant for people affected by leprosy as one of most disadvantaged and marginalised groups in society. However, the literature does not reveal their full application in the context of leprosy colonies or settlements.

3.6. Conclusion

This chapter reveals that paradigms to view disability have been changed from time to time. People tend to support social model of disability rather than moral and medical models, based on the assumption that disability is basically constructed by an oppressive and discriminatory society. Critical disability theory that emphasises the importance of social model and acknowledges the rights and voices of people with disabilities should be used as the spirit of disability services and policies. In the context of community-based rehabilitation for disabled people, community empowerment and social inclusion approaches are important to reduce social stigma and to increase control over their lives.

'There is no greater service than to help a community to liberate itself.'

(Nelson Mandela)

Chapter 4: Methodology

4.1. Introduction

This chapter discusses research methodology to explore the lived experience of people affected by leprosy, culture, and social structures in the Sitanala leprosy colony and the effectiveness of community empowerment and social inclusion programs. It presents the epistemology of the research and justifies that critical ethnography is an appropriate method to use. Furthermore, this chapter will explain in detail about research process, data collection and analysis, ethical considerations, and research rigour. The challenges of doing field research are also described.

4.2. Epistemology

Understanding and identifying philosophical worldviews is a crucial aspect in social research as it will affect design and research methods (Creswell, 2014). Epistemology can be defined as *'the study of the nature of knowledge and justification'* (Schwandt, 2007, p. 71). It also means *'theory of knowledge concerned with understanding how knowledge is defined, valued, and prioritised'* (Walter, 2006, p. 12). Whilst ontology embodies understanding of the nature of reality, epistemology tries to understand nature of the relationship between researchers and research including the outcome (Creswell, 2014; Darlaston-Jones, 2007; Gray, 2009; Lincoln & Guba, 2011). Epistemology provides the philosophical background to decide legitimate and adequate knowledge. It is related to the science of how knowledge is generated. It helps researchers to move from the abstract world of ideas to the observable world. In this context, there is an effort of how abstract concepts can be observed and measured (Carter & Little, 2007; Dudley, 2010).

This research is about the lived experiences of persons affected by leprosy in a leprosy colony and their perception of the impact of community empowerment and social inclusion program. From an epistemological view, the research can be categorised as constructivism or social constructivism associated with qualitative research. According to Crotty (1998), social constructivism assumes that the world is rich with meanings and therefore it is waiting to be discovered and interpreted by the researcher through language and culture. In relation to this, Creswell (2014) states that social constructivism believes individuals seek understanding of the world in which they live and work. Thus, based on their experiences, they develop subjective understanding of meanings toward objects or things. Due to different experiences, the meanings are varied and multiple. The researcher needs to focus on the complexity of views of participants rather than narrowing the meanings. It means the participants' views on the situation being studied become the essence of the research. Therefore, the questions asked of the participants are broad and general so that the participants can construct the meanings of each situation. The questions should be open ended as the researcher will listen to what they say and what they do in their daily life.

Social constructivism holds that subjective meanings are not only formed by interactions with others, but also through historical and cultural norms embedded in society. This explains that subjective meanings are often socially and historically negotiated. Regarding this, the researcher should address the interaction among individuals and understand the cultural and historical setting in which individuals live and work. The researcher also needs to acknowledge that the interpretation of these phenomena flows from and is influenced by their personal, cultural, and historical experiences. The efforts to interpret meaning will inductively generate a theory or meaning patterns (Creswell, 2014; Crotty, 1998).

In qualitative research, it is common that social constructivism is often combined with interpretivism (Creswell, 2014). Interpretivism refers to the idea that human interpretation is critically important to understand history and society (Hughes & Sharrock, 1997). The combination of interpretivism and social constructivism are

employed to guide this research. Research approaches such as ethnography are often used, where the researchers immerse themselves into the everyday life of group or community to understand the culture from the inside (Creswell, 2014; Crotty, 1998; Gray, 2009). Due to the nature of the leprosy colony that is associated with poverty, inequality, oppression and discrimination, the researcher decided to use critical ethnographic approach for the field research.

4.3. Design

In this research, the researcher used a qualitative method and critical ethnography. Qualitative method can be defined as a method, which analyses social and cultural phenomena, using the cultures that exist in the community itself to know the descriptions of prevailing patterns (Guest, Namey, & Mitchell, 2013). These patterns then will be analysed by objective theories (Babbie, 2013). Qualitative research is appropriate to observe aspects of livelihood in the community with their social and cultural characteristics (Rubin & Rubin, 2011).

Qualitative designs are naturalistic in that the researcher does not attempt to manipulate the research setting. Moreover, qualitative methods are particularly oriented toward exploration, discovery, and inductive logic (Patton, 1990). According to Pawar (2004, p. 9), *'if the existing knowledge is very little or nil and the gaps in the knowledge are very high, researchers begin exploring the problem by using observation and case study methods'*. Qualitative research draws on a variety of theoretical perspectives and practical techniques, including theories such as phenomenology, symbolic interactionism, cultural studies, psychology, and feminism, and techniques such as interviewing, narrative analysis, ethnography, and focus groups. Therefore, although qualitative data is collected from different social science disciplines, it essentially aims to capture the actual experiences of the social world and the meanings people give these experiences from their own perspectives (Liamputtong & Ezzy, 2005).

Qualitative research also involves the studied use and collection of a variety of empirical strategies, such as case study, personal experience, introspection, life

stories, interviews, observations, historical, interaction, and visual text, that describe routine and problematic moments and meanings in individuals' lives (Denzin & Lincoln, 1998). According to Liamputtong and Ezzy (2005), the best qualitative research depends on the creativity and insight of the researchers themselves. The researcher must find the best way of studying how meanings and interpretations are constructed in their particular substantive research area.

In this research, the researcher investigates the social and cultural structures including power relationships and social inequalities in the Sitanala leprosy village, covering not only social phenomena but an enriched understanding of the community. The researcher intended go to the field and get involved with the community as a participant observer, using self-knowledge and subjective experiences which are gained from social interaction through using 'the take a role' process as the main tool used in understanding what the member of a community does from their own perspectives. This means the researcher becomes involved in the community. By this method, the researcher hears, sees, and understands social phenomena as understood by the persons affected by leprosy themselves.

Bloor and Wood (2006) define ethnography as the description and interpretation of a culture or social group. Its purpose is to provide an in-depth study of a culture that includes behaviour, interactions, and language. The aim is to understand another way of life from their point of view by focusing on ordinary everyday behaviour. Denzin and Lincoln (1998) say that ethnography has a strong emphasis on exploring the nature of social phenomena and it refers to the investigation of a small number of cases, perhaps just one case in detail. Similarly, Liamputtong and Ezzy (2005) believe that the essential core of ethnography is to understand another way of life from the locals' point of view.

Ethnographic research emphasises the need to think oneself into the perspective of the members of the social group that one is studying. This involves an empathetic process that Weber termed *verstehen*. Ethnography has a commitment to naturalistic enquiry. This means that people are studied in everyday settings interacting, as they

would normally and naturally do. The ethnographic tradition recognises the relativistic status of knowledge in which there is no objective reality but rather a number of realities (Bloor & Wood, 2006).

This research is carried out by using 'critical ethnography', which emphasises processes of unfairness or injustice within a particular lived domain as ethical responsibility (Madison, 2011). This model is useful in the research because it represents and analyses social life for the political purpose of overcoming social oppression. Madison (2011) notes that critical ethnography stands against suffering and injustice. However, critical ethnography is not the opposition to interpretive or conventional ethnography, rather offers a more critical reflective style of thinking about the relationship between knowledge, society, and freedom from unnecessary forms of social domination. Critical ethnography shares the methods of traditional ethnography, such as by seeking the emic perspective gained through intense fieldwork. However, critical ethnography also adds an explicit political focus. It is methodology which tries to unmask hegemony and address oppressive and discriminatory forces (Crotty, 1998; Given, 2008; Thomas, 2004).

This methodological framework is appropriate for the research as it attempts to shift from the descriptive or storytelling to engage in a synthesis of description and theory. In other words, critical ethnography method will help to place persons affected by leprosy's experiences within larger structural systems. Furthermore, by using this method, it will assist individuals, groups, and communities that are researched in addressing their own situations or lobbying to change oppressive social structures. Finally, yet importantly, using this method helps practice-focused disciplines, such as social work, to instigate action around research findings due to lack of action resulting from such studies.

[4.4. Research setting and access](#)

This research is carried out at the Sitanala leprosy village, Indonesia. The reason for choosing this location from about 65 leprosy colonies in Indonesia is that the location is close to the power, facilities, and services, yet neglected; the researcher is familiar

with the area, similar study has not been conducted before and due to logistical reasons. Sitanala has about 847 persons affected by leprosy. This research is focused on a sub village in Sitanala called Rukun Tetangga (RT) 1. In this location, there are about 332 persons affected by leprosy who live with their families. Another reason to choose this location is that people who live there are the poorest group compared to other locations.

This research received approval from the Charles Sturt University Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC), with the protocol number: 2013/171. Research approval was also received from the head of Sitanala village before coming to Australia. To conduct a critical ethnographic study, the researcher needed to join the community and experience as closely as possible community life. The researcher began with some advantages: drawing on the researcher's experiences of living in poverty in Indonesia himself, speaking the four main languages spoken in Sitanala, being familiar with the customs of the areas from which the residents came, having relatives who had leprosy, and the researcher's experiences as a community development worker in several poor urban communities in Jakarta. All these helped the researcher to develop good relationships with this community. In addition, the researcher organised to live for seven months across the road from the community, spending most of his time in the community itself, joining in daily life including celebrations and more structured activities.

Interestingly, when the researcher got back to Sitanala, they still remembered the researcher. This is because the researcher gave 20 cents to a little kid who cried during the researcher's visit at Sitanala in 2012, although the researcher already had forgotten it. They said that, it was also rarely people came in the afternoon and dare to shake hands, kiss their hands and drink a glass of coffee they provided, even though it is common in villages in Indonesia. This is because having been visited by people from outside Sitanala made them happy. This means there is still people who are not afraid of them and are concerned about persons with leprosy. During the data collection, there are some protocols/ethical approaches followed by the researcher: (1) always being genuine and explicit about being a researcher - always get

permission whether verbally or in writing before recording anything; (2) written permission for interviews and focus groups; and (3) verbal permission for informal conversations.

The first task to collect data was to find accommodation in Sitanala. It was difficult to find accommodation as they are very short of space and face problems also in term of having an appropriate house. Houses are very crowded with whole families living in a single room for all their family tasks – cooking, sleeping etc. The researcher at last obtained a room to rent in front of Sitanala hospital. It needed two hours conversation before the owner said yes, as he initially said there was no room, perhaps because he wanted to assess whether the researcher was trustworthy and able to pay rent. Finally, after several conversations, the owner said he did have one room available. This is because the researcher had spoken in courteous ways and directly asked for help as the researcher really needed a room to stay during the research. After settling into the accommodation, the head of village and his wife introduced the researcher to people around their house. It was good having support from them as it would prevent the researcher from suspicious views from the community members.

4.5. Data collection

In data collection, the researcher used participant observation, focus group discussion (FGD) and in-depth interviews. The approach to this community was as friendly a manner as possible by going to the head of the village, his staff, and members of the community. The researcher used an informal approach especially while showing interest to gain a good relationship. This approach was meant to avoid rejection from this community. The researcher kept a low profile when entering this community as Lingam (2004) suggested that in a fieldwork research the researcher as a stranger should lower their profile to prevent bias perception during the research.

4.5.1. Recruitment of participants

The sampling technique that was used in this research was purposive sampling. The researcher chose some participants and informants in Sitanala leprosy village who related to the research to interview and gain a better understanding of their culture. Bloor and Wood (2006, p. 154) argue that in qualitative research, *'theoretical sampling (often referred to as purposive sampling) involves the selection of cases on the basis of the researcher's own judgment about which will be the most useful'*. According to Liamputtong and Ezzy (2005, p. 46), *'purposive sampling aims to select information-rich cases for in-depth study to examine meanings, interpretations, process and theory'*.

For focus group discussions, the researcher used piggyback as a method to get participants. Piggyback means that participants suggest others who meet the characteristics for focus groups (Liamputtong & Ezzy, 2005). The number of participants was 36 people divided into five group sessions. This refers to Stewart, Shamdasani, and Rook (2007, p. 58), saying *'most focus groups are composed of 6 to 12 people. Fewer than 6 participants make for a rather dull discussion, and more than 12 participants are difficult for the moderator to manage.'*

For in-depth interviews, snowball or chain sampling was a method to get informants in this research. Snowball or chain sampling means an initial participant, or group of participants, is asked to suggest other people who might be willing to participate in the research. This method of sampling is useful when the people being studied are well networked and difficult to approach directly (Liamputtong & Ezzy, 2005). The number of informants for an in-depth interview was 12 people, including the elderly who knew the history of the leprosy colony.

4.5.2. Participant observation

Participant observation is a research technique used to observe the phenomena in which people perform their daily activities in the community and the linkage between these phenomena (Minichiello, Aroni, Timewell, & Alexander, 1990). According to Spradley (1980), in ethnography, observation is the key instrument in acquiring

ethnographic knowledge. Researchers may observe actions or interactions, behaviour and listen to conversations while simultaneously observing the context (particularly the time and location) in which these actions are undertaken. Related to participant observation Liamputtong and Ezzy (2005) mention that the researcher needs to spend time in the field, talking with people and participating in their lives. Hence, it provides a deep and rich understanding of people in a way that is impossible in other qualitative methods. However, because full participant observation with persons affected by leprosy was impossible for the researcher due to their physical condition, so the researcher used a semi participant observation, which was more suitable for the research. By using this, the researcher found it impossible to participate fully, but there were times when the researcher could participate. The result was written in memos and field notes. The researcher also developed and used the participant observation guide.

4.5.3. Focus group discussion

This research also used focus group discussions to get general ideas about people's living experiences in the leprosy colony and their perception about the community empowerment and social inclusion programs. This probe was used as a starting point to find further information, which needed to be explored more intentionally. Facilitated by a researcher, a series of five group discussions were held with differently composed groups of individuals and they were audio-recorded. The focus group discussion aimed to collect data (via the capture of intra-group interaction) on group beliefs and group norms in relation to a particular topic or set of issues (Bloor & Wood, 2006). The logic for conducting the research in a group rather than an individual setting is to allow observations of how and why individuals accept or reject others' ideas. Stewart et al. (2007, p. 41) emphasise the reason for using focus groups, saying 'Focus groups may be useful at virtually any point in a research program, but they are particularly useful for exploratory research when rather little is known about the phenomenon of interest'.

4.5.4. In-depth interview

In-depth interview was a technique used to get information from members of the community in Sitanala leprosy village to talk about specific matters whilst using different questioning techniques based on an interview guide, to get information, which was relevant to the research. Interviews were conducted several times to provide depth of research. According to Bogdan and Taylor (1998), the in-depth interview can be defined as repeated face-to-face encounters between the researcher and informants directed toward understanding informants' perspectives on their lives, experiences or situations as expressed in their own words. Liamputtong and Ezzy (2005) state that an in-depth interview aims to explore the complexity and in-process nature of meanings and interpretations. Thus, it is more like a conversation rather than structured questionnaires. This acts as an excellent way of discovering the subjective meanings and interpretations that people give to their experiences. The reason to use an in-depth interview as given by Liamputtong and Ezzy (2005):

People's responses are less influenced by the direct presence of their peers during in-depth interviews. Participants may be more prepared to discuss sensitive matters, such as sexual practice or strong emotional responses, which they would not otherwise talk about in front of other people, and which could not be examined using methodologies such as participant observation or focus groups (Liamputtong & Ezzy, 2005, pp. 71-72).

4.5.5. Secondary data

The researcher also collected secondary data relevant to the study. These mainly included policy documents and annual reports from the government and local government and other agencies. This was useful to have insight about the community empowerment and social inclusion programs and the policies related to leprosy.

4.6. Data Analysis

Data analysis in this research was conducted using a qualitative analysis technique. According to Alston and Bowles (2012, p. 74), *'A qualitative research study produces vast amounts of new data – often unstructured – which must be coded, categorised and analysed'*. In relation to this, coding was done manually by hand, using coloured

highlights to sort. Thus, the coloured texts were cut for categorising data purposes. This task is a time-consuming process. The aim of qualitative data analysis is to find meaning in the information collected. Qualitative data analysis is the process of systematically arranging and presenting information to search for themes and ideas. Qualitative data analysis can be broken down into a series of decisions. According to Richard and Richard, *'theories are not little lizards waiting under rocks to be uncovered; but webs of understanding constructed by the researcher and used actively to make sense of the data'* (cited from Alston & Bowles, 2012, p. 68).

Bogdan and Taylor (1975) identify three distinct stages. The first stage involves coding the data, discovering themes, and developing propositions. The second stage is refining one's themes and propositions. The third stage, centres on reporting the findings. To do this, the researcher first examined each data set (observations, focus group discussions, in-depth interview, field notes, local documents); checked the consistency and then followed the three stages stated above.

Regarding the qualitative data analysis above, in more specific, the researcher used thematic analysis. According to Hardwick and Worsley (2011), thematic analysis consists of five sequences as follows:

- Knowing

To know and become very familiar with the data, the first stage that needs to do is transcribing the data and read it more than once. These activities must be done thoroughly. It usually requires time and hard work due to a lot of materials.

- Coding

Coding in qualitative research refers to the process of categorising the data. This can be done if the researcher was familiar with the data and started to get the meaning of the data and inter-connected pieces of it. The researcher then makes memos of thoughts or important information related to annotation of data from different resources.

- Theming

The next step is generating themes from the data. Generation of broader themes includes drawing together of the codes/categories that have been made into groups or themes. These themes will be substantive structure for data analysis.

- Selecting

After theming the data, the researcher chooses pieces of data that best illustrate the themes. This could be some quotes from the participants. To do this the researcher need to choose it wisely and honestly.

- Committing

The last stage is writing the research report. The researcher then decides to let go some data that have no connection or irrelevant with the committed themes. This can be difficult thing as the qualitative research usually has a large amount of data. However, the researcher must do this, otherwise the process will be very long.

Figure 4.1
Five Sequences of Thematic Analysis

Source: Hardwick and Worsley (2011)

Beside thematic analysis, in data analysis, the researcher also used micro analysis. According to Wengraf (2006), micro analysis is a method of exploring the relation between lived life and told story in very close up and detailed study using very small segments of text which is puzzling and potentially revealing. Micro analysis requires verbatim transcripts of interviews. By using this method, researcher will benefit in developing hypothesis. Microanalysis also helps the researcher to analyse the dynamics of the interview.

4.7. Ethical considerations

This research follows the ethics as outlined in the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Research Involving Humans and the Charles Sturt University Code of Conduct for Research. This section will describe some of key ethical issues that related to the integrity of the researcher.

4.7.1. Benefits and risks of participation

The researcher is aware that the expected benefits from the research includes: (1) this research will help people to understand the uniqueness of the leper colony in the Sitanala leprosy village based on their perspective; (2) provide basic information about the leper colony so that other scholars who want to explore more about this community can use it; (3) the research will generate new knowledge and understanding of their living experiences and their perspectives on the community empowerment and social inclusion program in the Sitanala Leprosy Village; and (4) the findings will help create new discussions with social workers and other professionals, volunteers, government and non-governmental organisations regarding the design and implementation of a future community empowerment and social inclusion programs that better address their needs. However, it is possible that they will be sad when talking about their experiences. Regarding this, even though the researcher did not provide counselling because it is uncommon in that place (Indonesia), the researcher connected them to the head of village to solve this problem. Furthermore, the head of village did 'traditional counselling' based on their culture.

4.7.2. Participant's involvement and the consent form

The participants of this research have to meet the criteria: (1) voluntariness; (2) members of the Sitanala Leprosy Village; and (3) know the history of the community and CESI program in the Sitanala Leprosy Village. I had approached them in person after being introduced with consent from the head of village. This method is preferred, as many people in that community cannot read well. The process included:

- Observe and attend social activities.
- Talk to the head of village about individuals who are potential to become participants.
- Make a list of participant candidates.
- Filter them during the participant recruitment process. In this stage, the researcher defines and selects participants that meet the criteria above to get relevant data and avoid wasting time. The researcher excludes participant candidates who are under 18 years old, those who are still in medical treatment and pay attention to the equal number between men and women to participate in this research.
- Confirming their willingness to participate in the research through consent form.

However, the researcher will give the consent forms only to some of the participants who were able to read and write. Other participants will be confirmed through oral consent. This is because most poor people in Indonesia are afraid to sign any documents, as it will be associated with land eviction. This required some steps, involving: (1) potentially willing participants will first have the chance to observe recording demonstration (The head of village will relate a brief story while I will record). This is to ensure that they are in no doubt as to the process; (2) Having completed the demonstration, those who would like to contribute will be taken through the letter and information sheet (3) ample time will be given for participant questions and decision making; and (4) Finally, willing participants will be asked to.

4.7.3. Confidentiality and privacy

For protection of confidentiality and privacy of the participants, interviews were audiotape recorded or electronically captured. Following the interview, a transcript was provided to the respondent, if s/he wished to see one. The participants were free to withdraw at any time throughout the process. Due to voluntary participation, the participants could withdraw from the project at any time and there was no disadvantage if they decided not to participate or withdraw at any time.

4.7.4. Dissemination of research results

The research findings are presented in the thesis. They may also be presented at academic or professional conferences or published in academic or professional articles or book chapters. The confidentiality of the participants regarding personal information will be protected by anonymising all quotations. Copy of general research report will be provided in English to Head of village's library which the members of village can access, and translation in Bahasa Indonesia of the Executive/Summary but not to a specific participant.

4.8. Trustworthiness

Bloor and Wood (2006) argue that reliability is an impossible criterion to achieve in practice, as different researchers will always produce different versions of the social world. However, to improve reliability ethnographers can use strategies, which include maintaining meticulous records of fieldwork and documenting the process of analysis (in a research diary or in analytic memos) so that others can follow the process in the form of an audit trail. To increase the credibility of the study, the researcher compared observation, interview and focus group data analyses to find out similarities, differences, and inconsistencies.

4.9. Conclusion

This chapter has discussed research methodology to explore the lived experience of people affected by leprosy, culture, and social structures in the Sitanala leprosy colony and the effectiveness of community empowerment and social inclusion programs. It has presented the epistemology of the research, research process, data

collection and analysis, ethical considerations, and research rigour. The analysis of the data is presented in the following chapters.

'My disability exists not because I use a wheelchair, but because the broader environment isn't accessible.'

(Stella Young)

Chapter 5: Government Policies

5.1. Introduction

This chapter discusses the government policy relating to disability issues, especially the issue of leprosy in Indonesia. Studying the framework of policies is very important to measure whether the policies are pro-disabled or not. The first subchapter will analyse laws and regulations at national levels and the roles of Ministry of Social Affairs (MoSA) and Ministry of Health (MoH) to deal with these issues. The policies relating to disability are presented in two sections, before and after the ratification of the *Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities* (CRPD). The second subchapter will present local government policies, both in Jakarta and Tangerang and analyse them through a human rights perspective.

5.2. Laws and regulations

Laws and regulations relating to disabled people are a crucial issue in Indonesia. Many policies have been created with the wrong perspective about people with disabilities. Therefore, there is no legal certainty for disabled people, no protection of their rights, and the state has not provided an expectation of justice for persons with disabilities. Through study of the documentation, the Indonesian government has tried to shift the paradigm from charity-based to human rights-based. This section will describe the influence and contribution of *United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities* (UNCRPD) on the history of creating policies relating to disabled people.

5.2.1. Before UNCRPD

Issues of disability have received a lot of attention from the Indonesian government since its independence in 1945. The first regulations dealing specifically with disability was Government Regulation No. 36/1980 on *Social Welfare Efforts for Penderita Cacat* (Persons Suffering from Deficits) (Indonesian Government, 1980). At that time, it was common in Indonesia to use term 'penderita cacat' (persons suffering from deficits) to refer to disabled people. Based on *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia* (Indonesian Dictionary), *cacat* has several meanings: (1) A lack which causes the value or quality to be not good or less perfect; (2) Conditions (blisters, damage, stains) causing the situation are not very good (less perfect); (3) Despicable; Disgraceful; and (4) Not (less than) perfect (Setiawan, 2016). The article 1 of this regulation defines *penderita cacat* as '*a person, who according to medical knowledge, has been declared to have physical and/or mental abnormalities that become barriers and obstacles for them to do normal activities*'. This includes: (1) Persons suffering from physical disabilities; (2) Persons suffering from visual disabilities; (3) Persons suffering from mental disabilities; (4) Persons suffering from hearing and speech disabilities; and (5) Persons suffering from disabilities due to chronic diseases (Indonesian Government, 1980).

This regulation emphasises the importance of rehabilitation for *penderita cacat*, in order to restore and develop their physical, mental, and social capacity so that they can perform their function in the society, in accordance with their level of ability, talent, education and experience. In this regulation, social welfare efforts for *penderita cacat* should cover medical rehabilitation, social rehabilitation, social assistance, help to get jobs, and further assistance. The Minister of Social Affairs has the responsibility of implementing this regulation, except for medical rehabilitation, which is the responsibility of the Ministry of Health. This regulation became a reference for the Ministry of Social Affairs to build many social rehabilitation centres for disabled in Indonesia (Indonesian Coordinating Ministry for Human Development and Cultural Affairs, 2015).

In 1983, the Indonesian government issued Presidential Decree No. 39/1983 about *Coordination of Social Welfare Efforts for Penderita Cacat* (Persons Suffering from Deficits). This decree was basically a follow-up from Government Regulation No. 36/1980, so that the government still used the term *penderita cacat*, instead of disabled people. This decree appointed responsibility to the Minister of Social Affairs as coordinator of inter-sectoral agencies that provide social welfare efforts for disabled people. Based on this decree, the Ministry of Social Affairs has responsibility to allocate the budget for coordination (Indonesian Government, 1983).

In 1991, Indonesian government issued Government Regulation No. 72/1991 on *Pendidikan Luar Biasa (PLB)* (Specific Education). This regulation mentioned that the government provides *PLB* that refers to *'education that is specially organised for students who have physical and/or mental abnormalities.'* In this regulation, the government replaced the term 'cacat' with 'tuna' (Indonesian Government, 1991). It seems that the law makers who created this regulation have background as educators, so that they tried to avoid using the term *cacat*. However, the meaning of *tuna* basically remains same as *cacat*. This is because *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia* gives meanings *tuna* as: (1) Injury; damage; and (2) less; do not have. Based on this regulation, the government divided disabilities, as follows:

- *Tuna netra* (sight disabilities)
- *Tuna rungu* (hearing disabilities)
- *Tuna daksa* (physical disabilities)
- *Tuna grahita* (mental retardation)
- *Tuna laras* (mental illness) (Setiawan, 2016).

In 1997, disability was an important issue due to the increasing numbers of persons with disabilities in Indonesia. Regarding this, the Indonesian government felt that a government regulation was not enough to address disability issues. Therefore, the government issued Law No. 4/1997, *Penyandang Cacat* (People who have Disabilities). In this law, the government changed the term *penderita cacat* into 'penyandang cacat' (persons who have disabilities). Interestingly, even though there was a change in using term to call persons with disabilities, from *penderita cacat* to

penyandang cacat, the definition remained same. Based on this law, the article 1 defines *penyandang cacat* as ‘those who have physical and/or mental abnormalities, that can disturb or that can be barriers and obstacles to properly doing their activities’. The government categorised *penyandang cacat* into: (1) persons who have physical disabilities; (2) persons who have mental disabilities; and (3) Persons who have physical and mental disabilities (Indonesian Government, 1997a). Law No. 4/1997 acknowledged that *penyandang cacat* have a right to: education; jobs and appropriate living based on the types and degrees of their disabilities; same opportunity to participate in development and benefit from the fruits of development; accessibility for independence; rehabilitation, social aids, maintenance of adequate social welfare; and the same rights to develop their talents, abilities, and social life as able-bodied people (Indonesian Government, 1997a).

Law No. 4/1997 was then followed-up by Government Regulation No. 43/1998 *Efforts to Increase Social Welfare of Persons with Disabilities*; and Presidential Decree No. 83/1999 *Institution for Coordination and Control to Increase Social Welfare of Persons with Disabilities*. These regulations show persons with disabilities as a group, in which their social welfare needs to be improved through: equal opportunities; rehabilitation; social aids, and maintenance of adequate social welfare (Indonesian Government, 1998, 1999d). To ensure those efforts, the government created an institution for coordination and control. The Indonesian government has followed-up Law No. 4/1997 through *National Action Plan for Penyandang Cacat, 2004-2013*. However, due to unclear coordination between institutions and ineffective monitoring and evaluation, on 22 June 2015, the government issued Presidential Regulation No. 75/2015 *National Action Plan for Human Rights, 2015-2019*. Through this regulation, National Action Plan for Persons with Disabilities has been covered and integrated in the National Action Plan for Human Rights (Indonesian Government, 2015b).

Many laws and regulations relating to persons with disabilities were influenced by Law No. 4/1997. For example, in 2009, Indonesian government issued Law No. 11/2009 on *Social Welfare*. In this law, the government views persons with disability

as persons who faced social dysfunction and categorised them as a social problem (Indonesian Government, 2009). Many laws and regulations relating to disability in this stage were influenced by medical views of disability, which views persons with disabilities as abnormal humans. Laws and regulations tend to interfere with the physical conditions of persons with disabilities. Instead of changing the environment so that it will suit the needs of disabled people, it pushes people with disability to adjust themselves into a normal or mainstream situation. Thus, disability was considered as misfortune and human tragedy, so that many programs focused on physical improvements and financial assistances to overcome obstacles and alienation in general society (Irwanto, Kasim, Fransiska, Lusli, & Siradj, 2010; PSHK, 2014). This means the spirit of laws and regulation relating to people with disabilities was not to fulfil their rights and to remove barriers, but rather simplified social 'band aids' for persons with disabilities. As a result, many programs were created based on a charity approach.

5.2.2. After UNCRPD

After the release of the *United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD)* in 2006, the discourse about shifting of paradigms from a charity base to a human rights base in Indonesia became intensified. There was a high demand from activists of disability to revise Law No. 4/1997 due to the outdated approach. They believed that the terms of *cacat* and *tuna* were labelling persons with disability as powerless, suffering and the object of pity, basically the beginning of a discrimination process. It was also grouping people with disabilities together that contributed to marginalising them. This law viewed disabled people as the object of a policy; people that need to be helped through social and health programs (Irwanto et al., 2010). As a result, in 2011, the Indonesian government ratified the *Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities* through Law No. 19/2011 (Indonesian Government, 2011a).

However, in this law, the government still used the term *penyandang cacat* to refer to persons with disabilities. Finally, in 2016, the Indonesian government issued Law No. 8/2016 on *Penyandang Disabilitas (Persons with Disabilities)*. Consequently, the

terms of *cacat* and *tuna* are automatically replaced by *disabilitas* (Indonesian Government, 2016). Based on this law, persons with disabilities have been defined on Article 1, as *'those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others'*.

The Law No. 8/2016 mentions that there are five rights that need to be respected, protected, and fulfilled:

1. Civil and political rights, such as: rights to live; freedom from stigma; rights to justice and protection of law; privacy rights; political rights; religious rights; rights of expression; communication and information; citizenship rights; and freedom from discrimination, neglect, abuse, and exploitation.
2. Economic, social, and cultural rights, such as: rights to education; employment rights; rights to health; culture and tourism rights; welfare rights; rights to public services; and rights to live independently and be involved in the community.
3. Other special rights, such as: rights of entrepreneurship and the formation of cooperatives; rights for accessibility; rights to get protection from disaster; rights for rehabilitation; rights of data collection; and rights for sport.
4. Women with disabilities rights, such as: health reproduction rights; rights to accept or reject contraceptives; rights to get more protection from discriminations; and rights to get more protection from violence, including sexual violence and exploitation.
5. Children with disabilities rights, such as: right to receive special protection from discrimination, neglect, abuse, exploitation and violence and sexual crimes; rights to receive family care or foster parents to grow and develop optimally; rights for protection of decision-making; rights to be treated humanely in accordance with their dignity and rights; rights to meet their special needs; rights to be treated as same as other children to achieve social integration and individual development; and rights to get social assistance (Indonesian Government, 2016).

Disability is a multisector issue and not only a social sector issue. It relates to other sectors, such as education, health, infrastructure, transportation, and

communication. Now, disability issues are under the Ministry of Social Affairs. There was a tendency in Indonesia that all social problems are the tasks of Ministry of Social Affairs. This paradigm should be changed, from sectoral to multisector approaches. Therefore, disability issues need to be attached in various sectors as a strategical way to mainstreaming disability issues in various sectors of development. Through Law No. 8/2016, all policies should be harmonised, so that clashes among policies can be avoided for the best interest of people with disabilities. It means the policies that are based on a charity perspective should be shifted to a human rights perspective. This is important to ensure that Indonesian policies will always respect, protect, and fulfil the rights of disabled people. As a result, all programs need to change their paradigms from rehabilitation-based to rights-based.

5.3. Central government policy

Understanding government policy at a national level is very important. This is because the laws and regulations that are issued will become the reference for local government to formulate policies in their regions. This subchapter will describe the long process taken by the Indonesian government to create policies for persons with disabilities based on a spirit of respect, protection, and fulfilment of their rights. Furthermore, it will suggest as a matter of urgency harmonising the policies in the best interest of persons with disabilities.

5.3.1. Ministry of Social Affairs

In carrying out their duties, the Ministry of Social Affairs use Law No. 11/2009 on *Social Welfare*, as their legal basis (Indonesian Government, 2009). Based on the Minister of Social Affairs Regulation No. 86/2010 on *Organisation and Working System of Ministry of Social Affairs*, disability issues are under the responsibility of *Direktorat Rehabilitasi Sosial Orang Dengan Kecacatan* (Directorate of Social Rehabilitation for Disabled People) (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2010b). The nomenclature of this directorate still uses term 'cacat'. This regulation also states that the position of *Direktorat Rehabilitasi Sosial Orang Dengan Kecacatan* is under Directorate General of Social Rehabilitation. Article 143 mentioned that this directorate has the following tasks: (1) Formulate and implement policies; (2) Prepare

norms, standards, procedures, and criteria; and (3) Provide technical assistances and evaluation related to social rehabilitation for people with disabilities (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2010b).

Directorate ODK has four Sub-Directorates and one Sub-Division to help them to achieve their tasks, as follows:

1. Sub-Directorate of Social Rehabilitation for People with Physical Disabilities and Former Chronic Diseases Sufferers;
2. Sub-Directorate of Social Rehabilitation for People with Sight, Hearing and Speech Disabilities;
3. Sub-Directorate of Institutional and Social Advocacy;
4. Sub-Directorate of Assistance and Social Welfare Maintenance; and
5. Sub-Division of Administration (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2010b).

Referring to article 148, Sub-Directorate of Social Rehabilitation for People with Physical Disabilities and Former Chronic Diseases Sufferers has two sections: (1) Social Rehabilitation based on Institutions; and (2) Social Rehabilitation based on Non-Institutions. Based on this article, persons affected by leprosy are under Sub-Directorate of Social Rehabilitation for People with Physical Disabilities and Former Chronic Diseases Sufferers (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2010b).

Finally, based on the Minister of Social Affairs Regulation No. 20/2015 on *Organisation and Working System of Ministry of Social Affairs*, the Indonesian government changed the nomenclature of *Direktorat Rehabilitasi Sosial Orang Dengan Kekacatan* to *Direktorat Rehabilitasi Sosial Penyandang Disabilitas* (Directorate of Social Rehabilitation for Persons with Disabilities) (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2015c).

In 1999, the Indonesian government issued Law No. 22/1999 on *Local Government* starting the regional autonomy era (Indonesian Government, 1999b). This law had been replaced by Law No. 32/2004 on *Local Government* (Indonesian government, 2004). Recently, the government also replaced it and issued Law No. 23/2014 on

Local Government. This law was a reference for local governments to get more autonomy in their regions (Indonesian government, 2014). In the past, the Ministry of Social Affairs had their office branches at provincial and district/municipal levels. After, issuing Local Government Law, these branches were owned by local governments. The tasks of Ministry of Social Affairs were lessened and most of the tasks were taken over by local governments, through their social offices (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2015b, 2015c).

The aim of these laws is basically to give more authority to local governments in formulating policies and programs on the provincial and district/municipal levels based on the assumption that they have more understanding about the issues, potentials, and resources in their regions (Indonesian government, 2014). However, in many cases, local governments did not allocated budget for social issues. They often relied on funds from the Ministry of Social Affairs. Furthermore, local governments also often changed or revised the priority programs of Ministry of Social Affairs without any notice to the Ministry. The reason often given is that local government law mentions that they must report to their governors, regents or mayors and not to the Minister. This reality often becomes a barrier and also a challenge for the Ministry of Social Affairs and other ministries (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2016a, 2016b). Based on Local Government Law, the Ministry of Social Affairs could not provide direct services to any regions without request by local governments. In other words, the Ministry of Social Affairs now shift their focus on indirect services dealing with social issues (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2015b).

In 2015, The Indonesian government allocated a state budget amount of \$204 billion. From this budget, Social Ministry Affairs received \$1.4 billion. Ministry of Social Affairs then allocated it an amount of \$35 million for *Direktorat Rehabilitasi Sosial Orang Dengan Kecacatan (ODK)* (Indonesian Ministry of Finance, 2015; Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2016a, 2016b). In other words, the allocation of budget for disability issues was very low as only 2.5% from total budget of this Ministry of Social Affairs or 0.02% from the total budget of the state. Compared to 2012 *Direktorat*

Rehabilitasi Sosial Orang Dengan Kecacatan (ODK) received only \$12 million from the total budget of Ministry of Social Affairs (\$0.46 billion). At that time, the total state budget was only \$142 billion (Indonesian Ministry of Finance, 2012, 2014; Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2013a, 2013b). It means that in 2012, the percentage of the budget for disability issues in the Ministry of Social Affairs was also low, with only 2.6% from the budget of Social Ministry and 0.01% from total budget of the state. Based on this data, the concern of the Indonesian government for social issues, especially disability was very low as reflected by the budgeting policy, both in 2012 and 2015.

5.3.2. Ministry of Health

In carrying out their duties, the Ministry of Health uses Law No. 36/2009 on *Health*, as their legal basis. Based on Article 325, the Minister of Health Regulation No. 64/2015 on *Organisation and Working System of Ministry of Health*, leprosy issues are under Sub-Directorate of Direct Contagious Tropical Diseases, especially the Leprosy Section (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2015a). This sub-directorate is under Directorate of Prevention and Control for Direct Contagious Diseases and Directorate General of Prevention and Control for Diseases. According to Article 326 of this regulation, the Leprosy Section has the following tasks:

1. Preparing materials for the formulation of policies and its implementation;
2. Formulating norms, standards, procedures, and criteria;
3. Providing technical assistance and supervision; and
4. Monitoring, evaluating and reporting on the prevention and control of leprosy (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2015a).

In relation to providing medical services for persons affected by leprosy, the Ministry of Health built leprosy hospitals in three locations, Sitanala Tangerang, Makassar and Palembang. Based on Ministry of Health Decree No. 398/MenKes/SK/IV/1994 on *Organisation and Working System for Sitanala Leprosy Hospital, Tangerang*; this hospital has the following tasks: (1) providing holistic, integrated, and sustainable services for leprosy patients; and (2) conducting education, training, research and

development on leprosy based on laws and regulations (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 1994).

In 1997, Sitanala leprosy hospital started to provide services not only for leprosy patients but also for general patients. This is based on the Permit Letter of the Director General of Medical Services No. IR.01.3.2.613 on 17 February 1997 concerning *Permit Principles for Providing Public Services*, to improve the medical care coverage area of Tangerang City and surrounding areas (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 1997). This explains why around 1997, the relationship between hospital and people in Sitanala began to deteriorate (discussed in chapter 7).

In 2005, the Indonesian government issued Government Regulation No. 23/2005 on *Financial Management Pattern for Badan Layanan Umum (BLU)* (Public Service Agency). Based on this regulation, all hospitals will get the status *BLU*. It means the hospital must gain profits for their services and not rely on the budget from government (Indonesian Government, 2005a). The implication of this policy is that Sitanala hospital must start to fund their operational costs and this can be achieved if the number of general patients who come to Sitanala increase as many leprosy patients are very poor and cannot contribute to health care costs. The consequence of *BLU* is that the staff will benefit financially. That is why in 2008, the general director of Sitanala hospital proposed a competition to change the logo of the hospital. The current logo is slanted towards leprosy and he said that this logo was out of date. There was also a demand to change the name from Sitanala leprosy hospital to just Sitanala hospital (Amru & Triyono, 2003; Sitanala Leprosy Hospital, 2009; Sulaiman, 2015).

However, based on Ministry of Health issued Regulation No. 011/2012 *Organisation and Working System for Sitanala Leprosy Hospital, Tangerang*, the name of Sitanala leprosy hospital remains the same. Sitanala leprosy hospital still has the job of organising efforts in terms of healing, recovery, and rehabilitation for leprosy patients in a harmonious, integrated way, along with other health promotion efforts and implement referral efforts. Based on this regulation, even though Sitanala leprosy

hospital is close to the Sub-Directorate of Direct Contagious Tropical Diseases, this hospital is still under Directorate General of Medical Services (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2012b).

In 2004, the Indonesian government issued Law No. 40/2000 on *National Social Security System*, to guarantee the fulfillment of basic needs and decent lives for participants and/or family members (Indonesian Government, 2000b). This policy was followed-up through Law No. 24/2011 on *Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial (BPJS)* (Social Security Administering Agency). This law clearly states that there are two *BPJS*; first is *BPJS* for health and second is *BPJS* for workforce (Indonesian Government, 2011b). This law was followed-up through Presidential Regulation No. 12/2013 on *Health Security*. In this regulation, the participants of *BPJS* are divided into two categories:

1. Beneficiaries of social security, who are poor.
2. Participants of social security who can pay for their membership.

Consequently, old social security programs for poor families such as *Jamkesmas* (Medical Social Security), is included into beneficiaries of social security (Indonesian Government, 2013).

Based on *BPJS* laws and regulations, patients receive the first level of health services in community health centres. Furthermore, the patients could receive advanced levels of health services to hospitals after getting referral letters from community health centres. These referral letters are valid for 1 month, but for chronic cases such as mental illness, leprosy, and chronic lung conditions, the referral letter is valid for 3 months. However, according to Minister of Health Regulation No. 40/2012 on *Guidance for Implementation of Medical Social Security*, leprosy hospitals should report medical costs into three phases:

- Phase 1, Day 1 – Day 35 : Tariff INA-CBGs
- Phase 2, Day 36 – Day 103 : \$5
- Phase 3, Day 104 – Day 180 : \$2.5 (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2012a).

INA-CBG is an abbreviation of *Indonesia Case Base Groups*, an application that is used by hospitals to make a claim on the government. INA-CBG is a payment system with a "package", based on the patient's illness. The meaning of *Case Base Groups (CBG)* is a method of payments, based on the diagnoses of patients or cases that are relatively similar. This tariff will not disadvantage hospitals because the payment covers all cost in one package until the patient is cured (Info BPJS Kesehatan, 2014). It is rumoured that this tariff benefits hospitals as the benefit is above the standard cost. This explains why leprosy patients in Sitanala are often sent to their homes before day 35 (as discussed in chapter 7), even though their referral letters are valid for 3 months.

5.4. Local Government Policy

Local regulation plays an important role in supporting development at local levels. This not only applies to physical development, but also social development. This section will discuss local policies relating to persons affected by leprosy in Jakarta as the closest neighbour and Tangerang where the *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* is situated. Studying these policies will help to understand the mindset of policy makers and its impact on persons affected by leprosy who live in their areas.

5.4.1. Jakarta Province

Geographically, the city of Tangerang borders the Jakarta Province, especially West Jakarta. The policy of the Jakarta Province will affect the persons affected by leprosy as there is a high degree of mobility by people who live in those areas. Many Jakarta residents work in Tangerang and vice versa. Administratively Tangerang city is under the Banten Province, but based on police law, it is under the territory of *Polda Metro Jaya* (Great Jakarta Police), as Tangerang is considered a satellite city of Jakarta, the capital of Indonesia.

The policy of the Jakarta government that directly relates to persons affected by leprosy is Local Regulation No. 8 of 2007 on Public Order. This regulation issued an order to create Jakarta as an orderly city, peaceful, comfortable, clean, and beautiful. This regulation also aims to protect citizens and infrastructures of the city (Jakarta

Local Government, 2007). The government considered the old regulation, Local Regulation No. 11/1988 on Public Order, was no longer appropriate to the soul and spirit of the government and the changes and developments of the values of Jakarta society (Jakarta Local Government, 1988). However, Article 41 Local Regulation No. 8/2007 clearly mentioned that persons with leprosy are prohibited in public places: *'Everyone who has diseases that disturb the public, are prohibited from being on the streets, green belts, parks, and other public places'* (Jakarta Local Government, 2007).

The disturbing diseases article 41 refers to are leprosy and mental illness. Based on this explanation, this regulation is very discriminatory, especially for persons affected by leprosy. Compared to the old regulation, article 23 Local Regulation No. 11/1988 also mentions the same statement and almost without any changes: *'Everyone who suffers from diseases that disrupt a public view and disturb the public, are prohibited from being on the streets, green belt, parks, and other public places'* (Jakarta Local Government, 1988).

From these articles, it can be concluded that local regulations in Jakarta restrict freedom of movement of persons affected by leprosy. Therefore, these regulations automatically violate citizenship rights of people with leprosy: the freedom of movement. This right is based on article 27 Indonesian Law No. 39/1999 on Human Rights: *'Every Indonesian citizen has the right to move freely, freedom to move and reside within the territory of the Republic of Indonesia'* (Indonesian Government, 1999c).

This article is consistent with article 12 verse 1 of *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)* that has been ratified by Indonesian government through Indonesian Law No. 12/2005 which states: *'Everyone lawfully within the territory of a State, shall, within that territory, have the right to liberty of movement and freedom to choose his residence'* (Indonesian Government, 2005c).

It is true that Article 28J, Indonesian Basic Law 1945 states that every citizen shall be subject to the laws that guarantee the recognition and respect for the rights and

freedom of others. Based on this article, most local regulations on public order are issued:

In carrying out the rights and freedoms, everyone shall be subject to the restrictions established by law with the sole purpose of securing due recognition and respect for the freedom of others and to meet the fair demands in accordance with considerations of morality, religious values, security and public order in a democratic society (Indonesian Government, 2000a).

In the Local Regulation No. 8 of 2007, the Jakarta government defines public order as they please. The law makers who created this regulation ignored article 5 of *International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)* that has been ratified by Indonesian government through Indonesian Law No. 11/2005:

Article 5

1. Nothing in the present Covenant may be interpreted as implying for any State, group or person any right to engage in any activity or to perform any act aimed at the destruction of any of the rights or freedoms recognized herein, or at their limitation to a greater extent than is provided for in the present Covenant.
2. No restriction upon or derogation from any of the fundamental human rights recognized or existing in any country in virtue of law, conventions, regulations, or custom shall be admitted on the pretext that the present Covenant does not recognize such rights or that it recognizes them to a lesser extent (Indonesian Government, 2005b).

It is important to understand that the implementation of this regulation has the potential to negate Indonesian citizen's rights, but also becomes a barrier for the Indonesian government to realise their duty as a state which has already ratified ICESCR and ICCPR. In the context of this study, this regulation could threaten the rights of persons affected by leprosy. It seems that this regulation is a systemic instrument that is used by Jakarta Province to drive away people with leprosy and other vulnerable groups under the pretext of public order.

Regarding this case, all laws and regulations in Indonesia should refer to Law No.39/1999 on Human Rights, Law No. 11/2005 on Ratification of *International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights*, and Law No. 12/2005 on Ratification of *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*. If the government ignores this, it will create a disparity between the laws and regulation in Indonesia. This is because in these laws the Indonesian government acknowledges and respects

human rights. Therefore, they also have a duty to protect and fulfil the laws for the sake of the improvement of human dignity, well-being, and intelligence and justice. The government's obligation to fulfil its commitments means it must take any steps in legislative, administrative, judicial, and practice to ensure the implementation of human rights. Based on these arguments, Jakarta Local Regulation No. 8 of 2007 on Public Order, especially article 41 needs to be revoked and revised because it tends to violate human rights, stigmatise, and discriminate against people with leprosy. This regulation also indirectly confirms the necessity of isolation for lepers.

5.4.2. Tangerang Municipality

The pro-disabled (due to leprosy) persons policy started when the status of Tangerang was still a *kabupaten* (district). The head of the district at that time was Tadjus Sobirin. He led Tangerang district in two periods, from 1983-1993 (Soedirdja, 1999). As regent, he had a good relationship with the Sitanala hospital and persons affected with leprosy in Sitanala. Once, when there was a conflict between the Sitanala community and people from the Ceper village, he facilitated a meeting between two communities in his office and became mediator, successfully reconciling them. He usually came daily to Sitanala and to interact with people affected with leprosy. Every Friday, he prayed with them in Rahmi Hatta mosque. Under his leadership people in Sitanala felt safe and protected. He made a policy which allowed former leprosy patients to stay in Tangerang. Many programs and funds were available for Sitanala people when he led Tangerang district. He often met and had dialogue with people in Sitanala to find the appropriate ways to empower them.

In 1993, Tangerang district became a municipality (Indonesian Government, 1993). The first Mayor at that time was Djakaria Mahmud. He led Tangerang in one period, between 1993-1998. He continued what Tadjus Sobirin did and made a policy to empower former leprosy patients as street sweepers under the Cleaning and Landscaping Agency. It was under Djakaria Mahmud's administration that the local government provided a budget for street sweepers in Tangerang (Banten Hits, 2013). This policy continues until today: there are about 200 street sweepers working to

help the local government to make Tangerang clean (Ningrum, 2013; Sadikin, 2013; Tempo, 2013). As a result, Tangerang often receives *Piala Adipura* (environmental award for clean and green city) (Banten Province Local Government, 2014). It is well known that persons affected by leprosy are very diligent and persistent in making the streets clean and free of rubbish

In 1998, Wahidin Halim became a Mayor of Tangerang replacing Djakaria Mahmud. At that time, the aid for the Sitanala people had been stopped by the hospital. Since that policy applied, many Sitanala people went to the streets as beggars to try and meet their needs (Tangerang Local Government, 2013). There was a shift in paradigm to see Sitanala people at that time, from being a vulnerable group that need to be supported and empowered to a group of people that had become a burden.

From the point of view of Sitanala hospital, the Sitanala community occupied their assets (buildings and lands of the hospital) and had become a barrier to achieving the status of *Badan Layanan Umum (BLU)* (Public Service Agency). To achieve this status, Sitanala hospital needed to have capacity to fund themselves. This meant the hospital needed to transform to become a general hospital that provided services for general patients (Amna, 2015). This status had the benefit to staff of an increase in their allowance. However, the image and status of Sitanala hospital as a leprosy hospital is deterring general patients from seeking medical treatment in that hospital. For that reason, the hospital then divided the facilities for leprosy patients and general patients. Buildings for general patients were located at the front of the hospital, while the buildings for leprosy patients were in the back. The hospital also built a gate in the back, so that leprosy patients could enter through this gate without disturbing the general patients.

From the perspective of local government, the Tangerang municipality viewed the Sitanala community as a beggar village and feared that such activities would damage the image of the city. Consequently, Tangerang government issued Local Regulation No. 6/2011 on Public Order. Through this policy, persons affected by leprosy who are begging in the streets will be raided by *the Satpol PP* (Civil Service Police Unit)

(Tangerang Local Government, 2011). However, many criticised this regulation and its approach as *tidak manusiawi* (inhuman). Criticism even came from the Indonesian police, who did not want to be involved in the raids because they know that the persons affected by leprosy who are begging in the streets do these activities because they are so poor. They asked the Tangerang local government to first empower and increase the prosperity of the beggars. If they prospered but still begged, then the police will become involved in the raid.

In response to this criticism, Tangerang government issued Local Regulation No. 5/2012 on Assisting Street Children, Homeless People, Beggars, and Street Performers. Based on this regulation, those who are caught by raids will receive assistance from the government (Tangerang Local Government, 2012). In article 13, former leprosy patients who work as beggars will receive compensation from the government to fulfil their daily needs:

Article 13

- (1) Former leprosy beggars who cannot work due to their physical condition, will be given social assistance and compensation by considering the financial capacity of local government.
- (2) The social assistance and compensation for former leprosy beggars as the verse (1) will be further regulated through Mayor's decree (Tangerang Local Government, 2012).

However, the years passed, and the Mayor never issued the decree. Consequently, the Social Office of Tangerang could not allocate the budget for them. The Local Regulation No. 5/2012 is just a paper document without any follow-up. Sadly, the new Mayor has said to the mass media that the regulation has not been followed-up because they are worried this policy will make the number of beggars in Tangerang increase. The Mayor also recommends that Sitanala leprosy hospital needs to be a general hospital. Furthermore, he believes that Sitanala community needs to be relocated outside Tangerang city because most of them were not originally from Tangerang (Djamal, 2014; Uis, 2015; Zuliensyah, 2015). Local government sees *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* as a cancer in the city. The local government insists on using a raids approach that will not solve the problem. After capture, the beggars are only imprisoned temporarily, and then released (Aceng, 2017). It is not surprising that

after releasing them, they will go back to the streets and play 'cat and mouse' with the *Satpol PP*.

5.5. Conclusion

The replacing Law No. 4/1997 on *Penyandang Cacat* by Law No. 8/2016 on *Penyandang Disabilitas*, has marked the shifting of the paradigm from charity-based to human rights-based. It needed a long period to deconstruct the mindset of policy makers both at the national and local levels. Law No. 8/2016 is the first step that shows the good will of the Indonesian government to respect, protect, and fulfil the rights of persons with disabilities. In this context, *United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD)* has brought positive influences in formulating policies related to disabilities.

Law No. 8/2016 is not the end of efforts to promote the rights of disabled people in Indonesia. The government needs to harmonise laws and regulations, so that it will minimise confusion and conflict in the future. The government also needs to change their approach, from sectoral to multisector approach. This means disability issues are not only the responsibility of Ministry of Social Affairs, but also other ministries. The residual and institutional approaches also need to be shifted to a social development approach. This chapter has shown that at local levels, the regulations relating to disabled people are still a far cry from what is expected. Persons affected by leprosy are seen as social problem for society. As a result, many policies are discriminative and more isolated them from general society.

'My greatest pleasure is to serve the Lord in his poor children rejected by other people.'

(Father Damien)

Chapter 6: Community empowerment and social inclusion program in Sitanala

6.1. Introduction

The previous chapter has discussed the Indonesian policies in relation to disability and people with leprosy. These policies have influenced the government programs and stakeholders, such as faith-based organisations, community associations, university community services, disabled people's organisations (DPOs) and Corporate Social Responsibilities (CSR). This chapter presents various Community Empowerment and Social Inclusion (CESI) programs in Sitanala, as well as non-CESI programs to get the whole picture of social interventions in this community since 1953.

6.2. Government

The Indonesian government has a responsibility not only to respect and to protect the rights of persons with disabilities, but also to fulfil their rights. In relation to this, the government has implemented community empowerment and social inclusion programs in Sitanala to improve their social welfare and to reintegrate them into general society. The government institutions that contribute most to the CESI program in Sitanala are the Ministry of Social Affairs (MoSA), the Ministry of Health (MoH), the Ministry of Manpower and Transmigration (MoMT), the Ministry of Sport and Youth Affairs (MoSYA) and the Tangerang Local Government.

6.2.1. Ministry of Social Affairs (MoSA)

Based on Presidential Regulation No. 46/2015 on Ministry of Social Affairs, the Ministry of Social Affairs has four directorate generals: *Direktorat Jenderal*

Rehabilitasi Sosial (Directorate General for Social Rehabilitation), *Direktorat Jenderal Pemberdayaan Sosial* (Directorate General for Social Empowerment), *Direktorat Jenderal Penanganan Fakir Miskin* (Directorate General for Poverty Reduction) and *Direktorat Jenderal Perlindungan dan Jaminan Sosial* (Directorate General for Protection and Social Security). These four institutions are jointly responsible in handling social problems including poverty and disability issues (Indonesian Government, 2015a).

Figure 6.1
Four Directorate Generals in the Ministry of Social Affairs

Source: Indonesian Government (2015a)

The Indonesian Government Regulation No. 36/1980 on *Social Welfare Efforts for Penderita Cacat* (Persons Suffering from Deficits), had been massively used by the government as the basis for establishing social rehabilitation centres for people with disabilities. For those who have disabilities due to chronic diseases such as leprosy and tuberculosis, the Ministry of Social Affairs built *Panti Sosial Bina Pasca Laras Kronis (PSBLK)* (Social Rehabilitation Centres for Former Chronic Diseases Patients). These social rehabilitation centres have functions to provide social rehabilitation and

social services, to facilitate them to live independently and participate actively in the society (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2009).

There are several PSBLKs built by the government, such as *PSBLK Nganget* in East Java, *PSBLK Wasana Bahagia* in Ternate - North Maluku, and *PSBLK Marsaninsa Belidahan* in North Sumatra. It is important to note that there are also leprosy social rehabilitation centres that are established by non-government organisations. Interestingly, most leprosy rehabilitation centres for persons affected by leprosy are founded and managed by the Christian churches. For example, *Wisma Rehabilitasi Sosial Katolik (Wireskat)* (Catholic Social Rehabilitation Home) in Blora - Central Java, *Panti Rehabilitasi Kusta Gema Kasih (PRK Gema Kasih)* (Gema Kasih Leprosy Rehabilitation Centre) in Galang Deli Serdang - North Sumatra, and *Panti Rehabilitasi Kusta St Damian (PRK St Damian)* (St Damian Leprosy Rehabilitation Centre) in Manggarai, Flores - East Nusa Tenggara.

These PSBLKs provide social guidance, rehabilitation, and social services. Their activities cover: (1) assisting the former leprosy patients with basic knowledge and education; (2) providing physical, mental, and social guidance; and (3) conducting vocational training and social reintegration (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2009). Due to a long process of services, persons affected by leprosy must stay in the PSBLK for 3 to 6 months or even more. Considering the location of the PSBLKs that are very far from Sitanala, these services are unavailable for people in Sitanala.

6.2.1.1. CESI program

As the leading sector in providing social services for disabled people, the Ministry of Social Affairs has three CESI programs. Those are *Program Kelompok Usaha Bersama (KUBE)* (Joint Business Group Program), *Program Usaha Ekonomi Produktif (UEP)* (Productive Economic Business Program) and *Program Karang Taruna* (Youth Organisation Program).

6.2.1.1.1. Joint business group program

The joint business group (KUBE) is a group of people formed by the beneficiaries to carry out social and economic activities in a spirit of togetherness, to improve their social welfare. The joint business group program was first launched in 1982 and aims to accelerate the eradication of poverty in Indonesia, through: (1) increasing the entrepreneurial skills of the KUBE members in a group; (2) increasing income; (3) developing business; and (4) increasing awareness and social solidarity among the KUBE members and their social environment (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2015a).

The formation of groups by the beneficiaries begins after receiving social counselling, vocational training and stimulant aids. In this program, the KUBE manager is elected from and by the group members. The manager should have a strong motivation and they are able to support KUBE development. In other words, the KUBE manager should have the ability and experience to organise their members. The number of KUBE members varies from 5 to 10 people (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2011c).

The KUBE program offers vocational training to improve the knowledge, skills and competencies of persons affected by leprosy. Before conducting vocational training, the program facilitator should consider the location area and its conditions, in terms of marketing and business development. The training available varied, such as sewing, screen printing, fattening goats, etc. After finishing the vocational training, the beneficiaries receive stimulant aid to start their business. It is expected that through this program, the beneficiaries will have self-confidence and self-esteem to overcome their own problems and to improve their living conditions (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2015a).

There is a community facilitator of the KUBE program that is recruited by the government, to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of their business. The facilitator is responsible for motivating and developing the capacity of the KUBE

manager. The facilitator is also responsible for monitoring and evaluation of the program. In the monitoring and evaluation process, the facilitator identifies problems, challenges, barriers and offers possible solutions, so that the KUBE can develop well according to the plan. Monitoring and evaluation must be reported through a gradual mechanism, starting from the village, district/municipality, province and central levels (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2011c).

6.2.1.1.2. Productive economic business program

The Productive Economic Business Program (UEP) is a program that attempts to empower people by providing seed and start-up capital to open a small business. Different from KUBE, the beneficiaries of the UEP program are individuals. The beneficiaries will not receive equipment or materials, but an amount of money (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2010c).

The UEP program also requires a community facilitator to assist the beneficiaries. The facilitator is needed to improve the ability of persons affected by leprosy in term of fund management and business development. The facilitators will help the beneficiaries to:

1. Analyse their businesses in relation to the location, type of business and the marketing prospects.
2. Record the revenues and expenditures.
3. Record the business profit and loss statements.
4. Develop their business through partnerships (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2011b).

The role of facilitators in this program is to increase self-confidence of persons affected by leprosy and motivate them to start and expand their business. By starting and running their own business, people affected by leprosy are expected to be able to make a living and no longer dependent on other people, as well as to socialise within their social environment. Furthermore, the facilitators are responsible for developing social awareness of the society surrounding Sitanala, so that people

outside Sitanala community can contribute to and support this program (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2011c).

6.2.1.1.3. Youth organisation program

The Youth Organisation (Karang Taruna) program aims to increase participation of youth in development programs. This program was launched by the Minister of Social Affairs through The Indonesian Minister of Social Affairs Decree No. 13/HUK/KEP/1981 on *Susunan Oganisasi dan Tata Kerja Karang Taruna* (Organisational Structure and Operational Mechanism of Youth Organisation) (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 1981).

Based on the Regulation of the Minister of Social Affairs No. 77/2010 on *Pedoman Dasar Karang Taruna* (Basic Guidelines for Youth Organisation), Karang Taruna has several functions as follows:

1. Conducting social welfare efforts
2. Organising education and training for the community
3. Organising community empowerment, especially to the young generation
4. Developing the entrepreneurship to the young generation
5. Raising awareness among young people
6. Promoting social solidarity and strengthening local wisdom
7. Increasing creativity of young generation including productive economic business
8. Making referrals, assistance, and advocacy for those who are categorised as having social problems
9. Strengthening networking, coordination, communication, and partnership with stakeholders
10. Conducting efforts to prevent social problems (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2010a).

The membership of *Karang Taruna* is *stelsel pasif* (automatic membership). It means all people in Sitanala between 11-45 years old, automatically become members of

Karang Taruna. The *Karang Taruna* has the main task partnering to government and all stakeholders to address social problems, as well as to develop the potential of young people (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2013c).

6.2.1.2. Non-CESI program

The Ministry of Social Affairs also conducted non-CESI programs in Sitanala through *Program Beras Miskin (Raskin)* (Rice Subsidy for the Poor Program) and *Program Bantuan Langsung Tunai (BLT)* (Cash Transfer Program). They also have delivered food for Sitanala people every month since 1980s. However, this subsidised food program was stopped in 1998 due to decentralisation and local autonomy policy.

6.2.1.2.1. Subsidised rice for the poor program

Subsidised rice for the poor (Raskin) is a food subsidy program conducted by the Indonesian government to improve food security and to provide social protection for poor families. This core of this program is selling rice to the beneficiaries under market prices. It is expected that this program will help to reduce the expenditure of poor families in Indonesia. This program began in 1998, in which the beneficiaries received 20 kilograms of rice per month per household with the price \$0.10 per kilogram. Starting from 2008, the price of rice changed to \$0.16 per kilogram and the beneficiaries received 15 kilograms per month (Perum Bulog, 2016; TNP2K, 2015b, 2016b). The details of this program can be seen from table 6.1.

Table 6.1
The Raskin Program in Indonesia
1998-2016

No.	Year	Allocation per Month	Price per Kilogram	Total to Pay
1.	1998	20 Kg	\$0.10	\$2
2.	1999	20 Kg	\$0.10	\$2
3.	2000	20 Kg	\$0.10	\$2
4.	2001	15 Kg	\$0.10	\$1.5
5.	2002	20 Kg	\$0.10	\$2
6.	2003	20 Kg	\$0.10	\$2
7.	2004	20 Kg	\$0.10	\$2
8.	2005	20 Kg	\$0.10	\$2
9.	2006	15 Kg	\$0.10	\$1.5
10.	2007	15 Kg	\$0.10	\$1.5
11.	2008	15 Kg	\$0.16	\$2.4
12.	2009	15 Kg	\$0.16	\$2.4
13.	2010	15 Kg	\$0.16	\$2.4
14.	2011	15 Kg	\$0.16	\$2.4
15.	2012	15 Kg	\$0.16	\$2.4
16.	2013	15 Kg	\$0.16	\$2.4
17.	2014	15 Kg	\$0.16	\$2.4
18.	2015	15 Kg	\$0.16	\$2.4
19.	2016	15 Kg	\$0.16	\$2.4

Source: Perum Bulog (2016); TNP2K (2015b, 2016b)

The Raskin program is a cross-sectoral national program both vertical (from central government to the local governments) and horizontal (between ministries and state agencies). Based on the Indonesian Coordinating Minister for People's Welfare Decree No. 29/2014, this program involves the Coordinating Ministry for People's Welfare, the Coordinating Ministry of Economic Affairs, the Ministry of Domestic Affairs, the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Social Affairs, the Ministry of National Development Planning (the National Development Planning Agency), the Central Bureau of Statistics and the National Logistics Agency. This decree also mentioned that the Ministry of Social Affairs is responsible for the budgeting, mentoring, dissemination, monitoring and evaluation of the Raskin program (Indonesian Coordinating Ministry for People's Welfare, 2014).

6.2.1.2.2. Cash transfer program

Program Bantuan Langsung Tunai (BLT) (Direct Cash Transfer Program) aims to support poor families that are vulnerable due to the impact of the fuel price adjustment. The source of fund for this program is from *Anggaran Pendapatan dan Belanja Negara (APBN)* (Indonesian State Budget). This program basically adopted the cash transfer program from Brazil. The beneficiaries of this program were verified by the *Biro Pusat Statistik (BPS)* (the Central Bureau of Statistics) and the *PT Pos Indonesia (the Indonesian Post Office)* (DPR, 2012; TNP2K, 2013, 2015a). The amount of money was varied, and it can be seen from table 6.2.

Table 6.2
The Cash Transfer Program in Indonesia
2005-2015

No.	Program	Year	Amount	Period	Total
1.	BLT	2005	\$10	12 months	\$120
2.	BLT	2008	\$10	7 months	\$70
3.	BLSM	2013	\$15	4 months	\$60
4.	BLSM	2014	\$20	2 months	\$40
5.	PSKS	2015	\$20	8 months	\$160

Source: DPR (2012); TNP2K (2013, 2015a)

In 2013, BLT changed its name to *Bantuan Langsung Sementara Masyarakat (BLSM)* (Temporary Direct Aid Program). Data of the beneficiaries were based on the integrated data base as the result of *Survei Pendataan Program Perlindungan Sosial (PPLS)* (Survey for Social Protection Program), in 2011. This survey was conducted by BPS in collaboration with *Tim Nasional Percepatan Penanggulangan Kemiskinan (TNP2K)* (National Team for Accelerating Poverty Alleviation). The data base contains detailed information of poor people, by name and by address. In 2015, the Indonesian government changed the name BLSM to *Program Simpanan Keluarga Sejahtera (PSKS)* (Prosperous Family Savings program) (TNP2K, 2013, 2017b).

It is important to note that there are also social security programs in Indonesia organised by the Ministry of Social Affairs, such as *Program Keluarga Harapan (PKH)*

(Family Hope Program), *Program Jaminan Sosial Penyandang Cacat (JSPACA)* (Social Security Program for Disabled People) and *Jaminan Sosial Lanjut Usia (JSLU)* (Social Security Program for Elderly). These programs also use conditional cash transfer (CCT) mechanism (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2013b, 2016b).

Both JSPACA and JSLU programs were launched in 2006. The beneficiaries are persons with severe disability and the elderly poor. The beneficiaries of these programs will receive \$30 per month. However, in 2012 the amount money for the JSLU program decreased from \$30 to \$20 per month, whilst the amount money for JSPACA program remained stable (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2013a, 2016a).

The PKH was launched in 2007 by the Ministry of Social Affairs. In this program, the beneficiaries received \$20 per year. However, \$80 per year will be added to their account if the family has pregnant mothers, babies, pre-school children or school children. This money was added to improve their nutrition, as well as to access the basic health services. For school children, those who are in primary school received \$40 per year, whilst children at Junior High School received \$80 per year. Maximum support for each family was \$220 per year (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2016c, 2016d; TNP2K, 2016a). The scheme of PKH can be seen from table 6.3.

Unfortunately, these programs (PKH, JSPACA, and JSLU), are somehow are not available in Sitanala community. The possible reason for this is because the local government i.e. the Social Office of Tangerang City and Banten Province felt that there were too many programs available in this community, so that for 'justice and equality' they put these social protection programs to other places outside Tangerang.

Table 6.3
The Program Keluarga Harapan in Indonesia
2007-2015

No.	Scheme	Amount per Year		
		2007	2013	2015
1.	Permanent support	\$20	\$30	\$50
2.	Pregnant mother/childbed/baby/pre-school children	\$80	\$100	\$100
3.	Children of primary school	\$40	\$50	\$45
4.	Children of junior high school	\$80	\$100	\$75
5.	Children of senior high school	-	-	\$100
6.	Total minimum support per family	\$60	\$80	\$95
7.	Total maximum support per family	\$220	\$280	\$370

Source: Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs (2016c, 2016d); TNP2K (2016a)

The other non-CESI program that the Ministry of Social Affairs has is *Program Rehabilitasi Sosial Rumah Tidak Layak Huni dan Sarana Prasarana Lingkungan (RS-TLH & Sarling)* (Social Rehabilitation of Inadequate House and Environmental Infrastructure Facilities Program). This program aims to improve environment and housing to a healthy standard (Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs, 2011a). However, due to the status of land in Sitanala which is the property of Sitanala Hospital/MoH, this program could not be implemented. This is similar to *Program Pemberdayaan Nasional Masyarakat (PNPM) Mandiri* (National Program for Independent Community Empowerment), run by the Ministry of Public Works and the Ministry of Domestic Affairs. This program also cannot reach Sitanala due to the status of land. The PNPM Mandiri was launched in 2007 and it is basically a combination of two programs: *Program Pengembangan Kecamatan (PPK)* (The Subdistrict Development Program) in 1998; and *Proyek Penanggulangan Kemiskinan di Perkotaan (P2KP)* (Urban Poverty Alleviation Project) in 1999 to accelerate the achievement of Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) 2015. This program aims to improve infrastructure facilities and housing as well as to provide revolving loan funds for poor families (TNP2K, 2017a).

6.2.2. Ministry of Health (MoH)

The Ministry of Health has responsibilities in prevention and control of leprosy as well as providing medical services for persons affected by leprosy. This Ministry provides free Multi-drug therapy (MDT) for leprosy patients and in 2008 they launched *Program Jaminan Kesehatan Masyarakat (Jamkesmas)* (Medical Social Security Program) (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2011). The Ministry of Health through Sitanala Leprosy Hospital also had a unit called *Unit Therapy Kerja* (Working Therapy Unit) to empower former leprosy patients in the Sitanala. However, in 1985, they changed the name of the unit to *Unit Keterampilan Kerja (UKK)* (Vocational Training Unit) (Sitanala Leprosy Hospital, 1991). Even though the name of the unit has been changed, the activities remain the same, to provide vocational training for persons affected by leprosy.

The vocational training provided by the UKK aims to increase self-confidence and to encourage the participation of former leprosy patients in social and economic activities. To perform their tasks, this unit has some functions as follows:

1. Doing selection and analysis of the talents and working skills of former leprosy patients.
2. Providing education and vocational training for former leprosy patients based on the evaluation results and the capability of the hospital.
3. Assisting former leprosy patients in job seeking (Sitanala Leprosy Hospital, 1991).

There are various training areas available in the UKK, such as welding, electronics, carpentry and sewing. In the welding training, the former leprosy patients are trained to fix the iron gates, wheelchairs, and so forth. Those who receive electronics training are trained to repair radios, televisions, fans, and to do electrical repairs and installation. For carpentry, the training covers how to cut and fasten the wood, making furniture (chairs, cabinets, tables, door frames, windows), painting and furnishing. In sewing training, they are trained to make tablecloths, clothes for children, adults, patients, and uniforms for health officers of the Sitanala hospital. The training is carried out in a building of 360 square meters. The building is divided

into some space for training purposes. For those who like farming, they are trained to plant vegetables, orchids, and to raise catfish (Sitanela Leprosy Hospital, 2013).

The Sitanela hospital in collaboration with stakeholders such as MoSA, international and local non-government organisations, and faith-based organisations provided monthly food for Sitanela people since 1970s. However, this program was stopped in 1998 due to the rumour that Sitanela people already had a better living and did not need food aid anymore. The hospital argued that providing food was neither part of their task nor their function.

6.2.3. Ministry of Domestic Affairs (MoDA)

The Indonesian Ministry of Domestic Affairs has a community empowerment program namely *Program Pembinaan Kesejahteraan Keluarga (PKK)* (Family Welfare Movement Program). Launched by the Minister of Domestic Affairs in 1972, this program encourages women's participation in development, improves family welfare and educates the younger generations (Ahdiyana, 2001; Tim, 2008). The membership of PKK is voluntary and most of members come from key people in the community, who are often directed by wives of the heads of villages. At upper levels, the PKK leaders are the wives of the heads of the subdistrict, the mayor/head of district, the governor, and the president. One of the important contributions from PKK program is in building *Pos Pelayanan Terpadu (Posyandu)* (Integrated Community Health Care Centre). The Posyandu helps pregnant mothers and children under five years old to receive basic health services. There are seven activities in Posyandu that cover some areas such as health for mother and children, family planning, immunisation, nutrition improvement, prevention and treatment of diarrhea, basic sanitation, and providing essential medicine (ARS, 2013; Sari, 2011).

6.2.4. Ministry of Manpower and Transmigration (MoMT)

Transmigration is a program created by the government of Indonesia to move residents of an area of density (city) to other areas (villages) in the territories of Indonesia. Residents who join with this program are called *transmigran*

(transmigrators). The aims of this program are: (1) to reduce poverty and population density in Java; (2) to provide opportunities for people who want to work; and (3) to meet the labour requirements for processing resources on other islands such as Papua, Kalimantan, Sumatra, and Sulawesi (Goldman, 2005; Indonesian Government, 1972).

The transmigration program contributes to the alleviating poverty, as the government provides land and new opportunities for the poor transmigrators. This program helps to unite the whole nation by creating a single national identity of Indonesia that replaces regional identity (Indonesian Government, 1997b, 1999a). It is noted that the Ministry of Manpower and Transmigration in 1985 had sent 67 former leprosy patients and their families to Banyu Asin, Muara Enim, South Sumatra (25 families) and to Rangkas Bitung, Lebak, Banten (42 families) (Setyarso, 2007).

6.2.5. Ministry of Sport and Youth Affairs (MoSYA)

In 1988, Indonesian President, Soeharto, shocked the world by receiving eight people with leprosy in his office and shaking hands with them during *Pekan Olah Raga Penyandang Kusta Nasional (Porseptanas)* (National Sport Week for People with Leprosy). The *Porseptanas* invited much attention because it was the first time the Indonesian government had organised a special sports event for persons with leprosy. The first *Porseptanas* was held in Jakarta on 10 November 1988. In his speech for this event President, Soeharto said that leprosy is like other contagious diseases and it can be cured. This was a significant statement, a strong message challenging the traditional belief that leprosy is a curse from God and cannot be cured (Soeharto, 1988).

The second *Porseptanas* was held in October 1991 in Ujung Pandang (now Makassar). At that time, the President said that diminishing the fear of leprosy in society will help persons affected by leprosy to regain their self-confidence and self-esteem. This was the next step from his statement in 1988. By saying this, President Soeharto was acknowledging that fear and discrimination still exists, despite the scientific evidence

that leprosy is a curable disease (Soeharto, 1991). In this period, the Indonesian government was very active and open to acknowledge the leprosy problem and attempted to address leprosy issues.

6.2.6. Local Government of Tangerang

The Tangerang Social Office (TSO) often organises vocational training programs for persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala. The training is varied, including sewing, screen printing, as well as making handicrafts (wallets, shoes, and sandals). Through this training, the local government expected that persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala would slowly or gradually master some working skills that can be used to make a living. As a result, persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala would be no longer begging on the streets (Sekarningrum, 2013). The Social Office of Tangerang also provide UEP so that people with leprosy in Sitanala can develop their small business. Most of the fund was coming from the Ministry of Social Affairs (Banten Province Local Government, 2016).

Due to the rising number of beggars from Sitanala, the Tangerang Government initiated *Program Penyapu Jalanan* (Street Sweeper Program), to empower them. This program is under the Tangerang Cleaning and Landscaping Agency (TCLA) and launched during the Mayor Djakaria Mahmud period. By launching this program, the Tangerang local government would like to show to general society that persons affected by leprosy can be empowered as janitors and contribute to the environmental health of the city of Tangerang (Harahap, 2016). This program requires the street sweepers to work sweeping the street for 1 kilometres for 8 hours (from 5 am to 9 am and from 1 pm to 5 pm). Now, there are about 200 people with leprosy who work as street sweepers (Ningrum, 2013; Sadikin, 2013; Tempo, 2013). The government pay them \$ 7 per day (\$ 210 per month) (Irawan, 2014).

6.3. Faith-based organisation (FBO)

The Marfati Foundation is one of the organisations that is famous in doing community empowerment and social inclusion programs for people affected by leprosy in

Sitanala. This is because of their commitment to empower communities in Sitanala since 1960s. Starting from Father Van Eeden, SJ in the early 1960s who bought land across Sitanala leprosy hospital and founded Centrum Marfati (abbreviation of Maria Fatima) by Jesuit priests in collaboration with Sisters Congregation JMJ (Jesus Maria Joseph). The idea of establishing Centrum Marfati arose when they saw the difficulties faced by former leprosy patients into getting a job after finishing their medical treatment. The first empowerment program they conducted is employing former leprosy patients in making soap and cardboard business (Gereja Katolik Hati Santa Perawan Maria Tak Bernoda Tangerang, 2017).

In 1962, Marfati Foundation established the Marfati Welfare Unit to deal with the welfare of former leprosy patients, such as health clinics, spiritual activities, special skills, and simple shelters for the elderly former leprosy patients. In 1963, they founded the Marfati Working Industrial Unit (WII). This unit produced cardboard from rice straw for packaging of household appliances such as metal pots, kettles, and plates that had been produced by a factory. There were 45 people who were accommodated in this unit. After several years of running, this unit was no longer operational due to high competition with other factories (Gereja Katolik Hati Santa Perawan Maria Tak Bernoda Tangerang, 2017).

In 1970, the Marfati Foundation founded the Selapajang Farming Unit (SFU), located in the village of Selapajang Jaya, Tangerang. In this unit, the former leprosy patients were given the skills for raising chickens, pigs and farming fruits. There were 30 former leprosy patients who were accommodated in this unit. However, this unit was also no longer operational due to the limited human resources and funding. In 1971, The Marfati Foundation founded a unit called *Koperasi Mantan Penyandang Cacat Kusta* (Komata) that provided vocational training related to sewing skills, such as making school uniforms, factory employees uniform, and individual orders (Marfati Foundation, 2013). The number of former leprosy patients who joined with the Komata Unit was 40 people. After getting the training, the former leprosy patients could work in the Komata Unit or go back to their community and receive a sewing

machine to start their business. In 1972, the Marfati Foundation also established the Marfati Carpentry Unit (MCU). This unit provided carpentry training and received orders for school supplies such as desks, chairs, bookcases, etc. The number of former leprosy patients who were accommodated in this unit were 40 people. However, due to limited human and financial resources, this work unit is no longer active (Gereja Katolik Hati Santa Perawan Maria Tak Bernoda Tangerang, 2017).

In 2004, the Marfati Foundation built a nursing home for the elderly (Marfati Foundation, 2013). Therefore, the focus of services for persons affected by leprosy began to decrease significantly, as most beneficiaries in the nursing home are still afraid of contracting leprosy. Currently, there are 25 persons affected by leprosy who are still active in the Komata Unit that focus only on convection. However, the problem that they faced is that the lack of orders. This causes a concern because it will affect the lives of people with leprosy who work for this unit. To deal with this situation, the Marfati Foundation Board seeks orders from schools and monasteries. The Marfati Foundation also asked the workers in Komata Unit to sew tablecloths, aprons, trousers, and small bags, and then sold these items to the people who visit the Marfati Foundation. Luckily, they received an order for aprons from Netherland and sent 50 aprons every year. Although they are lacking orders, the workers are still working there and there is a worker that has been working in Komata Unit since 1976 (Gereja Katolik Hati Santa Perawan Maria Tak Bernoda Tangerang, 2017).

Another faith-based organisation that was concerned about persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala was Tzu Chi Foundation Indonesia. In 2008, this foundation distributed 1,232 bags of rice. Each bag contains 20 Kilograms of rice. They distributed the rice every 6 months. During the distribution process, the volunteer played and sang with the kids (Winarto, 2008). However, after seeing a person affected by leprosy sell his rice, they stopped this program immediately. This is different from churches that still commit to help and keep distribute food for Sitanala people every 3 months. In 2012, another faith-based organisation namely Infaq Dakwah Club (IDC)

also provided capital for productive economic business. This organisation also distributed prostheses for persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala (Jundullah, 2012).

6.4. Community association (CA)

Most Koreans in Tangerang work in the manufacturing companies such as shoe and garment factories (Carey, 2010). Thousands of Koreans who work in Tangerang choose to live in Lippo Village Tangerang. It is noted that 40% of the total residents in Lippo Village are Koreans. Thus, almost 80% of the 600 commercial buildings in Lippo Village are owned by the people of Korea. That is why many people called it as *Kampung Korea* (Korean Village). The Korean village serves all the needs of Koreans living nearby, providing various services such as shops, restaurants, karaoke lounges, spas, saunas, and massages with a Korean flavour (Nurbianto, 2007).

Tangerang Korean Community Sitanala is active in empowering Sitanala communities in the education sector. They provide *program beasiswa* (scholarship program) for children of persons affected by leprosy. The amount of scholarship for primary school is \$10 per month, and for those who are in the junior and senior high school receive \$15 and \$20 per month respectively. This scholarship is intended to ease the burden of their parents in spending their money for education costs. This program was started in 2012.

Tangerang Korean Community is also active in organising social inclusion program in Sitanala through recreational activities to entertain them. They arrange recreation for children who get scholarship and their parents every year. They usually go by bus and visit nice places such as the Jakarta Ragunan Zoo, the Taman Mini Indonesia Indah (TMII) and the Bogor Safari Park. Tangerang Korean Community covers all costs in relation to transportation, entrance ticket and food during the visit.

The Tangerang Korean Community also distributes 5 kilograms of rice per family every Saturday and 1 package of instant noodles every month. This program was started since 1986. Other help is given, beside food aid: they also help people in

Sitanala to keep healthy by providing medicine, bandages, and iodine. In some cases, they will cover medical costs in the hospital when their children are very sick or in an emergency. For the elderly, the Tangerang Korean Community also support them with \$10 per month. Not only the Tangerang Korean Community, but also individual donors such as Henderson Family are active in covering medical costs for some people in emergency.

6.5. University community service (UCS)

According to the Indonesian Law No. 12/2012 on Higher Education, every university in Indonesia must perform *Tri Dharma Perguruan Tinggi* (Three Principles of Higher Education). Not just for the lecturers, these principles also must be implemented by students who study in the university. The first pillar, education, means that universities have an obligation to provide good education through teaching and learning; and produce good quality graduates. The second pillar, research, means that universities have obligation to carry out research to develop science and technology. The last pillar, community service, means that universities have obligation to do community service, through social activities that benefit society (Indonesian Government, 2012).

According to the research findings, there are two universities that conducting community services in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala*. The University of Indonesia has conducted economic empowerment for mothers who are affected by leprosy through Nalacity program, whilst the University of Bina Nusantara (UBINUS) has organised tutorial for school children in Sitanala through *Teach For Indonesia* (TFI) program. These programs are still running today.

Starting from the Indonesian Leadership Development Program (ILDLP) conducted by the University of Indonesia, some students proposed a small project called Nalacity in 2010. At the beginning, this project focused on community empowerment through raising chickens. However, due to circumstances that made chicken raising unsuitable, they changed to making *jilbab manik-manik* (beaded scarves) (Syahriyani,

2011). Nowadays, there are 20 mothers who have received training from Nalacity and produced beaded scarfs. The Nalacity will buy the beaded scarfs from them and sell it through their online shop (Khalid, 2016; Muthmainah, 2015).

Different from Nalacity, University of Bina Nusantara focuses their activity on a tutorial program for school children (primary school and junior high school) through TFI. Launched in 2010, this program aims to help children from persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala in understanding school lessons and to prevent children from begging on the street. The teachers are volunteers from UBINUS. The tutorial program is conducted from Tuesday to Thursday between 3 pm and 5 pm. They teach subjects such as maths, English and general knowledge (TFI, 2016). The schedule of the tutorial program can be seen from table 6.4. This program is held in the Rumah Belajar Sitanala (Sitanala Learning House) that was founded in 2006 by Mrs Sriyatmo, a former leprosy patient who live in Sitanala, with the help of the Dutasia Foundation (Peduli Disabilitas, 2013). TFI is also concerned with empowering people in Sitanala. In 2016, TFI launched a microcredit program for people in Sitanala. This program was inspired by a microcredit structure and funded by individual donor including the Henderson Family (individual donors) in 2014.

Table 6.4
The Schedule of Tutorial Program in Sitanala

No.	Day	Participants			Time
1.	Tuesday	Year 1 (PS)	Year 4 (PS)	Year 1 (JHS)	3 pm – 5 pm
2.	Wednesday	Year 2 (PS)	Year 5 (PS)	Year 2 (JHS)	3 pm – 5 pm
3.	Thursday	Year 3 (PS)	Year 6 (PS)	Year 3 (JHS)	3 pm – 5 pm

PS: Primary School

JHS: Junior High School

Source: TFI (2016)

6.6. Non-government organisation (NGO)

There are several local non-government organisations (NGOs) that work for leprosy issues in Sitanala. Unfortunately, their function is limited to aid distribution only. This means that if there are no donors, they have no activity. The dependency on external

donors makes their commitment and idealism questionable by people in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala*. However, there is a local NGO that consistently helps people in Sitanala, i.e. *Yayasan Anak Langit* (Children of the Sky Foundation) and *Gerakan Peduli Disabilitas dan Lepra Indonesia (GPDLI)* (Indonesia Leprosy and Disability Care Movement).

Yayasan Anak Langit aims to humanise people, treating the children as children (not miniature adults), and eradicating illiteracy by introducing a formal school with several school subjects. This foundation is concerned with issues of child education, health, and welfare; and strengthening the family bond. It is noted that the foundation also has been successfully in sending the street children to schools, even some to universities (Anak Langit Tangerang, 2013). In this foundation, they also teach some skills such as screen printing, sewing or embroidery, farming as well as machine repairs, so that after graduation from schools, they can live independently. Most of children in this foundation are from poor families who work on the street as beggars, scavengers and collecting worms (Ariyanto, 2015). Now, this foundation has run their activities for almost 13 years and assisted 137 children. Interestingly, this foundation often refuses to accept the aid from the government due to the complexity of administration and reasons of autonomy.

Different from *Yayasan Anak Langit*, Indonesia Leprosy and Disability Care Movement (GPDLI) focused on social campaigns and advocacy for disabled people, especially persons affected by leprosy. Founded in 2009, this organisation aims to: (1) Increase self-confidence and self-sufficiency of people affected by leprosy and other disabilities; (2) Eliminate negative stigma associated with leprosy or other disabilities; and (3) Empower people affected by leprosy, so that they can participate in general society. GPDLI was very active in anti-stigma campaigns, especially during the World Leprosy Day celebration every year (Peduli Disabilitas, 2017).

6.7. Corporate social responsibility (CSR)

According to the Indonesian Law No. 40/2007 on *Incorporated Company*, corporate social responsibility (CSR) refers to the commitment of companies to participate in the sustainable economic development and to improve the quality of life and environment that benefit the company, local community, and general society (Indonesian Government, 2007). Many companies come to Sitanala to help through their CSR programs. For example, it was noted that PT Telkom tried to empower people in Sitanala through lamp repairing training; the CIMB Syariah Bank also delivered 50 prostheses to support their daily activities; and PT Pertamina provides a scholarship program for children in Sitanala (Ani, 2016; Community Development Center, 2011; CSR Indonesia, 2011). Starting from 2010, the scholarship program has covered 172 children from leper families. However, this company only covers children in primary school and junior high school, in which they will receive \$60 and \$90 per month respectively (CSR Indonesia, 2011).

6.8. Conclusion

Poverty and social exclusion problems in Sitanala community invited concerns from many organisations and even individual donors. This chapter has presented various programs for persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala to improve their social welfare since 1953. These programs can be categorised as CESI and non-CESI programs. The CESI program consist of social, economic, and political empowerment programs. The CESI program also covers some programs that help to increase access of Sitanala people through health, educational, employment and recreational programs. These programs tried to enhance capacities and assets of Sitanala people, as well as to increase access education, health, public space, and employment.

Field research suggests that e non-CESI programs are also available in Sitanala. Most of the non-CESI programs are charity based, characterised by incidental and direct service programs. Food, medical, and cash transfer aids are the examples for non-CESI programs.

Some important programs such as the Social Rehabilitation of Inadequate House and Environmental Infrastructure Facilities (RS-TLH & Sarling), National Program for Independent Community Empowerment (PNPM Mandiri), Family Hope Program, Social Security Program for Disabled People, and Social Security Program for Elderly are unavailable in Sitanala community.

Table 6.5
The CESI and Non-CESI Programs Available in Sitanala
1953-present

No.	Program	Aim	Types of Institution	Institution Name	Period	Status
I.	CESI Program					
A.	Community Empowerment					
1.	Economic Empowerment Program					
	- Vocational training	Equip people in Sitanala with knowledge, know how, skills and competencies	Central Government	MoH	1953-present	Short-term
			FBO	Marfati Foundation	1962-present	Long-term
			Central Government	MoSA	1982-1998	Short-term
			Local Government	TSO	1998-present	Short-term
			CSR	PT Telkom	2011	Incidental
			UCS	Nalacity	2010-present	Long-term
	- UEP	Provide seed and start-up capital for people in Sitanala to open a small business	Central Government	MoSA	1982-1998	Incidental
			Local Government	TSO	1999-present	Incidental
			FBO	IDC	2012	Incidental
			Individual Donor	Henderson Family	2014	Incidental
	- KUBE	Develop ability of people in Sitanala to solve problems and fulfil daily needs through joint business group	Central Government	MoSA	1982-1998	Short-term
	- Microcredit	Provide small and low-interest loans without collateral	UCS	TFI	2016-present	Long-term
			Individual Donor	Henderson Family	2014-present	Long-term
2.	Social Empowerment Program					
	- Karang Taruna	Increase participation of youth in development programs	Central Government	MoSA	1981-present	Long-term
	- PKK	Increase participation of women in development programs	Central Government	MoDA	1972-present	Long-term
3.	Political Empowerment Program					
	- Leprosy anti-stigma campaign	Promote the rights of people with disabilities	NGO	GPDLI	2010-present	Long-term

B. Social Inclusion						
1.	Health Program					
	- Jamkesmas	Provide free medication and health treatment for the poor	Central Government	MoH	2008-present	Long-term
2.	Educational Program					
	- Learning house	Provide prevocational trainings for children	NGO	Anak Langit Foundation	2004-present	Long-term
		Provide tutorial for students	UCS	TFI	2012-present	Long-term
	- Scholarship	Provide scholarship for poor students	CSR	PT Pertamina	2010-present	Long-term
			CA	TKC	2012-present	Long-term
3.	Employment Program					
	- Transmigration	Facilitate on-farm self-employment	Central Government	MoMT	1985-1988	Long-term
	- Street sweeper	Provide job as street sweepers for persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala	Local Government	TCLA	1993-present	Long-term
4.	Recreational Program					
	- Sightseeing	Entertain people in Sitanala by visiting popular and beautiful places	CA	TKC	2012-present	Long-term
		Entertain people in Sitanala through children's dance performance	FBO	Churches	2010-present	Incidental
	- National sport and art week	Organise sport event for former leprosy patients	Central Government	MoSYA	1998, 1991	Incidental
II.	Non-CESI Program					
1.	Food Aid	Reduce the expenditure of poor families in Sitanala	Government and stakeholders	MoSA, MoH, KCA, Tzu Chi Foundation, Marfati Foundation, etc.	1978-present	Incidental, short-term, long-term
2.	Medical Aid	Provide first aid kits	CA	TKC	2012-present	Incidental
		Help with medical costs in emergency	Individual Donor	Henderson Family	2014	Incidental
		Distribute prostheses for disabled people in Sitanala	CSR	PT Bank CIMB Niaga	2016	Incidental
FBO	IDC		2012	Incidental		
3.	Cash Transfer (BLT, BLSM, PSKS)	Support poor families that are vulnerable from the impact of fuel price adjustment through extra money	Central Government	MoSA	2005-present	Incidental

*“When I give food to the poor, they call me a saint.
When I ask why the poor have no food, they call me
a communist.”*

(Dom Helder Camara)

Chapter 7: Social and historical context of the Sitanala leprosy village

7.1. Introduction

This chapter will describe the Sitanala leprosy village in Tangerang as a location of the study. The first subchapter will explain the history of this village. Therefore, the history of Sitanala hospital and its patients need to be explored. Understanding the history of Sitanala leprosy village is also a very strategic step to knowing more deeply this community. The next subchapter will present the situation of Sitanala leprosy village today. It covers the profile of this community and their social and economic living. This subchapter will also emphasise beggar issues, problem with drugs and alcohol, children and elderly as vulnerable groups, and discrimination in Sitanala and their strategy to cope.

7.2. The history of Kampung Kusta Sitanala

Kampung Kusta Sitanala is located in the Kelurahan Karangsari (village), Kecamatan Neglasari (subdistrict), Kota Tangerang (municipality), Propinsi Banten (province). The latitude and longitude coordinates are: -6.1625164, 106.6346271. It is established on 5 hectares of land owned by the Sitanala leprosy hospital, Ministry of Health (MoH). *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* is about 8 kilometres in distance from Soekarno Hatta International Airport and 26 kilometres from West Jakarta. Karangsari village has 19,947 population and has 15 *Rukun Warga (RW)* (citizen associations), RW 01-15. Because *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* is situated in RW 13, some people call *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* ‘RW 13’.

It is important to understand that the term of *kampung* in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala*, which is not referring to a government administrative region system (village in the real sense), but rather refers to a community that settled in one place and have a certain characteristic, such as *kampung idiot* (idiot village) in Ponorogo, *kampung pasir* (sand village) in Madura, *kampung gelandangan* (homeless village) in Jakarta, or *kampung pelacuran* (prostitution village) in Indramayu. *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* has many terms. Firstly, some people called it as *Komplek Serba Guna (KSG)* (Multipurpose Complex) because the location is originally a transit point for those who will return to their families after finishing their medical treatment. Secondly, many people also called *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* as *Kampung BBS* (BBS village), the abbreviation of *barang bekas* (second hand goods). This refers to the persons affected by leprosy in that place who are associated to goods that already are not used due to their missing organs (their bodies are incomplete or defective). Thirdly, *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* also often called as *Kampung Pengemis* (Beggar village), considering that most people who live there, work as beggars. Lastly, people from *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* also often called as *Orang Sewan* (people from Sewan). Sewan is an old name of this area in the past, refers to many people who are migrating from rural to urban locations and renting houses or rooms in that area). That is why when Sitanala Leprosy Hospital was first established in 1951, the original name is *Leprosarium Sewan* (Sewan Leprosarium).

7.2.1. Sitanala leprosy hospital

The origin of *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* cannot be separated from the history of Sitanala leprosy hospital. Sitanala leprosy hospital (at that time *Leprosarium Sewan*) was basically transferred from *Leprosarium Lenteng Agung* (Lenteng Agung Leprosarium) in Jakarta. This leprosarium was previously run by Dutch missionaries. This explains why when it began operating in 1953, the hospital was led by a Dutchman named Dr. E.G.E. van der Heyde, who led the hospital from 1953 to 1958. In 1962, the government renamed it as *Pusat Rehabilitasi Sitanala* (Sitanala Rehabilitation Center), before finally in 1978 the Ministry of Health changed its name into *Rumah Sakit Kusta Dr. Sitanala Tangerang* (Dr. Sitanala Leprosy Hospital,

Tangerang) as a tribute to a doctor from Ambon, Maluku named Dr. Jacob Bernadus Sitanala (1889-1958), who dedicated his life as a pioneer of modern leprosy treatment in Indonesia. Due to his dedication, the Indonesian government raised Sitanala as one of national heroes in Indonesia.

Figure 7.1
Sitanala Leprosy Hospital Map

Source: Google Maps

According to historical records, the first leprosy hospital in Indonesia was established in 1666 by the *Vereenigde Oostindische Compagnie (VOC)* (The Dutch East India Company) in Angke, North Batavia (now Jakarta). However, due to protests from Batavia residents, in 1679, Leprosarium Angke was transferred to Purmerend Island, in the bay of Batavia. Due to the decreasing population of leprosy patients, the Leprosarium of Purmerend was closed and stopped its activities in 1795 (Balk, van Dijk, & Kortlang, 2007; Boomgaard, 2007; Buijn, 2009). After being affected by the Krakatoa Eruption in 1883, this island was neglected. Today, people call Purmerend *Pulau Bidadari* (Angel Island) as a tribute to those who dedicated their lives to leprosy patients in the past. Nonetheless, some people in Indonesia still recognise Purmerend as *Pulau Sakit* (Sick Island).

Based on the Indonesian Minister of Health No. 140/Men.Kes/SK/IV/1978, Sitanala leprosy hospital is a technical unit under the Indonesian Ministry of Health, in which the Directorate General of Medical Services is directly responsible for it. Until today, the director of Sitanala leprosy hospital has changed 11 times.

Figure 7.2
The Sitanala Leprosy Hospital

The Sitanala leprosy hospital has a logo 'Sirno Dening Pangastuti', which means the disease and its stigma will only disappear with gentleness, patience, and compassion.

The hospital provides services to leprosy patients as follows:

- Outpatient unit, it has the tasks of providing outpatient services for leprosy patients.
- Radiology unit, it has the task of creating and analysing Rontgen photos.
- Surgical unit, it has the task of providing services for leprosy patients who need surgery.
- Prosthesis unit, it has the tasks of making prosthetic hand, leg and foot wear for leprosy patients.
- Physiotherapy unit, it has the tasks of providing services to the leprosy patients by relaxing their muscles, using gas, water and so forth.
- Vocational training unit, it has the tasks of providing vocational training for ex-leprosy patients who have disabilities.

As the first national leprosy hospital in Indonesia, Sitanala had complete and modern facilities. Many people came from all over Indonesia, and some of them were from overseas such as Malaysia, Pakistan, India, and Bangladesh. This was most likely because they were embarrassed at having leprosy, so that they preferred to seek a medical treatment in Indonesia - far from their homes. At that time, leprosy patients who had completed medical treatment were experiencing tremendous rejection from their communities because of the stigma of leprosy and disability. After considering this situation, Sitanala leprosy hospital had finally made a policy, in which they allowed former patients to occupy *Komplek Serba Guna*.

Sitanala leprosy hospital received funds from many donors both domestic and foreign. The funds then distributed by the hospital through monthly package for leprosy patients who lived at *Komplek Serba Guna*. The package consists of 10 kilos of rice, 15 packets of instant noodles, 1 kilo of sugar, 1 bottle of cooking oil (620 cc), 2 cans of condensed milk, 1 kilo of eggs, and 4 ounces of beef floss (Sitanala Leprosy Hospital, 1991). These packages were distributed mainly to the *Komplek Serba Guna* residents who were poor. For those who are in hospitalisation, they did not get the monthly package because the hospital already provided food in their wards. The funds from donors were also used by the hospital to provide scholarships for children who suffer from leprosy, children of lepers, and the children of ex-lepers.

In 1985, the Director of Sitanala leprosy hospital, introduced an initiative to send 67 former leprosy patients and their families to Banyu Asin, Muara Enim, South Sumatra (25 families) and to Rangkas Bitung, Lebak, Banten (42 families) on behalf of *Program Transmigrasi* (a resettling inhabitants program, migration from overpopulated area to less populated regions for farming). The hospital also repatriated 8 families back to their homeland in Rangkas Bitung. The program was intended to move the occupants of *Komplek Serba Guna* into general society. Unfortunately, their dreams to start a new life as farmers were dashed. The area in Muara Enim was still a swamp of waist depth and still forested with lots of tall grass, in which even for healthy people it would be difficult to manage. However, due to their hopes to start a new

life, they started to work on that land. However, when the plants had grown fertile, the rain suddenly came, and their agricultural lands were flooded up to 1 metres. As it happened so many times, after three years staying in that place, they decided to return to Sitanala. They questioned the pictures of fertile rice fields (disseminated by the official government staff), which did not correspond with the reality in the field. The same situation also occurred in Lebak, Banten. Their places were apparently geographically isolated areas, about 25 kilometres from the downtown. Shuttle buses could not go so far, so that crops could not be sold at a profit. The area was a rocky soil and when rain came all their plants flooded away. When drought came, they had to fetch water from the *Perkampungan Baduy Luar* (outer Baduy people's settlement, indigenous people of West Java) which was about 3 kilometres from their places. Enduring great difficulty to survive, finally, they decided to return to Sitanala. Now, only one family still lives in that area. This is because his land is relatively good and fertile. However, he still lives in poverty and works for the mosque near his house. Those who returned from transmigration areas, occupied unused buildings of Sitanala hospital. With others who came to Sitanala after 1990 they created a new settlement area that now becomes RT 01.

7.2.2. Leprosy patients

To get more understanding about the history of *Kampung Kusta Sitanala*, we should see it not only from the Sitanala hospital perspective, but also from the leprosy patients' point of view. This section will describe their experiences of having leprosy from the beginning when they lived in their hometown until they came to Sitanala hospital. These experiences will be presented systematically based on oral stories.

7.2.2.1. Tale from a place of origin

Many people see Sitanala community as a social problem. There are many negative stereotypes around this community that tend to blame them. The main question that people have is that why they live in such slum area and do not want to move to other places. To answer this question, we need to know exactly what happened to those living with leprosy in their villages.

7.2.2.1.1. First time having leprosy

At the beginning, leprosy patients who had medication in Sitanala had no idea about their diseases. They only knew from the symptoms such as many spots in their skins like tinea versicolor, but a bit reddish, thick, bulging, and numb. They said that they did not feel anything when the spots were needled or burned. If the spots hit the water, their skin became itchy. Then if the spots were scratched, it easily led to infection and injury. There was a case when a leprosy patient put his hands into hot water, he did not feel anything:

At first, I felt my hands so itchy and I often scratched it. Then, I saw boiling water in the basin. I put my hand into that water. What happened next had surprised me. The water was not hot like I thought. It was cold. Next, I just knew my hands blistered and soled. (Participant 1, male, in-depth interview)

Usually, leprosy patients felt their bodies became hot. Most of them easily got fevers and they felt so weak. Even for walking was not strong enough. They felt easily get tired and sick. Their bodies became swollen and red. In some cases, their skins turned to scaly like snake scales. It was also common that they experience hair loss and their appetites to eat and drink had gone. Those who had severe leprosy, usually their ears turned long, and their fingers transformed into claw fingers. Some leprosy patients usually walked by dragging their legs and they faced continuous tingling. Due to the red – white faces they got, people often called them strip face. Once they consumed *lamrene*, their entire bodies and faces became black. Thus, people often called leprosy patients as monsters, who had ghost or demons faces:

Having a disease like this always made me shy and unconfident. We were like a monster not a human. Our face was like ghost. Like a scarecrow... That was my bitter experiences when living in my hometown. (Participant 6, female, in-depth interview)

In many cases, leprosy patients often bleed and injured their feet due to shards or nails, but they were realised because their feet were numb. This can be seen through this case:

My legs were very weak. Every time I tried to walk, I fell. That is true. I'm not lying. Every time I tried to walk, I fell. Then, my legs were paralysed. Every time I used my footwear, I often lose it. Next, I felt pain on my waist and tingling over my body. Every time I touched something, I could not feel anything. In my

village, people rarely wear slippers, including me. My feet were injured by thorns, shards and nails till bleeding, but I did not feel anything. Once, I felt pain in one of my soles and got high fever. The sole was swollen and often bleeding. It was fester and rot. After having medical treatment, I just knew that there was a long conch in my sole for a long period and it was covered by the new skin. Can you imagine that? There was a conch in my sole for a long time, but I did not feel anything. (Participant 3, female, in-depth interview)

7.2.2.1.2. Seeking medication

Most of persons affected by leprosy came from poor and isolated villages, in which had difficulties to access health care centres. They were seeking medication from anywhere, there was no any change. Usually they went to *tabib* (traditional healers), *orang pintar* (clerics) and *dukun* (shamans). The reason why they went to these people instead of seeing doctor or modern health services is because it was cheaper and common to do it:

I lived at the village. My parents had no money to pay the doctor nor to go to the health care centre. Usually, we would wait till the harvest time to seek medication. That's why we went to tabib, orang pintar or dukun. (Participant 7, female, in-depth interview)

The second reason why they did not go to see doctors or health care services is because their villages were too far away to access it. If there was a health care centre, the doctor only came every 1-2 weeks:

I went to the dukun, orang pintar, or tabib because the health care centre was far away from my place. We needed money to take rural transportation. It was usually full and took one hour to get there. Sometimes, there was no doctor there, only nurses or health officers. The doctor came once a week, but sometimes the doctor did not come for two weeks. In contrast, if we went to the dukun, we went there by foot. No cost... We were neighbours. (Participant 2, female, in-depth interview)

Most of *orang pintar* and *dukun* said that the disease was caused by a devil or bad spirits. There is also a view that the disease occurs due to (*teluh*) black magic or (*guna-guna*) witchcrafts. Therefore, they asked persons affected by leprosy to do rituals to eliminate the bad spirits and black magic. Many of the people with leprosy were given incantations by the *dukun* or *orang pintar* and must drink a glass of water that had been recited over with incantations:

I worked as a farmer. After having serious ill, my father took me to the orang pintar. The orang pintar said there was a bad spirit in my body, came from my place of work. The spirit was angry because I did not ask permission when I went to the rice field. The orang pintar gave me a glass of water that had been given incantations. (Participant 6, female, in-depth interview)

Another research participant shares his story when he went to *orang pintar*. The *orang pintar* reading his palm and asked them to sleep covered by banana leaves:

I went to many orang pintars. Most of them had seen and read my palm. Usually after reading my palm they recited like a mantra and prayed. One of them that I remember the most is the orang pintar who ordered me to sleep covered by banana leaves. I did it for 2-3 months, but it did not work well. It was useless. (Participant 4, male, in-depth interview)

There was a *dukun* that gave a bottle of water and asked the person affected by leprosy to drink it once they arrived at their homes. The *dukun* said that they had to go back to their homes straight, otherwise the magic of the water would be gone:

If I felt not sure with the dukun, I changed my mind and went to other dukuns. I remember one of the dukuns said that I must drink the water he gave me, but I must return straight to my house. If not, the water would not be sacred anymore. I was just a stupid person. I did not go to school because my parents were very poor. So, I just taken for granted what the dukun said. But again, there was no changes to my disease. (Participant 8, male, in-depth interview)

Sometimes the *dukun* gave a glass of water that had been recited over with incantations and asked the persons affected by leprosy to wash his faces three times with the water:

I ever went to the dukun once. The dukun said that someone had sent teluh and guna-guna over me. Then, the dukun gave me a bottle of water and I should wash my faces three times with that water. (Participant 11, male, in-depth interview)

There was another experience that at midnight, they were ordered by the *dukun* to bathe with kinds of flowers in cold water which makes them chilled:

People in my village were not really knew about a doctor. So, we went to dukun if we were sick. The dukun said it was my bad luck because someone sent witchcraft to another person, but it had missed the target and hit over me. They asked me to bathe with kinds of flower using cold water at the midnight. The dukun gave me the list of the flowers and asked me to avoid consuming lamb. (Participant 9, female, in-depth interview)

There was another case in which the dukun asked persons affected by leprosy to bathe with *air kapur* (limewash), to purify their body. The *dukun* said that the disease was a cursed from God:

In the beginning, I did not know that I had leprosy. The dukun ordered me to bathe in the beach every midnight. By doing this, the spirits and demons would be disappeared. After no changing, the dukun ordered me to bathe with air kapur. Therefore, all skins over my body was destructed. Then the dukun said that it was a curse from God. I was the chosen one. At that time, I preferred to die rather than living with leprosy. (Participant 5, male, in-depth interview)

Similar experience also told by persons affected by leprosy, in which the dukun ordered to bathe with hot water and sleep in front of bathroom. Most villages at that time, built bathroom usually in the back of their houses in separate building. Sleep in front of bathroom means sleep outside their houses.

My neighbour advised me to go to a dukun. The dukun asked me to bathe at midnight with boiled water. Even that the water was very hot, I did not feel anything. Then, I must sleep outside my house, in front of the bathroom like a frog. I was prohibited to enter my house. My parents were just silent. They believed the dukun would diminish the black magic. The truth is that it was not black magic, it was just leprosy. (Participant 7, female, in-depth interview)

There was a case revealed by a participant of research that she was nearly raped by the *dukun* based on the reasoning that the spirit would disappear if she is having sexual intercourse with the *dukun*. However, she cried and ran away and refused to see the *dukun* again:

People in my village said that the cost to see a doctor was very expensive. It was very expensive. That is why many people in my village went to dukuns. There was a dukun said to me that I had a diabetic. To cure it I must sleep with him. I would be cured once I had slept with the dukun. The dukun also said that the sexual intercourse would show to him what other diseases in my body. At that time, it was true I felt very sick, but I was not crazy. I just cried and left the dukun immediately and told my parents that it did not make sense. (Participant 7, female, in-depth interview)

Those who went to *tabibs* also faced bitter experiences, similar like persons who went to *orang pintar* or *dukun*. The *tabib* said that the disease is caused by food allergies such as lamb and other meats. The *tabib* also said that leprosy is a common skin disease and ordered them to rub all over their body using tomatoes or lemons, even though their skin is sore:

The tabib advised me to go to market and buy tomatoes or lemons. I must take a bath with warm water and rub my body with tomatoes and lemons. My skin was sore and painful. I did everything what the tabib said, but it was still no changes. My condition was getting worse. (Participant 2, female, in-depth interview)

There was a case that the *tabib* wrapped the leprosy patient's legs with bandage and wood till they got injured:

I went to the tabib. After massaging my legs, the tabib wrapped it tightly with wood and bandage. Because my legs were numb, I could not feel that my legs were so hot. Thus, my legs were burnt and injured. I said to my mother, going to tabib did not make me better, in reverse, it made my condition worse. My mother was just silent. (Participant 6, female, in-depth interview)

Interestingly, there was a participant that went to the doctor at that time, said the doctor did not know that it was leprosy:

I had fever and my body was so hot. I went to a doctor. He said it was just an ordinary stomach ache. It had no impact on my illness. There was no connection between the disease and the medicine. This was crazy that the doctor did not know that it was leprosy. The doctor did not know... I just knew that it was leprosy a year after, when I went to the hospital. (Participant 10, female, in-depth interview)

From the gender perspective, stories of similar experiences were told by one of the female participants. When the symptoms of leprosy appeared, all traditional healings had been tried by her and failed. She finally decided to seek medical treatment at the health centre. At the health centre that was located quite far away, the doctor confirmed that she had *kusta* (leprosy). At that time, she did not know what leprosy was. One of the health workers said that once people have leprosy, they will lose their fingers and limbs. She was very shocked hearing this information. The health worker recommended her to go to Sitanala hospital to get better medical treatment. Unfortunately, when she told that to her husband, he rejected it. This is because her husband felt that nobody would do the domestic affairs when she went to Sitanala. In Indonesian society, especially in Java Island the patriarchal culture was very strong, all decisions are made by the husband. It can be illustrated by the saying 'Swargo nunut neroko katut' (a wife should follow her husband to go to heaven even to hell). After a long delay in going to Sitanala, her condition was getting worse and her neighbours started to isolate her. After speaking with her father, and her husband

rarely at home, so she decided to go to Sitanala. However, she was punished by her husband. The form of the punishment was divorce and loss of custody of children.

7.2.2.1.3. Facing discrimination

After they knew that they had leprosy, most of them were shocked and afraid. They were worried because stigma of leprosy could affect their lives. All the erroneous traditional religious views and beliefs about leprosy contributed to create stigma and it is passed from generation to generation through bedtime stories.

I had never heard about what leprosy is, but my mother told the story about it before passed away. She said that in the past there was a person who had leprosy. One of the signs was they had many ulcers. Because they had many ulcers, people did not care about them and exiled them. People took and put them in an ugly shack near forest. People exiled them. That is my mum's story about leprosy. It made me so scare. (Participant 2, female, in-depth interview)

Firstly, it is common in general society that leprosy is interpreted as a curse due to sins committed by people with leprosy or their predecessors (parents or grandparents) in the past. People often call this *karma*. As a result, people with leprosy are associated to a negative thing which could bring bad luck to their family and their community. They are considered as unclean, so that when they go to the mosque for worship, people immediately left. Secondly, many people also called leprosy as the 'king of diseases' that cannot be cured. For example, people in West Java call leprosy 'mariti' (abbreviation from *marinya mati*, which means there is no cure for this disease except death). They do not know that leprosy can be cured by MDT, a combination of drugs such as DDS (dapson), clofazimine (Lamprene) and rifampicin. That is why, in the past, people often assumed that persons affected by leprosy would be dead during their stay in Sitanala. This explains why most of the affected do not receive an inheritance and have lost contact with their families. Thirdly, most people accept the idea that leprosy spreads through any objects touched or used by lepers. Fear of its transmission and lack of information about leprosy isolate people with leprosy. Lastly, most people believed that leprosy is a heredity disease. It can be passed in the family because of the same blood. Consequently, people with leprosy have difficulties to marry or risks of divorces with their spouses.

Persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala feel that life is endless suffering. In their hometown, they were discriminated against in almost all aspects of life. For example, they could not watch TV in the village hall; they have to stand at the back of the line during the distribution of clean water or milk; children could not play with their peers, at school they are teased by their friends and teachers also were in fear of them, their fowls were often beaten by neighbours; food they had contributed was never touched or eaten during *sedekah bumi* (alms earth ritual); people dismissed straight away when they went to the mosque for praying, even their brothers and sisters do not want to eat together and ask for individual ware and toiletries; when they went to health care, the doctors, nurses and health workers were in fear, etc. These are bitter experiences people have as lepers.

The leprosy stigma and discrimination they experienced had a great impact on their psychological conditions. They became shy, had low self-esteem, frustration, and depression. That is why, many of the leprosy patients dropped out of school because of embarrassment and ridicule by their classmates. Many of them lose their jobs because of having leprosy. Some of them locked themselves in their room and contemplated their fate. Due to fear of being isolated by others, they hid their leprosy, and chose to go to traditional healers. Many of them stopped their treatment because of depression and had nobody to support them. Some people became alcoholic and used drugs. They even thought of committing suicide:

I heard the conversation between my wife and my father in law. My father in law said that my disease is very contagious, and it needs a long time to cure. My wife replied that she was also sad. She said that I still love to eat and drink but have no money. Hearing this conversation, I took a rope. I wanted to hang myself. I was so desperate and frustrated. But I remembered that a person who committed suicide, after death they will become a ghost. I remembered God. Therefore, I cancelled my desire to commit suicide. (Participant 1, male, in-depth interview)

Another participant told similar story about his willingness to commit suicide after broking his relationship with his girlfriend:

After having leprosy, I tried to run out from the reality. I consumed alcohol and drugs. I used to get drunk every day. I asked God to take my life. I slept for nearly

three days. My family was panic and screamed. The other day, I consumed DDS 200 mg from USA. It used to be eaten a quarter of the pill for treatment. I ate 5 pills. I was still alive, but for five days, my body was like watering by boiled water. I was trashing around like an overheating worm. (Participant 12, male, in-depth interview)

It is the truth that persons affected with leprosy who lived in the villages often thought about suicide. However, because of their spirituality they had not done it. They believed that God has a purpose. This made them to accept their condition and make peace with the situation. Most support is from their parents. However, they left their home because they did not want to make their parents sad as it would disgrace them to have a child with leprosy.

7.2.2.2. Having treatment in Sitanala

In the 1950s, the Indonesian government was involved in intense outreach to villages in remote areas, with the help of missionaries from the churches. Interestingly, it was common for leprosy patients to be from poor families. Some of them came to Sitanala due to their awareness after getting information from the missionaries and local health authorities:

After cancelling my desire to commit suicide, I met Sister Hilda, a church missionary from Australia. She asked me whether I agree to go with her to Sitanala for medical treatment. I said yes without hesitation. After arriving Sitanal hospital I cried. I felt free. I felt that all my burdens had gone. Sister Hilda was like a saint to me. God sent her to save my life. I was free. (Participant 1, male, in-depth interview)

However, many of them felt that they were exiled by their communities. This can be understood as during that time Sitanala leprosy hospital was very quiet place and surrounded by forests, in which many people knew Sitanala as the disposal place for persons affected by leprosy:

When I arrived Sitanala, I was so curious because I saw white linen in my bag. I checked carefully. You know what? When I opened my bag, it was 11 metres kain kafan (shroud). I was so shocked. It was like a message for me that my family wanted me to die. So, I met the leader of Sitanala leprosy patient association. I told him, if I died just bury my corpse into the graveyard. Don't wait my family from my village, because they did not acknowledge me due to my disability. (Participant 11, male, in-depth interview)

It was common for leprosy patients in Sitanala that they had lost contact with their family. It can be shown by stories that many of them had not been visited by their family during their stay in the Sitanala hospital. There was a case that their family came, but it just made them sadder:

My aunty looked very afraid of being contaminate of leprosy from me. She sent me to Sitanala hospital. One day, she came to Sitanala. She did not want to see me. She just stood at the security office. She just gave some money to me through the security. After that, she was never contacting me. That's why after finishing my medical treatment, I did not want to go back to my village. I better stay here until I die. (Participant 8, male, in-depth interview)

When they came to Sitanala for the first time, they were also experiencing discrimination. Many bus drivers did not allow them to get on the bus. If a bus stopped to transport them, many passengers disembarked straight away. Some people who were still on the bus, they covered their nose and sat far away from people who have leprosy. In the restaurants, it was common for the owners to just say that they had run out the food, although persons affected by leprosy knew that the food was still available. In markets, many traders disliked them and never touch money given by persons affected by leprosy with their hand, rather offered a paper holder to accept the money. At funerals, persons affected by leprosy were usually buried in the fringe areas, and when the body is carried, people step aside. No one would accept them for work. They said that they had faced too many sad experiences to tell.

At that time, it was the the Sitanala hospital that became concerned and recognised their dignity as human beings. Sitanala hospital, Ministry of Social Affairs (in the past Department of Social Affairs) and International NGOs helped them by providing food every month, so that they could survive. The relationship of people in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* and the hospital was very harmonious. All health care workers were so friendly to people with leprosy. If nurses showed their fear, the director reprimanded them immediately. This wonderful relationship developed when Princess Diana came from England to visit Sitanala hospital on November 5, 1989. Many health workers were inspired by her, when she came to shake hands with leprosy patients, hug, kiss, sit, speak with, hold the bandage places of their body, and play chess together,

without any fear. They remembered how the Director of hospital came every morning to visit Sitanala and have a conversation with them. Every Friday, he took time to pray in Rahmi Hatta Mosque together with persons affected by leprosy.

People in Sitanala remembered that in the past, Dr. Johannes Leimena, the Ministry of Health in the Soekarno's era showed his concern for people in Sitanala:

When Leimena became Minister of Health, he said to leprosy patients in Sitanala hospital, 'This is your paradise'. This statement reflects that our leaders in the past were very concerned about our lives. His signature still can be seen in the Sitanala hospital. (Participant 8, male, in-depth interview)

That is why the Sitanala leprosy hospital then allowed former patients to occupy *Komplek Serba Guna*. Starting from 3-5 families, the number of people who lived in *Komplek Serba Guna* increased quickly. Those who did not find a place in the buildings also received permission from the hospital to build houses behind the hospital. Having similar experience of suffering from leprosy made the solidarity among members of the community strong. Also, they were basically migrants from villages where the spirit of togetherness still existed. As many of them were separated from their spouses, they decided to marry other patients by developing new relationships and solidarity in the colony. Sadly, there was a case that a person affected by leprosy just knew that they cannot marry like normal people:

After I settled in Sitanala, I saw many leprosy patients married with other patients. I was surprised, because I thought a person who has leprosy like me was prohibited of having a wife. People said to me that if I married and have a family, all my kids will have leprosy like me. (Participant 11, male, in-depth interview)

Due to experiences of discrimination outside the colony, they support each other in Sitanala. Many worked as janitors, security guards, gardeners in the hospital even with a small wage. However, some people were still depressed and consumed drugs or alcohol. People in Sitanala said that there was a patient who committed suicide by throwing himself into the well and some of them drowned in Cisadane River. To thank the hospital, in May 1998, when mass riots against the Chinese happened, persons affected by leprosy guarded the hospital and rubbed their fingers on the ground until

they bleed to scare the masses who would rob and burn the hospital. Since that time, they were popular, and people called them zombies.

7.3. Kampung Kusta Sitanala today

The situation of Kampung Kusta Sitanala nowadays has changed a lot, compared to the past. The community is heterogeneous and multicultural, residents come from different places and ethnic groups. Most of the population is from the districts of West Java such as Cirebon, Indramayu, Subang, Bogor, Karawang, Purwakarta and Tasik. The rest are from East Java, Central Java, and Jakarta. Rarely do residents come from outside Java such as Lombok, Makassar, and Flores. This may be because there are two leprosy hospitals outside Java that already have the same status as Sitanala hospital, National Leprosy Hospital. One is Dr Tadjuddin Chalid Leprosy Hospital in Makassar, which provides services for people in the eastern part of Indonesia; and the other one is Dr. Rival Abdullah Leprosy Hospital in Palembang which serves the western part of Indonesia.

Figure 7.3
A Woman Cooking on an Open Fire Outside Her Home
in Kampung Kusta Sitanala

7.3.1. The profile of Kampung Kusta Sitanala

The number of people who live in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* reached 3,160 people, of which 780 of them are persons affected by leprosy. They are spread throughout five *Rukun Tetangga (RT)* (Neighbourhood Associations), RT 01-05. RT 01 has 332 persons

affected by leprosy or 43% of the total persons affected by leprosy in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* (Karangsari Village Office, 2016). Total number of persons affected by leprosy here is lower, compare to data owned by Tangerang Social Office (847 people) or media reports (about 5,000 people).

Figure 7.4
Total Population of Persons Affected by Leprosy in Sitanala
2015

Source: Karangsari Village Office (2016)

It is important to note that the number of non-disabled persons who live in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* is higher than those who are disabled due to leprosy. It is estimated that in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* today, more than 100 persons affected by leprosy use orthotic and prosthetic devices.

Figure 7.5
A woman Uses Orthotic and Prosthetic Devices

People in the *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* have *Kartu Tanda Penduduk (KTP)* (Identity Cards) as evidence that they are officially acknowledged by the local government as inhabitants in that area. For those who are poor, the government provides *Kartu Jaminan Kesehatan Masyarakat (Jamkesmas)* (Medical Social Security Card). The Jamkesmas program was launched by the Indonesian government in 2008. With these cards, they can have free medication and health treatment in *Pusat Kesehatan Masyarakat (Puskesmas)* (Community Health Centres). Following the procedure, they can have access to the hospital after getting a referral letter from community health centres. *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* looks very crowded and busy now. Factors such as the changing of Tangerang status from district to municipality and easy access to Soekarno Hatta Airport contribute to make the population of the community dense.

RT 01 residents as *orang baru* (new comers, they came to Sitanala after 1990), occupy old buildings that are often leaky and almost falling. Their houses are very messy and dirty, and the sanitation is very bad. They live in a 3x3 metres square room with their families, use the public toilet and there are no windows for ventilation. This single room is the place that they sleep, eat, change clothes, etc. It is common that a neighbour asks to share electricity supply through cables that are very unsafe. Some

of them still cook using fire wood. They cannot renovate the home like *orang lama* did to their houses. This is because these houses used to be old buildings, such as kindergarten and aged residential care buildings owned by Sitanala leprosy hospital. This is different from orang lama who built their houses in land near hospital. *Orang baru* are strictly prohibited from building house on the land of Sitanala, and because of the new policy of the hospital, even renovation is forbidden. They feel anxious as they can be evicted anytime by the government, while *orang lama* are not really worried about this matter because they believe that they will receive compensation for their house.

Figure 7.6
Poor Home Hygiene and Sanitation

There is a huge gap between people who are living in RT 01 and RT 02-05. *Orang lama* have a settled economy and life. That is why *orang baru* call them *orang mewah* (they who live in luxury). Access to community activities is dominated by the orang lama. This can be seen from the location of the RW office, which is in the territory of *orang lama*. As a result, most of the elite do not come from RT 01. The voices of people from RT 01 often are not heard, because many people who came to *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* go directly to RW 13 office. People in RT 01 also recognise the difficulties in accessing social services because they do not know the information.

At glance, this community is no different to other communities. The road is good, and houses are in a neat row. There are three mosques, one Christian church and three Buddhist temples for worship, based on the person's religion and faith. Access to

clean water and electricity are adequate. This settlement does not appear like slum or poor. This makes sense because these houses are in RT 02, 03, 04 and 05, in which belong to *orang lama* (Old-Timer People, those who have stayed in Sitanala before 1990) and has many non-disabled people from outside (they bought and renovated the houses from persons affected by leprosy, even though the houses have no clear title. Most of *orang lama* have children or grandchildren who work as civil servants, nurses, soldiers, or entrepreneurs. Because their children usually are already married and well established, they can support their parents or grandparents to live better. However, if we go to RT 01 and look at it carefully, a contrasting situation is apparent.

Most people in RT 01 are basically those who fail in transmigration programs. The government in the past claimed that 75 families were successfully empowered through the transmigration repatriation program. However, a few years later the program had failed as many people were back in Sitanala. This fact shows that the program was considered as lacking in proper planning. However, instead of evaluating and improving the program, they just blamed those people. The government considered them to be lazy and people who have a bad mental attitude. They were also considered as squatters who inhabit the hospital buildings by force. This is in contrast with the *orang baru* (RT 02-05) who could occupy and build houses on vacant land. As punishment, they did not receive monthly grocery assistance from government, with the reason given that their names were not on the list. Because their wives and children need to eat, they finally decided to be beggars. According to them, the other RT can live better because they had received a lot of types of programs and assistance. The policy of Sitanala Hospital to stop the monthly subsidy in 1998, made them more intensively beg in the street. This is not only done by people in RT 01 but also other RT's. From this description, they become beggar due to a new policy. They feel that they are victims of the new policy.

There are rumours that Sitanala Leprosy Hospital will transform from being a leprosy hospital into a general hospital due to high demand. However, this proposal was opposed by many parties as the mandate from the beginning for the hospital is

specifically to provide treatment for leprosy patients. This means additional services (accepting non-leprosy patients) may not remove essential services. The idea of transformation is based on consideration that the location of Sitanala hospital is near the Soekarno Hatta airport. It is expected that Sitanala hospital can be more involved in accepting general patients from the airport area. This idea affects the system from inpatient treatment for leprosy patients to outpatient treatment for others. As a result, the number of leprosy patients in Sitanala that used to be more than 400 people decreased dramatically. At first glance, it does not seem like a leprosy hospital anymore, but rather a general hospital. This system is seen as excluding leprosy patients from Sitanala hospital and now leprosy work is under emphasised.

People in Sitanala reveal that the outpatient system, in which leprosy patients can only stay at Sitanala hospital for about 20-30 days, is clearly disadvantageous to them. This is because leprosy patients who come to Sitanala hospital have been through a lengthy administrative process (from community health centres, public hospitals and then to Sitanala), a long journey from their hometown and it costs a lot of money for treatment (common leprosy patients are from poor family); so, it is unfair when they have not healed properly, the hospital already sent them back. People in Sitanala have guessed that with this new treatment system, the leprosy patients will never be back to Sitanala, unless their house is relatively close to the hospital. According to people in Sitanala, based on their own experience, the leprosy patient will not be cured. This is because the treatment is not about discipline to take medication, but rather during the long treatment (6-24 months) they should be free from stress, despair, and depression. Without the support of people in Sitanala, they will find it difficult to take treatment for their leprosy. They consider this as a decline in breaking the chain of transmission:

Now, medical treatment in Sitanala hospital were only short. Usually they will provide services for leprosy patients in only 20 days. The longest is 30 days. After that, the hospital will send them back home. The biggest enemy for curing leprosy is stress and depression. If people from far areas coming to Sitanala hospital and the treatment was like that, we are sure they will not continue their treatment. You know that stigma of leprosy is still strong in our society. How can the government tell media that they will try harder to eliminate leprosy,

while those who are obviously have leprosy and come for medical treatment were not addressed until they cured? (Participant 4, male, FGD).

It is acknowledged by people in Sitanala that the relationship between the Sitanala hospital and people in Kampung Kusta Sitanala has declined since 1998. They feel that Sitanala hospital is not welcoming them. The hospital fenced their area so that people in Sitanala find it difficult to access the hospital. The hospital also built a new big mosque in their area for their own worship, instead of using Rahmi Hatta Mosque together with people in Kampung Kusta Sitanala. There is no regular dialogue between hospital and former patients who live in Sitanala. They said that Sitanala hospital has changed. It seems that nowadays the hospital sees them as trouble makers who occupy the hospital's land. The contact then only happens between the hospital and the elite sufferers in the community.

7.3.2. Social and economic livelihood

Compared to people who live in RT 01-05, *orang baru* usually work as unskilled labours in informal sectors such as scavengers, peddlers, street sweepers and rickshaw drivers. Most of them work as beggars in their leisure time to earn more money as their jobs are inadequate to meet their basic needs. Interestingly, *orang lama*, even though they are quite stable in their economic circumstances also do the same thing, begging in the street. Data obtained from the Social Office, Tangerang in 2012, mentioned that there were about 186 people who are registered as beggars in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala*. About 86 of them are begging in Tangerang, while the rest spread to Jakarta and Bekasi. However, this data needs to be questioned as 33% persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala work as beggar, and this number will increase with those who only beg in religious special events such as Ramadan, Chinese New Year, and Christmas (in times of special events Chinese, Muslims, Christians distribute money).

Figure 7.7
Current Population of Disabled Persons due to Leprosy
in Sitanala by Occupation
2015

Source: Karang Sari Village Office (2016)

7.3.2.1. *Mete and keong* phenomena

Begging is being seen as the only way to survive because of their disability and the stigma of leprosy by the general society. That is why people call this community *Kampung Pengemis* (Beggars' Village). This is an embarrassment to the local government. People from Sitanala believe that it is better to be begging in the street rather than commit a crime. According to them, the main reason for begging is to get money to send their children to the school. Even though for primary school the school fee is free, they still must pay for the books, excursion, uniform, and extracurricular activities. For high school, they must pay all costs because only private schools are available. In Indonesia, to be able to study in the public school they must compete and pass the exam. If they fail, they must study in private schools, which are very expensive. That is why many of them are entangled with *Orang Batak* (Batak people, moneylenders) who lend an amount of money to a specific period with high interest and sometimes up to 50% per month. These are unsecured loans. In the event of non-repayment, loan collectors shame them publicly.

Orang baru in RT 01 call begging 'PT Al Amin' (Amen Factory). This means they will say 'amen' as an expression to people who give money due to their generosity and kindness. People in Sitanala divide the beggars into two groups. Those are a 'mete' (work for PT Al Amin) and 'keong' ('snail', working as a beggar from door to door in elite settlements by dragging their body along the ground like a snail). Both are basically begging but *mete* usually undertaken in the strategic and crowded places, such as street, traffic lights intersections, shops, and markets. Due to many raids by local government's officials, eventually they did *mete* at night. Some of them choose to *mete* in Jakarta or Bekasi. Usually they go home after two or three days and sleep in the street or stores' veranda. For *keong*, usually they got \$5 per day. Whereas for *mete* usually they get from \$2 to \$10 (for comparison, a labour wage is about \$7 a day). While begging, if they are arrested by the police, they have to stay confined in a 'social home' for 2 weeks with other inmates such as the insane or street people, homeless children. If they can pay bribe about \$20 or \$40, they are released in one or two days.

To drop off at and pick-up from begging locations, they are usually assisted by non-disabled persons. The payout is quite unique as paper money (notes) collected will be given to those who assist them, whilst coins collected will remain with beggars. It looks unfair process, but those are the rules. They must trust each other. The able-bodied persons believe that the beggars will not able to change the money due to his condition. Even though it seems like an easy job, but it has a high risk. They are very prone to getting hit by a car or injured when doing *keong*. They also easily get sick when the weather is too extreme such as heat or rain. Usually they get fever and have to have a break for two or three days.

7.3.2.2. Problem with drugs and alcohol

People feel embarrassed to do *mete* or *keong* work. That's why they consume *Pil Anjing* ('Dog's Pill', hypnotic drugs such nitrazepam, diazepam (valium) and barbiturate) which make them drunk:

First time doing mete, I was so ashamed. I knew that mete was a contemptible job, but we did that because there was no way out. We were forced by the

circumstance. We had no job except doing this. We still had stomachs to feed... The important thing was that we were not thieves. Yes, we were ashamed. That's why before going to the street we consumed alcohol or pil anjing or anything that made us drunk. (Participant 8, male, in-depth interview)

These pills are easily available in pharmacies or general stores. The price is relatively cheap; 1,500 pills will cost \$20. *Pil Anjing* has serious effects on users, such as: (1) Drooling, rambling, and cannot focus on the conversation; (2) Emotionally unstable and aggressive; and (3) Out of control or extreme actions. After consuming these pills, they do not feel embarrassed but just smile, because they think people around them are funny:

After consuming alcohol or drugs, we got dizzy in our head.... The earth was like spinning around.... We staggered when walking. People looked so funny. What we felt when we drunk was we just wanted to laugh. We didn't feel ashamed and sad anymore. Insulted and spitted by people was just fine for us. (Participant 31, female, FGD)

As for physical impact, these drugs can lead to continuous addiction and organ damage. Overdoses even can result in death. The psychological impacts can be: (1) Emotional instability, irritability, and depression; (2) forming an apathetic personality, violent and brutal behaviours; and (3) Decreased endurance, decreased concentration, becoming sluggish. Besides *Pil Anjing*, some people use *Autan* (insect repellent lotion) and mix it with *Bodrex* (sort of Panadol) and *Pentol Korek Api* (match heads) until they are drunk. This of course is very dangerous to their life and their safety. Sometimes, they buy a bottle of cheap and low-quality wine, just to be able to make them drunk before begging.

Before going to beg on the streets, we usually drink wine to get drunk. We pay a bottle of wine collectively. If we don't have any money, we just got to the stall because we can pay it later. It is very important for us to get drunk. If we get drunk, we don't feel ashamed when we beg on the streets. (Participant 15, female, FGD)

7.3.2.3. Children and elderly as vulnerable group

Children of people affected by leprosy families in Sitanala need to get serious attention from all parties as they have rights to grow up and get a proper education. The number of children who drop out from school reached 15 children in 2012. It is

estimated that these numbers will increase in the future. Most of children help their parents as street children:

Most children who live here help their parents as street performers. There are many children who become street children. They do these activities after school hours. Not only boys, girls do the same. Yes, we are worried when they are on the street, but we need money to eat and pay their tuition fees. What we can do is just praying. Pray for their safety during working on the street. It is common in here for mothers to bring their baby when begging in the street. I do too. If I left my baby in our home, who will look after her? (Participant 6, female, in-depth interview)

The children who live there are also at risk because of the lack of proper nutrition and an unhealthy environment. As an example, it has been found that two girls have been diagnosed with leprosy:

We were not surprised when we knew two girls here had leprosy. It is just still spots, still symptoms.... Pity of them, in schools, their school mates often ridiculed them... We think these girls will withdraw from their schools. Luckily, they have received early medical treatments. They will be fine. We are sure, they will not lose their legs and fingers like us... (Participant 2, female, FGD)

This indicates that the government needs to pay attention to the sanitation in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* and find a resolve this problem as the residents are prohibited to do renovations to their houses. It is ironic that the environment near hospital should be clean, but the reality is that it is unhealthy.

The condition of older people in Sitanala also is concerning. Some of them do not have family and cannot work. They can only stay at home and expect help from their neighbours and people from outside. Often, they are considered as a burden on the community. However, many of them do not want to be placed in a nursing home and prefer to live in the community until they die:

Many older people who don't have legs and can't walk. They are in devastating conditions. They rely their lives on support from neighbours and donations from outside. The neighbours often give them rice and vegetables to eat. In here we live like a chicken. What is in front of us, we eat. People in here live simply. Eating rice with salt is fine for us. We already told them to go to nursing home, but they said, they prefer to die in this community. They don't want to live outside this community. (Participant 20, female, FGD)

Due to living with the stigma of leprosy, they feel the trauma of facing the sad experience. Older people are also prone to be displaced during data collection by the government. For example, because they are elderly the assessor has not put them in the category of persons with disabilities due to the problem of double counting. However, during data collection of elderly people, they are often missed because of the assumption that they should be categorised as disabled people. Older people in Sitanala also have difficulty to accessing health services. Although they have *Jamkesmas* cards, they still need money for transportation costs and they have a long wait to see the doctor. Therefore, many of them were ill and untreated. They can only lie in their house.

Figure 7.8
An Old Woman Sitting in Her House in Sitanala

7.3.2.4. Discrimination and strategy to cope

Almost all people in Sitanala are still traumatised by the experiences that they have faced so far. This prevents them from going back to their hometown and they do not know how to seek justice for discriminatory practice around them. They cry when they remember their experiences. It seems that nobody understands their situation except people in *Kampung Kusta Sitanala*. This explains why some of them consume *Pil Anjing* (sedative drugs) as an escape for a moment from sad times in the past. However, many people died because of these drugs:

I heard that most people in here who consumed those drugs and drink alcohol because of shame of having leprosy, they just died. The doctor said that it was an overdose. Their hearts were burnt. I also heard that people use petrol mixed with mosquito repellent. Sometimes, they mixed paracetamol with energy drink and other chemical products. After drinking it, they became drunk. (Participant 1, male, in-depth interview)

Others are keen to worship God as their only resource. They try to have positive thinking that God has a specific purpose and God is testing their patience. This helps prevent them from committing suicide or negative behaviours, such as drugs and alcohol.

This phenomenon illustrates that psychosocial problems in people who live in Sitanala have been given a lack of attention and management. The focus on medical and employment aspects is simplistic and professionals have overlooked psychosocial consequences. This can be illustrated that in 1984 there were only two 'social workers' in Sitanala Leprosy Hospital. However, instead of acting as professional social workers, they were working as instructors (vocational trainers) and did not have proper qualifications in the field of social work. Currently, there are 4 'social workers' who are high school graduates who also acted as a vocational training instructor.

In group discussions, they said that they do not agree with newspapers stating that there is no more stigma and discrimination to people affected by leprosy. They believe that the society has not yet fully accepted them. If the community accepted them well, then there would be no *Kampung Kusta Sitanala*. From their perspective, the assimilation is running well only in the *Kampung Kusta Sitanala*. Outside of this place, they still experience stigma and discrimination. For example, when they tried to live outside in a rented house, people were still afraid of them and did not allow it. The same fear affects trading, once they know their goods or the sellers are from Sewan, people do not buy the products. One of the participants shared his recent experience, when he had a coffee in the morning and the trader knew that he had leprosy, the trader threw the glass into a gutter:

I was working to sweep the road at midday. Because it was hot, I was so thirsty and wanted to have a cup of coffee. It was like days before that the seller will provide a glass of hot coffee. The seller started a conversation and asked about the place where I live and that was the disaster began. When I said that I live in Sitanala and she knew that I was a former patient at Sitanala hospital, she threw my glass after I finished drinking it. It was only 5 metres when I left the coffee shop. My eyes still clearly see it. I still remember it. I cannot forget the moment she threw the glass. (Participant 9, female, in-depth interview)

The participants also mentioned that there was a lady working in a mall. However, after knowing her as a former leprosy patient, her boss fired her without any clear reasons. This also happened to their healthy daughters who worked and were fired due to their parents having leprosy. Also, when they use public transportation, there are still people who get out from the bus or step aside and look at them with disgust. Likewise, when treated in health centres, other patients step aside. This also happens when they go to community health or general hospital.

People from Sitanala also said that the efforts to combat stigma and discrimination are rather difficult because the doctors and nurses who are obviously educated and have sufficient knowledge are still scared of them. As an example, this can be seen from their negative attitude to shaking hands, do not want to touch the patient's body, and even open a door with their feet as the door handle has been touched by them. One participant said that in the World Leprosy Day celebrations, conducted on Sunday, 30 March 2014 at *Monumen Nasional (Monas)* (National Monument) in Jakarta; when the government and NGOs called for ending stigma and discrimination against leprosy affected people, a group of people who having lunch with Sitanala residents on a mat left because of fear:

We still remember our experiences when attending World Leprosy Day celebration in Monas, Jakarta. We had been invited to go there. Almost all people who came there were health people. They shouted about eliminating stigma and discrimination against people with leprosy. At lunch time, because there were no chairs there, we asked a group of people who sit on the mat, to share with us. We were so hungry that is why we asked them to sit on their mat, but we were so surprised when they just left us without saying anything. It seemed they were afraid sitting near us. Sometimes, anti-stigma campaigns were just only on their lips. (Participant 3, female, in-depth interview)

Healthy people cannot imagine how painful this is. Some of them also said 'How will the government fight against discrimination while in Leprosy Hospital at Sitanala, the health workers categorised their healthy family members into the ward for leprosy patients? After protesting, their family was eventually moved to a ward for general patients by Sitanala hospital. It is noted that Sitanala hospital started to serve non-leprosy patients in 1997 and separated leprosy treatment from non-leprosy patient. Possibly, they are worried many persons affected by leprosy will visit patients and scare non-leprosy patients.

According to people from Sitanala, some activists and social service officials, either from the government or NGOs are still scared to shake hands, including eating, and drinking what they provide. It is important to understand that, most people who live in Sitanala are originally from the villages whose custom was to provide food or drinks to their guests as a form of hospitality. They generally bring their own drinks and foods. If they are willing to shake their hands, then they quickly wash their hands. When they arrive home, they take some shower and change clothes immediately. If there are joint activities such as training, they tend to eat separately elsewhere. More extreme, there is an NGO who strictly prohibits them getting closer even to touch their cars or food they will distribute. They said that they will stop the aid when people stay close. So, according to them, it is far too early to say that stigma and discrimination have diminished. If *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* still exists, so does the stigma and discrimination. If modern society like Tangerang people still finds it difficult to accept them, how can they expect acceptance from people in their hometown who are still influenced by erroneous traditional views and religious beliefs. This question then must be answered by the government in terms of appropriate policies and programs and their implementation.

There are some strategies to cope with discrimination in Sitanala that were developed by people affected by leprosy, as follows:

1. If they went outside their house, they covered the entire face and body with linen and wore gloves;

2. To deal with transportation issues, many of them prefer to ride a bicycle or pedicab than taking public transportation. Usually, they will find the pedicab drivers that have leprosy like them;
3. In restaurants, many of them prefer to take away the food rather than eating in those restaurants;
4. Some of them grew vegetables to sell in the market and the non-disabled persons sold the produce, otherwise the vegetables could not be sold;
5. For daily goods, people in Sitanala prefer to buy from small stalls that are available in the surrounding community. However, if they need to go outside to buy something, they will take their children with them, so that the transaction will have no problem;
6. When they go to health care centres, they would rather sit in the corner or wear a mask over their face;
7. They will not offer the food or drink to their guests until they are sure that their guests are not afraid of them. They will see this through the body language of their guests such as whether their guests want to shake hand with them or whether their guest could sit or stand very close with them;
8. For praying, for those who are Muslims, they prefer to pray in the Rahmi Hatta mosque or praying at home, rather than praying outside Sitanala.

Members of the community in RT 01 Sitanala also feel that erroneous religious beliefs and traditional views also contribute to the creation of stigma. According to Dols (1983), a hadith which is often used as a justification for isolating persons affected by leprosy in Islamic society is *'One should run away from the leper as one runs away from a lion'*. This explains why in Indonesia leprosy is also called as lion face disease.

Although traditional views and religious beliefs play an important role in creating stigma, people in Sitanala believe that their disability also influences it. This is proven by those who have disability grade-0, can be more easily accepted in the society. They can work anywhere because people cannot see that they are affected by leprosy, even though their condition often worsening, and they shiver when the reaction

comes. People with leprosy declared cured by the doctor, but it just means that the bacteria cannot infect others. However, their physical condition is still weak especially when reactions occur. Some people in Indonesia accept that disability is also a curse. In other words, people with leprosy are seen as objects cursed by God due to their disability and their leprosy.

Images of *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* that are often negative, also play a role in promoting stigma. Associating this place as a scary place inhabited by people with the *penyakit daging busuk* ('rotten meat disease'), *barang bekas* (their organ body is not complete), monsters and zombies is an important factor to note. The image of this place worsened when many film companies used the Sitanala hospital as a setting for horror movies such as 'Bangsal 13' (Ward 13th), 'Disini Ada Setan' (There is a Satan here), and 'Suster Ngesot' (A crippled ghost). There is also an amateur movie made by high school kids with the title 'Sitanala' in which the story tells about lab exploded in Sitanala leprosy hospital and spread a new leprosy type that led people who infected transform into zombies. Interestingly, though this film reinforces the stigma of leprosy in the local community, they received praise for being creative.

7.4. Conclusion

This chapter has tried to portray the *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* from the social and historical context. It can be concluded that: (1) Sitanala community was born and existed because of a pro-leprosy patient policy from the Indonesian government through the Ministry of Health and Sitanala leprosy hospital; (2) Leprosy patients came to Sitanala not only with physical problem, but also with psycho-social problems; (3) The profile of *Kampung Kusta Sitanala* today shows that the percentage of people with leprosy is smaller compare to healthy people who live at Sitanala; (4) The physical problem has been successfully treated, but the psycho-social problems to have not received much attention; (5) Children and elderly are vulnerable groups due to neglected issues; and (5) Discrimination still continues in Sitanala and the strategies to cope shows that it is basically a passive strategy affected by feeling of a lack of confidence and shame.

'An educated person must learn to act justly, beginning, first of all, with his thoughts, then later in his deeds. That is what it means to be educated.'

(Pramoedya Ananta Toer)

Chapter 8: Perceptions and experiences about community empowerment and social inclusion program

8.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the perceptions and experiences of people affected by leprosy in relation to the community empowerment and social inclusion programs. It will focus on some critical aspects such as the implementation, benefit, and impact of these programs. This chapter will also reveal whether the programs really empower and increase the participation of Sitanala people in broader community activities. In general, perception refers to the way of thinking about something and the idea of what it is like. Knowing and understanding the perception of Sitanala people about the CESI program in their community is very important as it reflects their voices and awareness. The perception and experiences about non-CESI programs will also be presented to get the whole picture about social intervention programs in Sitanala.

8.2. Economic empowerment program

Economic empowerment is one of the most popular CESI programs in Sitanala. This program attempts to help people in raising their incomes, assets, and standards of living. The economic empowerment program available in Sitanala could be classified into four programs: vocational training, productive economic business, joint business group and microcredit. These programs are popular because they have the potential to empower people in Sitanala to fulfil their daily needs and to prevent them from begging on the streets.

8.2.1. Vocational training program

The Vocational training program in Sitanala was conducted by the Ministry of Health (MoH), the Ministry of Social Affairs (MoSA), Tangerang Social Office (TSO), Marfati Foundation and Nalacity. People in Sitanala acknowledge the benefits of this program, such as: (1) increased knowledge and skills; (2) improved performance and competencies; and (3) increased chances of employment. However, they believe that there are several issues that could be changed and improved in the future.

8.2.1.1. Mismatch between vocational training and interest/talent

The persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala admitted that vocational training is an important program that helped them to improve their knowledge, skills, and competencies. However, due to improper vocation assessments, there was a mismatch between the vocational training offered and their interests and/or talents. Consequently, the implementation of the program was top-down and far from their expectations:

From time to time the program is like that. Most of the vocational training programs were designed before they came to Sitanala. For example, the sewing training.... When they asked about the training we need, we had already told them that we need cake making training. However, the result was different from our expectations. They trained us how to sew. That happened many times. Sewing again and sewing again... Finally, we took training in sewing, but still we could not master it! The problem was simple. This is because sewing is not our talent... (Participant 14, female, FGD)

The participants mentioned that when they tried to tell the organiser about the mismatch between the vocational training and their interests, skills and talents, the organiser told them that lepers should be able to master a lot of skills. Therefore, many former leprosy patients were forced to participate in many kinds of vocational training even though they were not interested in it. In Indonesian culture, there is inequality of power between 'the haves' and 'the have-nots'. In this context, the former leprosy patients represent 'the have-nots' and the training organisers represent 'the haves'. It is common that 'the have-nots' should follow the will of 'the haves'. There is the expectation that the former leprosy patients should take as granted the training provided by the organiser, otherwise the organisers would be angry and blacklist them. The participants believe that it would be good if the

vocational training matched their talents, skills, and interests. This explains why the impact of the vocational training was quite low because most participants failed to master the skills:

We often tried to tell them that the training they provided to us, was not suitable for us. However, the organisers did not want to know... We must take the training. For example, the training for salon. The truth is we had difficulties to hold the scissors. Another example, they said lepers should also master screen printing skills.... We just followed all the vocational trainings although those training were not suitable for us. Could you imagine mastering screen printing skills without fingers? I think the organiser should select us based on our talents, skills, and interests.... We just followed what they wanted. We were afraid they would be angry with us and would not want to help us again in the future. (Participant 18, female, FGD)

Those who could master the skills still had trouble finding a job. Even though there were some people who succeeded in their jobs after receiving vocational training, it was because the training matched with their previous jobs:

There is a welder who is quite successful here. He received welding training. But, don't get it wrong... Welding was his skill even before coming to the Sitanala. That is why he succeeded working as a welder. The organiser should take this as a good example. Don't just take people and train them, again and again... It wouldn't work. After finishing the training, they would sell the equipment because they didn't know how to use it. (Participant 19, male, FGD)

8.2.1.2. Problem with incidental and short-term training

People in Sitanala revealed that the length of the training was very short. It used to be conducted in a week and even just in two or three days. As a result, the participants had difficulty mastering the skills. It also happened many times, when the participants started to understand the lessons, the organizer had already stopped the training:

Most vocational training in Sitanala was conducted in a week. A week was not enough to improve our competencies. We only learnt very basic skills... That was happened over and over. I think the organiser should consider our conditions and should add more time. However, we did not dare to complain about it... They helped us and for me it was more than enough. We thank God for it. We did not want to make trouble with them. (Participant 25, male, FGD)

I think the implementation of vocational training programs was very bad... How can a vocational training be conducted in only two or three days? What skills can be expected from that short time? There was no magic spell to master the

new skills. We need a longer time to learn and practise it. (Participant 35, male, FGD)

People in Sitanala acknowledged that there was vocational training conducted in a longer time about three or six months. This training was provided by rehabilitation centres. However, the location was too far from Sitanala and they could not leave their families for a long-time period. As a result, no one participated in that training:

There was vocational training organised by rehabilitation centres. The problem was the locations were too far from Sitanala and it took three or six months to complete it. We had to stay there for months. It was too long for us to leave our families in Sitanala. We couldn't leave them... We had to feed them... (Participant 28, male, FGD)

8.2.1.3. Physical distance during training

Based on their experiences in receiving vocational training, the research participants mentioned the distance between the organisers and them during the training. The organisers were scared and looked disgustedly at them. This occurred during the training and lunch breaks. The organisers used to provide take-away food and ate the food separately in the different room. They feared that they would contract leprosy:

Most people who came here were still afraid of us... Whether NGOs or the government officials, they were still afraid of us... The trainers and organisers kept their distance from us. They used to buy take-away food for lunch breaks and they ate it in different room. This was different from the Korean people, students from the University of Indonesia and people from churches. They were not afraid of us. We knew it because we could feel it... (Participant 22, female, FGD)

The stigma of leprosy that occurred during the training, made the persons affected by leprosy feel uncomfortable. In their opinion, the organisers and trainers were not wholehearted in conducting vocational training in Sitanala.

8.2.1.4. Unequal opportunities

The research participants mentioned that the opportunity to receive the vocational training was not equal among persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala. There were people with leprosy who received training more than 5 times, while others had never received any training at all. This is because the training participants were selected directly by the organisers without any discussion with them:

Frankly I received many vocational training sessions, but I had no capability in those areas... There were training programs such as screen printing, welding, wood craft, sewing and electronics. They gave training certificates as well. At that time, they just offered me participation in their training programs. I didn't know why they always chose me... It was a bit random... If the organiser knew us, the chance to be involved in the training was big. Maybe it happened because they didn't have much time to do proper selection... (Participant 12, female, FGD)

Those who had never received any vocational training said that they did not hear any information related to the vocational training. They only knew when the training began, and their names were not on the list of participants. Even though they were willing to learn, they had never had the opportunity to participate:

In the past, the government often organised vocational training for us. But, it is very rare nowadays... Those who participated in the training were invited by the organiser. We had no information about the training. We knew about it, when the training had already started. Only certain people knew about the training. They said our names were not on the list of beneficiaries.... It was unfair, those who were not serious about taking the training could have many opportunities, but people like us who really wanted to participate, had no opportunities at all.... (Participant 8, male, FGD)

8.2.1.5. Input-output paradigm

People in Sitanala revealed that the implementation of training programs only focused on administration. The organiser thought that the program was successfully implemented if the training was conducted, several people participated in it, and the equipment had been distributed to the participants. This input-output paradigm did not give much attention to the process and/or quality of the training:

I just knew that the organiser suddenly came to Sitanala with their program. They conducted training sessions over several days... After that, they gave us some equipment. Then, they left Sitanala... (Participant 21, male, FGD)

Interestingly, there are participants who said that they did not attend the training, but they received equipment from the training organiser. This reflects the unprofessional organisation of the training:

I wasn't involved in the sewing training, I don't know why they gave me a sewing machine. It really surprised me... because, those who took sewing course didn't receive any sewing machines. It was strange really. Many people were questioning it. (Participant 32, female, FGD)

8.2.1.6. No further assistance and follow-up

People in Sitanala also mentioned that many vocational training programs had no ongoing assistance. When the training finished, there was no follow-up from the organiser. Therefore, they faced difficulties in implementing their new skills:

We didn't want to see vocational training conducted like that... After the training finished, the class was dismissed and there was no further assistance from them. They should assist us until we master the skills. The reality is that most training programs were unsustainable and had no follow-up... (Participant 26, male, FGD)

There was a case, the organiser promised to follow-up the sewing training by seeking orders for trainees. However, it was only empty promises because they were never back to Sitanala. Many program officers also come and go as they like. People in Sitanala said that they should '*datang tampak muka, pulang tampak punggung*', means one should always be correct in someone's behaviour when visiting and leaving someone's house:

*In the past, we received a sewing training. After training, they promised that they would seek orders for us. However, after waiting for a long time, there was no news from them. Many program officers were like that. Come and go... Even without giving any notice to us. They should '*datang tampak muka, pulang nampak punggung*'... We were so worried the sewing machines would be unused and broken. Because we had no jobs and we had to survive, we decided to sell those sewing machines... (Participant 30, female, FGD)*

Based on their experiences, they hope that there is follow-up and further assistance after the finish of the vocational training, otherwise the organiser will only waste their time, energy, and money:

The problem is there was no follow up or further assistance from the organisers. The government and other organisations should help the trainees to get a job, otherwise they will still be unemployed and go back to the street begging. They are begging not because they are lazy, but because they are frustrated in finding a job. If this continues, the vocational training would not have a positive impact and they would only waste their time, money, and energy.... (Participant 8, male, in-depth interview)

8.2.1.7. Lesson learned from the Marfati Foundation and Nalacity

According to the research participants, the government and other organisations should learn from the Marfati Foundation and Nalacity in organising vocational

training. In their opinion, the Marfati Foundation has a lot of experience in empowering people with leprosy. The foundation offered training participants to work in their convection business under Komata Unit:

Talking about organising vocational trainings, the government and other organisations should learn from what the Marfati Foundation did... They have experiences in empowering people with leprosy in Sitanala. For example, in sewing training, they train the participants until the skills are mastered. Those who are good will be employed by the Marfati Foundation as tailors, whilst the rest can work in ironing or buttoning the shirts... (Participant 11, male, in-depth interview)

The interesting thing about vocational training conducted by the Marfati Foundation is that the trainer is also a former leprosy patient. This means the Marfati Foundation tries to empower persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala, so that they can empower the others:

The story goes like this... In the past, there was a former leprosy patient who was very diligent and honest. She worked in the Komata Unit. The foundation trusted her and gave responsibility to her to organise sewing trainings for Sitanala people. And she did very well... She said to the participants that the sustainability of the clothing business in the Marfati Foundation depends on their works. This method has successfully increased the sense of belonging to those who work under the Komata Unit. (Participant 11, male, in-depth interview)

People in Sitanala said that the Indonesian government could also learn from Nalacity. After providing training, the organiser put in a staff member to give further assistance in embroidery/embellishment of garments. They also help mothers in marketing their products by buying directly from mothers and selling it through the Nalacity online shop. However, like the Marfati Foundation, only few mothers participate in this economic empowerment program due to limited funds:

The embroidery/embellishment training conducted by the Nalacity was very good. They only focus on embroidery/embellishment training for mothers. Even though the training finished a long time ago, they are still providing a further assistance. They also give orders for us. We get \$2 for each veil... The problem is that Nalacity is a new organization and they have limited funds. That is why this program only covers 20 mothers. Many people would like to participate in it, but they couldn't... The other problem is sometimes they are too busy, so that they are late to pick up our embroidered/embellished work. (Participant 2, female, in-depth interview)

8.2.2. Productive economic business program

Productive economic business (UEP) aims to encourage entrepreneurship by providing seed and start-up capital to open a small business. It means Sitanala people benefit by having opportunities to start small enterprises. However, there are several issues that need consideration, such as the problems in determining the beneficiaries, administration fee issues and the rejection of the elite.

8.2.2.1. Problem in determining beneficiaries

Similar to the previous economic empowerment program, the first problem in implementing the UEP program was determining beneficiaries. People in Sitanala mentioned that the beneficiaries were selected randomly. Therefore, there were many people who received UEP program several times, whilst the others had never received the program:

In the past, the government often gave seed and start-up capital through the UEP program. However, the UEP stimulant aid wasn't well distributed in Sitanala. It was delivered to the beneficiaries randomly. Some people received a couple of times, whilst the others received nothing... I have never received UEP assistance. If I had capital, I would like to start as a vendor in a small business... I am so tired, begging on the street... Now, I am trying to save some money from begging. I hope I can start my small business soon... (Participant 16, female, FGD)

Sitanala people mentioned that there was a misleading statement in relation to the UEP program. The program officer said that the beneficiaries should be a person who has a small business as a vendor or would like to open a small business as a vendor. As a result, people who wanted to start other than small business vendor had difficulty to accessing the program:

I have no talent to become a street vendor... My talent is making metal crafts such as rings, bracelets, and necklaces. In the past, I had the equipment, but I sold it to pay my medical rehabilitation costs... The price for the equipment is about \$500. If I get this equipment, I will start making metal crafts. I can also teach people in Sitanala in making metal crafts. For marketing, I have network at Jatinegara market. The demand for metal crafts is still high. I have told this to the UEP program officer, but there was no follow-up. The program officer said that UEP program was only for those who would like to open a small business vendor. I had nothing to say. As far as I know, business is not only trading... Business does not have to be a street vendor... Here I am, still begging on the street. I have no other skills except making metal crafts. I have no capital... (Participant 10, male, FGD)

8.2.2.2. Administration fees issues

The research participants revealed that they received some money to start a small business, but the amount was different on the form that they had signed. The officer said that they reduced the money due to administration fees. This practice obviously made people in Sitanala very disappointed. They said that with small amount of money, they could not even start their business:

I ever received stimulant aid from the UEP program, to start a small business as a street vendor. I remember, we had to take the money at the village office. In theory, I would receive \$50, but I only received \$15. The officer took my \$35 for administration fees. That was not right. If they took \$5, it was fine. But they took \$35 from my stimulant aid. It was too much. They said that they need to give some money to some people who contributed to the program. It was unfair... I couldn't start a business with only \$15, but I didn't dare to complain about it... (Participant 24, female, FGD)

Based on their experiences, people in Sitanala suggested that the UEP programs should go directly to the beneficiaries without going through to the village office or the local NGOs. This is because they do not trust the commitment of local NGOs in Sitanala:

We suggest to any institutions that would like to help us, to come directly to Sitanala. Don't ever deliver your aid through any local institutions here, even through local NGOs... We don't trust them... We're just worried that the stimulant aid will be taken by them and it won't be fully delivered to us. We are sorry to say this... There were many cases related to these bad practices. For example, there was an institution outside Sitanala that gave us \$15, but we only received \$5. The officer from that institution looked very disappointed after knowing that we only received \$5 from the local NGOs. (Participant 13, female, FGD)

8.2.2.3. Rejection of the elites

The research participants said that the elites here refer to the government officials, community leaders and head of local NGOs. People in Sitanala criticised the elite members of the community that often take advantage of the UEP program. For example, all institutions outside Sitanala must ask permission from them, otherwise they will not be allowed to implement their programs in Sitanala. The research participants mentioned that there was a case, in which the former head of neighbourhood rejected the UEP program just because that institution did not want

to pay administration fees. In this context, the elites had blocked the community members from access to the program:

There was a social organisation that would like to help us through the UEP program. But they were not allowed by the former head of neighbourhood. He said that all programs and aids must go through him. Thus, this organisation left Sitanala and cancelled their program. Maybe if the aid came to him first, he would get administration fees... If the organisation came directly to us, he will get nothing... (Participant 17, female, FGD)

People in Sitanala did not trust the elites because of their actions. Sitanala people also believed that most of elites did not care about their lives:

Frankly speaking, we don't believe the elites in Sitanala anymore. They pretend to care, when they don't... They often take advantage of our conditions. They said that they will seek donors from outside. But when the aid came, they only prioritised their families or people who were close to them. They asked data from us many times without any realisation. We were often fooled by smart people like them... (Participant 7, female, FGD)

8.2.2.4. Small business failure phenomenon

There is a trend that many UEP programs in Sitanala are given to the beneficiaries through local institutions and local NGOs. Interestingly, individual donors are more selective in determining beneficiaries, compared to them. Individual donors usually go directly to the potential beneficiaries to do home visits and interviews, to see their sincerity and business plan, before giving the stimulant aid. However, almost all small businesses in Sitanala close due to lack of capital, competing with 'giants' and the profit was less than consumption expenditure, e.g. food, electricity and children's education. This phenomenon used to be overlooked by practitioners in the community development field:

That is my dream to start a small business. However, the situation didn't allow me to develop my business. The capital to start the business was too small, so was the profit I earned... Many small businesses in here were closed because we had to compete with big enterprises and our expenditure was greater than income. That is why we go back to the street. This situation forced us... (Participant 3, female, FGD)

This phenomenon shows that a fragmented approach in economic empowerment will not work if it is not followed by social protection programs. It means that Sitanala people need comprehensive and integrative programs to deal with their situation.

8.2.3. Joint business group program

Joint business group (KUBE) aims to develop ability of people in Sitanala, so that they can solve their own problems and fulfil their daily need. This program uses the group as a medium to empower Sitanala community. The members of KUBE are expected to support each other and work together to improve their economic conditions. KUBE is one of the priority programs in the MoSA that provides vocational training and UEP. However, the implementation of the KUBE program received criticism from the beneficiaries. The criticism is related to the group formation process, lack of dissemination and no community facilitator who provides assistance for them.

8.2.3.1. Instant group formation

Group formation is an important step in the KUBE program. It is basically a long process to form a group. This is because the group formation requires preparation stages such as: (1) orientation and observation; (2) identification; (3) action planning; (4) social counselling; (5) needs assessment; (6) motivational assistantship; and (7) evaluation. That is why the group formation may take a year to ensure that the members of the group are ready to receive vocational training and UEP stimulant aids. In contrast, the formation of a group in Sitanala was quick and instant:

I remember, we were collected, and they asked us whether we were interested in becoming beneficiaries of KUBE program. After saying yes, the group was formed directly by them. They said that the number of members in the group should be 10 people. We just followed their instruction. The training was short, and they gave us materials such as sewing machines, chickens, and goats. (Participant 5, male, FGD)

8.2.3.2. Lack of dissemination

The research participants also revealed that the KUBE program lacked dissemination. This made the beneficiaries confused in managing the group and the stimulant aid. For example, there was a group that consisted of 10 people which received one sewing machine. They just sold the sewing machine because they did not know how to manage it:

I just remember that each group received only one sewing machine. One group consisted of 10 people. We faced difficulties sharing this machine. To avoid conflict in our group, so we sold that machine and we shared the money to all the group members. It was difficult to manage one sewing machine in one

group. I did not know why they only gave one sewing machine. It should be ten sewing machines. (Participant 29, female, FGD)

The similar thing happened to the fatten a goat group. They were also confused as to how to manage the goats in their group:

We didn't know how to manage the goats. They only gave us 5 goats. It was difficult to manage it as we have 10 members... Our neighbours also complain because it was too smelly. That's why we sold the goats. Selling the goats was the best way for the group to avoid conflict... (Participant 34, male, FGD)

8.2.3.3. Missing community facilitator

The KUBE program has a long process in implementation, started from preparation stage, implementation, business development, business partnership and monitoring and evaluation stages. It requires intensive assistance from a community facilitator. However, there was no community facilitator during the implementation of the program:

The implementation of KUBE program was not that good... I have never heard of any successful story about a KUBE program in Sitanala. There was no community facilitator that would help and assist us to manage the stimulant aids.... After receiving goats, they had never visited us. You know, when people give you goats you have a responsibility to take care of them. For example, what if the goats died? What should we do? With whom we should consult? We were afraid of doing something wrong. So, we just sold the goats... (Participant 27, male, FGD)

The absence of a community facilitator also affected the sewing group in Sitanala. They were confused because they did not understand how the group should work:

We were totally confused about this program. We had to work together in a group. However, some people were good in sewing, whilst the rest were not. The government only provide one sewing machine. How could we manage that? No one helped to guide us. We were just worried the sewing machine would be broken. After having discussion, we just sold that machine. (Participant 23, female, FGD)

8.2.4. Microcredit program

Microcredit provides small and low-interest loans without collateral for poor people in Sitanala. This program helps poor people to cope with poverty and eliminates moneylenders who offer high interest loans. It is expected that the beneficiaries can start-up or expand their small business. However, there are several factors that

affected the implementation of microcredit program. Those are limited amount of funds, managerial problems, and loan for consumption phenomenon.

8.2.4.1. Limited amount of funds

As a new program in Sitanala, microcredit received great attention from persons affected by leprosy. Many people came to the microcredit officer to borrow some money. However, they could not get the loan from microcredit due to limited amount of funds. They must wait until the borrowers pay back the money. As a result, there are many people who are in the long waiting list:

I have heard about microcredit program in Sitanala. People in here are really interested to be the beneficiaries. However, the officer said that we must wait because the fund is limited. We do not know for how long we must wait as there are some borrowers who faced difficulties to repay the loans. (Participant 24, female, FGD)

8.2.4.2. Managerial problem

Due to the limited amount of funds in the microcredit program, there is no allocation budget for the officer. Consequently, the program is only managed by one person, and she receives salary from the interest on loans. From an organisational perspective, the program has potential to be abused because there are no checks and balances from other officers. This can be shown by the fact that the officer tends to prioritise the borrowers who give more voluntary additional fees when repaying the loans:

Usually people repay their loans with low interest and additional fees. The additional fees are voluntary... It is just very small amount of money to buy a drink when she collected the money from borrowers. The amount depends on the borrowers. This is because we know that the officer runs this program without receiving any salary. The problem is that the officer seems to be prioritising those who pay more additional fees... (Participant 32, female, FGD)

In Indonesian culture, it is common that people must repay all kindness to the helpers if they can. In this context, giving voluntary additional fees instead of the interest on the loans is acceptable, as the officer has no salary and the interest of the loans is still low, compared to money lenders. However, this practice makes the loans only available for certain people.

8.2.4.3. Loan for consumption

Another problem that affect the implementation of microcredit program is loan for consumption phenomenon. The microcredit program expects additional income for the borrowers through creation and expansion microenterprises. However, the research participants said that most of the borrowers used the loan for other purposes such as to pay bills, food, education costs and health care. As a result, some borrowers were trapped in debts and faced difficulties repaying the loans:

I borrowed the money from microcredit to pay tuition fees for my children. I had to pay it on that day, otherwise my children would not be allowed to sit exams... I didn't use it to expand my small business. Now, I have struggle to find money to repay my loan. I must pay it. If not, I would be in trouble to access the loan in the future... (Participant 2, female, FGD)

From this point, most borrowers repay their loans are not because they have earned profit and additional income, but rather they are worried about being blacklisted in accessing the program in the future. However, even though this practice does not fit the aim of microcredit, people in Sitanala see this program as critical survival instrument for poor people.

8.3. Social empowerment program

Social empowerment is a process to develop autonomy and self-confidence so that people can act individually and collectively to change social interactions, institutions and discourses that exclude poor people in the society. There are two social empowerment programs in Sitanala implemented by the Ministry of Social Affairs and the Ministry of Domestic Affairs. Those are *Program Karang Taruna* (Youth Organisation Program) and *Program Pembinaan Keluarga Sejahtera (PKK)* (Family Welfare Movement Program).

8.3.1. Youth organisation program

Youth organisation (Karang Taruna) aims to increase participation of youth in development programs. As a medium for communication and socialisation, Karang Taruna provides opportunities to learn organisational skills, as well as to develop

initiative and creative potential of young people. However, there are two main issues that affect implementation of Karang Taruna, as follows:

8.3.1.1. Insufficient understanding about program

As mentioned in chapter 6, there are ten functions of Karang Taruna that need to be implemented in the community. This means Karang Taruna is not merely a medium for communication and socialisation among young people, but also to promote social solidarity, raise awareness and to address social issues in their social environment. However, research participants said that Karang Taruna in Sitanala was not so active. Most activities are around sports only. They were active only during the celebration of Indonesian Independence Day. Therefore, they had little contribution in fighting against leprosy stigma and discrimination, as well as little support for socio-economic empowerment in Sitanala:

Karang Taruna in Sitanala is between life and death... The place is there, but no activities. Many young people used it as a place to meet and to socialise with others. No more than that... They had never been involved in any empowerment program or social campaign. They were only active when celebrating Indonesian Independence Day every year. (Participant 35, male, FGD)

8.3.1.2. Lack of support from government

In the beginning, when Karang Taruna was formed for the first time, people in Sitanala had high expectations for this program. However, not for long, as the activities decreased gradually until it is vacuum today. Sitanala people called this as *'hangat-hangat tahi ayam'* (literally, a hot chicken dirt) means not doing an activity wholeheartedly and continuously. Often in Indonesia the government builds new institutions and leave them without any continuous support. As a result, Karang Taruna failed to become a partner of government and all stakeholders to address social problems in the community:

In the beginning, Karang Taruna was promising program... As a national program the government supported Karang Taruna 100%. However, I don't know why, after several years, the government didn't seem to care about Karang Taruna anymore. The government seems like to build something new and then just leave it. We call this as 'hangat-hangat tahi ayam'.... (Participant 27, male, FGD)

People in Sitanala believe that leadership in the community also plays an important role in social empowerment. If the leader does not concern himself with the program, the program will not work properly:

Do you know the head of Karang Sari village? He keeps his distance with us... He rarely visits this place and has never shaken hands with us. This is in contrast to the former head of village who loved to visit this place for attending weddings or funerals. (Participant 4, male, in-depth interview)

8.3.2. Family welfare movement program

Family Welfare Movement (PKK) aims to increase participation of women in development programs, improve family welfare and educates the younger generation. To achieve this, PKK has ten agendas that related to: (1) civics; (2) mutual self-help; (3) food; (4) clothing; (5) housing and household management; (6) education; (7) health; (8) family planning; (9) sustainable environment; and (10) cooperatives. However, there are several issues that affect the implementation of PKK in Sitanala.

8.3.2.1. From women movement to 'arm of government'

Historically, PPK was born in 1967 due to the concern of Mrs Isriati Moenadi, the wife of Central Java Governor, after seeing many poor people with *busung lapar* (eden, kwashiorkor: a form of malnutrition caused by lack of protein and vitamin). However, after PKK became a national program, the bureaucracy was very strong in this organisation, shown by the hierarchal structure of the leader from the wives of head of village, sub district, district/municipality, province, and president. Consequently, PKK became an elite organisation and arm of government. That is why PKK often fails to address social issues at the grassroots level, as they wait for instruction from the top leader that is sometimes related to political situation. People in Sitanala use the sarcasm terms '*perempuan kesana kemari*' (women that are busy here and there) and '*perempuan kurang kerjaan*' (women who have nothing to do) in referring to PKK:

PKK is for elite women... We don't get involved in this organisation. The members are rich women who have a lot of time... Their activities are nothing to do with income enhancement. That is why in the past people called PKK as

'perempuan kesana kemari' or 'perempuan kurang kerjaan'. (Participant 3, female, in-depth interview)

8.3.2.2. Support domestication of women

People in Sitanala acknowledged that PKK has been successful in building *Pos Pelayanan Terpadu (Posyandu)* (Integrated Community Health Care Centre) that helps pregnant mothers and children under five years old to receive basic health services. Besides Posyandu, the activities are around domestic works, which unwittingly support domestication for women:

As far as I know, the activities of PKK are related to Posyandu and other domestic works, such as cooking, sewing and fashion design contests... The point is that all their activities try to make a good wife who should be able to do all domestic works. (Participant 15, female, FGD)

PKK is a women's organisation that has never built any networking with other organisations that fight for women's equality. PKK did not seem to increase critical thinking of women in relation to gender equality and gender justice. On large scale, PKK has restricted themselves and failed to accommodate aspirations in the community.

8.4. Political empowerment program

Developing inclusive political institutions that represent the interests of the poor is at the heart of political empowerment. In a community development perspective, political empowerment refers to the influence of policy making processes and participation in decision making, toward policies for the poor. In relation to this, political participation in elections and government are the most important ways.

Regarding the political empowerment programs in Sitanala, one of NGOs that is concerned about this issue is *Gerakan Peduli Disabilitas dan Lepra Indonesia (GPDLI)* (Indonesia Leprosy and Disability Care Movement). To do proper political empowerment, there are two important aspects that one needs to be aware of: (1) skills and understanding of political process; and (2) understanding the rights of people and local political issues. Realising that political empowerment is a long process, GPDLI and other organisations focus on campaigns about leprosy anti-stigma

and the rights of people with disabilities. People in Sitanala benefit from this program as it helps to increase their knowledge and understanding about their rights. In addition, most people in Sitanala have low educational background, so this program fits with their needs:

I think leprosy anti-stigma campaigns to support people like us are very important. Why do I say so? This is because leprosy stigma still exists in Tangerang. Many people are still afraid of us. Even people who live across the hospital are still afraid of us. (Participant 8, male, in-depth interview)

We're people who don't have higher education background. Of course, knowing about leprosy and our rights will benefit us... (Participant 1, male, FGD)

However, even though they were very pleased with the program, people in Sitanala feel that the program is just rhetoric. Some people also said that they do not trust NGOs due to lack of transparency and accountability. They believe that the external organisations used them as puppets and describe this as 'wong bodho dadi pangane wong pinter' (the stupid people eaten by the smart) - 'pecking order'. In addition, the NGOs also failed to stand for and advocate for them from the lying rumours about laziness

Many NGOs said that they advocate for us through campaigns against stigma and discrimination. The funny thing is that some of them are still afraid of us. They don't want to shake hands with us... (Participant 12, male, in-depth interview)

We, lepers, were like puppets only. They just sell the issues of leprosy in Sitanala to get money. Many educated people use us as puppets. They don't really care about us... We call this as 'wong bodho dadi pangane wong pinter'... (Participant 33, male, FGD)

They said they support us. They said they care about us. But where were they when people accused us of being lazy? (Participant 20, male, FGD)

The research participants feel that leprosy anti-stigma campaigns often become ceremonial activities, especially during celebration of the World Leprosy Day. Furthermore, some participants complain because they have never been involved in the celebration:

They only conducted leprosy anti-stigma campaigns during the World Leprosy Day. All the time it was just like that. When the event finished, the program had just gone. I think it should be like 1980s, the campaigns were massive and continuous until people understood about leprosy... (Participant 11, male, FGD)

Only few people were involved in the world leprosy day celebration... They only invited people with leprosy that they knew well. We had never been invited by them. Maybe they didn't invite us because they were worried we would speak up to the Minister. (Participant 9, male, FGD)

8.5. Social inclusion program

Social inclusion is a process in increasing access for poor and marginalised people, so that they can take part in society. Whilst community empowerment demands social changes from below, social inclusion is a complementary approach to change policies and institutions from above (Bennet, 2002). To combat social exclusion, there are various social inclusion programs that are available in Sitanala: (1) *Program Jaminan Kesehatan Masyarakat (Jamkesmas)* (Medical Social Security Program); (2) *Program Rumah Belajar* (Learning House Program); (3) Program Beasiswa (Scholarship Programs); (4) *Program Transmigrasi* (Transmigration Program); (5) *Program Penyapu Jalanan* (Street Sweeper Program); (6) *Program Pekan Olah Raga Penyandang Kusta Nasional (Porseptanas)* (National Sport and Art Week Program for People with Leprosy); and (7) *Program Kunjungan Wisata* (Sightseeing Program). Those programs benefit people in Sitanala who have a lack of access to vital activities, such as health, education, employment and recreational activities.

8.5.1. Health program

Program Jaminan Kesehatan Masyarakat (Jamkesmas) (Medical Social Security Program) that was launched in 2008, provides free medical treatment and services for poor people. This program is basically an improvement of *Program Jaminan Pemeliharaan Kesehatan bagi Masyarakat Miskin (JPKMM)* (Medical Social Security Program for the Poor) or better known as *Asuransi Kesehatan Keluarga Miskin (Askeskin)* (Health Insurance for the Poor) held in 2005-2007.

In relation to Jamkesmas, even though this program successfully increased the access of poor people to healthcare facilities and services, people in Sitanala revealed that some hospitals reject Jamkesmas patients for many reasons, such as full capacity, no room available for patient, there is no equipment and facilities for patient, etc. This

happened even for emergency patients. However, when non-Jamkesmas patients came, the hospital said that there are rooms still available for them:

Program that we appreciate most is Jamkesmas. We are very grateful there is a program like that... In the past, when we were sick, thinking about medical costs that was so expensive, made our illness worse.... Now, it is completely different. The government covers all medical costs. It is free... (Participant 3, female, in-depth interview)

My boy had an accident and I took him into hospital. However, the hospital said that there was no room available... There were so many reasons to reject Jamkesmas patients, such as the wards were full, no equipment or facilities available, full capacity of hotel, and so on... However, when non-Jamkesmas patients came, the hospital said that there were rooms still available for them. Pity my boy.... If you were me, what would you do? Luckily, there was a hospital that finally accepted my boy as a patient. (Participant 31, female, FGD)

Even though the government (MoH) reaffirms that they will sanction any hospital that rejects Jamkesmas patients, the rejection is still likely to happen. In this case, mass media play an important role as a watchdog in monitoring the conduct of hospitals:

I remember, my daughter was about to give birth to a baby. However, the hospital said the wards were full. I was so angry at that time... Luckily, there was a journalist that heard our conversation. He said he would report it in his newspaper. The hospital was so afraid and immediately said, there was still a room available for my daughter. It was crazy, wasn't it? (Participant 8, male, in-depth interview)

8.5.2. Educational program

Education is a basic need that is vital to be accessed for all people. This is because education plays a significant role in all aspects of life, such as social, economic, political, and cultural. However, people in Sitanala have difficulties in sending their children to school due to high educational costs. This can be seen from the dropout rate that is quite high in Sitanala. The false assumptions due to gender bias that a girl does not really need education as they will end up in domestic work also contributes to marginalising female students in accessing education. It is noted that there are two educational programs that are available in Sitanala. Those are *Program Rumah Belajar* (Learning House Program) and *Program Beasiswa* (Scholarship Program).

8.5.2.1. Learning house program

Learning house is a place in which, poor students get tutorials from the volunteers about school subjects and learn prevocational trainings. There are two learning houses that are managed by different organisations: Anak Langit Foundation and *Teach For Indonesia* (TFI). People in Sitanala welcome these programs by giving permission to their children to participate in the learning house.

Since 2004, Anak Langit Foundation has been at work in educational issues through the learning house. Their learning house offers prevocational training to increase knowledge and life skills of the children. This is very useful for their future, as they have skills to get a job and to be independent after graduating from school. However, after having activities for about ten years, they moved to other locations that are quite far from Sitanala. Consequently, people in Sitanala have difficulty accessing their services:

In the past, there was Anak Langit Foundation that helped children in here through prevocational training program. The volunteers in this foundation were activists. They rejected any aid from the government... They were all-out in helping the children to master life skills. Those who were good would receive a scholarship to study at university. The problem is that they left Sitanala for another location... (Participant 2, female, in-depth interview)

Different from Anak Langit Foundation, TFI provides a tutorial program through the learning house. People in Sitanala said that this program helps their children to understand some school subjects. However, there are some issues related to the implementation of the program. First, the tutorial program does not cover children from senior high school. Furthermore, the length of tutorial is too short. Therefore, only few students participate in it. Second, TFI gives an ultimatum for those who rarely come that they would not be allowed to join the tutorial program. As a result, most of students are from healthy families:

I've no children in tutorial program... They only focus on students in primary and junior high schools. The tutorial is very short. It's only an hour in a week. It's not even intensive, I think... (Participant 3, female, in-depth interview)

This program is too strict. Children must come regularly, otherwise they are not allowed to join the learning house. Consequently, our children are not involved in this program. Most of the students are from healthy families. They claim

learning house is for children from leprosy families, whilst the truth is, it is not... (Participant 2, female, in-depth interview)

8.5.2.2. Scholarship program

People in Sitanala acknowledged that the scholarship programs for poor students help them by reducing education costs. The scholarship programs in Sitanala are managed by the Tangerang Korean Community (TKC) and Corporate Social Responsibilities (PT Pertamina). However, these programs are basically a partial scholarship program, which covers the tuition fees only. Therefore, the Sitanala people still must spend some money for children's education expenses:

The scholarship only covers tuition fees... We still must spend money for books, school uniforms, bag, shoes, tutorials, entrance fees, registration, excursion, computer session and swimming. It is crazy. In some school, we have to buy many uniforms, as the schools required different uniforms to wear from Monday to Saturday. This is not cheap though... (Participant 15, female, FGD)

People in Sitanala revealed that the amount of scholarship that they received from TKC was different from PT Pertamina. The amount of scholarship from TKC was higher than PT Pertamina's scholarship. As a result, there was a social jealousy among the beneficiaries of these programs:

People from different countries such as France, India, Netherland, and Korea often come here.... Every month Korean people come to Sitanala and give scholarship for poor students. Primary students receive \$10 per month, whilst junior and senior high school students receive \$15 and \$20 respectively. This is higher than PT Pertamina's scholarship... This because the company only give \$5 for primary students, \$6 for junior high school students, and \$7 for senior high school students. This issue creates social jealousy among the beneficiaries and this is bad for Sitanala.... (Participant 12, male, in-depth interview)

Sitanala people said that the selection process of the beneficiaries between TKC and PT Pertamina was different. TKC goes directly to the potential beneficiaries, selects those who are really poor, and reselects those who have disability. In contrast, PT Pertamina delegates all selection and distribution process to a local NGO in Sitanala:

Talking about Korean's scholarship, they collected data and distributed scholarship directly. They were selective in determining beneficiaries... PT Pertamina was different. They didn't want to know the selection process as they delegated this to a local NGO. The person from this NGO asked \$2 or \$3 from several people in Sitanala and told them that it was for administration purposes.

However, they were disappointed that their names were not on the list. So, don't believe any local NGO in here... (Participant 25, male, FGD)

8.5.3. Employment program

There are two social inclusion programs in Sitanala that aim to increase access and participation in the employment sector. Those are *Program Transmigrasi* (Transmigration Program) and *Program Penyapu Jalanan* (Street Sweeper Program). Transmigration program is conducted by the Ministry of Manpower and Transmigration (MoTT), whilst street sweeper program is under the Tangerang Cleaning and Landscaping Agency (TCLA).

8.5.3.1. Transmigration program

Transmigration is a resettling inhabitant program that is organised by the Indonesian government to empower poor people in Indonesia. It is noted that in 1985, the government sent 67 former leprosy patients and their families to Banyu Asin, Muara Enim, South Sumatra (25 families) and to Rangkas Bitung, Lebak, Banten (42 families) through the transmigration program. The program was intended to give an opportunity for persons affected by leprosy to start a new life as farmers. The government gave them 2 acres of land for each family and provided living allowances for two years. However, the program failed and almost all of them resettled back in Sitanala. This section presents their experiences relating to the transmigration program.

8.5.3.1.1. Poor site preparation

Before sending 67 former leprosy patients and their families, the government conducted program dissemination in the Sitanala leprosy hospital. During the dissemination, the government officers presented some pictures about transmigration program. Through these pictures, people in Sitanala could see happy farmers were harvesting rice and fruits, fertile soils, and good irrigation system. After seeing the pictures, they decided to join this program. However, after arriving at Banyu Asin, Muara Enim, South Sumatera they were very disappointed. This is because the location of transmigration was very far from the city and the site was not

prepared well by the government. They did not see any rice field, fruit trees, or good irrigation system, but swamp forests:

In 1985, I participated in the transmigration program to Banyu Asin in South Sumatra. When we arrived at the location, it was like in the middle of nowhere. There was no rice field, fruit trees and even people who lived there. It was swamp forests. It was flooding when we came there, and the water reached our waists... We were so disappointed. I asked the director of Sitanala hospital who accompanied us to the location, why the site was so different from the pictures they had shown to us in Sitanala. The director was so afraid, and he could not answer it.... He knew that the site was not prepared well by the government. When he just remained silent and could not answer my question, we just realised that we were deceived. They used us as object of experiment. They played with our lives... (Participant 10, male, FGD)

8.5.3.1.2. Poor farming condition

Even though people from Sitanala were very disappointed at that time, they kept working and clearing the area together. Thus, they started to plant rice and fruits. However, when the flood came all their plants had gone. One of the research participants described the situation, as follows:

I was so disappointed. If they would like to empower persons affected by leprosy, why they did not find a location that more suitable for us? As a normal human, we would like to start a new life. We cleared the area in only a month. We worked very hard. Then, we started to plant rice and fruits. However, when the flood came, all plants had gone. Our houses were flooded too. It happened all the time. I think even healthy people would give up managing those lands and live at that location. Maybe the government forgot that we are disabled people. (Participant 11, male, FGD)

The similar situation also experienced by those who migrated to Rangkas Bitung, Lebak, Banten. They said that the geographic location was very difficult to reach. Furthermore, the soil quality was very low. It was rocky soil, so the plants were difficult to grow. When the rain came, all plants had gone too. This poor farming condition made them so frustrated:

In 1985, I visited my friend who joined the transmigration program in Rangkas Bitung. The location was very far from the city. The road was very slippery. My foot was blistered. My friend said that it was rocky soils and they faced difficulties to plant rice or fruit tree. If rain was coming, all the plants had gone, then followed the rainwater. When the dry season was coming, they must go to the Baduy village and asked for water. It was 3 kilometres from the transmigration site... (Participant 19, male, FGD)

8.5.3.1.3. Poor market access

People from Sitanala admitted that the obstacles related to transmigration program were not only poor site preparation and poor farming conditions, but also poor access to markets. The location that was very far from the city, made them difficult to sell their rice or fruits. Thus, their harvest was damaged and rotten because there was no one who would buy it. In addition, after two years, they did not receive living allowance from the government anymore. Due to this situation, they just left Banyu Asin and went back to Sitanala, Tangerang:

The access to markets in Banyu Asin was very poor. We faced difficulties in selling our rice and fruits. We were able to keep the rice, but the fruits were damaged and rotten. That was so sad. After living two years in Banyu Asin, we did not receive an allowance from the government anymore. Finally, we decided to leave and went back to Sitanala. There was no hope in there... (Participant 10, male, FGD)

It was very hard living in Rangkas Bitung. We could not stand that location anymore. No one bought our agricultural products. It was very hard living in Rangkas Bitung. This program was useless... (Participant 20, male, FGD)

8.5.3.1.4. Blaming the lepers for program failure

When they came back to Sitanala, they were so filled with panic because the director of the Sitanala hospital was replaced by a new person. The new director did not know the history of the transmigration program. Because they were homeless, and their family need a place to stay, they decided to stay in unoccupied buildings in the Sitanala hospital. They did this because they were panicked. These buildings used to be a nursing home and a kindergarten school. This incident occurred between 1989 and 1990. The hospital was not pleased with their action:

When we came back to Sitanala, we were so panicked... Our family needed a place to stay. We were homeless. After knowing that there were unoccupied buildings, we decided to break the doors and live there. We were doing something crazy at that time. This is because we were so panicked... The new director came and interrogated us about staying in the hospital's buildings without any permission. We just said that the hospital should also take responsibility and not only blame us for the failure. The director then left us. He was not pleased with our actions, but we didn't care. If the new director knew the history of this program, I bet he would cry for us... That was like 'buruk muka, cermin dibelah'... (Participant 11, male, FGD)

Many people blamed them for the failure of transmigration program both in Banyu Asin and Rangkas Bitung. They were labelled as lazy people who did not have the spirit to change their lives. They called this as *'buruk muka, cermin dibelah'* (ugly face, the mirror is split), a similar meaning to "a bad workman blames his tools". The worst thing was that they were excluded from the list of beneficiaries in Sitanala. The reason of excluding them was they had received transmigration program, so that they could not receive aids such as food and scholarship for children:

When we resettled back in Sitanala we did not receive much aid. They said we were not on the list of beneficiaries. They said we had received the transmigration program. So, if it failed, it was our own fault. They said the program failed because we were so lazy. If we were so lazy, why did we go to Rangkas Bitung and Banyu Asin? This was because we had a good attitude to change our lives, compared to those who did not join the transmigration program. It was easy to make us as the scapegoat for the program's failure... The government should prioritise us, but what we received was exclusion. It was like rubbing salt into the wound. People who blamed us basically never heard the real story. Because we had to survive, we started begging on the streets. We were forced by circumstances... (Participant 10, male, FGD)

8.5.3.2. Street sweeping program

This program is one of Tangerang local government programs and it is considered as a solution to empower people affected by leprosy in Sitanala. People in Sitanala said that the program was pro-disability and had some positive impact for them. However, there were some critics of this program who need to be heard to improve the program in the future.

8.5.3.2.1. Pro-disabled program

Based on the experience of the persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala, the street sweeping program was considered as a pro-disabled program. There were some reasons behind this view. Firstly, the program was proposed by the head of district and mayor of Tangerang who was concerned about their lives. It is noted that this program was firstly initiated by the head of Tangerang District, Tadjus Sobirin (in office 1983-1993), before being implemented by the Tangerang Mayor, Djakaria Mahmud (in office 1993-1998). Both had a close relationship with the Sitanala people:

Many people here work as street sweepers. The street sweeping program was started under Djakarta Mahmud. He was the mayor of Tangerang at that time. The program basically was initiated by Tadjus Sobirin. He was a pioneer who cared for lepers in Tangerang. He was the head of district, who was very kind to us... After finishing his office work, he always visited us. Every Friday, he prayed with us in our mosque. The only head of district who was not afraid of leprosy was Tadjus Sobirin. He loved all people with leprosy in Sitanala... (Participant 14, female, FGD)

Secondly, the program was also designed as a disability-friendly program for persons affected by leprosy. There were no complicated requirements for people with disabilities to join this program. The only requirement to work as street sweepers was they are willing and able to sweep:

Formerly leprosy patients worked as street sweepers. I had been never asked about education or any certificates... They only asked whether we could sweep or not. We had to prove and demonstrate that we could hold the broomstick and tie it... (Participant 11, male, in-depth interview)

Thirdly, the street sweeping program is categorised as a sustainable community empowerment program and it is still running today. Even the elderly, were still allowed to work if they are still productive and capable of doing their job:

The street sweeping program started in 1990s and it still exists today. There are many elderly people who are still working as street sweepers. It is allowed by the government of Tangerang.... The important thing is that they are still able to do it. (Participant 1, male, FGD 4).

Lastly, the government kept improving the street sweeping program based on the principle of the program being in the best interests of people affected by leprosy. For example, in the past they had to work for 12 hours, the government changed it to 8 hours. Thus, in the past they had to sweep 1 kilometre's street alone, now it is conducted by two people. This was revealed by the participants as follows:

The government pay us per day, not per hour... In the past, we had to work all day. We had to work for 12 hours. I worked from 6 am to 6 pm. I finished my work at 6 pm. The government then changed the program, in which we only worked for 8 hours. We started early morning and finished at 9 am. We started work again at 1 pm and finished at 5 pm. In the past, we swept 1-kilometre of road alone, but now it is conducted by two people. (Participant 11, male, in-depth interview)

8.5.3.2.2. Significant Impact

Street sweeping program is a community empowerment program that has significant and positive impact on the population Sitanala. The first positive impact of this program is that the program provided jobs for persons affected by leprosy. Thus, persons affected by leprosy could earn money and improve their lives:

We were so lucky. The mayor employed us as street sweepers. This was good for us. We got jobs and earned money to improve our lives. We could not expect much for other jobs. It was difficult to find jobs. For example, when we worked as a street vendor outside Sitanala, nobody wanted to buy because they saw our fingers. Who wanted to buy? When we would like to work at the factory, no factory employed us due to our leprosy. This made us so frustrated. The street sweeping program helped us to deal with our situation. The mayor said that we as humans also need to eat, pay tuition fees for our children, and so on. If we did not have jobs, it would influence us to do something bad, like drink alcohol or consume drugs and that was not good for our society. (Participant 4, male, FGD)

The second positive impact of the street sweeping program is that the program helped in creating solidarity among people with leprosy. Through this program, persons affected by leprosy could show to the general society that they were productive and able to work if they got opportunities:

Even though the salary was not high, we felt the solidarity among us... We had lunch together and it was beautiful for togetherness. So, we and healthy people are basically the same. If we had the opportunities to get jobs, we could be more productive like them. Furthermore, in terms of cleanliness, the works of people with leprosy are neater and cleaner compare to healthy people. This is because we are afraid of losing our jobs. That is why we did our work as best as we can... (Participant 22, female, FGD)

The third positive impact of this program is that the program contributed to increase their self-confidence and raise their self-esteem. Based on their experiences, working as street sweepers was more honourable than begging on the streets:

Since I joined this program, we have never begged on the street anymore... We have never played cat and mouse with the civil service police unit anymore... We realise that begging has made our image worse. This is because begging was associated with laziness. Being street sweepers means we are more confident... (Participant 24, female, FGD).

The fourth benefit of this program is that the program provided a space for people with leprosy to be able to participate in helping the cleanliness of the city. They were very proud working for the Tangerang Cleaning and Landscaping Agency:

When the Tangerang government received the Adipura award as the most clean and beautiful city, we were very proud of it. In the history of Indonesia, only in Tangerang, the local government empower and employ persons affected by leprosy through the street sweeping program. I think other local governments should do the same thing. Through this program, we could participate to make our city clean... (Participant 4, male, in-depth interview)

8.5.3.2.3. Critics about program

Although the street sweeping program is considered as a pro-disability program and it has positive impacts, the program has received critics from people in Sitanala. The first critic is based on the recruitment and payment system. People in Sitanala mentioned that the implementation of street sweeping program today has deviated from its aims and purposes, especially in terms of recruitment. They believed that the program was designed and intended specifically for persons affected by leprosy. However, the reality shows that many healthy people from outside Sitanala also worked as street sweepers. Therefore, the opportunity of the Sitanala people to work as street sweepers has been reduced. They think that this practice of recruitment was unfair. This is because, in the past when the salary as a street sweeper was very small, no healthy people were interested. However, after the salary reached \$200 per month, the healthy people vied to become street sweepers:

Obtaining a job as a street sweeper now is difficult... We must compete with healthy people. Healthy people from outside Sitanala are interested in becoming street sweepers too. The positions are already full because the healthy people also work as street sweepers... (Participant 9, female, in-depth interview)

When the director of the hospital was Haryanto, from the military, and the mayor was still Zakaria Mahmud, we were empowered as street sweepers. At the beginning, the salary was only \$5 per month and no healthy people were interested in that job. However, when the salary increased to \$200 per month, the healthy people were eager to work as street sweepers too... (Participant 21, male, FGD)

In relation to recruitment for the street sweeper program, people in Sitanala complained about the rumours of corruption, collusion, and nepotism in the

recruitment process. They strongly objected to this practice, because it is clearly contrary to the spirit of the program:

The chance to work as street sweepers now is limited... Many healthy people work as street sweepers too. We ever protested it, but they said the past is the past and today is today. It is difficult to work as street sweepers if you do not have money, connection and relatives who work the Tangerang Cleaning and Landscaping Agency.... (Participant 36, male, FGD)

Most people here work as street sweepers. There is no other job except street sweepers, but we must pay \$700 to get that job. It's bribery... My experience to apply for that job was difficult. We were like a ball. They asked us to come to this section and that section. It was so tiring. My friend told me that he got the job because he paid \$700. (Participant 27, male, FGD)

People in Sitanala also mentioned that the payment system needs to be changed. This is because the salary of the street sweepers is based on daily payment. For example, if they cannot work due to illness or urgent matters, their salaries will be cut \$ 7 per day. This means to get a salary of \$200 per month, they must work every day. There is no pension or superannuation when working as street sweepers:

For street sweeping, we have got salary \$200 per month. That is based on daily work. If you are absent a day, they will cut your wage about \$7. That is why if you are sick or have an urgent matter in your family, you will never get the full \$200. (Participant 12, male, in-depth interview)

Working as a street sweeper is like putting our sweat and blood in there. If we do not work for a day, they will cut our salary. That is why I said that our sweat and blood is in there. The payment is daily and it is paid once a month. No pension... So, if we stop working because we are old, we will not receive anything. (Participant 9, female, in-depth interview)

8.5.4. Recreational program

There are two programs that aim to increase access to recreational needs. Those are *(Pekan olah raga dan seni bekas penyandang kusta nasional) (Porseptanas)* (National sport and art week for people with leprosy) and *Program Kunjungan Wisata (Sightseeing Pogram)*.

8.5.4.1. National sport week and art program

According to persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala, Porseptanas helped them to gain self-confidence because they can perform to the limit of their ability in sports and

arts. This program also strengthened the brotherhood among persons affected by leprosy:

The program that I remember most was Porseptanas. The participants of this event were from all provinces in Indonesia. There were many sports contested in Porseptanas such as athletics, football, volleyball and so on. We were very excited and entertained by this event. We also realised that it was not only we who were affected by leprosy.... There were other brothers and sisters that had leprosy who joined this event. This event helped us to increase our confidence as well as strengthening brotherhood among former leprosy patients. We were so proud there was a big sport event that was organised for people like us... (Participant 33, male, FGD)

During the Porseptanas, the Indonesian president, Soeharto, came directly with his family to watch the event. President Soeharto also delivered his speech to encourage people in Indonesia to accept those people affected by leprosy and to fight against leprosy stigma:

In Porseptanas, Mr President invited us to come to his office. He dared to shake hands with and hug us... Mr Soeharto was the president who was really concerned about us. We were happy that he had a program such as Porseptanas. He also asked people not to be afraid of lepers and encourage people to fight against stigma and discrimination. However, after changing the president, there was no such activity like Porseptanas. The new presidents seemed less concerned about us.... (Participant 19, male, FGD)

Although the program was useful, the government only held these events twice. The first Porseptanas was held in Jakarta in 1988, and the second was conducted in Ujung Pandang (now Makassar) in 1991:

All former leprosy patients were happy with Porseptanas. The problem was Porseptanas was only held twice. There was Porseptanas in Jakarta and Ujung Pandang. The events held in 1988 and 1991. After that, there was no event like that anymore... It would be good if the government could organise events like Porseptanas... (Participant 20, male, FGD)

8.5.4.2. Sightseeing program

Regarding the recreational program in Sitanala, the Tangerang Korean Community organise a sightseeing program every year. This program benefits Sitanala people as they can go to recreational places like 'normal' people do. It is noted that they had visited some beautiful places, such as *Taman Safari Bogor* (Bogor Safari Park), *Kebun Binatang Ragunan Jakarta* (Jakarta Ragunan Zoo) and *Taman Mini Indonesia Indah (TMII)* (Beautiful Indonesia in Miniature Park):

Every year, the Korean people invite us to visit nice places. We visited Taman Safari, Kebun Binatang Ragunan and Taman Mini Indonesia Indah. All costs were covered by the Koreans... We were excited about this because there was a program that dared to invite and travel together with us. This is because no organisation would like to carry lepers like us, right? That's why we thank Korean people for having program like this... (Participant 2, female, FGD)

This sightseeing program facilitated the lepers to appearance in and access to public places, so that their confidence would increase. However, this program only covers children who received scholarships from the Tangerang Korean Community and their parents. Therefore, those who did not receive the scholarships cannot participate in the sightseeing program:

We would like to join in the recreational program organised by the Korean people, but it was limited to families who receive a scholarship from the Korean people. So, we couldn't participate in the sightseeing program... This program is important to us, because we can visit tourist sites together and we don't feel embarrassed. (Participant 28, male, FGD)

Regarding recreational program, some churches often organise kids stage performances, to entertain people in Sitanala. However, even though the events were so entertaining, the events had never involved children of Sitanala:

Some churches used to organise kids stage performances. Children from churches performed dances. I liked the butterfly dance. It's so beautiful... However, all the children were from the churches. There's no single kid from Sitanala. We would be very happy if our children can perform on stage too. Our children deserve it. They're not lepers... (Participant 12, male, in-depth interview)

8.6. Non-CESI program

Non-CESI program is a charity program, which aims to maximise support for persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala through direct services such as giving money, food, medicines, and medical devices. There are several non-CESI programs available in Sitanala, those are food aid, medical aid, and cash transfer programs.

8.6.1. Food aid program

In the past, Sitanala leprosy hospital received food aid from many donors both domestic and foreign. The food was then distributed by the hospital through a monthly package for leprosy patients who lived at Komplek Serba Guna. People in

Sitanala benefit from this program as it helps to protect them from hunger and malnutrition, and reduces family expenditure:

When we had finished medical treatment, the hospital gave permission to stay in Sitanala. The hospital also distributed food for us regularly. It really helped us to survive because we didn't have jobs at that time.... Many donors came to the hospital and donated foods for us.... Not only did this reduce family expenditure, this program protected us from hunger and malnutrition, and showed us that there were some people who still cared for us. (Participant 11, male, in-depth interview)

However, in 1998 the hospital stopped the program. Other food aid programs could not be expected as it was rare and incidental. As a result, most people in Sitanala went to the streets, begging to meet their daily needs. Those who worked as street sweepers also did the same thing after finishing their work:

Our nightmare began when the hospital stopped the food aid program. We didn't know what we had to do.... Many people went to the streets as beggars to survive. Those who worked as street sweepers did the same thing due to small salary. Me and my wife tried to sell cassava in the market to survive. We didn't eat food from morning to afternoon.... After having money from selling cassava, we bought rice and ate. However, it didn't last long. We then decided to become beggars too... (Participant 11, male, in-depth interview)

Luckily, in 2004 the Indonesian government launched *Program Beras Miskin (Raskin)* (Rice Subsidy for the Poor Program). People in Sitanala really appreciate this program as it helps them to buy rice from government under the market price. However, due to poor public administration, many people in Sitanala do not receive Raskin. In contrast, those who are unqualified to be beneficiaries of this program, receive the rice subsidy:

Raskin is a good program, but many of us don't receive it... The funny thing, the healthy people who are not the poor also receive the Raskin... We are not thinking negatively, but the data collectors often prioritise their family, close friends, and their groups. That's why the data is very poor and many of us are excluded from the program... We even went to the village office several times to question this, but no response... They said the data couldn't be changed. (Participant 7, female, in-depth interview)

Interestingly, those who receive the Raskin complain about the quality of rice that is very bad and it is not suitable for consumption. To solve this, they mix the raskin with other rice that has better quality:

The quality of the Raskin is poor. If you feed a cat that rice, maybe the cat will vomit. That's like poisoning us slowly... If even a cat doesn't want to consume it, this means the quality of rice is very poor... (Participant 7, female, in-depth interview)

Sometimes, if we have money, we mix the Raskin with good rice. We feel pity for our children... The rice is too smelly and difficult to swallow it. The rice already turned to yellow and it was like powder when we receive it. Chicken in here won't eat that rice... If we didn't have money, we just eat that rice. We are fine with that, but not our children... (Participant 16, female, FGD)

8.6.2. Medical aid program

People in Sitanala admitted that they received a medical aid program, such as first aid kit for self-care, medical payment support in emergency, and prostheses to support activities in daily living (ADLs). This program helps them to assess and manage their ulcer problems and prevents any further injury and disability, as well as increasing their productivity:

We were very happy because some donors helped us by providing first aid kits and prosthetic limb devices. When we were sick or in an emergency, they also supported us by paying all medical costs. With the first aid kit, we can manage our ulcer problems... The prosthetic limb device supported us to do daily living activities. (Participant 6, female, FGD)

People in Sitanala said that the problem with the medical aid program was the limited number of prosthetic limb devices, so that some people did not receive it:

The prostheses aid was incidental. It was difficult to distribute prosthetic devices to people in Sitanala, and the number of devices was limited. Consequently, some people who really needed the prostheses, didn't receive it. We called these unlucky. In my opinion, the donor should thoroughly select the beneficiaries, before sending the devices to Sitanala. Otherwise, it would create conflict among us...

8.6.3. Cash transfer program

Another non-CESI program available in Sitanala was *Program Bantuan Langsung Tunai (BLT)* (Cash Transfer Program) that in 2013 changed its name to *Program Bantuan Langsung Sementara Masyarakat (BLSM)* (Temporary Direct Aid Program). Other cash transfer programs such as *Program Keluarga Harapan (PKH)* (Family Hope Program), *Program Jaminan Sosial Penyandang Cacat (JSPACA)* (Social Security Program for Disabled People Program) and *Program Jaminan Sosial Lanjut Usia (JSLU)*

(Social Security Program for Elderly Program) are not available in this community. Regarding the BLT program, people in Sitanala revealed that they benefit from this program even though the amount of money was very small:

We received \$20 per month from the BLT program. At that time, we were in a difficult situation... The government increased the price of oil again and it was followed by increasing price of daily goods. At the same time, I was sick... I used the money to buy some food... (Participant 29, female, FGD)

Similar in case to the Raskin program, many poor people in Sitanala were still excluded from BLT program. Sitanala people believed that this happened due to poor public administration and data inaccuracies. Consequently, people who were not poor, in contrast, received the BLT program:

Many people in here didn't receive BLT program. Even me, I also have never received the BLT. I think this was because data inaccuracies. The government should improve their method of collecting data of the beneficiaries, so they could avoid errors in determining the beneficiaries who are poor... (Participant 18, female, FGD)

We had never received BLSM program, when all prices of daily goods were increased due to adjustment in oil price by the government. It really hurt seeing people received money from BLSM, but we didn't... They even asked me, why I didn't receive the BLSM? I didn't know how to answer this.... Many people in Sitanala didn't receive this program. In contrast, people who were healthy and had a better life than us, received the BLSM. To me, this is unfair... (Participant 21, male, FGD)

Sitanala people also revealed that the common problem about the BLT/BLSM program was the delaying in transferring the funds. They used to receive the money several months after the government increased the price of oil:

I received the BLT program and I didn't know why my neighbours didn't receive it... What I thought about this program was we used to receive the money from BLT program three or four months after the government adjusted the oil price. It was too long for poor people like me... (Participant 22, female, in-depth interview)

8.7. Conclusion

This chapter has presented perceptions and experiences of people in Sitanala about CESI program available in their community. The implementation, benefit and impact of CESI and non-CESI programs in Sitanala can be seen with the help of Table 8.1. From this table, some programs did not meet the felt needs of people. Table 8.1 also

shows that many CESI programs are dominated by the government. Furthermore, many CESI programs have a good design and potential to benefit people in Sitanala but are poor in implementation. Consequently, most of the programs have a low impact on the beneficiaries and fail to increase their participation in economic, social, and political aspects. Some Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) provide good examples for lessons learned in empowering persons affected by leprosy in sitanala. However, lack of funding becomes the greatest challenge. Lastly, the non-CESI programs that are expected to provide social protection and to maximise CESI programs in Sitanala are very few, incidental and unsustainable. From this point, the rumours about laziness and dependency that blame people in Sitanala make the people basically scapegoats, due to poor implementation of programs in this community.

Table 8.1
The Implementation, Benefit, and Impact of CESI and Non-CESI Programs in Sitanala

No.	Program	Benefit	Implementation	Impact
I.	CESI Program			
A.	Community Empowerment			
1.	Economic Empowerment Program			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vocational training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase new knowledge and skills - Improve performance and competencies - Better chances of employment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mismatch between vocational trainings and interest/talent - Problem with incidental & short-term training - Physical distance during training - Input-output paradigm - No further assistance 	<u>Low:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Most participants fail to master the skills. - Those who can master the skill still have trouble finding a job
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UEP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opportunities for starting a small business - Encourage entrepreneurship 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Problem in determining beneficiaries - Administration fees issues - Rejection of the elites 	<u>Low:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Only few people receive stimulant aids from UEP - Almost all small business close due to lack of capital, competing with 'giants' and profit is less than expenditure/consumption
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KUBE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning organisational skills - Increase interaction and social solidarity - Encourage and motivate members through self-help group - Opportunities to increase income through business group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instant group formation - Lack of dissemination - Missing community facilitator 	<u>Low:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Group is easily broken - Confusing to start-up the business group - Fail to increase income

	- Microcredit	- Opportunities for getting low-interest loan to start-up or expand a small business - Critical survival instrument for poor households	- Limited amount of funds - Managerial problem - Loan for consumption	<u>Low:</u> - Only few people have opportunities to get loans - Forced borrowers into debt traps
2.	Social Empowerment Program			
	- Karang Taruna	- Medium for communication and socialisation - Develop initiative and creative potential of young people - Opportunities to learn organisational skills	- Lack of understanding about program - Lack of support from government	<u>Low:</u> - Fail to become a partner of government and all stakeholders to address social problems in the community - Lack of contribution in raising awareness on leprosy stigma and discrimination
	- PKK	- Medium for communication and socialisation - Opportunities to learn organisational skills - Develop initiative and creative potential of women	- Lack of understanding about program - From women movement to 'government arm' - Unwittingly supporting domestication women	<u>Low:</u> - Lack of contribution in promoting family welfare in the community - Fail to accommodate and carry out aspiration in the community
3.	Political Empowerment Program			
	- Leprosy anti-stigma campaign	- Increase knowledge and understanding about leprosy - Increase knowledge about human rights	- Transparency and accountability issues - Dominated by the elites - Rhetorical issues	<u>Medium:</u> - Connecting Sitanala community with donors - Increase networking - Widely untrusted from the community - Fail to advocate rumours of laziness and dependency
B.	Social Inclusion			
1.	Health Program			
	- Jamkesmas	- Have treatment and medication for free - Reduce the expenditure of the poor	- Rejected by hospital issues - Unfriendly services	<u>High:</u> - Increase access to health care facilities and services - Increase quality of health services for the poor

2. Educational Program				
	- Scholarship	- Reduce education costs	- Problem in determining beneficiaries - Using tuition fees support for consumption	<u>High:</u> - Increase access to education - Prevent and reduce the dropout rate in Sitanala
	- Learning house	- Increase more understanding about school subjects	- Does not cover senior high school student - Banned children who rarely come to learning house	<u>Low:</u> - Only few students join this program - Most of the students are from healthy people families
		- Increase knowledge and life skills - Learn to be independent	- Location too far - Problem in accessing information	<u>Medium:</u> - Students ready and able to work after finishing high school - Prevent children from being street children
3. Employment Program				
	- Transmigration	- Receive houses, land for farming, and a subsistence and production package during their early settlement years - Opportunities to work on-farm self-employment	- Poor site preparation - Poor farming condition - Poor market access	<u>Low:</u> - Fail to increase income the beneficiaries - Decrease the motivation of Sitanala people - Contribute to create rumours of laziness to Sitanala people
	- Street sweeping	- Opportunities to work as street sweeper under local government - Successfully providing permanent job for Sitanala people -	- Problem with recruitment nowadays: not transparent, nepotism, and bribery issues - Competition with healthy people - No pension and daily basis payment	<u>High:</u> - Prevent for being beggar at the street - Increase self-confidence and independency - Increase participation in maintaining cleanliness of the city

4.	Recreational Program			
	- National sport week	- Opportunities to meet with people with leprosy from other provinces in Indonesia - Sport event as free entertainment	- Supported directly by the Indonesian President - Call to fight stigma and discrimination through keynote speeches - Only held in 1988 and 1991	<u>High:</u> - Promote the spirit of togetherness among former leprosy patients - Increase self-confidence - Increase their potentials in sport - Support leprosy anti-stigma campaign
	- Sightseeing and kid stage performance	- Opportunities to visit recreational places/public spaces without worried of being discriminated - Enjoy entertainment and performance	- Only for children and parents who receive scholarship - Kid stage performances did not involve Sitanala children	<u>High:</u> - Promote the spirit of togetherness among former leprosy patients - Increase self-confidence
II.	Non-CESI Program			
1.	Food Aid	- Receive food and reduce family expenditure - Protect people from hunger - Improve their nutrition	- Inclusive error and exclusive error - Poor quality of rice - Most food aids are incidental - Aids decreased sharply since 1998	<u>Low:</u> - Fail to provide good quality of rice - Unsustainable program
2.	Medical Aid	- Receive first aid kit for self-care - Receive medical payment support in emergency - Receive prostheses to support activities in daily living (ADLs)	- Limited number of prosthetic limb devices - Incidental	<u>High:</u> - Able to assess and manage their ulcer problem - Prevent further injury and disability - Increase productivity
3.	Cash Transfer (BLT, BLSM, PSKS)	- Receive additional extra money for daily consumption needs	- Inclusive error and exclusive error - Incidental - Delay in transferring funds	<u>Low:</u> - Fail to protect poor families from the impact of fuel price adjustment - Unsustainable program

'Washing one's hands of the conflict between the powerful and the powerless means to side with the powerful, not to be neutral.'

(Paulo Freire)

Chapter 9: Theorising and analysing the practice of community empowerment and social inclusion

9.1. Introduction

Chapter 5, 6, 7 and 8 explored the government policy relating to leprosy and disability issues; various community empowerment and social inclusion programs available in Sitanala; the situation of Sitanala leprosy village today; and the perceptions and experiences of people affected by leprosy in relation to the community empowerment and social inclusion programs. This chapter focuses on analysing research findings with existing theories and theorising grounded on the findings based on the field data.

9.2. Exploring findings with existing theories

As discussed in Chapter 2 and 3, this research employs theories and concepts of social stigma (Falk, 2001; Goffman, 1963; Heijnders & van Der Meij, 2006; Jones et al., 1984; Link & Phelan, 2001; Weiss et al., 2006), social exclusion (de Haan & Maxwell, 1998; Jenks, 2003; Silver, 1994; Singer, 1997), critical disability (Bellamy, 1998; Hosking, 2008; McDonald et al., 2007; Oliver & Zarb, 1989; Scott-Hill, 2002; Zola, 1993), community empowerment and social inclusion (Abbott & Mcconkey, 2006; Bates & Davis, 2004; Hayes et al., 2008; Israel et al., 1994; Jackson et al., 1989; Labonte, 1989; Rissel, 1994; Zimmerman, 1999). By using critical ethnography and these theories as lenses and, it helps to clarify the focus of the research and analyse the description of the Sitanala case study. This is because critical ethnography represents and analyses social life for the political purpose of overcoming social oppression (Crotty, 1998; Given, 2008; Madison, 2011; Thomas, 2004).

9.2.1. Examination of findings through social stigma and social exclusion theories

In relation to the theory of social stigma, Goffman (1963) says that stigma is a phenomenon in which an individual is deeply discredited due to his/her attributes. Thus, the reactions of others spoil normal identity. In the context of the Sitanala community, persons affected by leprosy faced stigma and brutal discrimination due to leprosy and disability. Leprosy and disability based on Goffman's work have been categorised as abominations (disfigurement) of the body.

9.2.1.1. Factors contributing to leprosy stigma

Labelling, stereotype and prejudice are important components and entry point of creating stigma. It leads to a separation between 'us' and 'them'. Furthermore, following by emotional reactions by 'normal' people, it results in loss of status and discrimination (Link & Phelan, 2001; Weiss et al., 2006). The findings show that there are three factors contributing to the stigma of leprosy.

9.2.1.1.1. Traditional beliefs and religious views

Traditional beliefs and religious views play an important role in creating leprosy stigma (Edmond, 2006; Kazeem & Adegun, 2011; Volinn, 1989; Wong, 2004). Some participants mentioned that people in their hometown believed that leprosy is basically the disease occurs due to *teluh* (black magic) and *guna-guna* (witchcrafts). Almost all persons affected by leprosy went to *dukun* (shamans), *tabib* (traditional healers) and *orang pintar* (clerics) in the first instance, to cure leprosy. The reasons they went to these people instead of going to modern healthcare is because it was cheaper and common to do it. The other reason is that their villages were too far away to access it. In some cases, the doctor only came every 1-2 weeks. Many participants revealed that they received various treatments, from just drinking a glass of water that had been recited over with incantations, taking a bath with kinds of flowers in cold water at midnight, taking a bath with hot water, and taking a bath with *air kapur* (limewash) that damaged their skin. In some cases, the *dukun* told the female participants to having sexual intercourse with them so that the bad spirit would disappear. This explains why persons affected by leprosy who came to the

Sitanala hospital, mostly had severe deformities and disfigurements due to maltreatments.

9.2.1.1.2. Lack of knowledge and understanding about leprosy

The second factor which contributes to leprosy-related stigma is the lack of knowledge and understanding about leprosy (Rafferty, 2005; Rao et al., 2006; Rensen et al., 2011; Tsutsumi et al., 2007; Wong, 2004). The findings reveal that most participants admitted that people in their villages called leprosy as *raja penyakit* (king of diseases) and *penyakit daging busuk* (rotten meat disease) that cannot be cured. In West Java, people call leprosy 'mariti' (abbreviation from *marinya mati*, which means there is no cure for this disease except death). People in their villages also believed that leprosy spreads easily through any objects touched or used by lepers. They did not know that leprosy is difficult to transmit and contract, and it can be cured by MDT, a combination of drugs such as DDS (dapson), clofazimine (Lamprene) and rifampicin.

Persons affected by leprosy who live in Sitanala mostly have a low level of education. Many of them never attended primary school and are illiterate. So, when they heard that they had leprosy and their family or neighbour told them that leprosy was highly contagious disease that cannot be cured, and their body would be rotten soon, they were shocked and cried. Some participants could not even stand when they heard this information. People in their villages received this false information about leprosy passed from generation to generation through bedtime stories.

Interestingly, participants mentioned that health workers such as doctors and nurses who are obviously educated and have sufficient knowledge are still scared of sufferers. Some health workers still accept the idea that leprosy is highly contagious. This can be seen from their negative attitude to shaking hands, reluctance to touch the patient's body, and even open a door with their feet as the door handle has been touched by them.

9.2.1.1.3. Grade of disability and deformity

Disability and deformity contribute to leprosy stigma (Cross & Choudhary, 2005; El Hassan et al., 2002; Rafferty, 2005). The findings show that most participants said that people with severe leprosy and grade 2 disability experienced more rejection by society, compared to those who are without visible deformity. The severe leprosy is characterised by deformity in physical appearance of facial symptoms - wider nose, ridged and thick skin, loss of their fingers and legs. Persons affected by leprosy who are without visible deformity or ulceration are more easily able to integrate into the society. The more deformity and disability they have, the more rejection they receive from society. Persons affected by leprosy who have more disability and deformity are often shy, and have low self-esteem, frustration, and depression. This explains why many people in Sitanala often cover their entire face and body with linen and wear gloves.

9.2.1.1.2. Leprosy stigma and social exclusion

Based on the experiences and voices that have been revealed by research participants, it is clear that people in Kampung Kusta Sitanala are still having difficulties in meeting their daily basic needs. They are also still vulnerable to the practice of discrimination because of the stigma and their disability. Thompson (2006) states that discrimination and injustice arises because of the interaction between personal, cultural and social structure. Discriminatory behaviours that are displayed by individuals is strongly influenced by cultural values prevailing in the local community, and this is reinforced by the social and political structures that exist. Furthermore, Thompson explains that discrimination does not occur in one aspect only, but it happens with other aspects of what he called it 'multiple oppression', in which is experienced by people in Sitanala.

In the context of programs for people in Sitanala, many of them are influenced by the paradigm of the medical model, where they do not have a choice to choose their services. Psychosocial problems are often overlooked during their medical treatment. This contrasts with the definition of well-being that includes all aspects such as physical, intellectual, emotional, social and spiritual that must be viewed as a whole

(DuBois & Krogsrud Miley, 2011). Therefore, social work as a profession that is directly in contact with marginalised groups and actively promoting justice and human rights in order to improve the quality of life, needs to address this problem.

Leprosy studies (Coveying-Kwong et al., 2001; Kaur & van Brakel, 2002b; Nicholls, 2000; Weiss et al., 2006) consistently show that many persons affected by leprosy suffer from social rejection and experience socioeconomic difficulties due to leprosy stigma. The literature also illustrates that leprosy stigma creates extreme social exclusion. In general, social exclusion refers to the situation in which individuals cannot participate in key activities in the communities in which they live (Burchardt, 2002). According to Jenks (2003), there are at least three paradigms to understand social exclusion: specialisation, solidarity, and monopoly paradigms.

9.2.1.2.1. Specialisation paradigm

In relation to specialisation paradigm, social exclusion reflects discrimination which prevents full participation in their society (Jenks, 2003). The findings show that people who live in Sitanala experienced discrimination that impacted their full participation in the society. They were discriminated against in almost all aspects of life. In the economic aspect, the participants mentioned that most of the persons affected by leprosy were refused employment or lost their jobs because of having leprosy. This phenomenon of Job loss leads to brutal consequences on their finances. They live in extreme poverty, with few opportunities of earning income and end up as beggars and begging is their main source of income. For example, there was a lady who was working in a mall. However, after knowing her as a former leprosy patient, her boss fired her without any clear reasons. The participants also mentioned about their healthy daughters who worked and were fired due to their parents having leprosy. Socially, they experienced discrimination when going to the mosque for worship. People around them considered persons affected by leprosy as unclean. So, when they came for worship, people immediately left. Another example is that many persons affected by leprosy lost custody of their children and were forced by their spouse's family to divorce. In accessing medical services, they were often refused treatment as leprosy patients. Participants also reported that even in Sitana leprosy

hospital, the health workers categorised their healthy family members into the ward for leprosy patients. It is likely that the hospital was worried many persons affected by leprosy will visit patients and scare non-leprosy patients. White (2008) illustrated these phenomena as *iatrogenic stigma* (stigma produced by the attitude and behaviours of professional health workers).

9.2.1.2.2. Solidarity paradigm

From the solidarity paradigm, social exclusion is basically a structural process caused by malfunctioning of social institutions that leads to the breakdown of the social cohesion and fragmented social relation (Room, 1995). The findings show that participants experienced social estrangement and progressive loosening of social bonds with their families and communities. Kaur and van Brakel (2002b) called this as *dehabilitation*. They who live in Sitanala were discarded by their family and people in their villages. The participants called themselves as *barang bekas* (second-hand goods) or *barang sortir* (rejected goods) due to their disfigurement and loss of limbs; that is why their family and people in their community rejected and discarded them. From this point, persons affected by leprosy who lived in the Sitanala leprosy colony, worked as beggars, became alcoholic, used drugs, and even committed suicide, basically due to lack of social support from the community. This means the community has failed to deal effectively with leprosy.

9.2.1.2.3. Monopoly paradigm

Monopoly paradigm views society as hierarchical and a different group control the resources and creates barriers to other groups (Appasamy et al., 1996). The findings show that due to leprosy stigma and discrimination, persons affected by leprosy experience difficulties in accessing occupations, cultural resources, goods, and services, such as public transportation, healthcare facilities, restaurants, and accommodation, which further marginalises them. Moreover, the local regulations that prohibit persons affected by leprosy from being on the streets, green belts, parks, and other public places, show how this monopoly paradigm works to exclude people in Sitanala.

Based on these paradigms, persons affected by leprosy were marginalised by general society as their rights were violated, access to resources were restricted and they experienced progressive loosening of social bonds with their families and communities. This fits with de Haan and Maxwell (1998) statement that rights, resources and relationships/networks have three common elements to identify social exclusion.

9.2.1.3. Gender issues of women with leprosy

Issues of women with leprosy are rarely discussed by scholars who have researched the topic of leprosy (Arole et al., 2002; Salodkar et al., 2000; Shale, 2000; Vlassoff et al., 1996). The findings show that women were in double jeopardy because of leprosy and gender. For example, a woman who had leprosy was not allowed to seek medical treatment as her husband felt that nobody would do domestic chores when she went to Sitanala. After a long delay in going to Sitanala, her condition was getting worse and her neighbours started to isolate her. When she decided to go to Sitanala, she was punished by her husband with divorce and loss of custody of her children. This phenomenon reflects the strong patriarchal culture in Indonesia.

In Indonesian society, especially in Java, the patriarchal culture is very strong, and all decisions are made by the husband as the head of the household. It can be illustrated by the saying 'Swargo nunut neroko katut', a wife should follow her husband to go to heaven or even to hell. When a man is considered as the bread winner in Java, a woman must do specific domestic roles such as *macak* (dress up), *masak* (cooking) and *manak* (delivering babies); whilst in other communities, they called these domestic roles as *sumur* (washing clothes), *dapur* (cooking) and *kasur* (bed, the sexual relationship). In relation to this, Butler (1993) mentioned that the perceptions of a woman's body are created, constructed, and imposed through cultural norms. Thus, the hegemonic culture appears in the language and accepted universally (Butler, 1990). According to LeMoncheck (1985), women are systematically sexualised by men in a way that dehumanises women. Similarly, Wollstonecraft (1974) entitled this phenomenon as insulted practices over women.

9.2.2. Examination of findings through critical disability theory

Critical theory has been employed in the study of disability. This section discusses findings through some critical areas in relation to leprosy and disability issues in the Sitanala leprosy colony. In this analysis, the researcher will use Hosking's work. Hosking identified areas of critical disability such as models of disability, multidimensionality, valuing diversity, rights, voice, language, and transformative policy (Hosking, 2008).

9.2.2.1. Models of disability

The findings show that moral and medical models are still dominant in viewing disability due to leprosy. Participants revealed that being disabled because of leprosy is basically a human tragedy. It is common in Indonesia that people including persons affected by leprosy themselves view their disability as a sin and shameful, based on religious mythology. Through this model, persons affected by leprosy become the perfect object of charity and pity. Yet, even though the medical model took over from religion in the explanation of disability, this model sees the disability as 'diseases' or 'illness'. Therefore, this model labels the persons affected by leprosy as a sickness that need to be 'fixed', and a menace for themselves and society. As a result, it is seen to be excusable to conceal and exclude individuals who have a disability from general society and restrict them from social circles. This explains why the Sitanala leprosy colony exists and people who live there have limited access and inadequate services. This model contributes to making persons affected by leprosy powerless and controlled by 'professionals'.

According to Oliver (1990), the social model should be used to define disability. This model views disability as a problem that is constructed by an oppressive and discriminatory society that limits activities and restricts full participation in society. However, in Indonesia, this model is only popular at the elite level and tends to be used as jargon and rhetoric for some activists. Although the Indonesian government nationally has successfully ratified the *Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities* through Law No. 19/2011, the implementation of the contents is still far away from what is expected. In short, the moral and medical models in viewing

disability are more dominant in viewing disability due to leprosy, compared to the social model.

9.2.2.2. Multidimensionality

It is acknowledged that disability has many intersections with other issues in relation to oppressed and vulnerable groups (Hosking, 2008; McDonald et al., 2007). The findings show that women affected by leprosy in Sitanala experienced discrimination more than men, not only because of their leprosy, but also because they are women. Some participants also mentioned that persons affected by leprosy who came from wealthy families did not experience much discrimination compared to those who are poor. This was also the case with those who have a good job and education, such as civil servants or Islamic teachers. Older people with a disability due to leprosy also experience more discrimination in obtaining a job, as some people think that they are no longer productive. A case which illustrates this is, when a Tangerang government official asked a woman to retire because of her age. To conclude, the leprosy disabled can be marginalised and oppressed in many other ways, due to class, gender, low education, disability and age, ethnicity, race, sexuality, culture, and language.

9.2.2.3. Valuing diversity

It is common that society usually thinks that something different to 'normal' is something that is deviant and 'abnormal'. The idea of valuing diversity as a strength is foreign. Critical disability theory requires a way of thinking that everyone is an individual and different (Campbell, 2002; Hosking, 2008). However, in the context of Sitanala community, participants revealed that instead of celebrating diversity, people outside Sitanala often rejected and humiliated them for their disability. This can be seen through discrimination and the barriers they are created to restrict them from fully participating in the society. The Sitanala leprosy colony is basically the antithesis of valuing diversity.

It is true that in reality there is a 'dilemma difference', questioning whether we should acknowledge and respond to the difference or ignore it. The answer depends on the context, equality objectives become important whether we will acknowledge and

respect the difference or ignore it. In brief, the principle of the best interests of disabled people becomes the key to solving the dilemma. In relation to valuing diversity, participants believed that much homework needs to be done as the policy makers and executives did not value the diversity, and they did not visit Sitanala.

9.2.2.4. Rights

The findings show that persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala were subject to multiple and aggravated human rights violations, including both their individual and social rights. The general community often deny their rights in all aspects, such as economic, social, and political aspects. Even the local regulation has constrained the disabled from entering public space and services. Violations of human rights are influenced by their lack of education, limited or no access to information and lack of control over their own lives. To respect, promote and fulfil their rights, the legal policy should become a tool for equality, promoting integration in all aspects, valuing and welcoming diversity, and all social intervention should be based on a rights approach (Banks & Kayess, 1998; Barnes & Mercer, 2006; Bellamy, 1998; Hanley, 1998; Yeo & Moore, 2003).

9.2.2.5. Voice

Voice is an important aspect in the concept of disability, the potential and role of the disabled. It is common that this voice is often marginalised and suppressed by able bodied people. Therefore, all discourses about disability are dominated by able-bodied perspectives (Hosking, 2008; Scott-Hill, 2002).

The findings show that persons affected by leprosy never have any chance to speak on their own behalf. This can be seen when there is a meeting with the policy makers, the disabled have never been invited. Most participants who live in Sitanala admitted that they never met people who asked about their voice, like the researcher did. They were forced to be silent by their circumstances.

That is why in the first informal introduction with them, they often said that the government is good, all is fine, and repeated it several times. However, after

explaining by the researcher that this research required genuine voices rather than fake voices, some of them voiced their opinion with angrily, some people expressed it with sad face, and many of them were crying during the interview process. They said that they have kept their voices silent for decades. However, to hear these genuine voices an interviewer must get their trust, otherwise they will only hear 'goody-goody talk' from them. They do this because they are worried that speaking the truth will anger the authority.

9.2.2.6. Language

Language influences the concept of disability and status of disabled people. Therefore, it is important to understand the words used in describing and labelling; and the words and images used to portray disability. This is because these words are basically political and reflect the ideology of the society. Labelling usually uses negative attributes and it leads to negative connotations. That is why using neutral words such as disabled people, people with disability and the disabled community are more appropriate (Hosking, 2008; Longmore, 1985; Zola, 1993).

The findings show that persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala have been portrayed using inappropriate words, such as leprosy sufferer, zombie, monster, *barang bekas* (*second hand goods*) and *barang sortiran* (*damage goods*). In other words, they have been portrayed as deficient, pitiable, wicked, malign, dangerous, and valueless. These words make the people in Sitanala powerless, vulnerable, and dependent.

9.2.2.7. Transformative policy

The critical theory of disability tries to link theory and practice. In this context, the theory is not just for the joy of theorisation, but rather self-consciously politicized theory. The theory is not just to improve understanding and explanation. The theorisation itself should emphasise empowerment and equality (Hosking, 2008; Oliver & Zarb, 1989). The findings show that many research projects conducted in Sitanala are from a medical perspective, and if not, are usually focused on clinical psychology, such as social adjustment and self-esteem of persons affected by leprosy.

It is rare to find research in Sitanala that aims to create a policy of inclusion and contributes to enhanced policy effectiveness for people affected by leprosy.

9.2.3. Examination of findings through community empowerment and social inclusion theories

The concepts and theories of community empowerment and social inclusion have influenced practice and policy in public human services. It is important to analyse to what extent policy makers and practitioners have used the concepts and theories of community empowerment and social inclusion.

9.2.3.1. Program management and role of outside agents

Program management that empowers the community should increase their control over decisions of planning, implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and finances. To do this it requires outside agents. Outside agents play an important role in community empowerment and the social inclusion program. According to Dr Arole (cited in Nicholls & Smith, 2002), the role of outside agents should be as enablers and not providers. As enablers, they are expected to facilitate the community members' involvement in designing, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating the CESI programs. They also need to transform the power over the control of decisions and resources by transferring their responsibility to the community members through a systematic capacity building.

In relation to the CESI program in Sitanala, many outside agents take a role as providers rather than enabler. There are no efforts to involve people in Sitanala in designing, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating programs (see Table 6.5). Consequently, the programs tend to see people in Sitanala as objects, not subjects. The outside agents take a position as experts and put Sitanala people as only service users.

By taking the position as experts, the outside agents create an unequal power relationship with people in Sitanala. Therefore, this kind of practice has the potential to destruct the essence of the CESI program. This is because CESI program entails the

equal relationship between the outside agents and the beneficiaries. The unequal relationship also contributes to silencing or at least ignoring the voices of Sitanala people.

9.2.3.2. Organisational structure

Organisational structure is a vital aspect that influences the implementation of CESI programs. It is believed that the organisational structure should have fewer levels of ranks and hierarchy. This aims to diminish the barriers of information toward all organisation members. With fewer levels of ranks and hierarchy, it also avoids the barrier in presenting ideas and voices of the members (Laverack & Wallerstein, 2001).

Learning from the Sitanala case, Table 6.5 shows that most organisations have many levels of ranks and hierarchy. For example, the organisational structure of PKK that is led by the wives of head of village, head of subdistrict, mayor, governor and president. In addition, under the wife of head of village, there are wives of head of citizen association (RW) and neighbourhood association (RT). Therefore, the members of PKK face difficulties in voicing their aspirations as communication is just instruction from the upper levels. This organisational structure also reflects and strengthens bureaucracy. Often many organisations need to work with groups in the community. Instead of using existing groups, they prefer to build new groups. Usually they create new groups instantly to save their time. Thus, the leaders who should be chosen by the members, are in fact determined by organisations. As a result, the structure of the groups is unclear and vulnerable to collapse.

9.2.3.3. Leadership

In the CESI program, local leaders have significant roles to make the program successful. This is because the local leaders liaise between community and government organisations and/or non-government organisations. The local leaders also help in decision making that affects all community members. The role of local leaders (that is also important to the community) is to monitor and evaluate CESI programs (Laverack & Wallerstein, 2001).

Even though the local leaders are key people that need to be approached by organisations to make the program successful, reality is that these people often become barriers and threats to the implementation of CESI programs. This is because many of them are basically the elites of the community. Since many CESI programs are associated with aid, some local leaders will only support and help the organisations, if they benefit from the program. This can be illustrated by the fact that the former head of the neighbourhood in Sitanala used to reject the CESI programs because the organisation refused to give administration fees to him. On a small scale, the organisations faced difficulties in obtaining data about persons affected by leprosy from him.

In relation to this, the organisations should be careful in choosing the local leaders with whom they will work. This is because not all local leaders want to take advantage of CESI programs. To know the good local leaders, the best way is to ask the members of community directly before determining with whom they will work. This assumes that those who really know about community is the community itself.

9.2.3.4. Problem assessment and critical assessment

Problem assessment is a crucial stage in the community empowerment and social inclusion program. The assessment should explore the real problems that are faced by the community and identify their needs. Accuracy in problem assessment will influence the success of CESI intervention. It is important to facilitate a community to do the assessment through a solution-oriented approaches rather than a problem-oriented approaches. This is because commonly a problem-oriented solution makes the community members pessimistic, unproductive, and angry. In contrast, a solution-oriented approaches will help them see more options to solve the problem (Laverack & Wallerstein, 2001).

However, the reality shows that few organisations involved in Sitanala in problem assessment. This can be seen from the case, in which mothers in Sitanala said that they need vocational training about making cake. However, instead of organising cooking training, the provider organised sewing training. This shows that the

organisation ignores the aspirations of people in Sitanala during problem assessment. In other words, the organisation refused to listen the voices of Sitanala people.

One of the purposes in implementing CESI program is to facilitate marginalised people to be able to express their critical thinking about information that has relation to their community. In the past, there were some people in Sitanala that often expressed their critical thinking. However, after expressing their views and ideas, they were blacklisted as beneficiaries. Since then, people prefer to be silent because they did not want to make trouble with the donors.

9.2.3.5. Networking and mobilisation of resources

Networking is basically agreements and actions made by consenting organisations to accomplish mutual goals. Building partnerships and establishing networks require sharing resources, such as finance, knowledge, and people (Laverack & Wallerstein, 2001). However, Table 6.5 shows that the Sitanala community face obstacles in establishing networks due to unreliable funding.

Mobilisation of resources is an effort to solve community problems. The forms of resources could be money, materials, support from volunteers, social services, etc. Mobilising resources requires social and political action. Thus, the community should be taught skills in communication and negotiation, including skills in making proposals. However, the implementation of the CESI program in Sitanala shows that there is no transfer of skills in communication, negotiation and even in making proposals.

9.2.3.6. Participation

According to WHO (2002a), participation refers to the action to become actively and genuinely involved in social, economic, political, and cultural aspects in society. In the context of CESI program in Sitanala, many cases show that:

- People in Sitanala had tried to express their aspirations when the organisers asked about the kinds of vocational training that is suitable for them. However, the organisers provided different kind of vocational training.

- Even though the vocational training did not fit with the potential and interests of Sitanala people, they still joined the training and pretended to be happy with the programs
- People in Sitanala were forced to master many skills and joined some vocational trainings because they did not want to be in any trouble with the organisers.

According to Pawar (2005), the first case reflects pseudo participation, whilst the second and third cases reflect unreal and coerced participation. Thus, from the continuum of participation perspective, these kinds of participation can be categorised as manipulation (Anscombe, 2005).

9.3. Grounded theorising the findings based on field data: Paternalism in human service practice

Chapter 8 has presented the perceptions and experiences about CESI programs in Sitanala. However, this chapter raises a big question mark regarding the poor implementation of the programs. How can the good design of CESI programs become so discriminative, insensitive, and unprofessional? To get an answer for this question, we should look at the bureaucracy system in Indonesia.

Bureaucracy in Indonesia is strongly coloured by the Javanese culture. This culture is characterised by social class hierarchy. Like the Javanese kingdoms in the past, the leader is associated with the king and superior, whilst the staff is associated with the commoner and subordinate. In this context, the leader is a person with higher class and the staff is a person with lower class. In paternalistic leadership, the leader is the protector and patron, while the staff represents dependence and clients (Dwiyanto & Kusumasari, 2001a; Mahar, 1998).

In the context of human services, paternalism views the service provider as patron and the beneficiary as client. This means the beneficiary has a weaker position compared to service provider (Dwiyanto & Kusumasari, 2001a). The findings show that paternalism considers people in Sitanala as the lowest class in society due to

several factors such as beneficiary, poverty, leprosy, disability, job (beggar) and sex (women). The last factor is related to a patriarchal culture that sees women as subordinate to men. From this point, it is clear that the status of people in Sitanala is categorised as the lowest class.

Figure 9.1
Paternalism Views Sitanala People as the Lowest Class

In relation to public services, paternalism has the potential to lead lack of accountability (Dwiyanto & Kusumasari, 2001b). The implementation of the CESI program in Sitanala shows that many social providers do not consider whether their programs are categorised as managed from the top-down, unsustainable, incidental, not transparent or lacking in accountability. This is because as clients, the beneficiaries realise their position is subordinate to the social providers. They will not ask too much of their patron, otherwise the social provider will blacklist them or in an extreme circumstance, they will leave Sitanala and move their programs to another location. If their programs failed, the social provider can easily blame the beneficiaries. They make all decisions related to the programs and beneficiaries. Critics of social providers can be interpreted as rude, impolite, and not Javanese. Paternalism also implies the customs *Asal Bapak Senang (ABS)* (Pleasing the Boss). Social providers want to be heard, but when they hear the beneficiaries' expression, they will have no response to the beneficiaries. Usually, even though the beneficiaries

feel that the social providers are unprofessional, uncommitted, and inconsistent; they will take it for granted. This explains why programs in Sitanala from time to time are similar without any improvement, and the social providers work as usual. This also explains why people in Sitanala are afraid to speak freely and preferred to be silent.

The findings also show that paternalism also contributes to poor public administration. It makes the services low in quality, disorganised and messy. The system is also slow to respond to complaints in relation to exclusion errors and inclusion errors. The services also tend to be trapped into *Korupsi, Kolusi, Nepotisme (KKN)* (Corruption, Collusion, Nepotism). From this point, paternalism hinders the success human services and public administration.

The profession of social work has a close tie with persons affected by leprosy, as one of its fields of practice is people who are subjected to discrimination and oppression. Social work aims to promote social change and development, social cohesion, and the empowerment and liberation of people (IFSW, 2014). However, almost all practitioners who work in the CESI programs in Sitanala are unqualified social workers. This can be illustrated that in 1984 there were only two 'social workers' in Sitanala Leprosy Hospital. However, instead of acting as professional social workers, they were working as instructors (vocational trainers) and did not have proper qualifications in the field of social work. Currently, there are 4 'social workers' who are high school graduates who also acted as a vocational training instructor. This situation is illustrated by Pawar (2012a), who states that in developing countries including Indonesia, social workers are fewer, both in terms of quantity and quality. Thus, many people think that anyone can be a social worker even without special education and training.

What is learnt from the implementation of CESI program in Sitanala, is that many unqualified social workers lack knowledge about the issues of community empowerment and social inclusion. According to WHO (2015b), community empowerment refers to *'the process of enabling communities to increase control over*

their lives'; whilst social inclusion can be defined as *'the process of improving the terms for individuals and groups to take part in society'* (World Bank, 2013). Based on these definitions, CESI program requires enhancement of access, capacities, and assets for individuals and groups within community, so that they can actively participate in economic, social, cultural, and political aspects of life.

Many unqualified social workers claim that they have implemented CESI programs in Sitanala. However, most of these practitioners only provide some vocational training and leave the community when the training is finished. Similarly, some practitioners that give seed and start-up capital, then leave the community immediately, stating that they have already implemented CESI program. Ironically, unqualified social workers that deliver food aid incidentally also claim that it is a CESI program. The misconception about community empowerment and social inclusion is that it assumes that CESI programs are merely economic intervention matters. Thus, through incidental and instant programs, they ignore the truth that community empowerment and social inclusion is a long process that requires sustainability as the spirit of program.

Community empowerment and social inclusion are popular jargon that are widespread among practitioners. This means that the true meaning of community empowerment and social inclusion has been eroded, and distorted, and a lack of knowledge about these concepts causes the poor implementation of the CESI programs in Sitanala. This explains why the impact of CESI programs in Sitanala is very low.

According to Reamer (2006), there are four basic principles in social work that need to be considered by social workers. Those principles are: (1) the individual is unique; (2) has human dignity; (3) equal opportunity; and (4) self-determination. Many unqualified social workers who work in Sitanala also seem to ignore these principles. For example, they do not want to shake hands with people in Sitanala; only select beneficiaries from Sitanala people that really are close to them; generalise all people

in Sitanala are lazy; and force people in Sitanala to participate in their vocational program.

Many practitioners in Sitanala also have a lack of skills in community work practice. This can be seen from their difficulties in engaging with the community, assessing their problems and needs, formulating plans of intervention, implementing plan of intervention, monitoring, and evaluating. Therefore, many of them skip the stage of community work practice such as assessing community problems and needs. These practitioners do not know that needs assessment is a vital stage in the helping process. The practitioners also faced difficulties in performing skills in relation to their roles as enabler, facilitator, and agent of change. Since the unqualified social workers do not know about the skills required, the programs become disorganised and the beneficiaries have difficulty understanding the aims and purposes of the programs.

Unqualified social workers contribute to the low impact of CESI programs in Sitanala. This is because their practices in the CESI programs are not supported by a body of knowledge, a body of values or a body of skills in social work. Furthermore, unqualified social workers combined with paternalism endanger the success of CESI programs in Sitanala.

People in Sitanala are powerless due to stigma and discrimination. Consequently, they have limited access and control of resources. In contrast, the elites in Sitanala control key institutions, such as media, education, political party, social policy, bureaucracy, parliament, profession, and so on. Based on elitist perspective of power, the Sitanala community reflects a hierarchal society, in which only certain groups hold power and control (Mayo & Craig, 1995). From the structural perspective of power, the paternalism in the Sitanala community reflects structural inequality or oppression. Ife and Tesoriero (2006) note that the elites as a dominant group usually tend to reinforce structural inequality. Based on these points of views, empowerment becomes crucial as it aims to increase the power of the disadvantaged. Thus, instead of 'power over, Ife and Tesoriero (2006) believe that 'power to' and 'power with' fit with the spirit of community empowerment.

Through the social inclusion theory, the Sitanala people are having difficulties to have full and fair access to services and activities. According to Abbott and Mcconkey (2006), social inclusion aims to increase the greater participation in community-based activities and a broader social network within communities. In this context, people in Sitanala should have many bonding and bridging relationships. This is because those who are excluded from society often have few bonding relationship, whilst bridging relationships are limited and poorly developed (Annison, 2006).

Social inclusion and empowerment are the main methods used to achieve socially sustainable development in Sitanala; and they are basically complementary and mutually reinforcing approaches. Using the assumption that a society is a product of people and institutions, empowerment and social inclusion is the best approach to achieve inclusive and accountable institutions.

Empowerment tries to enhance assets and capabilities of individuals and groups, and to influence and hold accountable the institutions that affect their lives. Empowerment aims to help poor and socially excluded individuals to realise the power they gain from collective action based on social mobilisation. This approach usually works 'from below' to create a voice and demand for change among diverse groups of poor and socially excluded citizens. In reverse, social inclusion works 'from above' and aims to remove institutional barriers to increase the access of individuals and groups to assets and development opportunities (Bennet, 2002).

Regarding the community empowerment, Powell (2001) states that community empowerment is both a goal and a process for overcoming social exclusion and cultural disrespect. The process of community empowerment can be considered as a dynamic continuum involving: (1) personal empowerment; (2) development of small mutual groups; (3) community organization; (4) partnership; and (5) social and political actions (Jackson et al., 1989; Labonte, 1989; Rissel, 1994). Thus, Laverack (1999) mentions that each points of this continuum can be viewed also as an outcome. In this context, individual change is a prerequisite for social change (Wilson,

1996). However, the findings show that many social providers in Sitanala often ignore and skip the process to gain the quick result. Consequently, many small mutual groups are not cohesive and easily broken before achieving social and political actions stage.

The findings also show that during the implementation of CESI program in Sitanala, many social providers did not pay attention to the capacity building and participation. Therefore, the ability of individuals, organisation or system did not increase significantly. Regarding this, Brown et al. (2001); Labonté and Laverack (2001); Laverack and Wallerstein (2001) believe that capacity building is important part of empowerment as organising and mobilising individuals, groups and communities will help to achieve social and political changes; whilst participation enables people to learn new skills, gain confidence, and develop their own voices and ability to control their lives (Minkler & Wallerstein, 2004).

Figure 9.2 shows the phenomena of paternalism and unqualified social worker that could have negatively impact to the implementation of the CESI program in Sitanala. In reverse, community empowerment and social inclusion program with strong participation and capacity building could also reduce paternalism in Sitanala and improve professionalism of social workers.

Figure 9.2
Paternalism and Unqualified Social Worker
in the CESI Program

Figure 9.3 shows the intervention approach with people affected by leprosy and disability in Sitanala. It can be seen from the figure that capacity building and participation are the motors in the CESI program, as well as to minimise the paternalism and unprofessional community workers. This intervention requires: (1) social model in viewing disability; (2) basic principles in social work; (3) high social mobility; (4) policies and institutions changes; in enhancing capacities, assets, and access to achieve well-being.

Figure 9.3
Intervention Approaches with People Affected by Leprosy and Disability
in Sitanala

9.4. Conclusion

This chapter has explored findings with existing theories. These findings have been examined through social stigma, social exclusion, critical disability, community empowerment and social inclusion theories. Thus, theorising findings based on field data has been formulated to answer the main factors that cause low impact of CESI programs in Sitanala.

Using social stigma and social exclusion theories, the findings are consistent with previous research, in which there are three factors that influence leprosy stigma: (1) Traditional beliefs and religious views; (2) Lack of knowledge and understanding about leprosy; and (3) Grading of disability and deformity. Thus, leprosy stigma leads to social exclusion. In relation to the gender issues, women with leprosy were in double jeopardy because of leprosy and gender.

Through critical disability theory, the findings show that the moral model and the medical model still dominate in viewing disability. Persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala were subject to multiple human rights violations, including both their individual and social rights. They were forced to be silent by their circumstances. Persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala have been portrayed using inappropriate words. These words are 'powerless, vulnerable and dependent.'

Examination of findings through community empowerment and social inclusion shows that the success CESI programs are influenced by six factors. Those are: (1) Program management and role of outside agents; (2) Organisational structure; (3) Leadership; (4) Problem assessment and critical assessment; (5) Networking and mobilisation of resources; and (6) Participation.

Grounded theorising the findings based on field data reveals that paternalism and unqualified social workers/community workers contribute to the low impacts of CESI program. Thus, if these phenomena continue, it will endanger the community of Sitanala. To deal with the paternalism and unqualified social worker/community workers, intervention approaches with people affected by leprosy and disability in Sitanala should have strong capacity building and participation.

'There is no Them. There are only facets of Us.'

(John Green)

Chapter 10: Conclusion and recommendations

10.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the overall findings and significance of the research. The first section will critically examine core findings and arguments in relation to research questions. It will also discuss limitations and strengths of the study, as well as the implications and directions for future research.

10.2. Conclusion in relation to research question

The aims of this research are to:

1. Explore the leprosy colony in Sitanala and its culture.
2. Consider the implementation of the community empowerment and social inclusion program in the leprosy colony and its use by people affected by leprosy.
3. Analyse the experiences and perceptions of people affected by leprosy about community empowerment and social inclusion program and its impact.
4. Contribute to the knowledge base about what key elements are required for a successful community empowerment and social inclusion program.
5. Suggest policy and practice implications for relevant stakeholders.

For this purpose, qualitative, ethnographic, and observational research methods were used to collect the field data.

The following research questions clarify the research focus:

1. What are the conditions of the leprosy colony and people living there?
2. How are the community empowerment and social inclusion programs implemented and what impacts does it have on the Sitanala community and people affected by leprosy?

10.2.1. Core findings for research question 1

The first research question is about the conditions of the leprosy colony and people living there with five associated sub-questions:

1. What is the origin and nature of the leprosy colony?
2. What are the current conditions in the leprosy colony?
3. How do people live there?
4. What is the leprosy colony's culture?
5. How do persons affected by leprosy sustain this colony?

10.2.1.1. The origin and nature of the leprosy colony

The Sitanala leprosy village has existed since 1950s. It began when persons affected by leprosy who had finished their medical rehabilitation in the Sitanala leprosy hospital, could not return to their homes because they were rejected by their families and communities. At that time, Dr Johannes Leimema, the Indonesian Minister of Health allowed the persons affected by leprosy to occupy a land behind the hospital called *Komplek Serba Guna* (KSG) (Multipurpose Complex). Starting from 3-5 families, the population persons affected by leprosy in this colony increased sharply. Considering the geographic location of Sitanala at that time, which was very quiet and the higher population of people with leprosy, people then called this colony as Sitanala leprosy village. Interestingly, many Sitanala people married to other persons affected by leprosy because they were traumatised of being abandoned and left by their spouses. Later, Sitanala leprosy village became a scary place to visit by general society.

10.2.1.2. The current conditions in the leprosy colony

The majority residents in Sitanala came from West Java and the rest are from Central Java, East Java and Jakarta. Those who are from outside Java are rare. Currently, there are five RTs (neighbourhood associations) in the Sitanala leprosy village. From those RTs, RT 01 is the poorest. This is because the residents of RT 01 are basically ex-transmigrants from Rangkas Bitung and Banyu Asin that returned to Sitanala in 1990s due to program failure. Different from RT 02-05, in which they build their-own house in the hospital land; the residents of RT 01 occupied old hospital's buildings and they

are not allowed to renovate it. Their houses are often leaky, almost falling and have lack of sanitation. People in Sitanala called people from RT 01 as new people and those who are from RT 02-05 as old-timer people who live in luxury. As old-timer people, they have good access to the resources because the citizen association office is located there.

10.2.1.3. Social and economic livelihoods of persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala

Most people who live in Sitanala work as unskilled labours in informal sectors such as scavengers, peddlers, street sweepers and rickshaw drivers. Even though they have a job, many of them are still begging during their leisure time. That is why people often refer Sitanala community as beggar village. People in Sitanala classified beggars into 'snail' who are begging from door to door; and 'Amen Factory' who are begging on the streets, traffic lights intersections, shops, or markets. Many people in Sitanala are entangled with moneylenders who lend an amount of money for a specific period with high interest and sometimes up to 50% per month. Regarding the stigma discrimination that still appear to them, some people also open small vendors inside the community so that they do not have to go outside to buy dairy goods.

10.2.1.4. The leprosy colony's culture

Due to frustration and embarrassment of being beggars, many people in Sitanala consume a hypnotic drug called *pil anjing* (dog's pill), which help to make them drunk. This pill is very cheap and with \$20 they can have 1,500 pills. Some of them consume insect repellent lotion and mix it with sort of Panadol and match heads until they are drunk; whilst the other consume cheap and low-quality of wine. In relation to their culture, they will examine through body language when they meet someone for the first time. It is important to note that people in Sitanala only offer foods or drinks for those who are willing to shake hand with them.

10.2.1.5. Ways to sustain the leprosy colony

People in Sitanala are very grateful that they can stay in Sitanala, since most of them are rejected by their families and communities. One of the ways to make the existing Sitanala leprosy village is by creating the solidarity among members of the

community and developing the spirit of togetherness. Thus, some social activities such as communal Islamic studies, centre for pre- and postnatal health care and information for women and for children and wedding help them to create the solidarity. They also develop some strategies to cope with stigma and discrimination, such as wearing gloves, covering their face and body with linen, riding bicycles, asking healthy people to help in selling their products, ordering take away food, buying dairy foods from small stalls inside the community and so on.

10.2.2. Core findings for research question 2

The first research question is about the implementation and its impacts of the community empowerment and social inclusion program in the Sitanala community with eight associated sub-questions:

1. What are the services relating to community empowerment and social inclusion programs in the leprosy colony?
2. How is the community empowerment and social inclusion program implemented?
3. How do people benefit from the program and services?
4. What are the experiences of persons affected by leprosy in receiving the community empowerment and social inclusion program?
5. What are their perceptions of the community empowerment and social inclusion program?
6. Does the community empowerment and social inclusion program empower this leprosy colony?
7. Does the community empowerment and social inclusion program facilitate participation in community activities?
8. What key elements are required to enhance the benefit of the community empowerment and social inclusion program to the community?

10.2.2.1. The services relating to the CESI programs in the leprosy colony

There were various organisations that contributed to the CESI program in Sitanala: (1) Central government; (2) Local government; (3) Faith-based organisation; (4) Community association; (5) University community service; (6) Non-government

organisation; and (7) Corporate social responsibility. They provided services in the Sitanala leprosy village, as follows:

1. Economic empowerment program:
 - Vocational Training Program.
 - Joint Business Group Program.
 - Productive Economic Business Program.
 - Microcredit Program.
2. Social empowerment program:
 - Youth Organisation Program.
 - Family Welfare Movement Program.
3. Political empowerment program:
 - Campaigns about leprosy anti-stigma.
 - Campaigns about the rights of persons with disabilities.
4. Social inclusion program.
 - Medical Social Security Program.
 - Learning House Program.
 - Scholarship Program.
 - Transmigration Program.
 - Street Sweeper Program.
 - National Sport and Art Week Program for People with Leprosy Program.
 - Sightseeing and Recreational Program (detailed can be seen on chapter 6).

10.2.2.2. The Implementation of CESI program

Program implementation refers to how well a proposed program or intervention is put into practice. The implementation of CESI program in Sitanala can be seen by the following structures: (1) program dissemination; (2) involvement of community members in problem assessment, plan of intervention, intervention, monitoring and evaluation; and (3) the role of facilitator.

10.2.2.2.1. Program dissemination

Program dissemination provides information to the community members about CESI program, in terms of purposes, goals, objectives, and working mechanism. This stage

is very important because it helps the community to know and understand the program. This activity is also important for community-based organisations because they will receive some feedback from the community in relation to the program. Based on the information from participants, there are no, or few programs disseminated in Sitanala. This activity, if any, is conducted partially and to certain people only. The information is circulated among the elites and it is usually not passed on to other members of the community. As a result, many community members have no adequate information about the program. Thus, this lack of information about the program creates confusion among beneficiaries. As an example, the KUBE program failed because the beneficiaries were confused, and they did not know much about the purposes and objectives of the program. Similarly, many people in Sitanala did not know that in Sitanala there was a microcredit program. Therefore, they were too late to access this program.

10.2.2.2.2. Community involvement in the CESI program

There are three patterns in the implementation of the CESI programs in Sitanala, as follows:

10.2.2.2.2.1. Through village office

The implementation of the CESI programs through the village office is characterised by inefficient government bureaucracy that produced a privileged group for those who have administrative power. The implementation of the programs emphasises administrative aspects rather than processes and field practices. This pattern usually does not provide room for the community to participate in decision making due to the top-heavy downward management approach and the gap in the relation of power. It is also slow to respond to any complaint from the community members. The unnecessary delay in decision making relating to the implementation of CESI programs often produces frustration among the community members.

10.2.2.2.2.2. Through local NGOs

The implementation of the CESI programs through the local NGOs is based on two main assumptions. First, NGOs are the organisations that are commonly accepted in

the society because it is associated with 'doing good'. Second, NGOs are the organisations that work at the grassroots level and it ensures that they understand the community well and how the system works in Sitanala. However, it seems people do not pay attention to the issue of trustworthy and untrustworthy NGOs. The untrustworthy NGOs are characterised by lack of commitment, transparency, and accountability. They are too dependent on donors and position themselves as aid distributors. Consequently, their activities fail when the donors stop the funds. In the context of Sitanala, the community members distrust local NGOs as many cases show that they tend to corruptly use the funds for their own interests. The local NGOs also often act as new rulers that offer promises but rarely fulfill them. In front of the donors they act as representatives of the community, whilst they are not. Their lack of commitment can be seen from the fact that they run NGOs as a side job.

10.2.2.2.3. Through local leaders

There are two types of local leaders. First, are the formal leaders who have a formal position in the bureaucratic and administrative structure. Those who can be categorised as the formal leaders are the head of neighbourhood associations, the head of citizen associations, the head of village, the teachers, the officials of local institutions and political officials. Second, the informal leaders are the commoners who are prominent in the community and have the quality, ability, and initiative to take the lead and give confidence to others.

In relation to the local leaders, Sitanala people prefer to work with local informal leaders. This is because there is a psychological barrier between them and the local formal leader due to the large gap in the power structure. They are also still traumatised due to the incident of a local formal leader who rejected donors from Sitanala.

10.2.2.2.3. Role of facilitator

The CESI program aims to increase community control over decisions of planning, implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and finances. Therefore, the role of facilitators is vital in the implementation of the CESI programs in Sitanala, as they are

expected to facilitate the community members to be involved in designing, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating the CESI programs. They also need to transform the power structure over the control of decisions and resources by transferring their responsibility to the community members through a systematic capacity building. Unluckily, in Sitanala, the outside agents seem to undervalue the role of facilitators in the CESI program. Thus, undervaluing the role of facilitators means ignoring the importance of the process and quality of the CESI programs. The outside agents also often provide facilitators who do not have competencies in working with the community. As a result, the community has a minimal contribution in problem assessment, planning of intervention, implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and finances.

10.2.2.3. The benefit from the program and services

Even though the implementation of the CESI programs is still far from the ideal, people in Sitanala still benefit from the program and services. In the economic empowerment program, the vocational training program equips people in Sitanala with knowledge, knowhow, skills, and competencies, to increase their economic standard of living. People in Sitanala acknowledge the benefits of this program, such as increasing knowledge and skills, improving performance and competencies, and increasing chances of employment. The productive economic business (UEP) provides seed and start-up capital for people in Sitanala to open a small business. It means Sitanala people benefit for having opportunities to start small businesses; and developing their entrepreneurship. The Joint business group (KUBE) develops the ability of people in Sitanala to solve their own problems and fulfil their daily needs through the joint business group. Sitanala people benefit from this program, as this program helps them to learn about organisational skills, increase interaction and social solidarity, encourage, and motivate them to establish self-help group, and to have opportunities in increasing their income. The microcredit provides small and low-interest loans without collateral for poor people in Sitanala. This program helps to eliminate reliance on moneylenders who offer high interest loans in Sitanala. People in Sitanala do benefit from this program by having opportunities to get low-

interest loans to start-up or expand their small businesses. They also benefit from this program as critical survival instrument for their households.

In the social empowerment program, Youth Organisation (Karang Taruna) aims to increase participation of youth in development programs. As a medium for communication and socialisation, Karang Taruna provide opportunities to young people to learn organizational skills, as well as to develop initiative and creative potentials of young people. The Family Welfare Movement Program (PKK) aims to increase participation of women in development programs, improve family welfare and educates the youngest generation. Like the Karang Taruna program, people in Sitanala benefit from the PKK program as this program provides a medium for communication and socialisation, opportunities for women in Sitanala to learn organizational skills, and to develop initiative and creative potentials of women.

Political empowerment is a long process and to implement proper political empowerment, requires skills and understanding of political process, political rights, and local political issues. The purpose of this program is for people in Sitanala to be able to influence the policy making process and participate in decision making. In relation to this, leprosy anti-stigma and the rights of people with disabilities campaigns, benefit Sitanala people, because it helps them to increase their knowledge and understanding about their rights.

In the social inclusion program, the Medical Social Security Program (Jamkesmas) provides free medical treatment and services for the poor. This program benefits people in Sitanala as this program increases the access of poor people into healthcare services. This program also contributes to reducing the expenditure for medical costs. The Learning house program help to increase the access of poor students to get informal education, by providing free tutorial and prevocational trainings for children in Sitanala. This program also helps the children to learn of being independent by increasing their life skills. In Indonesia, tuition fees for students in primary school, junior high school and senior high school are basically free. However, for students who do not pass the entry exam in public schools must study at private schools. Most

of children in Sitanala study at private schools. People in Sitanala feel that this education system is unfair for them. This is because the government only supports public schools, whilst the costs to send their children to private schools are very expensive. That is why the scholarship programs from Korean Tangerang Association and corporate social responsibility (CSR) of PT Pertamina are very useful to them, as it helps in reducing education costs for their children.

In the employment program, to increase access to employment for Sitanala people, in 1985 the Indonesian government tried to facilitate on-farm self-employment through a transmigration program. The Sitanala people benefited from this program because the government gave 2 acres of land for each family and provided living allowances for two years. This program also gave an opportunity for persons affected by leprosy to start a new life as farmers. Sitanala people acknowledged that the street sweeping program is a pro-disability program. This program provides permanent job as street sweepers for persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala. Therefore, they can earn some money and improve their standard of living. This program also contributes to increase their self-confidence and raise their self-esteem.

In the recreational program, the National Sport and Art Week (Porseptanas) provides opportunity for people in Sitanala to join into national sport and art events. Through this program, they could meet persons affected by leprosy from all provinces in Indonesia. This program helped them to increase their self-confidence, because they can perform their abilities in sports and arts. Porseptanas also strengthens the brotherhood among persons affected by leprosy, as well as providing free entertainment in sport and art. The sightseeing program facilitates persons affected by leprosy and their children to visit recreational places. This program benefits people in Sitanala, as it increases their access to public spaces. This program also increases their self-confidence to appear in recreational places without fear of discrimination. Some churches often organise kids stage performances, to entertain people in Sitanala. They benefit from this program because they can enjoy the entertainment through children's dance performance.

10.2.2.4. The experiences of persons affected by leprosy in receiving the CESI program

There is a growing recognition that a marginalised and disadvantaged community rarely has opportunities to make their voices heard. This is because their experiences have been ignored by many social scientists. Therefore, their experiences just become untold stories. In fact, learning from their experiences will give government and development actors invaluable data and real insight to improve their programs in the future. Some of the experiences of persons affected by leprosy in receiving the CESI programs in Sitanala are as follows:

1. Many CESI programs in Sitanala are implemented abruptly without proper dissemination and they end without any notice. As a result, the beneficiaries have lack of knowledge, low sense of belonging, and confusion about the programs.
2. Most CESI programs are 'top-down', in which the agendas are set by external organisations and the community is asked to support it. This planning model closes the opportunity for people in Sitanala to identify the issues on their own and to have control over planning decisions. Consequently, the programs often do not meet the community needs.
3. The CESI programs lack sustainability, evident by incidental and short-term programs. Making the Sitanala community aware of their problems and addressing them with temporary or incomplete measures can do more harm than good.
4. CESI programs are a long process. However, the external organisations often skip and shorten some steps due to impatience and expectations of instant results. Consequently, the quality of programs and services are very low.
5. Most CESI programs in Sitanala are partial and fragmented. Each external organisation carries out their own program and lacks coordination with other organisations. The programs also tend to undermine the holistic bio-psycho-socio-spiritual aspects.
6. Local elites who wield power do not really care about community welfare. They often take advantage of the CESI program for their own interests. For example, they tend to abuse their power by putting and prioritising their

family members, friends, and close neighbours on the list of beneficiaries. Local elites also often ask for an administration fee to external organisations that will implement their program in Sitanala.

7. Poor assistance from the community facilitators in the implementation of CESI programs. Most facilitators are unprofessional, uncommitted and have a lack of motivation to work with Sitanala people. This can be understood as the facilitators are basically unqualified social workers and many of them work as facilitators just as a stepping stone to getting a better job with higher salary or a scholarship to pursue higher studies. The facilitators and external organisations are superior as shown by the subordination of community to them.

10.2.2.5. [The perceptions of persons affected by leprosy about the CESI program](#)

The perceptions of persons affected by leprosy about the CESI programs in Sitanala are as follows:

1. Many people in Sitanala believe that the CESI program basically refers to the idea of 'one drug to rule them all'. The program does not match other social problems. For example, offering the Transmigration Program, that was originally designed for healthy people, to them is basically the embodiment of the idea 'one drug to rule them all'. This means whatever the problems, the interventions and approaches are the same. In this context, the government and external agents have ignored the uniqueness of each community and its problems. If this practice continues, people in Sitanala believe that it will only waste time, money, and energy. This is because the CESI programs have never changed from the beginning and ignore the aspirations of the Sitanala community members.
2. In the view of most persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala, CESI programs do not respect their human dignity. This can be seen from the lack of commitment of external organisations and facilitators in embracing and valuing diversity related to their disabilities. They feel that the external organisations and facilitators have treated them as commodities to get funding from donors. In their approach, the external organisations and facilitators also treated them as

mere recipients of aid. Many facilitators refuse to shake hands with them or drink and eat the food they have offered. Interestingly, the facilitators often do not know what to do. The facilitators are also changed quickly. Today is this person and on the next day a different person. The facilitators often leave the Sitanala people without any notice.

3. The majority people in Sitanala feel that the community members receive different treatment to access the CESI programs. The opportunity to join the programs or to become beneficiaries is not equal. For example, in vocational trainings, some community members have opportunities to join many types of training, whilst the other members do not. The inclusion and exclusion errors phenomena also show that some people in Sitanala still do not have equal opportunity to benefit the CESI program. Inclusion error refers to the inclusion of non-deserving candidates as beneficiaries of the programs. To the contrary, exclusion error refers to the exclusion of deserving candidates. This error happens because the government and external organisations failed to identify the beneficiaries.
4. Most Sitanala people were of the view that the CESI programs do not involve them in planning decisions because the external organisations have set the agendas for Sitanala community. This means people in Sitanala do not possess power to determine their own agenda and intentions. For example, in economic empowerment, many vocational training occupations have been determined by external agents. That is why in many cases, the CESI programs are not effective and fail to meet the needs of people in Sitanala. This is because they ignore the voices of people and do not support the rights of Sitanala people to determine and choose what programs are fitting for them.
5. People in Sitanala believe that the CESI programs are full of rhetoric. This is because they feel that the programs are basically no different from the old programs. The difference is only in using new terms like empowerment, participation, capacity building, etc. However, the practices of the CESI programs remain the same. In addition, by saying that the CESI programs are the community-driven development (CDD), any unsuccessful program becomes the fault of the community.

6. People in Sitanala agree that most of the CESI programs lack transparency and accountability. The lack of transparency and accountability are often characterised by the inaccessible administrative and financial reports, including the program's effectiveness at every stage of implementation. Thus, the program is at risk due to misconduct, corruption, ineffectiveness, and inefficiency. People in Sitanala believe that this happens because the external organisation does not provide space for social audit, does not involve them in the budgetary process as well as the monitoring budget execution or expenditure.
7. People in Sitanala criticise the CESI programs for not doing a job wholeheartedly and continuously. Many programs start when there are strong issues of leprosy because for example, there is a blow-up in the media or it is close to the World Leprosy Day. The CESI programs are also implemented with high enthusiasm only at the beginning when their programs are captured by the media.
8. Sitanala people admit that some organisations have good CESI programs. However, due to lack of funds and lack of government support, their programs are stopped and not well developed. They believe that the government should learn from their practices and provide assistance and support them.

10.2.2.6. Impact of the CESI program in empowering leprosy colony

As explained in the chapter 8, the CESI programs have a low impact in empowering persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala. This can be seen from the fact that there are no significant social and political changes resulting from the CESI programs. For example, the programs are unsuccessful in increasing their self-sufficiency, self-advocacy, competence, and self-worth. The CESI programs also failed to develop the voices of Sitanala people and to increase their ability to control their lives. As a result, they still live in poverty and work as beggars, they have no representation in political institutions nor government, and there is no structural change in the social institutions that disadvantaged them. The following details the impact of the CESI program in Sitanala:

10.2.2.6.1. Economic empowerment

The impacts of the economic empowerment programs in Sitanala are as follows:

1. In the vocational training program, most participants fail to master the skills. Furthermore, those who can master the skill, still have trouble in finding jobs.
2. In the UEP program, only few people receive stimulant aids from UEP and almost all small business closes due to lack of capital, competition with 'giants' and the fact that profit is less than their expenditure/consumption.
3. In KUBE program, the group is easily broken due to instant formation of the group. The group members are confused about starting the business group. As a result, the program failed to increase their income.
4. In microcredit program, only a few people have opportunities to get loans and this program forces borrowers into debt traps.

10.2.2.6.2. Social empowerment

The impacts of the social empowerment programs in Sitanala are as follows:

1. In the Karang Taruna program, the Karang Taruna failed to become a partner with the government and all stakeholders to address social problems in the community. It also lacks contribution in raising awareness on leprosy stigma and discrimination.
2. In PKK program, the PKK failed to accommodate and carry out aspiration of the community and it also lacks contribution in promoting family welfare in the community.

10.2.2.6.3. Political empowerment

The CESI programs have a low impact in political empowerment. This is because even though the community members have more understanding about their rights, they are still facing difficulties to influence the policy making process and participate in decision making. They are still a silent community that is vulnerable to oppression and is marginalised by policies and discriminatory practices. Even in the election, they did not dare to say that they needed an assistant to help them to pierce the candidate pictures on the paper. The papers are still blank, and they just put the papers in the box because they could not pierce the papers with their fingers due to

their disability. Consequently, the papers are considered invalid. It means, they had lost their rights to choose in the election. The CESI programs have low impact in political empowerment as they are not able to represent in the government.

Apart from poor implementation, the CESI programs have difficulty in achieving their goals because it is not supported by good non-CESI programs. These programs, unluckily, are not available in Sitanala. Therefore, the profits of their business are used for consumption instead of developing their business.

10.2.2.7. Impact of the CESI program in facilitating participation in community activities

It is a fact that the more people feel empowered, they are more likely to participate. People in Sitanala have low genuine participation rate in making decisions about planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation. Thus, participation in the policy making processes and the implementation of policies, programs and projects is basically pseudo, unreal, induced, coerced, partial and consumerist participation. The programs that are considered to have high impacts and facilitate participation in the health, employment, recreational and educational settings are Jamkesmas, Street Sweeper, Porseptanas, Sightseeing, Jamkesmas and Scholarship programs.

10.2.2.8. Key elements required to enhance the benefit of the CESI program to the community

The following are the key elements required to enhance the benefit of the CESI program:

1. An urgent paradigm shift in the community empowerment and social inclusion program:
 - from top-down approach to bottom-up approach;
 - from charity-based approach to right right-based approach;
 - from partial and fragmented approach to holistic and integrative approach;
 - from problem-oriented approach to solution-oriented approach.
2. Government commitment to fully support the CESI program, in terms of funding and guidance.

3. The importance of program sustainability in achieving goals.
4. Urgency to change the role of external agents from social providers to facilitator.
5. The need for strengthening the role of the facilitator in transferring skills and knowledge to mobilise resources, establish networking and build partnership.
6. The importance of anti-discriminatory practice in working with people in Sitanala.
7. The necessity of involving and getting support from good informal local leaders.
8. The importance of authentic, full, or democratic participation from the community members to have control over decisions of planning, implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and finances.

10.3. Limitations and strength of the study

10.3.1. Limitations of this study

This study is limited in three ways. Firstly, the data was collected by interviewing Sitanala community members, rather than external organisations. Therefore, this study missed the clarification from the external organisations. Secondly, translation of interviews is another limitation as when researcher translates from Bahasa Indonesia to English, it often loses the actual meaning. Lastly, bias in research can occur intentionally due to the background of the researcher as civil servant who works for the Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs.

10.3.2. Strengths of this study

The major strength of this research is that it was carried out at the grassroots level. It means the research grasps the voice of local people in Sitanala, free from dominant culture. This study also contributes to an understanding of the uniqueness of the leprosy colony in the Sitanala leprosy village based on the perspective of persons affected by leprosy. It also provides basic information about the leprosy colony, so that it can be used by other scholars who want to explore more about this community. Thus, through the qualitative method, this study will get a deeper understanding about the impact of community empowerment and social inclusion programs and all associated issues. Finally, through critical ethnographic study, this research provides an opportunity for participants to self-advocate about the issues and rumours that marginalised and disadvantaged them.

10.4. Implications of this research

This research has implications for theory, policy, and practice. The implications are derived from the research findings and support the significance of the study.

10.4.1. Implications for theory

This research in an implicit way, recognises the paternalistic culture in the practices of community empowerment and social inclusion in Sitanala. This culture is basically influenced by the Javanese culture, characterised by social class hierarchy of a patriarchal culture. The paternalism views unequal relation of power between two parties as the relation between 'father' and 'son' or 'patron' and 'client'. In this context, the client is subordinate to patron. The paternalism slowly transforms into the Indonesian bureaucracy. That is why, instead of serving people, many officials of government often act as those who have to be served, by the commoners. Even though, Indonesia since reformation era 1998 has successfully converted to a democratic system, the paternalism still widely appears in the Indonesian bureaucracy system.

Looking closely at the implementation of CESI programs in Sitanala, the relation of power between external organisations and Sitanala community is unequal. The influence of paternalism puts the external organisations as patron, whilst Sitanala people are considered as client. As a client, Sitanala people cannot question and criticise the programs. Any complaint from Sitanala people will be counted as unethical and rude. Consequently, misconduct practices such as unprofessional, uncommitted, inconsistent, discriminatory are often found in Sitanala. From this point, the paternalism that worships and enjoys inequality is contradictory to the spirit and philosophy of community empowerment and social inclusion program.

In Indonesia, a common assumption about social work is that, all people can easily claim that they are social workers, even without qualifications in social work education. This is because most people believe that social work is the same term as voluntary or charity activities, and social worker refers to social volunteer. As a result,

social workers/facilitators who work in the community development setting, do not even know what to do because they have no knowledge, values, and skills in social work. This explains why the facilitators are easily replaced. Together with paternalism, unqualified social workers potentially endanger the implementation of CESI programs. In other words, due to paternalism and unqualified community workers, the practice of the community empowerment and social inclusion program will go nowhere. Furthermore, blaming the community for program failure is the manifestation of these two factors. Therefore, these findings contribute to the future study of the manifestation of paternalism theory in human services setting.

10.4.2. Implications for policy

The findings of this study lead to some implications for policy as follows:

1. The Indonesian government should understand that only a few external organisations are concerned with persons affected by leprosy in Sitanala and should implement CESI programs in this community. However, many of them have lack of funds and appreciation. Thus, giving rewards to these organisations for their commitment and contributions to Sitanala people is very important. Incentive funding is a good reward to encourage and support the sustainability of their program.
2. To improve the quality of CESI programs in Sitanala, the Indonesian government, in this context is the Ministry of Social Affairs, should provide adequate training for developing staff and external organisations. It is good to involve the Indonesian Social Worker Association in organising the training. The Ministry of Social Affairs also needs to provide guidance books about the implementation of CESI program and related policies. This is because many guidance books piled up in the Province Social Office. Putting the electronic version of the guidance books in the Ministry of Social Affairs' website is the best way to do it.
3. Regarding the decentralisation and local autonomy issues, the Tangerang Social Office should be more active in increasing the coordination, collaboration and cooperation among actors that implement the CESI programs in Sitanala. Establish a joint secretary office as a place to meet and share information in a strategic way.

4. Many CESI programs conducted by NGOs are local small-scale programs at the micro level that can fail in wider economic and political context. The government can use this as lesson learned, scale up the programs and replicate it to other leprosy colonies.
5. In all the above four areas, social work and human services professionals can play important roles by contributing to organising and mobilising people and communities, lobby groups and advocacy, and policy formulation, implementation and evaluation.

10.4.3. Implications for social work practice

The research findings indicate implication for social work practice as follows:

1. The research findings urge the practitioners, including social workers to pay attention to paternalism and power between external organisations or facilitators and people in Sitanala as the beneficiaries, in implementing their programs in Sitanala. This is because failure to recognise this issue will lead to misconduct and practices that disadvantage people in Sitanala.
2. Communication is an important factor in engaging with the community. Therefore, disseminating program details early and often would be strategic to create a good connection between the Sitanala people and the CESI programs. Social workers can play an important role in these activities. It is good also to visit and give assistance frequently and directly to the groups in the community to establish support system in Sitanala.
3. It is important to facilitate the community members to have control over making decisions in program planning, implementing, monitoring, evaluation, and finances. This will help them in the future to involve with and influence government policies so that they are not disadvantaged.
4. The transforming of power from external organisations and facilitators through the transfer of knowledge, skills, and responsibility to the community, so that they have power to mobilise resources, establish networking and build partnership. This requires genuine participation and intense capacity building.

5. As the implementation of CESI programs is a long process that requires commitment, consistency, time, and energy; it would be good for external organisations to avoid the replacement of their facilitators very often and quickly.
6. The facilitators need to observe and identify thoroughly the local informal leaders in Sitanala community. The facilitators can ask the members of community about these natural leaders. The characteristics of the good local informal leader include: (a) able to take the lead and give confidence to other community members; (b) be educated and literate; (c) be reliable and attend regularly (d) innovative; and (e) trusted by community members. Getting support from them will be invaluable in implementation CESI programs.
7. Facilitators and external organisations need to use a flexible approach in implementing CESI program. The creativity to approach the community is important as 'one size doesn't fit all'.

10.5. Directions for future research

This research focuses on the impacts of CESI programs in the Sitanala leprosy colony. Even though the CESI programs have been conducted for a long time, the colony still exists, and they still live in poverty. The author believes that this study has revealed the solution. The paternalism and unqualified community workers play important roles in hindering the successful CESI programs.

This study has raised several questions that need to be answered in future studies. Do paternalism and unqualified community workers also contribute to lowering the quality of CESI programs in other leprosy colonies in Indonesia and among other nations? What model of CESI program is really fit to deal with the issues of poverty and social inclusion in leprosy colonies? To answer this, it needs to undertake a comparative research in leprosy colonies in Indonesia or Asian countries such as in Bangladesh and India. Thus, action research is needed to find a new model of CESI programs that meet the needs of persons affected by leprosy and to respect, protect and fulfil their rights. Drawing on their practice, social workers can provide new insights for research.

10.6. Conclusion

The study about the impact of the CESI program in the Sitanala leprosy village shows that people affected by leprosy encounter significant systemic barriers to full inclusion and participation in their community. The barriers that prevented full participation in society ranged from social to physical. Thus, inflexible laws, policies and practices play an important role in making the barriers more cultural and systemic. The study also reveals that the dominance of moral and medical models makes the barriers difficult to eliminate. Further, the analysis shows that lack of information of their disability and rights contribute to perpetuating the existing barriers. Finally, this research found that paternalism and unqualified community workers contribute to lowering the impacts of CESI programs in Sitanala. The findings have implications for all stakeholders, including the social work profession, government, non-government organisations and private sectors to provide a wider support through empowering and anti-discriminatory approaches.

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Appendices

Appendix A-1: Information Sheet for Participants (Focus Group Discussion)

SCHOOL OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES
FACULTY OF ARTS

Locked Bag 588
Boorooma Street

Wagga Wagga NSW 2678

Tel: +61 2 6933 2249

Research Project:

Community Empowerment and Social Inclusion Program at the Sitanala Leprosy Village, Indonesia

I wish to invite you to participate in my research on the above topic. The details of the study follow, and I hope you will consider being involved. My name is Arif Rohman and I work for the Ministry of Social Affairs. I am conducting this research project for my PhD at the Charles Sturt University. My supervisors are Professor Manohar Pawar, Associate Professor Wendy Bowles, and Dr Bill Anscombe of Charles Sturt University. Professor Manohar Pawar can be contacted by email at mpawar@csu.edu.au or by phone on +61 2 6933 2497. Associate Professor Wendy Bowles can be contacted by email at wbowles@csu.edu.au or by phone on +61 2 6933 2695. Dr Bill Anscombe can be contacted by email at csuhum@csu.edu.au or by phone on +61 2 6933 2631.

Aim of the Study:

This research aims to explore the experiences and perceptions of the members of Sitanala leprosy village about community empowerment and social inclusion program.

Time Requirements:

As a participant in this project you will be expected to take part in focus group discussion (FGD). The topic of discussion will be your experiences and perceptions about community empowerment and social inclusion program in Sitanala leprosy village. All answers, responses, and explanations will be recorded. The length of the discussion will be about 90 minutes.

Methodology:

The study will be qualitative in nature. The focus group discussion will last for approximately 90 minutes. There will be a series of open-ended questions that allow you to explore your views about community empowerment and social inclusion program.

These discussions will be audiotape recorded or electronically captured. Following the focus group discussion, a transcript will be provided to you if you wish to see one. You will be free to withdraw at any time throughout the process.

Participation is voluntary. You may withdraw from the project at any time prior to publication of results and there will be no disadvantage if you decide not to participate or withdraw at any time. However, because of the semi-public nature of the group process, anonymity and confidentiality cannot be guaranteed in a focus group setting and that individual contributions cannot be withdrawn if a decision is made to withdraw participation after the focus group has been held.

The audiotapes will be kept in a locked filing cabinet at the researcher's office until they are transcribed and then they will be destroyed. The transcriptions will be kept in the same manner for 15 years following thesis submission and then destroyed.

Research Process:

It is anticipated that this research will be completed by the end of December 2016. A copy of the research report in English and executive summary in Bahasa Indonesia will be provided to Head of the Sitanala Leprosy Village. The results may be presented at conferences and written up in journals or book chapters without any identifying information. Analysed data will be used for research training, policy and publication purposes.

Research Funding:

Data collection expenses are partially met by CSU Research Office and the chief of investigator. This project has been approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of Charles Sturt University (Approval No. 2013/171).

Should you have any complaints concerning the manner in which this research is conducted, please contact me or the Research Ethics Officer at the following address:

Arif Rohman
PhD Student in Social Work
School of Humanities and Social Sciences, Charles Sturt University
Locked Bag 678, Wagga Wagga, NSW, 2678, Australia
Tel: +61 2 693 32552
Email: arohman@csu.edu.au

or

The Executive Officer
Ethics in Human Research Committee
Academic Secretariat
Charles Sturt University
Private Mail Bag 29, Bathurst, NSW, 2795
Tel: +61 2 6338 4628
Fax: +61 2 6338 4194
Email: ethics@csu.edu.au

Thank you for considering this request and I look forward to further contact with you.

Regards

Appendix A-2: Information Sheet for Participants (Focus Group Discussion) in
Bahasa Indonesia

SCHOOL OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES
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Proyek Penelitian:

Program Pemberdayaan Masyarakat dan Inklusi Sosial di Kampung Kusta Sitanala, Indonesia

Saya ingin mengundang saudara sekaalian untuk berpartisipasi dalam penelitian saya dengan topik tersebut di atas. Rincian penelitian terlampir di bawah dan saya berharap saudara sekalian dapat mempertimbangkannya untuk terlibat dalam penelitian ini. Nama saya Arif Rohman dan saya bekerja di Kementerian Sosial. Proyek penelitian ini dilakukan untuk mendapatkan gelar Doktor di Charles Sturt University. Berikut adalah dosen pembimbing saya Professor Manohar Pawar, Associate Professor Wendy Bowles, dan Dr Bill Anscombe dari Charles Sturt University. Professor Manohar Pawar dapat dikontak pada email mpawar@csu.edu.au atau melalui telepon di nomor +61 2 6933 2497. Associate Professor Wendy Bowles dapat dikontak pada email wbowles@csu.edu.au atau melalui telepon di nomor +61 2 6933 2695. Dr Bill Anscombe dapat dikontak pada email csuhum@csu.edu.au atau melalui telepon di nomor +61 2 6933 2631.

Tujuan Penelitian:

Penelitian ini dimaksudkan untuk memahami pengalaman dan persepsi masyarakat di Kampung Kusta Sitanala terkait dengan program-program pemberdayaan masyarakat dan inklusi sosial.

Waktu yang Dibutuhkan:

Sebagai partisipan dalam proyek penelitian ini saudara diharapkan untuk berpartisipasi dalam diskusi kelompok terarah (FGD). Topik diskusi berhubungan dengan pengalaman-pengalaman serta persepsi mengenai program pemberdayaan dan inklusi social di sini. Semua jawaban, respon, penjelasan akan direkam. Lama diskusi kurang lebih 90 menit.

Metode Penelitian:

Penelitian ini adalah penelitian kualitatif. Diskusi kelompok bertujuan akan dilakukan selama 90 menit. Akan ada sesi tanya jawab yang memungkinkan saudara untuk menggali pandangan-pandangan terkait program-program yang ada.

Diskusi kelompok bertujuan yang akan dilakukan akan direkam. Terkait dengan diskusi tersebut, transkrip akan diberikan apabila ada yang ingin melihatnya. Saudara bebas untuk membatalkan keterlibatan saudara kapan saja selama proses berlangsung.

Partisipasi dalam penelitian ini sifatnya sukarela. Saudara bisa kapan saja mundur dari penelitian ini sebelum hasil penelitian diterbitkan, dan tidak akan ada yang dirugikan kapan saja saudara mengundurkan diri. Namun demikian, karena sifat diskusi kelompok yang semi publik, maka anonim dan kerahasiaan tidak dapat dijamin sepenuhnya dalam kerangka diskusi kelompok bertujuan dan kontribusi perseorangan tidak dapat dibatalkan jika keputusan tersebut diambil sesudah diskusi bertujuan dilakukan.

Rekaman diskusi kelompok bertujuan akan disimpan tertutup di tempat file kantor saya sampai selesai ditranskrip dan rekaman tersebut akan dimusnahkan. Transkrip akan disimpan dengan baik selama 15 tahun setelah thesis diserahkan dan selanjutnya dimusnahkan.

Proses Penelitian:

Perlu diperhatikan kemungkinan penelitian ini akan selesai pada bulan Desember 2016. Foto copy laporan penelitian dalam Bahasa Inggris dan Ringkasan Eksekutif dalam Bahasa Indonesia akan diberikan pada Kepala Kampung Kusta Sitanala. Hasil penelitian ini mungkin akan dipresentasikan dalam konferensi dan ditulis di jurnal-jurnal atau bab-bab buku tanpa menyebut nama. Analisis data akan digunakan untuk keperluan pelatihan penelitian, penyusunan kebijakan, dan publikasi.

Dana Penelitian:

Pengumpulan data pada penelitian ini dibiayai secara parsial oleh CSU Research Office dan peneliti sendiri. Proyek penelitian ini telah disetujui oleh Komite Etik Penelitian Kemanusiaan Charles Sturt University (No. Persetujuan 2013/171).

Jika saudara ingin menyatakan keluhan terkait perilaku pada saat penelitian ini dilakukan, saudara bisa menghubungi saya atau Komite Etik Penelitian Manusia pada alamat berikut ini:

Arif Rohman
PhD Student in Social Work
School of Humanities and Social Sciences, Charles Sturt University
Locked Bag 678, Wagga Wagga, NSW, 2678, Australia
Tel: +61 2 693 32552
Email: arohman@csu.edu.au

atau

The Executive Officer
Ethics in Human Research Committee
Academic Secretariat
Charles Sturt University
Private Mail Bag 29, Bathurst, NSW, 2795
Tel: +61 2 6338 4628
Fax: +61 2 6338 4194
Email: ethics@csu.edu.au

Terima kasih atas perhatian dan saya harap saudara dapat berpartisipasi dalam penelitian ini.

Salam hormat

Appendix A-3: Information Sheet for Participants (In-depth Interview)

SCHOOL OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES
FACULTY OF ARTS

Locked Bag 588
Boorooma Street

Wagga Wagga NSW 2678

Tel: +61 2 6933 2249

Research Project:

Community Empowerment and Social Inclusion Program at the Sitanala Leprosy Village, Indonesia

I wish to invite you to participate in my research on the above topic. The details of the study follow, and I hope you will consider being involved. My name is Arif Rohman and I work for the Ministry of Social Affairs. I am conducting this research project for my PhD at the Charles Sturt University. My supervisors are Professor Manohar Pawar, Associate Professor Wendy Bowles, and Dr Bill Anscombe of Charles Sturt University. Professor Manohar Pawar can be contacted by email at mpawar@csu.edu.au or by phone on +61 2 6933 2497. Associate Professor Wendy Bowles can be contacted by email at wbowles@csu.edu.au or by phone on +61 2 6933 2695. Dr Bill Anscombe can be contacted by email at csuhum@csu.edu.au or by phone on +61 2 6933 2631.

Aim of the Study:

This research aims to explore the experiences and perceptions of the members of Sitanala leprosy village about community empowerment and social inclusion program.

Time Requirements:

As a participant in this project you will be expected to take part in in-depth interview. The topic of interview will be your experiences and perceptions about community empowerment and social inclusion program in Sitanala leprosy village. All answers, responses, and explanations will be recorded. The length of the discussion is about 90 minutes. However, further interviews will be conducted several times to provide depth of research.

Methodology:

The study will be qualitative in nature. The interview will last for approximately 90 minutes. However, further interviews may be conducted several times to provide depth of research. There will be a series of open-ended questions that allow you to explore your views about community empowerment and social inclusion program. These interviews will be audiotape recorded or electronically captured. Following the interview, a transcript will be provided to you if you wish to see one. You will be free to withdraw at any time throughout the process.

Participation is voluntary. You may withdraw from the project at any time prior to publication of results and there will be no disadvantage if you decide not to participate or withdraw at any time. However, because of the semi-public nature of the group process, anonymity and confidentiality cannot be guaranteed in a focus group setting and that individual contributions cannot be withdrawn if a decision is made to withdraw participation after the focus group has been held. The audiotapes will be kept in a locked filing cabinet at the researcher's office until they are transcribed and then they will be destroyed. The transcriptions will be kept in the same manner for 15 years following thesis submission and then destroyed.

Research Process:

It is anticipated that this research will be completed by the end of December 2016. A copy of the research report in English and executive summary in Bahasa Indonesia will be provided to Head of the Sitanala Leprosy Village. The results may be presented at conferences and written up in journals or book chapters without any identifying information. Analysed data will be used for research training, policy and publication purposes.

Research Funding:

Data collection expenses are partially met by CSU Research Office and the chief of investigator. This project has been approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of Charles Sturt University (Approval No. 2013/171).

Should you have any complaints concerning the manner in which this research is conducted, please contact me or the Research Ethics Officer at the following address:

Arif Rohman
PhD Student in Social Work
School of Humanities and Social Sciences, Charles Sturt University
Locked Bag 678, Wagga Wagga, NSW, 2678, Australia
Tel: +61 2 693 32552
Email: arohman@csu.edu.au

or

The Executive Officer
Ethics in Human Research Committee
Academic Secretariat
Charles Sturt University
Private Mail Bag 29, Bathurst, NSW, 2795
Tel: +61 2 6338 4628
Fax: +61 2 6338 4194
Email: ethics@csu.edu.au

Thank you for considering this request and I look forward to further contact with you.

Regards

Appendix A-4: Information Sheet for Participants (In-depth Interview) in Bahasa Indonesia

SCHOOL OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES
FACULTY OF ARTS

Locked Bag 588
Boorooma Street

Wagga Wagga NSW 2678

Tel: +61 2 6933 2249

Proyek Penelitian:

Program Pemberdayaan Masyarakat dan Inklusi Sosial di Kampung Kusta Sitanala, Indonesia

Saya ingin mengundang saudara sekaalian untuk berpartisipasi dalam penelitian saya dengan topik tersebut di atas. Rincian penelitian terlampir di bawah dan saya berharap saudara sekalian dapat mempertimbangkannya untuk terlibat dalam penelitian ini. Nama saya Arif Rohman dan saya bekerja di Kementerian Sosial. Proyek penelitian ini dilakukan untuk mendapatkan gelar Doktor di Charles Sturt University. Berikut adalah dosen pembimbing saya Professor Manohar Pawar, Associate Professor Wendy Bowles, dan Dr Bill Anscombe dari Charles Sturt University. Professor Manohar Pawar dapat dikontak pada email mpawar@csu.edu.au atau melalui telepon di nomor +61 2 6933 2497. Associate Professor Wendy Bowles dapat dikontak pada email wbowles@csu.edu.au atau melalui telepon di nomor +61 2 6933 2695. Dr Bill Anscombe dapat dikontak pada email csuhum@csu.edu.au atau melalui telepon di nomor +61 2 6933 2631.

Tujuan Penelitian:

Penelitian ini dimaksudkan untuk memahami pengalaman dan persepsi masyarakat di Kampung Kusta Sitanala terkait dengan program-program pemberdayaan masyarakat dan inklusi sosial.

Waktu yang Dibutuhkan:

Sebagai partisipan dalam proyek penelitian ini saudara diharapkan untuk berpartisipasi dalam wawancara mendalam. Topik wawancara berhubungan dengan pengalaman-pengalaman serta persepsi mengenai program pemberdayaan dan inklusi social di sini. Semua jawaban, respon, penjelasan akan direkam. Lama wawancara kurang lebih 90 menit. Namun demikian, wawancara lanjutan akan dilakukan beberapa kali untuk kedalaman penelitian.

Metode Penelitian:

Penelitian ini adalah penelitian kualitatif. Wawancara akan dilakukan selama 90 menit. Namun demikian, wawancara lanjutan akan dilakukan beberapa kali untuk kedalaman penelitian. Akan ada sesi tanya jawab yang memungkinkan saudara untuk menggali pandangan-pandangan terkait program-program yang ada.

Wawancara yang akan dilakukan akan direkam. Terkait dengan wawancara, transkrip akan diberikan apabila ada yang ingin melihatnya. Saudara bebas untuk

membatalkan keterlibatan saudara kapan saja selama proses berlangsung. Partisipasi dalam penelitian ini sifatnya sukarela. Saudara bisa kapan saja mundur dari penelitian ini sebelum hasil penelitian diterbitkan, dan tidak akan ada yang dirugikan kapan saja saudara mengundurkan diri. Namun demikian, karena karena sifat diskusi kelompok yang semi publik, maka anonim dan kerahasiaan tidak dapat dijamin sepenuhnya dalam kerangka diskusi kelompok bertujuan dan kontribusi perseorangan tidak dapat dibatalkan jika keputusan tersebut diambil sesudah diskusi bertujuan dilakukan. Rekaman wawancara akan disimpan tertutup di tempat file kantor saya sampai selesai ditranskrip dan rekaman tersebut akan dimusnahkan. Transkrip akan disimpan dengan baik selama 15 tahun setelah thesis diserahkan dan selanjutnya dimusnahkan.

Proses Penelitian:

Perlu diperhatikan kemungkinan penelitian ini akan selesai pada bulan Desember 2016. Foto copy laporan penelitian dalam Bahasa Inggris dan Ringkasan Eksekutif dalam Bahasa Indonesia akan diberikan pada Kepala Kampung Kusta Sitanala. Hasil penelitian ini mungkin akan dipresentasikan dalam konferensi dan ditulis di jurnal-jurnal atau bab-bab buku tanpa menyebut nama. Analisis data akan digunakan untuk keperluan pelatihan penelitian, penyusunan kebijakan, dan publikasi.

Dana Penelitian:

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Jika saudara ingin menyatakan keluhan terkait perilaku pada saat penelitian ini dilakukan, saudara bisa menghubungi saya atau Komite Etik Penelitian Manusia pada alamat berikut ini:

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Atau

The Executive Officer
Ethics in Human Research Committee
Academic Secretariat
Charles Sturt University
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Fax: +61 2 6338 4194
Email: ethics@csu.edu.au

Terima kasih atas perhatian dan saya harap saudara dapat berpartisipasi dalam penelitian ini.

Salam hormat

Appendix B-1: Observation Guidelines

OBSERVATION GUIDELINES
VOICES FROM A LEPROSY COLONY: A CRITICAL ETHNOGRAPHY OF THE IMPACTS OF
COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT AND SOCIAL INCLUSION PROGRAM
AT THE SITANALA LEPROSY VILLAGE, INDONESIA

No.	Dimension	Results
1.	Space/Location/Place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Geographic information: Province, District, Village, Latitude, Longitude b. Demography: Population (Sex, Age, Literacy), Number of Houses, Family Size, Ethnic Groups, Languages c. Infrastructure and Services: Education, Social, Health, Water Source, Government, Electricity, Communication, Transportation, Other Services and Infrastructure, Infrastructure and Services share with other villages (school, wells, clinics) d. Infrastructure and Services: General Description of Terrain, Transportation Access to Village, Connection to Other Villages (roads, wades, passes)
2.	Government and Leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Elders b. Religious Officials c. Other Influential People
3.	Economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Shops b. Nearest Bazaar c. Main Sources of Income d. Industry e. Crops f. Livestock g. Threats to Local Economy
4.	Social Institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Religious Group b. Mothers Group c. Fathers Group d. Youth Group e. Other Social Group
5.	Most Vulnerable groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Children b. Women c. Elderly
6.	CESI Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Actors: Government, Non-Government, Private Sector b. Activities: Charity, Professional c. Time: Incidental, Short Term, Long Term d. Purposes/Objectives e. Methods f. Goods/Tools g. Impacts h. Feeling

Appendix B-2: Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guidelines

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION (FGD) GUIDELINES

**VOICES FROM A LEPROSY COLONY: A CRITICAL ETHNOGRAPHY OF THE IMPACTS OF
COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT AND SOCIAL INCLUSION PROGRAM
AT THE SITANALA LEPROSY VILLAGE, INDONESIA**

- Welcome
- Introduction
- Describe living experiences
 - Reasons to live in the colony
 - Live with leprosy
 - Religious views and traditional beliefs related to leprosy
 - Social solidarity
- Any other experiences you would like to discuss?
- Perception about community empowerment and social inclusion program
 - What the program does/includes?
 - How is the CESI program implemented?
 - How do they participate in the programs?
 - What changes/outcomes have come from it? For themselves and their family? For others in the community?
 - Have there been disadvantages with the program?
 - How do they give meaning to these programs?
 - Does the program fit their needs?
 - How is the level of participation in the program?
 - What are the impacts of the program?
 - What changes would they like to see?
 - What are their hopes for future programs?
- Notable strategy to cope with the stigma? (A sensitive question will be ask in the end)
- Key reflections for participants
- Anything else to discuss or ask?
- Conclude and wrap up – confirm follow up details

INTERVIEW GUIDELINES
VOICES FROM A LEPROSY COLONY: A CRITICAL ETHNOGRAPHY OF THE IMPACTS OF
COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT AND SOCIAL INCLUSION PROGRAM
AT THE SITANALA LEPROSY VILLAGE, INDONESIA

1. What is the origin and nature of the leper colony?
2. What are the characteristic of the leper colony?
3. What are the current conditions in leper colony?
4. How do people live there?
5. What is the leper colony's culture?
6. How do they make this colony exist?
7. What is the CESI program in the colony?
8. Which are the CESI services?
9. Are there other services? Tell me about them?
10. How the CESI program is implemented?
11. How does the CESI program benefit persons affected by leprosy in the colony?
12. What are the experiences of PALs in receiving the CESI program?
13. What are their perceptions of the CESI program?
14. Does the CESI program empower the leper colony?
15. Does the CESI program facilitate their participation in broader community activities?
16. What key elements are required to enhance the benefit of the CESI program to the community?
17. What are the implications for policy and practice?
18. Etc.

APPENDIX B - 4

DOCUMENT STUDY GUIDELINES
VOICES FROM A LEPROSY COLONY: A CRITICAL ETHNOGRAPHY OF THE IMPACTS OF
COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT AND SOCIAL INCLUSION PROGRAM
AT THE SITANALA LEPROSY VILLAGE, INDONESIA

1. The Program and Policy of the Ministry of Social Affairs (MOSA) of Indonesia
2. The Program and Policy of the Ministry of Health (MOH) of Indonesia

OFFICE OF
ACADEMIC GOVERNANCE

Private Mail Bag 29
Parsons Avenue
Bathurst NSW 2795
Australia

Tel: +61 2 6338 4185
Fax: +61 2 6338 4194

17 September 2013

Mr Arif Rohman
14 Beltana Avenue
WAGGA WAGGA NSW 2560

Dear Mr Rohman,

Thank you for the additional information forwarded in response to a request from the Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC).

The CSU HREC reviews projects in accordance with the National Health and Medical Research Council's *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Research Involving Humans*.

I am pleased to advise that your project entitled **"Voices from a Leper Colony: A Critical Ethnography of the Impacts of Community Empowerment and Social Inclusion Program at the Sitanala Leprosy Village, Indonesia"** meets the requirements of the *National Statement*; and ethical approval for this research is granted for a twelve-month period from 17 September 2013.

The protocol number issued with respect to this project is **2013/171**. Please be sure to quote this number when responding to any request made by the Committee.

Please note the following conditions of approval:

- all Consent Forms and Information Sheets are to be printed on Charles Sturt University letterhead. Students should liaise with their Supervisor to arrange to have these documents printed;
- you must notify the Committee immediately in writing should your research differ in any way from that proposed. Forms are available at: http://www.csu.edu.au/_data/assets/word_doc/0010/176833/chrc_annrep.doc (please copy and paste the address into your browser)
- you must notify the Committee immediately if any serious and or unexpected adverse events or outcomes occur associated with your research, that might affect the participants and therefore ethical acceptability of the project. An Adverse Incident form is available from the website: as above;
- amendments to the research design must be reviewed and approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee before commencement. Forms are available at the website above;

Approval_after_further_information.doc

Last updated: February 2013
Next review: February 2014

www.csu.edu.au

CRCOS Provider Numbers for Charles Sturt University are 00005F (NSW), 01947G (VIC) and 02660E (ACT). ABN: 83 878 708 551

- if an extension of the approval period is required, a request must be submitted to the Human Research Ethics Committee. Forms are available at the website above;
- you are required to complete a Progress Report form, which can be downloaded as above, by 18 July 2014 if your research has not been completed by that date;
- you are required to submit a final report, the form is available from the website above.

YOU ARE REMINDED THAT AN APPROVAL LETTER FROM THE CSU HREC CONSTITUTES **ETHICAL APPROVAL ONLY**.

If your research involves the use of radiation, biological materials, chemicals or animals a separate approval is required from the appropriate University Committee.

The Committee wishes you well in your research and please do not hesitate to contact the Executive Officer on telephone (02) 6338 4628 or email ethics@csu.edu.au if you have any enquiries.

Yours sincerely

Julie Hicks
Executive Officer
Human Research Ethics Committee
Direct Telephone: (02) 6338 4628
Email: ethics@csu.edu.au

Cc: Professor Manohar Pawar Associate Professor Wendy Bowles Dr Bill Auscombe

This HREC is constituted and operates in accordance with the National Health and Medical Research Council's (NHMRC) *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research* (2007)

Appendix D: Conference Presentations

Some part of the thesis has been presented at academic conferences:

Rohman, A., Pawar, M., Bowles, W., & Anscombe, B. (2014, 9-12 July). *Leprosy in Indonesia: A case for anti-discriminatory practice*. Paper presented at the Joint World Conference on Social Work, Education and Social Development, Melbourne, Australia.

Rohman, A., Pawar, M., Bowles, W., & Anscombe, B. (2015, 16-18 January). *The Resilience and Coping Strategies of Persons Affected by Leprosy*. Paper presented at International Conference on Human Development and Sustainability: Challenges and Strategies for the Asian Century, Sriniketan, India.

Rohman, A. (2015, 15-16 October). *Housing Problems in an Abandoned Leprosy Colony*. Paper presented at International Seminar on Partnership for Sustainable Housing and Urban Development, Surabaya, Indonesia.

Rohman, A. (2017, 1-4 August). *Paternalism in Rural Development and Poverty Eradication (RDPE)*. Paper presented at Regional Expert Meeting: Revitalizing Rural Development for Poverty Eradication in Asia, Udon Thani City, Thailand.